

100 Households, 100 Circular Stories: Inspiring Sustainable Living in Europe

Deliverable 2.1: Conceptual framework for behavioural approaches and measures of circular practices intervention program

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D2.1 Conceptual Framework

Work package	WP2 - Development of conceptual framework and methodology
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Report description	This document shows the development of the conceptual framework through a combined top-down and bottom-up process, aligns the intervention strategy with the theoretical framework and details the development of the CircleUp app concept. As such, this document forms the backbone for the implementation of the interventions in the households in WP4.

Revision History

Version #	Implemented by	Revision Date	Description of changes
V0.1	Carina Hermandi	13.06.25	Minor changes

Approval Procedure

Version #	Deliverable Name	Approved by	Institution	Approval Date

List of abbreviations

LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
SSBC	Stage model of Self-regulated Behavioural Change

List of Tables

Table 1: Concepts and components relevant for circular economy practices.

Table 2. An overview of the research articles included in the literature review

Table 3. Overview of empirically tested socio-psychological constructs as postulated by the SSBC

Table 4: Concepts of Citizenship

Table 5: Game elements

Table 6: Fulfilment of the three basic psychological needs (Deci & Ryan, 1985) within the gamified app

Table 7: Workshop 1 (Personas) – Tasks

Table 8: Main results of Workshop 2 (Circular Stories)

Table 9: Circular economy practices as named in the proposal

Table 10: Selected prime target behaviours for CircleUp

Table 11: Summary of the workshop results for the food sector

Table 12: Summary of the workshop results for the packaging sector

Table 13: Summary of the workshop results for the textile sector

Table 14: Summary of the workshop results for the electronics sector

Table 15: List of behaviours within the food domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

Table 16: List of behaviours within the packaging domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

Table 17: List of behaviours within the electronics domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

Table 18: List of behaviours within the textile domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

Table 19: Challenges created for FOOD in Oxford for WP2

Table 20: Challenges created for PACKAGING in Oxford for WP2

Table 21: Challenges created for TEXTILES in Oxford for WP2

Table 22: Challenges created for ELECTRONICS in Oxford for WP2

Table 23: List of final challenges for CircleUp

Table 24: Building blocks following the SSBC mode

Table 25: Framework for the individual food challenges

Table 26: Framework for the community food challenges

Table 27: Framework for the individual packaging challenges

Table 28: Framework for the individual electronic challenges

Table 29: Framework for the community electronics challenges

Table 30: Framework for the individual textiles challenges

Table 31: Framework for the community textiles challenges

List of Figures

Figure 1. Overview of the core concept of CircleUp.

Figure 2. Overview of the process leading to the final conceptual framework.

Figure 3. Circular consumer behaviour according to Camacho-Otero et al. (2018)

Figure 4. Circular consumer behaviour according to Shevchenko et al. (2023)

Figure 5. Stages of self-regulated behavioural change by Bamberg (2013)

Figure 6. The selection process of the literature review according to PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009)

Figure 7: Interactive Model of Social Identity Formation (Postmes et al. 2005). Own illustration, simplified.

Figure 8: Design Process and Design Principles.

Figure 9: Workshop 2, Pool of Circular Stories

Figure 10: Example of clustering stories based on emotions

Figure 11: Interplay of digital components and real-world activities towards the formation of a Circular Citizen Identity.

Figure 12: Example for a "small" Circular Story

Figure 13: Example for a "big" Circular Story

Figure 14: General assessment of the behavioural domains

Figure 15: Prioritised behaviours in the four domains (survey results, max three answers)

Figure 16: Bottom-up framework model for "Plan purchases to avoid food waste / only buy what is needed"

Figure 17: Bottom-up framework model for "Cooking – only what they will eat / Utilise leftovers in the kitchen"

Figure 18: Bottom-up framework model for "Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting)"

Figure 19: Bottom-up framework model for "If too much is purchased, give to neighbours, friends, family, community fridges"

Figure 20. Bottom-up framework model for "Use reusable containers / bags".

Figure 21. Bottom-up framework model for "Avoid packaging / buy products with reduced packaging".

Figure 22. Bottom-up framework model for "Reuse packaging (e.g. paper bags), reuse plastic shopping bags".

Figure 23. Bottom-up framework model for "Sort and dispose of used packaging".

Figure 24. Bottom-up framework model for "Reduce buying clothes".

Figure 25. Bottom-up framework model for "Take better care of textiles / repair damaged textiles / buy durable and repairable textiles".

Figure 26. Bottom-up framework model for "Buy second-hand clothes".

Figure 27. Bottom-up framework model for "Reuse and upcycle, recombine clothes to new outfits".

Figure 28. Bottom-up framework model for "Share products (e.g., drills, lawn mowers)".

Figure 29. Bottom-up framework model for "Buy durable and repairable electronics / repair damaged electronics".

Figure 30. Bottom-up framework model for "Question the need of buying electronics / assess status quo".

Figure 31. Bottom-up framework model for "Give electronics to friends and family / other people / give electronics to proper recycling".

Figure 32. Framework model of the circular economy practices

Figure 33. Overview of the CircleUp app functionalities

Figure 34. Challenges flow of the CircleUp app

Figure 35. Model of the building blocks following the individual challenge

Figure 36. Model of the building blocks following the collective level

Table of content

List of Tables	3
List of Figures	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1. Introduction and Overview	10
1.1 Background of CircleUp.....	10
1.2 Structure of this document.....	11
1.3 Future revisions of this document	12
2. Literature review (top-down process)	13
2.1 Point of departure from the proposal.....	13
2.2 Literature review of circular economy behaviour.....	15
2.2.1 Circular economy consumer behaviour	16
2.2.2 R frameworks to explain consumer behaviour	17
2.2.3 Frameworks for conceptualizing consumer behaviour.....	19
2.3 A theory-based framework model suggestion.....	24
2.3.1 The stage model of self-regulated behavioural change explained	24
2.3.2 A literature review of the stage model of self-regulated behavioural change	26
2.3.3 Explaining consumer behaviour changes with the stage model of self-regulated behavioural change.....	44
2.4 Building community through collective actions and circular stories	45
2.4.1 Theoretical Background	45
2.4.2 Process of developing the circular stories gamified approach	58
2.4.3 The revised structure of the community building element - Circular stories embedded in a challenge-based approach.....	87
3. Stakeholder involvement (bottom-up process)	91
3.1 Specification of behaviours and first collection of concepts	91
3.2 Internal survey	95
3.3 Focusing of behaviours	99
3.4 Workshop 1: Bottom-up framework models	100
Food	101
Packaging.....	107
Textiles	113

Electronics	118
3.5 Workshop 2: A solidified framework model across domains	125
3.6 Workshop 3: Stakeholder involvement in the framework development	144
3.7 Workshop 4: Defining the challenges	149
4. List of final challenges	162
5. Guidelines for the CircleUp app	164
5.1 The ambition of the app	164
5.2 The intervention strategies within the app.....	164
5.3 The circular stories concept	165
5.4 The challenges within the app	165
6. Matching the interventions to the conceptual framework	169
7. The 15 challenges following the building blocks based on the SSBC model	176
8. References.....	403
9. Appendices.....	411
9.1 Appendix a. Outline of the NTNU workshop organized to finalize the challenges.....	411
9.2 Appendix b. Results from the internal survey.....	419

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

CircleUp aims to understand households' behaviours and attitudes in the transition towards a circular economy, focusing on minimising waste in everyday behaviour and practices related to food, textiles, electronics and packaging. While a lot of work has been done on the production side, consumer research remains underdeveloped. This deliverable presents a conceptual framework to address this gap by developing, testing, implementing, evaluating, and disseminating a tailored intervention to enhance consumer engagement in a circular economy at both individual and collective levels.

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the development and rationale behind the conceptual framework that forms the basis of the CircleUp project. It outlines the steps taken throughout the project, divided into several parts, each contributing to the overall conceptual framework.

The main parts of this work include i) the literature review of the SSBC stage model. This review forms the theoretical foundation for the further development of the project; ii) the workshop results; summarizing the outcomes of the different workshops held during bi-weekly and project meetings organized by NTNU and Prosperkolleg, highlighting collaboration between the project partners and stakeholders; iii) the CircleUp app concept; providing some details about the functionalities of the app iv) and the behavioural challenges, providing a detailed outline of the sixteen behavioural challenges, following the SSBC stage model.

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1. Introduction and Overview

1.1 Background of CircleUp

CircleUp is a highly innovative endeavour that aims to increase the diffusion rate of circular practices at the micro level, as a vital step towards achieving a circular economy, optimising material streams into and out of households and closing the loops wherever possible. It seeks to achieve this goal by developing, testing, implementing, evaluating, disseminating an innovative behavioural intervention package consisting of consultation and information, gamification elements, and feedback approaches, supplemented by a technical application to provide this intervention package. This intervention package is solidly anchored in a theoretical framework model that has been developed in a thorough process combining top-down, and bottom-up components to integrate both theoretical and empirical knowledge from the research literature, and hands-on knowledge from project beneficiaries and stakeholders.

The main goal of CircleUp is to implement an innovative intervention package to motivate the uptake of circular economy practices at the household level and reduce the environmental footprints of the 100 households involved. CircleUp does not only want to look at the individual or household level but also want to stimulate and influence households' social norms by promoting communication of different stakeholders and encouraging participants to question the status quo. Furthermore, it will establish and foster the social identification of individuals as circular citizens, inviting them to engage in and organize group activities that reinforce sustainable social norms and discourage unsustainable habits. The project will leverage an innovative, and theory-informed technology tool to stimulate and channel interactions, allowing participants to engage with people beyond their direct circle of neighbours or friends. This deliverable focuses on the development of the content-related side of this tool.

By sharing circular stories and participating in group activities on a local level, participants will not only strengthen social bonds and satisfy the need for social connection and self-esteem. Interactive Learning Environments, life cycle assessments, and simulation tools will support the transfer of insights and develop competencies for integrated analysis and model-based assessments of key sustainable consumption policy and practice topics. System dynamics mode-based

tools will support scoping and appraisal of strategies and policies related to sustainable consumption. The success of this intervention package in 100 model households in four structurally and culturally different countries will demonstrate CircleUp's potential to transform the way people consume, how they can benefit from the circular economy, and reduce social disparity, environmental footprints, GHG emissions. Figure 1 below shows the overall concept of CircleUp as was included in the project proposal. The theoretical framework presented in this deliverable is particularly relevant for the behaviour science toolkit and the community building tool.

Figure 1. Overview of the core concept of CircleUp.

1.2 Structure of this document

The process of developing the theoretical framework in CircleUp combined different approaches into an overall concept (see Figure 2). Taking a point of departure in the brief literature review presented in the proposal (see Section 2.1 for a summary), three main paths of framework development were followed: (1) a thorough literature review was implemented extending the review presented in the proposal (see Section 2), (2) a bottom-up stakeholder involvement process starting within the consortium but also planned in a later stage outside the consortium to anchor the theoretical framework in the realities of our households. In section 3, the conceptual framework itself for the

development of the technology tool or app will be presented based on both the literature review and the stakeholder input. In the fourth section of this document, the challenges that form the basis of the CircleUp app are presented.

Figure 2. Overview of the process leading to the final conceptual framework.

1.3 Future revisions of this document

Until its publication in M18, the document was a work-in-progress document, archiving the process of how the theoretical framework for the project was developed. After the publication as D2.1, this document will be further updated until the end of the project (M42) as a revised and improved conceptual framework based on the learning from the implementation of the framework in the model households.

2. Literature review (top-down process)

In the proposal, a first brief review of the relevant literature to base the framework model on was included. In Section 2.1, a summary of this starting point will be presented. In the first months of the project, this initial overview has been supplemented by a thorough review of the behaviour science literature around drivers and barriers of circular economy practices, which will be presented in a structured overview in Section 2.2. In Section 2.3, a joined framework based on these inputs from the literature will be outlined.

2.1 Point of departure from the proposal

The theoretical background outlined in the proposal is based on three comprehensive frameworks for conceptualising and encouraging sustainable behaviour change:

- Comprehensive Model Framework for Environmental Behaviour (Klöckner, 2015): The framework is based on a combination of the most common theories of environmental psychology and conceptualises important psychological factors of behaviour change.
- SHIFT Framework (White et al., 2019): Based on a review of the literature, the authors conceptualise key psychological factors in the acronym SHIFT: Social influence, Habit formation, Individual self, Feelings and cognition, and Tangibility.
- PSICHE framework (Nascimento et al., 2022): Based on a bibliometric analysis, the authors uncovered the major theories and constructs from the state-of-the-art and synthesised the key determinants of factors that influence green purchasing behaviours: Product-related factors, Social influences, Individual factors, Concerns about the environment, Habits and Emotions.

These frameworks are already rather comprehensive and identify a high number of potentially relevant factors. The concepts mentioned in these frameworks overlap partly. The models have not been applied to circular economy, but singular practices that may fall under the definition of circular economy practices as followed in this project.

Table 1 below lists the components included in each of the frameworks and are sorted into the different categories which are 1) individual factors, 2) social factors, 3) emotions, 4) automaticity, and 5) contextual factors.

Table 1: Concepts and components relevant for circular economy practices.

	Klößner (2015)	White et al. (2019)	Nascimento et al. (2022)
Individual factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived behavioural control and self-efficacy • Personal norms • Ecological attitudes and value orientations • Awareness of consequences, perceived responsibility and feasibility • Attitudes towards change strategies • Cognitive and action planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-concept • Self-consistency • Self-interest • Self-efficacy personal norms and values traits (e.g. agreeableness, openness to experience) • Demographics (e.g. gender) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-concept • Individual cultural dimensions • personal norms • Perceived self-efficacy • Consumption goals (e.g., gain, normative, hedonic) • Values (e.g., Egoistic, Altruistic, Biospheric) • Attitudes and Concerns about environment (evaluative: environmental concerns, vs. cognitive: knowledge, beliefs, problem awareness)
Social factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salient social norms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social norms • Social identities • Social desirability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social norms • Green social identity
Emotions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negative emotions • Emotions anticipated with goal progress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negative emotions: fear, guilt, sadness • Positive emotions: joy and pride, affinity to nature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic emotions (e.g., excitement, happiness, arousal) • Self-conscious (e.g., pride, guilt, shame) • Others-directed/moral emotions (e.g., awe, gratitude)
Automaticity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habits • Heuristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habit reformation by discontinuity, penalties, implementation intentions, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pro-environmental behaviour spillover

		prompts, incentives and feedback	•Past and/or Frequent behaviour
Contextual factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Goal framing •Enabling or limiting contextual conditions •Choice situation •Choice set generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Framing of message •Tangibility of impacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Product-related factors (e.g. knowledge, perceived value, perceived risks)

In the following section, this very rudimental overview will be supplemented by a deep review of the literature, where the different concepts will also be presented in more detail.

2.2 Literature review of circular economy behaviour

The traditional, linear economic approach is based on a business model in which products are purchased, used, and eventually discarded as waste. The essential shift towards sustainability requires us to move to a more sustainable alternative of a production and consumption system, also known as the circular economy model. While a linear economy views resources as abundant, the life cycle of products and materials in a circular economy is extended (White, Habib, & Hardisty, 2019). Furthermore, resources are reused, refurbished, remanufactured, and recycled in a closed-loop system (Kirchherr, Reike, & Hekkert, 2017). The circular economy contributes to tackling climate change and biodiversity loss, as recycling materials for instance requires less energy and produces fewer greenhouse gas emissions than consuming natural resources (Björklund & Finnveden, 2005). However, the approach can only become effective if consumer and user acceptance and collective action is taken by different stakeholders such as individual consumers, policy makers, and industries (Parajuly, Fitzpatrick, Muldoon, & Kuehr, 2020). Although it is changing somewhat, most of the research into the circular economy has been devoted to materials and the production side, while consumer involvement is often neglected (Camacho-Otero, Boks, & Pettersen, 2018; Tunn, Bocken, van den Hende, & Schoormans, 2019). For instance, Kirchherr et al. (2017) found that only one in five publications defining the circular economy consider the role of consumers. Notwithstanding, the transformation to a circular economy requires significant behaviour changes among consumers such as adopting practices involving repairing and returning goods (Camacho-Otero et al., 2018). The multitude of determinants

associated with long-term circular economy behaviour, such as the drivers, barriers, and motivations, are still largely unexplored in today's research (Camacho-Otero et al., 2018; Parajuly et al., 2020). One purpose of the CircleUp project is to fill this gap by identifying psychological factors associated with consumers' attitudes and behaviours to explain variability in circular behaviour to ultimately design tailored structural interventions. By identifying these factors, CircleUp will then be able to target intervention packages to these factors. In the following section, we will expand on consumer behaviour in greater detail.

2.2.1 Circular economy consumer behaviour

Today, several definitions are used in the literature to define the circular economy concept (Kirchherr et al. 2017). Recently, a literature review by Kirchherr et al. (2018, p.229) was conducted to contribute to a more coherent concept of the circular economy. The authors defined circular economy as:

“An economic system that replaces the ‘end-of-life’ concept with reducing, alternatively reusing, recycling and recovering materials in production/distribution and consumption processes. It operates at the micro level (products, companies, consumers), meso level (eco-industrial parks) and macro level (city, region, nation and beyond), with the aim to accomplish sustainable development, thus simultaneously creating environmental quality, economic prosperity and social equity, to the benefit of current and future generations. It is enabled by novel business models and responsible consumers.”

Although the above definition is more specific and precise compared to earlier definitions in literature, the concept of circularity in the consumption context is still not well-defined, and the role of consumers remains unclear, supporting the similar argument put forward by Camacho-Otero et al. (2018). It is therefore of great importance to come to a more complete and comprehensive definition. The definition of consumer behaviour suggested by White et al. (2019) is the starting point in the present theoretical framework. Circular economy consumer behaviour is generally defined by the authors as behaviour resulting in a decrease of negative environmental impacts and an increase in the use of natural resources across the lifecycle of products or services.

2.2.2 R frameworks to explain consumer behaviour

During the last few decades, circular economy practices have often been operationalised by researchers and practitioners in different so-called R models or R frameworks (Kirchherr et al., 2018). These frameworks typically use “R” verbs to describe strategies that consumers can adopt. Several authors have used a combination of reduce, reuse, and recycle activities in the concept of circular economy (Murray, Skene, & Haynes, 2017). Later, scholars have included a fourth type of activities that attempt to capture `recover`. This approach is now adopted as the 4R framework including reduce, reuse, recycle and recover and is generally used in the literature (Kirchherr et al., 2018; Sihvonen & Ritola, 2015). In addition, scholars have proposed other R frameworks such as the ReX framework (Sihvonen & Ritola, 2015) or the more comprehensive 9Rs framework including refuse, reduce, reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, recycle, and recover energy (Van Buren, Demmers, van der Heijden, & Witlox, 2016). Furthermore, the R frameworks are sometimes referred to as the R-Hierarchy due to the recognition of a hierarchy among the different R behaviours, prioritizing refusing and reducing over recycling and recovering (Kirchherr et al., 2018).

A similar line of framework is found in the work of Camacho-Otero et al. (2018). According to the authors, there are nine behaviours that consumers need to actively participate in, for a circular economy:

Acquisition phase: Consumers can buy used products, rent them, or trade them.

Usage phase: Depending on the business model, consumers can do things to keep or own the product for a longer time or pass it on to others. Repairing the product can extend the product's lifespan. Compensation can give consumers additional value (e.g., compensation for recycling). Retention means that the product is not disposed too early.

Disposal phase: Consumers engage in activities that enable a cycle. They can return the product to the manufacturer, re-sell it to other consumers, or give it away for free.

The figure below depicts the nine behaviours within the different consumption stages.

Figure 3. Circular consumer behaviour according to Camacho-Otero et al. (2018)

Another framework is the work from Shevchenko et al. (2023). The authors describe circular consumption as a cycle of three interrelated actions "buy - use - discard".

The role of the consumer includes the consumer as

- Buy: a customer who buys products or services
- Use: a user who uses the product and takes care of the product to keep the value of products
- Discard: an owner of products who disposes the product at the end of their life cycle

This three-dimensional framework is crucial for closing the product cycle through (i) careful use and maintenance, (ii) proper collection, and (iii) reuse, repair or recycling (Shevchenko, Saidani, Ranjbari, Kronenberg, Danko, & Laitala, 2023). Figure 4 shows the interrelated actions of circular consumption.

Figure 4. Circular consumer behaviour according to Shevchenko et al. (2023)

2.2.3 Frameworks for conceptualizing consumer behaviour

Within the environmental psychology literature, several theoretical frameworks have been widely used to understand the processes underlying environmental behaviour including consumer behaviour such as recycling (Chen & Tung, 2010), food choice, car use reduction (Jakovcevic & Steg, 2013), and energy savings. In the following section, three different frameworks on which the CircleUp project interventions will be based, are discussed in more detail, with the key fourth model discussed in section 2.2.4.

2.2.3.1 *The Comprehensive Action Determination model (CADM) (Klöckner, 2013; Klöckner & Blöbaum, 2010)*

The CADM framework has been empirically tested across a wide variety of environmental behaviours, such as transportation (Klöckner & Blöbaum, 2010; Nayum & Klöckner, 2014), recycling behaviour (Klöckner & Oppedal, 2011), and clothing consumption (Joanes, Gwozdz, & Klöckner, 2020). This framework integrates three prominent theories in environmental psychology: the theory of planned behaviour (TPB; Ajzen, 1991), the norm activation model (NAM; Schwartz, 1977) and the value belief norm theory (VBN; Stern et al., 1999), addressing the limitations found in individual models (Nayum & Klöckner, 2014). First, the theory of planned behaviour states that behavioural intentions are a proximal predictor behaviour. Intentions are influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. The latter refers to “an individual sense of the own capability to perform the behaviour” (Camacho-Otero et al., 2018, p.4). Some of the critics argue that the TPB fails to adequately account for normative and moral influences on behaviour (Arvola et al.,

2008). Second, the norm activation theory assumes that pro-environmental behaviour is executed once moral or personal norms are activated. This activation occurs through awareness of the problem and a feeling of personal responsibility towards the relevant environmental domain (Gölz, 2017). Third, the value-belief-norm theory describes the relationships between values, beliefs, norms, and behaviors and highlights the indirect relationship between values and environmental behaviour, via beliefs and personal norms. A shortcoming of the NAM and the VBN frameworks is that they do not sufficiently consider possible non-normative impacts on behaviour (Joanes, Gwozdz, & Klöckner, 2020). The CADM overcomes the shortcomings of the TPB, the NAM, and the VBN, and explains how behaviour is the result of both intentional, normative, situational, and habitual constructs (Klöckner & Blöbaum, 2010). The framework posits that habits, intentions, and situational influences (both objective and perceived) directly influence behaviour, whereas norms (both social and personal) are mediated by intentions and habits.

2.2.3.2 SHIFT framework (White et al., 2019)

White et al. (2019) have identified key psychological drivers summarized by the acronym SHIFT: Social influence, Habit formation, Individual self, Feelings and cognitions, and Tangibility. This framework highlights various factors that can specifically be used to encourage sustainable consumer behaviour, extending beyond the scope of sustainable behaviour explored in previous research (White et al., 2019). The authors argue that there are often multiple barriers to sustainable behaviour change and therefore combining different strategies from the developed framework is recommended.

Social influence: The first factor that the authors emphasize is social influence, encompassing social norms, social identities, and social desirability. As social beings, consumers are often guided by what other people do and think. Additionally, consumers are often affected by the “presence, behaviours, and expectations of others” (White et al., p.24). To influence consumer behaviour, the authors recommend making certain behaviour appear more socially approved, more desirable and more commonly enacted by others. Social influence captured as “social norms” in the CADM described above.

Habit formation: Many environmental behaviours, such as food consumption, choice of transportation, energy and resource use, shopping, and recycling involve repeated action. In the literature, habits are seen as behaviours that are “guided by automated cognitive processes, rather than being preceded by elaborate reasoning” (Steg & Vlek, 2009, p.312). Disruptions like life changes or penalties can interrupt unsustainable habits. Conversely, making things easy to make the right choice, prompts, feedback, and incentives can foster more sustainable habits. Habits are also part of the above-mentioned CADM.

Individual self: Another key factor in promoting sustainable consumption is related to the individual self. More specifically, the authors focus on enhancing self-concept, self-interest, self-consistency, self-efficacy, and individual differences to encourage sustainable consumer engagement. People want to see themselves as positive and consistent. Therefore, positively associating sustainable behaviors with the self-concept and buffering against self-threatening information can be important for change. Furthermore, both consistency and inconsistency effects can occur among individuals in behaviour change. Self-efficacy as part of perceived behavioural control is represented in the CADM, while the other self-related factors are not.

Feelings and cognition: People are influenced by both negative emotions (e.g. fear, guilt, and sadness) and positive emotions (e.g. warm glow, joy, and pride) which can affect their pro-environmental behaviours. Furthermore, although interventions that rely solely on information are often ineffective for long-term behavioural change, knowledge about issues appears to be an important driver of consumer action. Both information and learning, eco-labeling, and framing might drive the role of cognition in predicting sustainable actions. The CADM does not mention feelings and cognitions specifically, thus their function as described in the SHIFT framework could be considered as an extension of the CADM.

Tangibility: The concept of sustainability and its long-term goals often seem abstract and challenging for some people. To make sustainability more visible and tangible, the authors propose some strategies. These include matching temporal focus by encouraging consumers to consider the future benefits of environmental action, communicating local and immediate impacts such to make sustainability issues more concrete, and promote the desire for intangibles by promoting dematerialization (e.g.,

sharing economy). Tangibility is another factor that is not referred to in the CADM, but it may be subsumed in the perceived control section of the model.

2.2.3.3 PSICHE framework (Nascimento & Loureiro, 2022)

Based on a literature review within sustainable consumer behaviours, the authors uncovered the major theories and constructs from the state-of-the-art and synthesized six key determinants that influence green purchasing behaviours of consumers: Product-related factors, Social influences, Individual factors, Concerns about the environment, Habits and Emotions.

Product-related factors: The factors summarized as the product-related factors are product knowledge, perceptions on consumption value (e.g. functional, quality, emotional value, and social value), green trust, brand, product category (e.g. type, role, and involvement), and perceived risks or barriers (e.g. social risks, inconveniences, price). As such, this specific focus on product features was not included in the CADM or SHIFT. However, they would in a broader sense be part of the attitudes in the CADM and the feelings and cognitions of the SHIFT model.

Social influences: In line with several other theoretical frameworks including SHIFT and CADM, social or subjective norms (e.g. descriptive, injunctive, normative goals) and green social identity are included, representing the impact of other people on behavioural choices. This includes when and under which circumstances, personal values, concerns and personality traits and self-expressive benefits.

Individual factors: The factors related to this construct are self-concept, individual cultural dimensions and location (e.g., rural/urban setting), personal moral norms, perceived green self-identity or self-concept, perceived self-efficacy, consumption goals (e.g., gain, normative, hedonic), and personal values (e.g. egoistic, altruistic, environmental or biospheric). Individual factors are, therefore, a collection of several factors that the CADM and SHIFT comprise of. The only aspect going beyond the already described models are individual cultural dimensions.

Concerns about the environment: The extent to which consumers are aware of and concerned about environmental issues, and feel responsible for solving them, has been shown to have an impact on environmental behaviour. The authors categorize environmental concerns into two types: evaluative concerns, which include attitudes

and concerns and cognitive concerns, which encompass knowledge, beliefs, and problem awareness.

Habits: Cross-category spill-over of pro-environmental routines (e.g. from private to public sphere, from domestic to traveling context) and past and/or recent and frequent behaviour. Habits are an essential component of both the CADM and the SHIFT framework.

Emotions: Basis emotions (e.g., excitement, happiness, arousal), self-consciousness (e.g. pride, guilt, shame) and others-directed/moral emotions (e.g. awe, gratitude). With the explicit mention of emotions, the PSICHE framework is in line with the SHIFT framework and potentially goes even beyond it by specifying the emotional categories further.

2.2.3.4 SSBC framework (Bamberg, 2013)

The Stage Model of Self-regulated behavioural Change (SSBC) views behavioural change as processing through a temporal series of four stages characterized by stage-specific tasks: (I) the pre-decisional, (II) the pre-actional, (III) the actional, and (IV) the post-actional stage. An individual moves from one stage to the next by forming the relevant intention. In the first stage, the pre-decision stage, an individual re-evaluates the behaviour, resulting in the development of a goal intention. In the second stage, the pre-action stage, an individual chooses an alternative strategy to achieve this goal, resulting in a behaviour intention. In the next stage, the action stage, the individual plans to perform the behaviour, resulting in the implementation intention. In the last stage, the post-action stage, the new behaviour is carried out. Each of the four stages is influenced by different socio-psychological factors, such as norms (personal and social), emotions (positive and negative), responsibility, perceived negative consequences, and feasibility in the first stage. Attitudes, and perceived behavioural control in the second stage. Planning (action and cognitive) and self-efficacy in the third stage and self-efficacy in the fourth stage. This model might be helpful in designing interventions tailored to the specific stage an individual is part of, making it more effective in promoting sustainable behaviour. Furthermore, between every stage, forming intentions act as bridge.

In essence, while the frameworks differ slightly in their specific constructs and emphases, both the CADM, the SHIFT, the PSICHE, and the SSBC framework

converge on fundamental aspects such as automaticity, social factors and the importance of social norms, individual factors, emotions, and contextual factors to influence sustainable behaviour.

2.3 A theory-based framework model suggestion

2.3.1 The stage model of self-regulated behavioural change explained

Figure 5 depicts the SSBC model which outlines different stages of decision making and different factors that influence each decision. Based on the idea of Lewin (1944), to successfully change behaviour, individuals must be motivated on the one hand and able to develop strategies and skills to implement certain behaviour on the other hand (Bamberg, 2013; Schaffner, Ohnmacht, Weibel, & Mahrer, 2017). Several authors have used the SSBC model to understand the motivational and self-regulation processes that lead to environmental behaviour change. Previous studies applying the SSBC have found evidence for different environmental behaviour shifts, such as transportation (Bamberg, 2013a; Klöckner, 2014; Olsson, Huck, & Friman, 2018; Sunio, Schmöcker, & Kim, 2018), beef consumption (Klöckner, 2017; Klöckner & Ofstad, 2017; Weibel, Ohnmacht, Schaffner, & Kossmann, 2019), energy use (Schaffner et al., 2017), and postponing smartphone purchases (Ohnmacht, Thao, Schaffner, & Weibel, 2018). Bamberg's model delineates four stages: pre-decisional, pre-actional, actional, and post-actional, drawing on earlier theories that elucidate pro-environmental behaviour (Keller et al., 2019). The SSBC combines elements of previous frameworks such as the model of action phases (MAP; Gollwitzer, 1990), the norm activation model (NAM; Schwartz & Howard, 1981), the theory of planned behaviour (TPB; Ajzen, 1991) as well as emotional and normative approaches to explain environmental behaviour change (Schaffner et al., 2017).

According to the SSBC model, there are four distinct and independent stages in which an individual must address a specific task to successfully change their behaviour. The initial stage is the *pre-decisional stage*, in which individuals recognize that their current behaviour is problematic and may have harmful consequences. In this stage, an individual needs an intention to reduce this behaviour or its negative outcomes (so called "goal intention"). The goal intention must be strong enough to proceed to the pre-actional stage. This intention is driven by an activated personal norm, as proposed by the norm-activation theory developed by Schwartz and Howard (1981). The

personal norm is activated when an individual is aware of the behaviour's consequences, feels responsible for it, and experiences negative emotions. Furthermore, individuals feel external pressure to change current behaviour through social norms. This stage is also characterized by a strong motivating role of emotions (both negative emotions realizing the negative effects of one's own actions on something that is valued, as well as positive emotions anticipating successful behaviour change).

The second stage is the *pre-action stage*. In this stage, individuals form the intention to perform a new, and less harmful behaviour. The behavioural intention is influenced by the attitudes and the perceived behavioural control (PBC) of an individual which is based on the theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). Here the negative components and beliefs about different behavioural alternatives become most relevant.

In the *action stage*, the individual implements the new intention into action. At this point, individuals need to plan and overcome obstacles. The so called "implementation intention" in the actional stage is based on the theory derived by Schwarzer in the health domain (2008). This theory states that the individual is influenced by the level of planning (action planning), the belief in their ability to overcome encountered obstacles (maintenance self-efficacy), and the capacity to foresee obstacles to the chosen alternative behaviour (cognitive planning).

Finally, in the last stage, the *post-action stage*, the individual evaluates the new behaviour, where it is important to maintain the behaviour without relapse.

One of the objectives of the CircleUp project is to promote circular economy practices among 100 households through various interventions. Given the characteristics of the SSBC outlined above, the implementation of the model seems appropriate in developing and evaluating the interventions for the project. Aspects outlined in the model frameworks above, which the SSBC does not address explicitly are habits and self-related components such as identify or self-image. As for habits, the SSBC can be understood as that if habits are strong, then the awareness of a need for change in the pre-decision stage does not develop, because no attention is paid to potential misalignments between the habitualized behaviour and the own values. Regarding self-related aspects, they can be conceptualized within the SSBC as catalysts of

barriers of perceiving negative consequences of the behaviour in the pre-decision stage. If a person has a strong-environmental identity, it is more likely that they will perceive the cues that trigger a negative feeling regarding their own behaviour.

Figure 5. Stages of self-regulated behavioural change by Bamberg (2013)

2.3.2 A literature review of the stage model of self-regulated behavioural change

In the following part, we present a theoretical review on the SSBC stage model. This review is part of an ongoing research paper intended for publication.

Method

In the following paragraph, we describe the search strategy and explain how we included the research articles in our literature review. Figure 6 provides an overview of the selection process, which was based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) provided by Moher et al. (2009). The aim of the literature search was to identify published empirical studies examining the theoretical SSBC framework of Bamberg (2013a) within the context of pro-environmental behaviour. Within the Web of Science database, we searched for publications citing the initial publication of Bamberg (2013a). The web of science database listed 186 articles. We used the following criteria to include articles in the literature review: (i) use of the SSBC as an explicit theoretical framework explaining environmental behaviour change, (ii) use of the SSBC within a cross-sectional, a

longitudinal, and/or an interventional design, (iii) original research article, and (iv) published in English in scientific peer-reviewed journals since 2013, which is the publication year of the original article conducted by Bamberg (2013a). The search for articles in the Web of Science database was conducted on 1st and 2nd July 2024. As a result, 186 research articles were listed. First, we looked at whether and how Bamberg's work (2013a) was cited in the research articles. In total, 37 articles were excluded in which Bamberg (2013a) was only cited in the reference list, but not in the article itself. Furthermore, three other articles were excluded because one article was published in French, one article was a book review, and one article neither mentioned Bamberg (2013a) in the reference list nor in the research article. Next, after a more extensive screening of the full texts, another eight articles were excluded because they did not look at the socio-psychological constructs from the SSBC framework, or because they did not focus on the topic of environmental behaviour. After further examination of Bamberg's citation in the articles, 117 items were excluded because they did not use the SSBC as their main theoretical framework. Next, after a more extensive screening of the full texts, another eight articles were excluded because they did not look at the socio-psychological constructs from the SSBC framework, or because they did not focus on the topic of environmental behaviour. Some articles were excluded because they only developed or proposed an intervention but did not empirically test it afterwards. Hence, the final review includes 20 original research articles using the SSBC framework, published between 2013 and 2024.

Figure 6. The selection process of the literature review according to PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009)

Next, after a more extensive screening of the full texts, another eight articles were excluded because they did not look at the socio-psychological constructs from the SSBC framework, or because they did not focus on the topic of environmental behaviour. Some articles were excluded because they only developed or proposed an intervention but did not empirically test it afterwards. Hence, the final review includes 20 original research articles using the SSBC framework, published between 2013 and 2024. For the literature review, we focus on a broad range of studies looking at the socio-psychological constructs to identify key themes and gaps in the mechanisms that are part of the SSBC.

Table 2. An overview of the research articles included in the literature review

Author/ published year	Sample size	Country	Outcome measure	Environmental behaviour	Design
Bamberg, 2013a (1)	N=908	7 European cities in Germany, Greece, France, Slovenia, Scotland, and Austria	Car use reduction	Transport	Cross- sectional
Berger & Burkhalter, 2022 (2)	N=855	Switzerlan d	Eco- friendly purchasin g	Food choice	Experimental, four treatments and one control group
Friman et al., 2019 (3)	N=190	Sweden	Public transport	Transport	Pre-test, post- test
Keller et al., 2021 (4)	N=573	Germany	Reduce single- use cups	Packaging	Cross- sectional
Klöckner, 2014 (5)	N=113	Norway	Car use reduction	Transport	Longitudinal (60 days)
Klöckner, 2017 (6)	N=746, 2967	Norway	Beef consumpt ion	Food choice	Cross- sectional
Kowalska- Pyzalska & Byrka, 2019 (7)	N=142	Poland	Energy monitorin g (energy saving)	Energy	Cross- sectional

Li et al., 2019 (8)	N=1000	China	Car use reduction	Transport	Experimental
Mei et al., 2024 (9)	N=294	China	Car use reduction	Transport	Cross-sectional
Ohnmacht et al., 2018 (10)	N=1818	Switzerland	Postponement of purchases of new phone	Purchasing	Cross-sectional
Olsson et al., 2018 (11)	N=794	Sweden	Car use reduction	Transport	Cross-sectional
Olsson et al., 2021 (12)	N=380	Sweden	Car use reduction	Transport	Experimental, longitudinal (three waves)
Richter & Hunecke, 2020 (13)	N=560	Germany	Organic food consumption	Food choice	Cross-sectional
Schaffner et al., 2017 (14)	N=1295	Switzerland	Energy-efficient home (energy saving)	Energy	Cross-sectional
Schroter et al., 2022 (15)	N=168	Germany	Buying electric cars	Transport	Cross-sectional + experimental
Siebertz et al., 2022 (16)	N=182	Germany	Organic food consumption	Food choice	Cross-sectional + experimental
Sunio et al., 2018 (17)	N=788	Philippines	Car use reduction	Transport	Experimental (treatment

					and control group), longitudinal (pre-test, post-test)
Wang et al., 2023 (18)	N=93	Netherlands	Adoption of climate mitigation measures	Climate mitigation	Cross-sectional
Weibel et al., 2019 (19)	N=1818	Switzerland	Meat consumption	Food choice	Cross-sectional

Table 3 displays the different research articles included in the systematic review. The first column indicates the number of studies together with the author(s) and the year of publication. In the second column, the number of participants is given. The third column describes the country of origin of the participants. The fourth column lists the outcome behaviour, while the next column classifies the behaviour within the field of consumption. Finally, the last column describes the method of design used in the research article.

The Table shows that most studies were conducted in the European region. More specifically, it was mainly Northern and Western European countries that were included, while only one Eastern European study was conducted (Poland). Furthermore, three studies were conducted outside Europe (Asia). As illustrated in Table 3, different sets of research methods and study designs were used to collect and analyze data. To date, longitudinal SSBC studies with more than two data points have only been conducted twice. Looking at the topic of the study, another observation from the Table is that most studies are related to transport, followed by food, and energy domains.

Table 3. Overview of empirically tested socio-psychological constructs as postulated by the SSBC

Variable from SSBC	Bamberg, 2013a	Friman et al., 2019	Keller et al., 2021	Klöckner, 2014	Klöckner, 2017	Li et al., 2019	Mei et al., 2024	Ohnmacht et al., 2018	Olsson et al., 2018	Olsson et al., 2021	Richter & Hunecke, 2020	Schaffner et al., 2017	Schroter et al., 2022	Siebertz et al., 2022	Sunio et al., 2018	Wang et al., 2023	Weibel et al., 2019
Social norms	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x			x	x	x	x
emotions	x		x	x			x	x							x	x	x
Personal norms	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x	x	x	x	x
Responsibility	x		x	x	x	x	x								x		
Perceived negative consequences of own behaviour (awareness of need)	x		x	x	x	x	x	x							x		x
Negative emotions																	
Goal feasibility	x		x				x									x	
Goal intention	x		x	x	x	x	x				x		x	x	x	x	
Attitudes	x	(x)	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Perceived behavioural control	x	(x)	x	x	x	x	x	x				x				x	x
Behavioural intention	x		x	x	x	x	x					x			x	x	
Implementation intention	x		x		x	x	x									x	
Planning ability			x		x	x									x	x	
Action planning			(x)														
Coping planning			(x)														
Maintenance self-efficacy			(x)													x	
Recovery self-efficacy															x	x	

Results

In this section, we discuss the existing literature based on the stage model of self-regulated behavioural change by conducting a systematic literature review. First, we review articles that use the SSBC framework and its socio-psychological constructs to encourage sustainable behaviour. We investigate whether we can find similarities in the socio-psychological constructs and intentions of the underlying SSBC framework across different studies. We will synthesize findings from previous conducted studies.

Relations between the social-psychological variables of the SSBC Based on the norm activation theory and the theory of planned behaviour, Bamberg (2013a) developed the model of the self-regulated behavioural change. Within this SSBC framework, Bamberg (2013a) included 13 different stage-specific socio-psychological constructs and three different intentions that can lead to a behaviour change. In this section, we briefly outline the stage model variables across the different studies included in the literature review and try to explore potential differences and similarities between the constructs

Stage 1

Social norms

Social norms are described in the literature as “rules and standards that are understood by members of a group, and that guide and/or constrain human behaviour” (Cialdini & Trost, 1998, p.152). Social norms are sometimes discussed with a distinction made between descriptive and injunctive social norms. Beliefs about what most people `are doing` are called descriptive social norms, while beliefs about what people `should do` are referred to as injunctive social norms (Cialdini et al., 1990). Bamberg (2013) however, does not make this distinction in the original SSBC framework.

In the original article of Bamberg (2013a), applying the SSBC framework to promote the reduction of car use for everyday trips, social norms have an indirect influence on goal intentions in the first behavioural change stage, the predecision stage. He argued that social norms constitute a relationship between personal norm.

A similar line of argument has been used by Li et al. (2019) who tried to understand the shift from car use to sustainable travel modes. The authors have found that personal norms depend on social norms. Accordingly, they demonstrated that the impact of other people is more important on personal norms among regular car users compared to less regular car users. Also Keller et al. (2021) who investigated the shift from single-use to reusable drink cups and Klöckner (2017) who looked at beef consumption reduction, found a similar association between social and personal norms. An earlier study of Klöckner (2014) looked at variation in intentions for electric car purchases at both between- and within-person levels. He found that while social norms between people are only marginally significant, the effects of changing perception of social norms within people over time are more relevant in understanding people`s intentions. In a similar vein, social norms were having an indirect effect on personal norms towards organic food consumption in the study of Richter and Hunecke (2020). In a more recent study on the shift in car use towards active school travel, Mei et al. (2024) suggested that social norms influence personal norms. Different to other authors, they found also a significant impact of social norms on people`s attitudes towards the shift in travel mode.

Ohnmacht et al. (2018) for instance, wanted to examine whether the socio-psychological factors had a different impact on the stages of change in postponing the purchase of a new mobile phone. Their assumption that higher social norms lead to a higher probability of belonging to a higher stage of the SSBC framework had to be rejected. In short, social norms have received much attention and are widely used in environmental behaviour research building upon the SSBC framework. It was one of the few constructs included in all studies in the literature review (see Table 3). In sum, we can conclude that most studies found an influence of social norms in the early stage of the SSBC framework and authors generally consider social norms as an important predictor for pushing people over to the next stage. It has also been shown that the influence of social norms operates through personal norms.

Emotions

In line with the proposed SSBC framework of Bamberg (2013a), some scholars in our literature review look at positive and negative emotions as two different constructs. Similar to Bamberg (2013a), Mei et al. (2024) found that positive emotions anticipated

with goal progress were important to understand the variance in goal intention. Negative emotions at the other hand were not directly relevant to explain goal intention but they were found to be associated with personal norms. A similar argument is found in the study of Klöckner (2014), who has shown that the emotions anticipated with goal progress are an important predictor of goal intention when considering purchasing an electric car.

Further, the results of Keller et al. (2019) suggested that positive emotions were a positive predictor in the first stage of the SSBC framework. Another explanation of emotions can be found among Sunio et al. (2018) who divided the construct into negative emotions and anticipated positive emotions. Their results demonstrated that goal intention is activated by anticipated positive emotions while negative emotions could not be used in their analysis due to reliability issues.

In contrast to the importance of emotions in the first stage, Ohnmacht et al. (2018) found that higher emotions were associated with a higher probability of progressing to the second phase of the SSBC framework. Therefore, it is clear from literature that emotions, either with regard to positive anticipation of goal progress or negative emotions, are a useful driving force for progressing to higher stages of environmental behavioural change. In terms of positive emotions anticipated with goal progress, research findings have shown that they often have a direct effect on goal intention while the effects of negative emotions are mediated through personal norms.

Personal norm

Following Bamberg (2013b, p.153) personal norms are “the felt obligation to behave more in line with personally important moral standards”. In addition, Schwartz (1977) argued that when social norms are internalized, they can lead to personal norms. Bamberg (2013a) showed that personal norms are a predictor of goal intentions in the pre-decision stage of the initial SSBC framework. Similarly, Keller et al. (2019) claimed that personal norms are among the strongest predictors for goal intentions for reducing single use cups. Klöckner (2017) also argued that personal norms, which are determined by social norms and awareness of consequences, are important for goal intentions in the pre-decision stage which is in line with various scholars such as Li et al. (2019), Richter and Hunicke (2020) and Sunio et al. (2018). Furthermore, Mei et al.

(2019) stated that personal norms are the most important predictor for an individual to form goal intentions.

Klößner (2014) found that personal norms were only relevant in predicting goal intention on the within-level but not between people, meaning that increase in personal norms over time within a person triggered a change in goal intentions. Similarly, in the study of Ohnmacht et al. (2018), it was found that the higher the personal norms, the higher the probability of belonging to a higher phase.

In addition to social norms, research applying the SSBC framework often incorporates personal norms and tends to show their importance in predicting goal intention. Contrary to the indirect effect of social norms, personal norms seem to have a significant main effect. Although the studies above clearly show a promising potential of personal norms, it is important to note that previous research found that personal norms are not only important in the pre-decision phase but also in the later phases of the SSBC framework. Furthermore, there are also few authors who did not find any effect of this construct such as Kowalska-Pyzalska and Byrka (2019).

Perceived responsibility

In Bamberg's initial study (2013a), showing responsibility for behaviour that causes environmental harm may lead to negative emotions which might in turn activate personal norms leading to goal intentions. Bamberg also found that there is a relation between perceived responsibility and social norms. In the study of Keller et al. (2019), perceived responsibility was together with social norms and awareness of consequences important for personal norm. Similarly, Klößner (2014) argued that perceived responsibility and social norms can explain differences in personal norms on a between-people level. More recently, Mei et al. (2024) argued that perceived responsibility played a moderating role between awareness of negative consequences and negative emotions. The authors found that perceived responsibility affected personal norms indirectly, mediated by social norms and negative emotions, which is also in line with Bamberg (2013a). The other study from Klößner (2017) found only a weak impact of perceived responsibility on personal norms. In contrast to the results above, Sunio et al. (2018) found that perceived responsibility is not a significant predictor associated with personal norms. It is also noteworthy that there are authors

in our literature review who did not include perceived responsibility in adopting the SSBC framework such as Richter and Hunecke (2020).

Despite the lower popularity of the construct, the findings highlight the overall effect of perceived responsibility on personal norms in the first phase of the SSBC framework, which in turn might result in goal intention. Because there is some disagreement in the literature regarding the impact of the construct, more research on the impact of perceived responsibility is recommended.

Perceived negative consequences of own behaviour

Within the initial study of Bamberg (2013a), perceived negative consequences of current behaviour is also a predictor of goal intentions in the first stage of the SSBC. This construct is sometimes conceived as “problem awareness” among authors included in our review. Mei et al. (2024) found that perceived personal responsibility played a moderating role between awareness of the negative consequences of the own behaviour and negative emotions. The study by Li et al. (2019) also found that personal norms were influenced by awareness of consequences in the pre-decisional stage. The authors also found that awareness played a more important role on personal norms among less habitual car users compared to more habitual car users. Also, according to Klöckner (2017), awareness of the negative consequences of beef consumption (along with social norms) is important to determine personal norms. The results in the earlier study of Klöckner (2014) showed that the perceived negative consequences of behaviour could explain differences in goal intentions on the between-people level. On the contrary, Sunio et al. (2018) did not include problem awareness in their model because it was no significant predictor. With regard to the stage affiliation effect, Sunio et al. (2018) found no significant impact. It is important to note that various authors, such as Richter and Hunecke (2020), did not include this variable in their study.

Although perceived responsibility or problem awareness is only applied by a few authors in the field, we find (with the exception of one study) general support for the significance of the variable in the pre-decisional stage.

Perceived goal feasibility

Although goal feasibility was an important predictor of goal intention in Bamberg's (2013a) model, few authors in our literature review looked into detail at this variable. According to Keller et al. (2019), perceived goal feasibility was the second strongest predictor of goal intention after personal norms. Another finding stemming from the study of Mei et al. (2024) is the significant association between perceived goal feasibility and perceived behavioural control. Another attempt at analysing perceived goal feasibility was undertaken by Kowalska-Pyzalska and Byrka (2019). The authors included perceived goal feasibility and perceived behavioural control as one variable and found that it was a significant predictor of monitoring energy use in almost all stages of the SSBC framework.

There are very few studies covering the construct of perceived goal feasibility. The results above indicate that perceived goal feasibility, although conceptualized differently, is an important factor in the SSBC model and can sometimes play a role across different stages.

Goal intention

The first transition from the pre-decisional to the pre-actional stage in the stage model of Bamberg (2013a) is marked by the formation of the goal intention. As already described above, goal intention can directly or indirectly be activated by various constructs from the pre-decisional stage. Sunio et al. (2018) pointed out that goal intention is activated by personal norm, attitude, anticipated positive emotions, and self-efficacy. Goal intention is explained by personal norms, perceived goal feasibility, and positive emotions anticipated with goal achievement in the study of Mei et al. (2024). Further, Klöckner (2017) showed that goal intentions in the pre-decision stage were determined by personal norms. He also showed that goal intentions were higher in the pre-action, action, and post-action stage compared to the first, pre-decisional stage. In another study of Klöckner (2014), it was found that positive anticipated emotions were the main predictor of goal intentions. Richter and Hunecke (2020) found an indirect effect of their variable of mindfulness (observing) on goal intention for organic food consumption which was mediated by personal norms and attitudes. In line with Bamberg (2013a), the study carried out by Li et al. (2019) showed the importance of goal intention on behavioural intention in the pre-actional stage. Furthermore, the authors suggested that relationship between social norm and goal

intention were also mediated by personal norms. These results contrast with some previous research in the field, in which no relationship was found. According to Keller et al. (2021), goal intention in the pre-decisional stage was formed by personal norm (strongest effect), followed by perceived goal feasibility and positive emotions. However, in contrast to the studies above, there was no or only a very small significant relationship between goal intention and behavioural intention. Furthermore, the authors found no significant difference between the goal intentions of individuals in the pre-decisional and pre-actional stages.

Thus, the view that different constructs from the pre-decisional stage are important to form a goal intention and that also goal intention itself seems to be important to form behavioural intentions seems to be shared by the majority of the authors with an exception of the study by Keller et al. (2021).

Stage 2

Attitudes

Attitudes are an important predictor of behavioural intentions in the pre-action stage of the original SSBC framework (Bamberg, 2013). Next to social and personal norms, attitudes are also often discussed among other authors in the literature making use of the SSBC framework. Klöckner (2017) found that attitudes were among the strongest predictors for behavioural intentions. The study of Li et al. (2019) and Keller et al. (2019), also found that attitudes were important for the behavioural intention. This is similar to the recent study of Mei et al. (2024), where behavioural intentions toward active school travel mode were activated by attitudes.

Some scholars looked at the importance of attitudes across the different phases in the stage model. Kowalska-Pyzalska and Byrka (2019) for instance, found attitudes to be important in the first stage. Also Richter and Hunecke (2020) identified an indirect role of positive attitudes toward organic food consumption in the relationship between mindfulness and goal intention part of the first phase. In the study of Sunio et al. (2018) behavioural and goal intentions are both influenced by attitudes. Furthermore, participants in their study were more likely to hold a low level of attitudes at the lower stages. In the study of Klöckner (2014), although only marginally significant, attitudes predicted the behavioural intention in the pre-action stage on the between level but not on the within person level.

Next to social and personal norms, attitudes are a construct which is often empirically tested in the SSBC framework among all the included authors in our literature review. Although the construct is investigated in the second phase of the original SSBC framework of Bamberg (2013a), different authors look at attitudes in other stages as well. Based on the literature, attitudes might play a role in different phases and are not only important to predict the behavioural intention.

Perceived behaviour control

Perceived behavioural control refers to beliefs about someone's ability to perform a specific behaviour (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). The mechanism of perceived behavioural control is (next to attitudes) an important predictor of behavioural intention in the second stage (Bamberg, 2013). Keller et al. (2019) argued that perceived behavioural control is the strongest predictor in the pre-actional stage. In the study of Li et al. (2019) perceived behavioural control was also found to be an important predictor for behavioural intention. Although Klöckner (2017) found a significant effect of perceived behavioural control on the behavioural intention for introducing more vegetarian meals, the effect was much smaller for reducing portion size and was not significant for substituting beef. Differently is the study of Mei et al. (2024) who did not find any direct effect of perceived behavioural control on behavioural intention but only an indirect effect through the construct of attitudes. In contrast to the authors mentioned above, Klöckner (2014) did not find an impact of perceived behavioural control on either the between person or the within person level.

Perceived behaviour control is an often examined and well-established construct in the applied SSBC framework. Although the great majority of the authors (with the exception of Klöckner in both his studies) found perceived behavioural control to be important in the second phase of the stage for the behavioural intention, some authors argue that the construct has also an importance in the first or later stages.

Behavioural intention

A second intention type in the SSBC framework from Bamberg (2013a) is the behavioural intention. Li et al. (2019) found that behavioural intention is important to predict the implementation intention which is in line with Mei et al. (2024). This latter study also found that behavioural intention was predicted by goal intention, attitude, and habits. Also in Sunio et al. (2018) behavioural intentions are formed by goal

intentions, action plans and attitudes. The behavioural intention in the pre-action stage of Klöckner (2014) is marginally significantly predicted by positive attitudes towards a specific electric car model and significantly predicted by the construct of knowledge about electric cars which was also included in his model. In his study only differences in knowledge were statistically significant towards behavioural intentions on the within person level. In the study by Keller et al. (2019), behavioural intention was the strongest predictor in the actional stage of the framework. Although Bamberg (2013a) included behavioural intention in the transition from the second to the third phase, other authors do not always follow this direction.

Stage 3

Maintenance self-efficacy

Maintenance self-efficacy is one of the constructs being part of the third stage, the action stage, in the initial study of Bamberg (2013a). Self-efficacy is defined as the confidence of being able to perform and maintain a difficult behaviour (Schwarzer, 2008). Given the cross-sectional design of the study, Bamberg (2013a) did not measure the constructs being part of the third and fourth phase of the SSBC model and referred to it as a weakness of the study.

Sunio et al. (2018) and Richter and Hunecke (2020) discussed the construct of maintenance self-efficacy in their studies but did not empirically measure it. Hence, given the lack of research looking at the construct of self-efficacy, future studies are needed to assess the role of this construct in applied SSBC models.

Planning ability

Next to self-efficacy, coping planning and action planning are included in the third phase of the SSBC framework from Bamberg (2013a). Based on Schwarzer (2008), Sunio et al. (2018) define action planning as “action planning refers to the specific situation parameters, e.g. “when” and “where”, and the sequence of actions necessary to implement the target behaviour, i.e. “how” and coping planning as “the ability to anticipate situations that may hinder the individual to perform the target behaviour and to develop a plan to cope with such situations.” (Sunio et al., 2018, p.100). Different to the original framework of Bamberg (2013a), Sunio et al. (2018) suggested that action planning and coping planning are important for someone's behavioural intention. Li et

al. (2019) also looked at action planning and coping planning and it was found that both constructs had a significant positive impact on an individual's implementation intention although the impact of action planning was greater compared to coping planning.

Although Bamberg (2013a) discussed coping planning and action planning as two different constructs, some authors identified the constructs together (e.g., minimizing questionnaire length) and refer to it as "planning ability". Klöckner (2017), for instance, found that planning ability was important for substituting beef and eating more vegetarian meals. He also found planning ability in the action stage to be the only important predictor on both the within and the between level. Also Keller et al. (2021) combined both variables of planning into one construct. Planning ability was only a weaker predictor in the model of the authors since it was only significant for using a refundable cup and not for reduced consumption.

Thus, although the concept of planning ability has rarely been tested within the SSBC framework, the few studies show that planning ability seems to be important for behavioural change.

Implementation intention

The third and last intention included in the SSBC framework is the implementation intention. The formation of an implementation intention marks the transition to the post-actional stage. In the study of Li et al. (2019) and Mei et al. (2024), implementation intentions are important for conducting the new behaviour. More specifically, implementation intention had a significant negative impact on participants who continued using the car while they found a significant positive impact on participants who planned to switch to more sustainable travel modes. Implementation intentions were also a strong predictor for the new behaviour in the study of Keller et al. (2019). Klöckner (2017) found that implementation intentions were almost solely determined by behavioural intentions. Furthermore, strong implementation intentions for substituting beef and eating more vegetarian meals were important for reducing beef, but this was not the case for the behaviour of reducing portion size of meat. Sunio et al. (2018) did not test the impact of implementation intention itself but found out that implementation intention is predicted by behavioural intention, action planning, coping planning, and recovery efficacy. Overall, although depending on the behaviour itself,

the studies above reveal the fact that the implementation intention is important to perform new behaviour.

Stage 4

Recovery self-efficacy

Following Schwarzer (2008), recovery self-efficacy refers to a person's confidence in being capable of resuming a difficult behaviour after a relapse. The only authors in our review who empirically tested the construct of recovery self-efficacy are Sunio et al. (2018). They found out that the construct had the largest influence on performing the new behaviour. It has to be noted that the authors tested the constructs differently compared to the original framework of Bamberg (2013a). They found for instance, that a goal intention depended on the mechanism of recovery self-efficacy (next to perceived behavioural control).

Conclusion

The primary aim of this study was to provide insight into the mechanisms of behaviour change and identify important factors through a review of the literature on the SSBC model. Understanding these mechanisms can improve the effectiveness of interventions designed to promote pro-environmental behaviour. This paper combines data from various studies, increasing the reliability of the findings and providing a clearer understanding of the pathways between the different constructs of the SSBC model. While there are ongoing discussions about the promise of tailoring interventions to stages of change, our review shows that the stage model has potential to include in the CircleUp project. Therefore, after conducting a literature review on the SSBC, the CircleUp project suggests Bamberg's (2013b) stage model of self-regulated behavioural change (SSBC) as its main theoretical framework, since it combines most of the abovementioned components in a structured, dynamic conceptual framework. The shift from a linear to a circular economy requires behavioural changes in consumption patterns, particularly for high-income consumers and high levels of consumption (Steffen, Rockström, Richardson, Lenton, Folke, & Liverman, 2018). Yet, one could argue that consumers' adoption of circular economy practices gradually unfold in different stages and evolve over time. To address the perspective of behavioural change, stage models have been implemented within the field of environmental psychology (Keller, Eisen, & Hanss, 2019). Stage models view

behavioural change as a dynamic process, while statistical models such as the Theory of Planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) mostly consider behaviour change as a one-step decision. Furthermore, stage models have been proposed to clarify the so-called intention-behaviour gap, emphasising that having an intention does not ensure that the action will be carried out (Mack & Tampe-Mai, 2016). By utilizing the SSBC model as our theoretical framework, we aim to understand and explain the changing consumer behaviour and develop structural consumer interventions within the CircleUp project.

2.3.3 Explaining consumer behaviour changes with the stage model of self-regulated behavioural change

Within the CircleUp project, we want to explain the processes of change in circular economy behaviour by the stage model of self-regulated behavioural change (SSBC). The SSBC is a useful framework for understanding consumer behaviour, especially in the context of adopting new behaviours. The SSBC model outlines four different stages that individuals go through when changing their behaviour and attitudes.

In the pre-decisional stage, people become aware of the consequences of their behaviour and start considering the need to change their old behaviour. For example, a person in the first stage might realize the environmental impact of using single-use plastic and starts to think about reducing their use of single-use plastic. At the end of the second stage, the pre-actional stage, people form an intention to change their behaviour and start planning how to implement the new behaviour. For example, a person decides to switch to a reusable shopping bag and starts planning where and when to buy or how to get the reusable bag. At the end of the actional stage, the consumer starts to perform the new behaviour and its planning. In this case, the person starts to use the reusable bag more often and integrates the new behaviour in his or her daily routine. In the post-action stage, the person starts to reflect on the new behaviour and evaluate the behaviour. The person must deal with the challenges to not revert to the old behaviour. By using the SSBC stage model, we can design tailored interventions to each of the stages, making it easier and more motivating for the consumer to progress through the new stages and adopt the new behaviour. Based on the literature, we know that different interventions strategies are important across the different stages. For example, providing information on why single-use plastic is damaging our planet and raising awareness can be effective in the first stage, the pre-

decision stage. While offering people practical tips and tools can help people in the pre-action and the action stages.

2.4 Building community through collective actions and circular stories

2.4.1 Theoretical Background

The behavioural change required to achieve systemic sustainability cannot be achieved by focusing solely on the attitudes and behaviour of individuals. Conversely, changing individual behaviour has the potential to shape broader social norms and practices, thereby influencing the behaviour of others (Nielsen et al. 2021). Also, individual behaviour is closely linked to social and societal structures: They both develop within and shape these structures. Therefore, focusing solely on the individual level would limit individuals to the role of mere 'green consumers' and neglect their potential as active citizens and agents of change (Schulte et al. 2020). Furthermore, belonging to social groups fulfils the fundamental human need for social connection and acceptance by providing a source of social validation (Haslam et al. 2022; Fong et al. 2021).

In line with these ideas, we complement the stage model approach as described in the previous section with an innovative theory-driven community building approach. While its core elements have shown robust empirical support in the healthcare sector, they have rarely been applied in the context of sustainability. This section outlines the rationale and introduces the theoretical foundations and core concepts on which it is based.

What is community?

The concept of community can extend beyond geographical boundaries. Communities can also be seen as units of social interaction, as symbolic units of collective identity, and as social units where people come together politically for change (Minkler et al. 1997). Rooted in Situated Learning Theory (Wenger 1998), the concept of Communities of Practice emphasises a community as the context in which individuals develop values and identities, as well as knowledge and skills relevant to that community. Learning, in this view, involves a process of understanding who we are and in which communities of practice we belong and are accepted. On a pragmatic level, a community of practice can be defined as a group of individuals who are informally connected by their collaborative activities, such as discussions and problem-solving, and by the knowledge they acquire through these shared engagements (Wenger 1998).

Community and pro-environmental action in light of the social identity approach

A theory that similarly emphasises the importance of social interaction and belonging to groups is the Social Identity Theory (Tajfel and Turner, 1979), which builds together with the Self-Categorisation-Theory (Turner, 1982, 1985; Turner, Oakes, Reichel and Wetherell, 1987) the Social Identity Approach (SIA). The SIA explains how individuals develop and maintain their sense of self based on their group memberships. People categorize themselves and others into social groups based on shared characteristics, such as race, ethnicity, gender, religion, nationality, or profession. A person's social identity is defined as "the sum total of the social identifications used by a person to define him or herself" (Turner 1982). Examples of social identifications in connection with pro-environmental behaviour include social identification as a recycler or as organic consumer (Udall et al. 2020). When individuals self-categorise in terms of a social identity and that specific identity becomes salient, their thoughts, emotions, and behaviours tend to align with the norms, values, and shared understandings of that group (Postmes et al. 2005).

In the context of climate action, the consequence of a cognitive shift from individual goals, beliefs, or cost-benefit considerations to group-oriented goals ("We want to do more to protect the climate"), collective benefits ("My climate-friendly behaviour supports the well-being of my group"), and shared beliefs in collective efficacy ("Together, we can make a difference in addressing climate change") can be a key

driver for behavioural change, as Masson and Fritsche (2021) put it. Empirical evidence from meta-analyses supports this (Vesely et al. 2021): Identification with groups considered to directly support climate-friendly behaviour had a stronger effect on pro-environmental intentions and behaviour ($r = 0.48/0.51$), compared to identification with groups unrelated to environmental topics ($r = 0.30/0.15$). It is noteworthy that even identification with these unrelated, neutral groups shows a moderate positive effect - Vesely et al. attribute this to the broad societal consensus that climate protection is regarded as a significant collective goal.

To use social identification as a driver for behavioural change, it is important to understand how social identity forms. We draw on Social Identity Approach and specifically use the Common Ingroup Identity Model (Gaertner et al. 1993) and the Interactive Model of Social Identity Formation (Postmes et al. 2005). The Common Ingroup Identity Model was introduced by Gaertner et al. (1993) as a means to reduce intergroup bias and group-based discrimination. It emphasises *recategorisation* as a mechanism for shaping social identification. When individuals of different groups are encouraged to perceive themselves as part of a unified, shared group, their attitudes toward former outgroup members tend to become more positive – an effect grounded in the principles of SIA. Based on this assumption, the authors propose two ways for fostering a more inclusive social categorisation: the first is to increase the salience of existing common superordinate group memberships, and second, by introducing new shared factors, such as common goals, tasks or a sense of collective fate.

The Interactive Model of Social Identity Formation (Postmes et al. 2005) highlights social influence in small groups as a mechanism to form social identification. In this perspective, the process of forming social identification is inherently interactive, occurring through two complementary pathways (figure Figure).

Figure 7: Interactive Model of Social Identity Formation (Postmes et al. 2005). Own illustration, simplified.

From a top-down perspective, social identity is influenced by group-level processes and intergroup comparisons. From a bottom-up perspective, social identity emerges dynamically through interpersonal interactions and shared experiences within the community.

To promote the development of a shared social identity within the CircleUp project, we build on the principle of re-categorisation (Gaertner et al., 1993) by fostering a sense of common fate, i.e. identifying as part of the CircleUp project, and introducing shared tasks, particularly through largely simultaneous challenges. These challenges include collaborative elements, encouraging interaction and cooperation. This will allow for small group engagement, both within the digital environment and, importantly, also in the real-world. Like this, we establish the bottom-up formation of social identity, as outlined in the Interactive Model of Social Identity Formation (Postmes et al., 2005).

Building Social Identification in Interventions – Empirical Evidence

Based on the theoretical underpinning of social identity, social identification building interventions have emerged as promising approach (Steffens et al. 2021). These interventions seek to cultivate a shared sense of identity ("we") with the aim of reinforcing various positive psychological factors by leveraging group dynamics and identity processes. For example, social identity building interventions have shown to reduce stress and loneliness (Haslam et al. 2005; Haslam et al. 2022). They have been applied in various fields: in educational programmes (Berman et al. 2008; Horowitz et al. 2018; Oyserman 2014; Oyserman and Destin 2010; Thomas et al. 2008), in work contexts (Simbula et al. 2023), in community-building contexts (Cruwys et al. 2022; Fong et al. 2021b) and in healthcare (Haslam et al. 2022; Morina et al. 2021; Steffens et al. 2021; Watts and Hovick 2023), with the vast majority of studies published in the latter.

In the healthcare sector, social identification-building interventions have demonstrated a positive impact on psychological health and well-being (Steffens et al. 2021). In their meta-analysis, Steffens et al. classify these interventions into four distinct categories: (a) group-relevant decision making, involving reflection and decision-making about group dynamics; (b) reminiscence groups, focusing on shared reflection on past memories; (c) shared activities, including both simultaneous individual tasks and interdependent tasks; and (d) group-based therapy programs, explicitly focusing on

developing the self for improved functioning and health. The results reveal that interventions focusing on group-relevant decision making and therapy programs had the strongest impact on health-related outcomes (Hedges' $g = 1.26$ and 1.02).

The majority of these mechanisms have been applied in small group settings. To ensure scalability and enable a broader reach, CircleUp will add a digital storytelling component. This element is grounded in ethnographic approaches, as outlined in the following section.

Formation of Identity in the Lens of Narrative Approaches

The "Circular Story" is the central narrative element in CircleUp's social game and community-building concept. The function of narratives is "a way of making sense of the world, at times equated with experience, time, history and life itself" (see Georgakopoulou & Goutsos, 2000, pp. 64–68). According to discursive approaches (Bamberg et al. 2011), identity is constructed through two complementary pathways, which align with the interactive social-psychological perspective outlined earlier. From a top-down perspective, identity is formed through societal discourse ("capital-D discourse"), which determines identities through societal norms and traditions. From a bottom-up perspective, "the person agentively constructs who they are by use of discourse", referred to "small-d" discursive practices (Bamberg et al. 2011). The main difference between the two pathways lies in the agency and control of the individual.

In the context of consumption experiences, ethnographic approaches distinguish between "big stories" and "small stories" (Carù and Cova 2008). *Big stories* are detached from the routine of everyday life and entail introspection and broader reflections on life episodes or individually important experiences. *Small stories*, on the other hand, emerge from daily experiences and therefore function as "the fabric of social practices that ordinary people engage in" (Georgakopoulou, 2022). Like this, they help individuals connect with others, make sense of emotional experiences, and position themselves socially.

These everyday narratives are not merely personal expressions; they might also communicate values or reinforce social norms, and there they contribute to identity construction. For example, if somebody shares that today they got their long-cherished leather purse repaired, and expresses satisfaction in doing so, they are signaling care, frugality, and commitment to CE principles.

Example for circular consumer behaviour, own picture.

The use of storytelling reflects a broader paradigm shift in climate change communication, from linear transmission of facts to interactive, participatory approaches. Rather than treating communication as a one-way flow of information, current models view it as a constitutive process in which shared meanings are produced and reproduced (Ballantyne 2016).

One key reason for this shift is the differing psychological impact of stories versus facts. The motivation to process information depends heavily on scientific literacy and existing beliefs; in some cases, facts that contradict an individual's worldview may even increase resistance (Toomey 2023). In contrast, stories are processed experientially rather than analytically. They feel less abstract, more relatable, and can reduce counter-arguing by engaging audiences emotionally (Morris et al. 2019).

Stories as drivers of emotion and motivation

This relatability of stories is greatly influenced by emotions. Personal stories can evoke climate-related emotions, such as worry and compassion, which have been shown to mediate the change in climate beliefs and risk perception (Gustafson et al. 2020). While negative emotions, such as fear or worry, tend to be more arousing (Zaremba et al. 2024), positive emotions broaden people's thought-action repertoires, increasing creativity and solution-oriented thinking (Fredrickson 2001). Particularly, the anticipation of warm glow, "an affective-emotional state, [which] captures the feeling of wellbeing related to the contribution to a good cause" is associated with prosocial behaviour (Hartmann et al. 2017). Thus, as Brosch (2021) argues, warm glow can act as an emotional reward, reinforcing sustainable choices. In this way, emotions and anticipated affect play a crucial role as intrinsic motivators for sustainable action

(Brosch 2021). They function both as outcomes of pro-environmental behaviour (experienced warm glow) and as precursors to such actions (anticipated warm glow). This dynamic suggests a reinforcement mechanism whereby the warm glow experienced can inspire future pro-environmental behaviour.

Through the storytelling element, we aim to foster identification with the Circular Citizen by encouraging people to share personal stories about their engagement in circular practices. In this way, we understand circular stories as creative and educational elements that encourage participants to engage with CE practices through storytelling. Through the storytelling element of the intervention, we aim to foster identification with the Circular Citizen by encouraging individuals to share personal experiences related to circular practices. This component invites participants to reflect on and document moments in their everyday lives where they engaged in sustainable behaviours, such as repairing an item, reusing materials, or choosing second-hand products. These personal accounts, referred to as Circular Stories, form a central part of the intervention and are encouraged and shared within the digital platform. We understand these stories as both creative and educational tools that not only strengthen individual engagement with circular practices but also contribute to a shared identity and collective learning through narrative exchange.

The Circular Stories serve multiple purposes. First, they give participants a sense of agency by offering the opportunity to document their engagement in circular practices, creating space for reflection and creativity. Second, they make individual actions visible to others, enabling social interaction through likes and comments, which fosters a sense of connection and shared purpose. Third, Circular Stories contribute to a growing repository of lived experiences and creative solutions, expanding the collective imagination of what Circular Citizenship can entail and helping to normalise circular practices in everyday life.

Importantly, sharing and receiving recognition for these stories can evoke or strengthen a feeling of warm glow as positive emotional reward for the documented actions. We expect that this emotional reinforcement may support the emotional attachment towards the shared Circular Citizen identity and, in turn, strengthen intrinsic motivation. The next section will give a rationale for the possible content of this social category, focusing on the citizen component.

What is Circular Citizenship?

While the concrete circular practices have been outlined earlier in this document, we now briefly turn to a political science perspective to conceptualise the idea of *citizenship* - a notion central to understanding the deeper societal implications of participation in circular economy initiatives.

Traditional conceptions of citizenship, such as Turner's (1990) Theory of Citizenship, emphasise civil, political, and social rights, alongside duties to the state and society. This understanding is primarily grounded in the framework of the nation-state and formal institutions.

More recent expansions of this concept, such as Green European Citizenship (Machin & Tan, 2024), acknowledge the political and ethical dimensions of environmental sustainability. Here, citizenship is no longer limited to institutional engagement, but includes responsibilities toward global communities, non-human nature, and future generations. It encompasses lifestyle choices and collective activism aimed at ecological justice and democratic environmental governance.

Circular Citizenship, as we propose it here, builds upon and extends these traditions by rooting citizenship in the practices, values, and infrastructures of the circular economy. It frames individuals not just as consumers or private actors, but as co-creators of systems that enable more sustainable, resilient, and inclusive communities. Circular citizens are actively involved in shaping local circular infrastructures (e.g. sharing platforms, repair cafés, reuse systems) and developing everyday habits that reflect care, cooperation, sufficiency, and creativity.

Tabl 4 outlines how circular citizenship compares to classical and ecological citizenship models across several key dimensions:

Table 4: Concepts of Citizenship

	Classical theory of modern social citizenship (Turner 1990)	Green European Citizenship (as outlined by Machin and Tan 2024)	Circular Citizenship
Rights	civil, political, and social (e.g. free speech,	access to environmental goods, such as clean air and	Rights to participate in shaping local circular

	voting, education, welfare)	water, and the protection against environmental harms, but also the procedural rights to participate in the debates over definition and allocation of those substantive rights	infrastructures and policies; access to resources and services enabling circular lifestyles (e.g. right to repair)
Duties	Obeying laws, paying taxes, fulfilling civic responsibilities (e.g. jury duty or military service)	private and public: - private duties involve changing lifestyle and consumption habits, e.g. eating, travelling and communicating differently - public duties: actively taking part in policy debates	Circular citizenship emphasises local embeddedness (e.g. community-level repair cafés) while acknowledging the need for systemic transformation beyond individual behaviour change.
Virtues	Civic responsibility, loyalty, respect for law, social solidarity	ideal of the 'ecological steward', i.e. considering the interests of fellow citizens, non-humans, foreigners and future generations	Cooperation, care, sufficiency, creativity, mutual responsibility, (local) solidarity
Practices	Voting, participating in civil society, engaging in public debate, joining unions or associations	participation which include activities - that match and support governmental strategies - that contest and challenge those, e.g. through non-violent activism and direct actions	Practicing private circular behaviours (reuse, repair, share), engaging in public collaborative infrastructure, (e.g. community repair or sharing initiatives, or urban composting/ gardening).

By embedding the principles of circularity and sustainable practice in a collective identity, *Circular Citizenship* offers a powerful and inclusive framework. Identifying as

a circular citizen can function as an empowering narrative that helps people see themselves as agents of change by recognising their collective agency.

Motivating participation through gamification

To support this identity-building process and encourage sustained engagement, gamification offers a promising tool. Gamification is popularly understood as “using game elements in contexts other than games” (Deterding et al., 2011). The principles of gamification encompass clearly defined progression paths with attainable goals, structured levels and rewards, which give players agency over their actions (Douglas and Brauer, 2021). Game elements such as points, meaningful narratives, player rankings, performance graphs, badges, teammates, avatars etc, are building blocks of games (Sailer et al. 2017). These are quite readily implemented in most video games and have been shown to provide a variety of benefits also in non-game contexts.

Introducing game-like elements can elevate user motivation and engagement, leading to greater participation, better interaction, more knowledge sharing, and an overall improved user experience and satisfaction with the application (Koroleva und Novak 2020). In the context of serious games, such elements can also foster a sense of narrative, enhance social interaction, add enjoyment and increase interest in science as well as in exploration and discovery (Latifi et al. 2022).

However, in the context of sustainability interventions, the application of gamification should not be pursued solely for its own sake. Instead, it must be purposefully designed to support behavioural change and, ideally, to strengthen intrinsic motivation towards sustainable actions. Caution is especially warranted when extrinsic rewards are introduced. For instance, Hanus and Fox (2015) found in their experimental study that combining leaderboards, badges, and competitive mechanics in an educational setting did not enhance learning outcomes. Instead, it diminished students’ motivation, satisfaction, and sense of empowerment. The authors suggest that when such rewards are perceived as controlling, they may undermine autonomy, reduce confidence, and ultimately discourage deeper engagement with the content.

Sailer et al. (2017) examine the purpose and function of commonly used game elements. Table 5 summarises their discussion and outlines the motivational mechanisms associated with each element.

Table 5: Game elements

Element	Definition, purpose and limitations (Sailer et. al 2017)	Motivational aspects
points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - numerically represent the players' progress - provide continuous and immediate feedback - allow measurement of the players' in-game behavior 	rewards, extrinsic motivation
badges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - visual representations of achievements that can be earned or collected - serve as goals, feedback, or virtual status symbols - influence player choices by leading them to select certain routes - may symbolize exclusive group membership if challenging to achieve 	rewards, extrinsic motivation, social comparison, group dynamics
leaderboards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - competitive indicators comparing a player's performance to others - motivate if close to achieving next higher rank - demotivating if consistently low-ranked - social pressure is effective when competitors have similar skill levels 	social comparison, social pressure
performance graphs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - visually depict player's own performance over time, highlighting personal improvement - use individual standards rather than social comparison (as in leaderboards) - promote a mastery orientation beneficial for learning 	rewards, intrinsic motivation
meaningful stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - narrative context in which a gamified application can be embedded - contextualise activities, providing meaning beyond points and achievements - enrich mundane real-world tasks by analogy or fictional overlay (e.g., zombie chase during a jog) - may increase motivation particularly if the story is in line with the players' personal interests 	intrinsic motivation, imagination, identification with respective characters/context

avatars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - visual representations uniquely distinguishing individual players from other human or computer-controlled avatars - can be selected or created by the player - enable identity creation and exploration - signal community belonging in cooperative contexts 	identification, intrinsic motivation, self-expression
teammates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - real players or virtual characters (NPCs) - sources of conflict, competition, or cooperation - may foster collaboration by grouping players towards shared objectives 	group dynamics, social interaction

With its strong motivational potential, gamification is frequently employed to encourage behaviour change and reinforce positive actions (Bassanelli et al. 2022). A widely adopted theory for understanding the motivational appeal of games and gamification is Self-Determination Theory (Koivisto and Hamari 2019; van Roy and Zaman 2019; Sailer et al. 2017).

Self-Determination theory (Deci and Ryan 1985, p.417) posits that “the human organism is evolved to be inherently active, intrinsically motivated, and oriented toward developing naturally through integrative processes. These qualities need not be learned; they are inherent in human nature.” Motivation, in this context, arises within the dynamic tension between autonomy and external control. Therefore, human motivation can be described as either intrinsic or extrinsic, depending on whether an activity is undertaken for its inherent enjoyment and value, or for external reasons such as rewards, approval, or obligations. If a behaviour is intrinsically motivated, it most likely fulfils the three universal psychological needs that are fundamental to human functioning and well-being: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Competence involves the sense of effectively mastering a given challenge, while autonomy reflects the freedom to choose which challenges to pursue. Relatedness refers to the experience of being recognised, accepted, and connected to others (Deci et al. 2001).

These three needs provide a valuable design lens for developing an engaging gamified experience within CircleUp’s stage model approach. Table 6 outlines how the gamified approach will build on these needs:

Table 6: Fulfilment of the three basic psychological needs (Deci & Ryan, 1985) within the gamified app

Social Relatedness	Competence	Autonomy
<p>The platform will provide a basis a social network where players can connect, share, and support one another, both in the app and in the real world.</p>	<p>The approach fosters a sense of competence by enabling players to track their progress, reflect on their achievements, and receive feedback on their actions.</p>	<p>Participants can actively generate content and explore new sustainable practices, knowledge and resources, both in the app and the real world.</p>
<p>Elements:</p>	<p>Elements:</p>	<p>Elements:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges: run simultaneously for all participants in one country • Circular Stories: liking each other's stories, giving feedback • Group formation • Group challenges: collaborative actions, group decision making, group discussions • Real-world: small group interactions, e.g. skill sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habit tracker: supports self-monitoring • Performance graphs: visual feedback on progress of challenge completion • Badges or achievements: optional gamified reinforcement for completed actions or skill development • Challenge completion summaries: include the content from journaling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges: decide <i>how</i> to do the challenge • Circular Stories: foster a sense of creativity • Knowledge Base/ Local Map: exploring CE resources and initiatives in the neighborhood • Real world: e.g. exploring "hidden treasures" in their households

Summary

In summary, the gamified Circular Stories Community Building Approach takes into account the social embeddedness of people and their need for social connection and acceptance. It provides opportunities for social support, which can buffer against the negative effects of stress and adversity, which may occur when people face life changes or are anxious about the future of the planet. Enabling peer-to-peer-learning and group activities will potentially shape social norms and establish and foster the social identification as a Circular Citizen. This will be done by get people talking about their sustainable practices and sharing their own ideas. Furthermore, reporting their actions in “Circular Stories” allows individuals to see the impact. Together with applying gamification principles, the participants are provided with a sense of accomplishment and progress. Beyond that, the “Circular Stories” will rise the tangibility of the behaviour changes not only in the participating individuals, and but also give possibility to disseminate what the CircleUp project has achieved to a wider audience. Overall, the approach presented here will most likely have the following effects:

- promote the social identity of a circular citizen;
- strengthen the social bonds within the group participants;
- fulfil the need for social connectedness and to rise self-esteem;
- allow design thinking for creative solutions with high contextuality;
- enable communication, also across national borders
- provide a strong multiplier effect through the creation of narratives on circular practices

2.4.2 Process of developing the circular stories gamified approach

Following Morschheuser et al. (2018), we have adopted an iterative approach to develop the circular stories concept. While the *Project Preparation* was mainly completed during the proposal phase, the steps *Analysis of Context and Users*, *Ideation*, *Design*, *Implementation of Design* and *Evaluation* was iterated several times to date, involving feedback loops from gamification experts as well as CircleUp partners. The *Monitoring* and *Evaluation* steps are excluded from this report, as those will be defined in Deliverable 2.2.

Figure 8: Design Process and Design Principles.

This section outlines the key feedback loops integrated into the design process. Two collaborative workshops and one simulation were conducted with all project partners. Workshop 1, held online in May 2024, focused on understanding user needs through the development of personas and user journeys. A simulation, conducted in October 2024 involving all CircleUp partners in presence, focused on testing the first prototype of the gamified approach. Workshop 2, held as well in presence with all CircleUp partners in March 2025, centered on testing in particular the *Circular Stories* element.

In addition to the workshops, two expert interviews were conducted with former professional game designers who now work as researchers and educators in the field of serious games. These interviews provided valuable input along with the workshops and simulation during the ideation and design phase.

Workshop 1 – Understanding user needs through personas and user journeys

Objective. Workshop 1 was designed to support the development of the CircleUp Circular Stories Game by deepening the understanding of user needs, motivations, and contextual factors. The central aim was to collaboratively explore how different types of users presented as personas might interact with the gamified platform, following a user centered design approach (Nielsen 2019)

Participants and Setting. The workshop was held online using MiroBoards to allow for collaborative working. Around 20 project partners from the CircleUp consortium participated. Participants were divided into five heterogeneous working groups. Each group was assigned one out of five different pre-developed personas prepared by the workshop leader. These personas served as fictional yet realistic and research-informed user profiles to anchor discussions and scenario work. The personas represented a diverse range of ages, national backgrounds, available resources (in terms of both time and money), and motivations. To make them more tangible and relatable, each persona was assigned a name, and a photo.

Furthermore, each persona had a detailed character description, which is shown below in the results section.

Workshop Structure and Activities. The workshop was divided into two main tasks, combining creative and analytical elements (Tab17). The first task – persona completion – aimed to foster empathy and establish a narrative basis for the subsequent user journey work. The second task – developing a user journey - enabled participants to contextualise the gamification concept and identify practical touchpoints for supporting behavioural change.

Table 7: Workshop 1 (Personas) - Tasks

Task 1: Persona Completion – Expectations, Goals & Emotions	Task 2: User Journey – Interaction with the Circular Stories Game
<p>Participants were invited to enrich their assigned persona by reflecting on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivations for participating in CircleUp • Goals related to engagement with the Circular Stories Game • Emotional landscape, including potential fears and excitements 	<p>Participants constructed a fictional user journey illustrating how their persona might interact with the game.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities during engagement with the game • Personal Challenges the persona might encounter & possible solutions • Interaction points with material advisors

Content Basis: The Gamification Concept. The activities were grounded in the current gamification concept, which had four realms with extending social context at this time, from “Circular Haven” to “Sustainable Hub”. The user journeys created during the workshop served as a testing ground for applying this concept to different user archetypes.

Results

This section shows the results of the workshop from each group, starting with the persona description provided. This is followed by the workshop results created by the participants on the expectations and goals of this persona, which were clustered into individual and group levels by the workshop leader after the workshop. Then come the emotions, which were clustered into positive and negative after the workshop. Finally, the results from the user journeys are presented.

Group 1 - Camilla and Jasper, the time-bounded¹

Age: 35 and 39
Marital Status: married
Location: Bergen (Norway)
Household/family: Yannik (3), from previous relationships: Christina (8) & Caroline (11), living in the household every second week
Education: M. Sc. in engineering (Camilla), M.A. Administration (Jasper)
Workplace: Production Company (Camilla), Head of Environment in a municipality (Jasper)
Living condition: townhouse with small garden in the outskirts of Bergen
CE knowledge: unfamiliar with this concept, but have a strong understanding of climate change and environmental issues

Hobbies
 - Kayaking (Camilla)
 - spending time with kids, running (Jasper)

What is important
 - that the children grow up in a world worth living in
 - find a good balance between family, career and hobbies

CE practices
 - good in recycling and composting
 - buying durable products

Wishes
 - reduce food waste, buy more regional food
 - minimise the wardrobe
 - knowing how their actions affect the environment and current policies

Camilla and Jasper have enough on their plate with **children and career**. They have lived together for the last five years, and three years ago they got their son Yannik. Jasper has two children from his previous marriage: Christina and Caroline who by now are 11 and eight years. The children stay with Jasper and Camilla every second week.

Camilla and Jasper's **days are busy**, and they spend the weekends on planning who is going to do what in the coming week. Even though they have help to do the cleaning, it is difficult for them to find time for everything. When the older children stay with them, they also have to drive them to their after-school activities.

Jasper and Camilla try to optimise time as much as possible.

Expectations & goals

What's their motivation to participate?
 What does the persona want to achieve by taking part in the CircleUp project and the circular stories game?

Emotions

What fears might they have?
 And what could particularly excite them?

¹ The persona in group 1 is based on a persona example from Nielsen (2019) and was adapted by the authors. The personas in group 2 - 5 were created by the authors. Image sources: ChatGPT

Group 2 – Gisela, the economic carer

Gisela
the economic carer

Age: 56
Marital Status: Single
Location: Bottrop (Germany)
Household/Family: Single household; no children; nurses her mother (82)
Education: Middle School
Workplace: Part-time as an office administrator (15 hrs/week). Receives an additional 332 euros a month in care allowance as a family carer.
Living Condition: Flat in a well-kept apartment building in Bottrop Holthausen
CE Knowledge: unfamiliar with this concept; basic knowledge of environmental issues and climate change

Hobbies:

- Reading mystery novels
- Walking in the forest
- Making handmade jewellery
- Sewing

What's Important:

- Getting by with the money
- Providing the best care for her mother
- Maintaining her own health and well-being

CE practices

- Shopping in second hand stores
- Repairing, upcycling and sewing clothes
- Online selling and buying of used items
- Repurposing and reusing items
- Cooking fresh and seasonal food

Wishes

- more social contacts in the city of Bottrop
- taking a nice holiday

Gisela lives in a flat in an apartment block in Bottrop Holthausen, a city district with a village-like feel. She **appreciates the quiet neighbourhood and nearby forest**, where she likes to go for walks to relax. Five years ago, Gisela moved back to Bottrop to take care of her elderly mother. Since then, she has mastered the balancing act of caring for her mother and herself, and sometimes she reaches her limits.

One of Gisela's main concerns is getting by with the limited financial resources she has. Managing her household on a **tight budget requires careful planning and resourcefulness**. Gisela practices cost-saving measures, such as repairing clothes, and online selling and buying of used items. In general, Gisela questions whether she needs to buy anything at all.

Gisela wishes for more social contact in Bottrop. Her caregiving responsibilities often limit her opportunities to socialize, leaving her feeling isolated at times.

Expectations & goals

What's their motivation to participate?
 What does the persona want to achieve by taking part in the CircleUp project and the circular stories game?

 individual

getting new ideas about sewing, repurposing

Maybe there are engaging stories (she likes stories)

Learning something new about nature and systems

Learning new ways to save money

Emotions

What fears might they have?
 And what could particularly excite them?

 x x

Limited capacity to engage 100% in this project (lack of time)

Fear of lacking money

feeling alone / isolated

 😊

Learning unexpected things could give her a positive feeling

Good feeling about saving money

Appreciation of her skills in sewing / repurposing

becoming happy because of new friends

 group

Socialize with other people

Group 3 – Anna and Fred, the active retirees

Age: 70 and 72
Marital Status: married
Location: Oxford (UK)
Household/family: The two of them, with 2 adult children and 2 grandchildren (12 & 14) living in Banbury, 32 miles away from Oxford
Education: Teacher of English and Fine Arts (Anna), Export Merchant (Fred), both retired
Workplace: Voluntary work in the local hospice (Anna)
Living condition: Central apartment with balcony in the city of Oxford
GE knowledge: Basic understanding of this concept (Anna), quite unfamiliar with this concept (Fred); both are interested in understanding climate change and environmental issues

Hobbies
 - Singing in the chor and gardening on their balcony (Anna)
 - Reading historical novels and engaging in an History Club; cooking (Fred)

What is important
 - Staying active and engaged in their community
 - leaving a good legacy for their children and grandchildren

GE practices
 - Recycling and reducing plastic use
 - Supporting local farmers' markets
 - Using public transportation and walking instead of driving whenever possible

Wishes
 - Learning and adapting to new concepts and technologies
 - Share their knowledge and practices with their family and spending more time with grandchildren

Anna and Fred live in Oxford, a city with lots of history and culture. Three years ago, they sold their house and bought an apartment with an elevator in Grandpont, near the city centre. They have a balcony. The **neighbourhood in the house is nice**, there are like-minded residents of senior age. Also, there is a family living next door with children who regularly come to visit them. That comforts them somewhat that that they **rarely see their grandchildren**, perhaps only once a month.

The couple stays **active and connected to their community**. Fred is in the History Club of Radley, a small town nearby Oxford where he was born. Anna sings in the church chorus and works at a hospice twice a week. At home, Anna looks after her plants and Fred cooks. They like going to the theatre and other cultural events. They try to be sustainable, from recycling to choosing local produce and not using the car much.

Their busy yet balanced lifestyle shows how dedicated they are to living a meaningful and impactful life.

individual

They have the time to do this activity and participate (and doing something meaningful with their time)...

.They want to learn about new technologies, motivated to learn something new...

Achieve -long term - knowledge about the circular economy and what the future holds

They already recycle and want to reuse etc....

Achieve - a sense of achievement and feel good about themselves

group

Already active in the community with volunteering etc....

Want to achieve - represent their generation and showing they can also be part of the game

Want to achieve - learn new things to help their grandchildren and attending different activities with their grandchildren

Motivated by their children and grandchildren for their future....

Bring skills to share with other e.g. gardening and sharing knowledge about past experience

Emotions

What fears might they have? And what could particularly excite them?

Sceptical for the privacy of posting pictures/sharing circular stories

Fear: give too much information on their personal life, and may not be willing or trusting to give too much info away

Sceptical or fearful of the game and the outputs

Fear: Too complicated with the IT skills they need for the game and to learn something new

...Excited to be connected to and a part of the community on another level

Excitement: also excited to learn something new and expand their knowledge

...Excited to meet new people, locally and internationally!

Group 4 – Janis, the music-loving teenager

Age: 17
Marital Status: single
Location: Sakstagals (Latvia), a small village close to Rēzekne
Household/Family: Lives with his parents, Damirs (44, professional soldier) and Agnese (45, works at the Tourism Information Center of Rēzekne), and his sister, Lilija (15)
Education: Attending secondary school in Rēzekne, a town 16 km from Sakstagals
Workplace: None
Living Condition: Own room in the rural family house
CE Knowledge: unfamiliar with this concept; basic knowledge of environmental issues and climate change

Hobbies:
 - Playing guitar
 - Listening to heavy metal music
 - Playing video games

What's Important:
 - Expressing himself through music
 - Staying connected with friends and the online gaming community

CE practices
 - basic recycling at home
 - duty of helping his parents in the family vegetable garden

Wishes
 - start a band
 - finish school and move to a bigger city

Jānis is a 17-year-old teenager living in Sakstagals, Latvia, with his parents and younger sister, Lilija. He attends secondary school in the nearby town of Rēzekne, **commuting 16 km** each day. Jānis has his own room in the rural family house, which he has decorated with posters of his favorite heavy metal bands and gaming setups.

Jānis's relationship with his family is characterized by mutual respect and support. His parents encourage his ambitions in music. They bought him his first guitar and pay for his music lessons. It is difficult for Jānis to find like-minded people in Rēzekne who share his passion for heavy music. **Lilija, Jānis's 15-year-old sister, has very different interests, she is passionate about environmental issues.**

Sometimes Janis feels limited by the lack of opportunities and in comparison to a larger city.

Expectations & goals

What's their motivation to participate?
 What does the persona want to achieve by taking part in CircleUp project and the circular stories game?

no goals related to CU, just music and wish to get to big city

He does not want to achieve anything (most probably his family wants to take part)

his duties in family could motivate him to take some action related to CU (family instructions)

He is not motivated but (could be) pushed by his sister

Emotions

What fears might they have?
 And what could particularly excite them?

fear not to get to Riga, find job, right living partner

no fears related to environmental issues

CU community could help him to find friends in Riga, make contacts to find job, new friends

day 0

Circular Haven

He will not do the game
 annoyed

 or because of agreement with family he will take part
 annoyed

(in case each family member should participate to collect points, Janis is obligated to do his tasks)

 get direct benefits promised by parents
 excited

to get a new guitar (as completing his obligations in game)
 proud

resell his old guitar - to get additional bonus points for family
 happy

Eco Alliance

He could join the group through his sister (make a music & poems on CE topic, see that being in group is cool (because of people, not CU project))

he creates a song about CE (being annoyed by his sister)

 contented

 excited

Sustainable Hub

Global Nexus

Phase 1

Group 5 – Ali, the engaged student

Ali
the engaged student

Age: 23

Marital Status: single

Location: Bottrop (Germany)

Household/family: Shared flat with 2 fellow students. He was born in Gelsenkirchen, a town nearby. Here he has two younger brothers (16 & 19), an older sister (30) and his mother's siblings with their families.

Education: Striving to reach a Bachelor's degree in Energy Informatics

Workplace: Working 6 hours a week as a student assistant; helping out in his parent's supermarket

Living condition: 3-room apartment with a spacious shared kitchen

CE knowledge: Very good understanding of the concept, as he has taken an elective course on Circular Economy as part of his study degree.

Hobbies

- playing football
- hiking in the Taurus Mountains when he visits his grandparents
- going out with his friends

What is important

- Excelling in his studies to create impactful environmental solutions
- Supporting his family both emotionally and - in the future - financially

CE practices

- Advocating for and practicing recycling and waste reduction in his flatshare
- helps friends and family with repairs and updates for their electronic devices

Wishes

- learn more about how to implement CE principles in everyday life
- inspire family and peers to adopt more sustainable habits
- get a good job and income

Ali shares a 3-room apartment close to the Campus of Bottrop with two fellow students, Hannah (24) and Arjun (22), who are less sustainable. The **spacious shared kitchen is the heart of their social life**. Overall, they get on very well, eventhough they regularly argue about politics and housekeeping. Afterwards, Ali is often **disappointed with the lifestyle choices of his flatmates**.

Ali **balances his academic responsibilities with part-time work** as a student assistant, contributing six hours a week to his university's research projects. Nevertheless, it sometimes **gets tight at the end of the month**. On Saturdays, he frequently helps out in his parents' supermarket in Gelsenkirchen. Afterwards, he often stays over in the house of his parents and **enjoys big family dinners**.

His education has made him highly aware of environmental issues and this knowledge fuels his passion for making a positive impact on the environment.

Expectations & goals

What's their motivation to participate?
What does the persona want to achieve by taking part in the CircleUp project and the circular stories game?

Emotions

What fears might they have?
And what could particularly excite them?

Summary and Reflections

Workshop 1 on personas and their journey through the gamified platform produced a rich set of fictional yet plausible user experiences that reflect diverse motivations, barriers, and contextual needs. Key insights included:

- The importance of addressing emotional barriers, such as insecurity or fear of judgement
- The need for clear entry points and motivational hooks early in the game experience
- Potential roles for material advisors in guiding users through reflective or challenging moments

- Opportunities to adapt interventions to specific persona characteristics and phases of engagement

These outcomes informed the iterative refinement of the Circular Stories Game and support the integration of user-centric thinking across the project.

Simulation

Thanks to the early prototype that has been created for the project simulation at the 2nd face-to-face meeting in Bottrop, we were able to test the concept. Colleagues from our different NGOs took on the role of fictional participants and were tasked with selecting and working on actions on the platform in collaboration with “advisors”. This showed that testing is key to the development of the concept, as provided very valuable feedback. The following list summarises the main critical points of the written feedback handed in by the participants directly after the simulation, with selected illustrative quotes from the written reflections (comments on technical issues due to the early prototype status are not included):

- **Far too many different actions are required** to provide sufficient amount of content for the current prototype.
- **Unclear distinction between Realm 2 and Realm 3:** “It took me some time to understand the different realms and the differences between realm 2 and 3.”
- **Uncertainty about the purpose of groups:** “Why make a group? It is not explained and I don’t see the connection.” “Is it mandatory to create/participate in groups?”
- **Unclear which information is visible to others:** “Not clear who can see your finished tasks and diary. Everybody?” “As our household was skeptical about sharing information publicly, there was a question about what to write in the bio when filling in the profile. What information is visible publicly, and to whom? Who can see the stories, diaries, and information on tasks?”
- **Overwhelm noted on structural level:** “Going too fast to the next level. Add badges and more ways to give positive feedback. For example, when someone prepares five meals using leftovers.” **and on content:** „Most of the explanations of the tasks are by far too long.“

- **Knowledge Platform:** “The interactive learning thing looks nice, but it needs a better story behind it or better instructions to be valuable for the users.”
- **Inclusion considerations:** “The platform is too hard to manage for kids. Make it easier/simpler to find the content.”

Following the evaluation, it became evident that revisiting the concept would be beneficial in order to enhance the experiential quality of the gamified platform, making it more engaging and enjoyable while keeping the structure simple. The revised concept sought to address the feedback gathered during the Bottrop simulation comprehensively, by taking a simpler approach. Consequently, the realms were replaced by stages, adopting a more minimalist, challenge-based approach that closely aligns with Bamberg’s stage model (Bamberg 2013).

Workshop 2 – Refining the storytelling element

Goals

The workshop looked at the idea of Circular Stories and how they can be used to encourage people to change their behaviour in the context of the Circular Economy. Participants prepared a personal *Circular Story* in advance, using prompts and structural aids to guide their writing. This pool of stories served as the basis for shared reflection and discussion during the workshop.

The participants generated the following output:

- Authentic stories from the CircleUp team: Sharing personal experiences and stories related to circular practices and emphasizing authenticity and relatability
- Reflection on the stories: Identifying which stories are particularly motivating or impactful and discussing why certain stories resonate more than others.
- Reflection on the writing process: Testing tool that facilitated storytelling by supporting reflection and creativity.

Procedure - Preparation Task

A week before the workshop, participants were asked to prepare by reflecting on their personal experiences with circular practices. The aim was to identify stories that felt meaningful or impactful to them. To support this process, they were encouraged to use

- An emotion list to capture feelings associated with their experiences.
- Guiding questions to help shape the narrative and highlight key elements.

The preparational instructions were presented in four steps:

Please contribute to our upcoming workshop:

- Your story: Think of a circular action you have taken, for example within the last four weeks.
- How did this experience make you feel? Choose one (or more) emotions that best describe your feelings. Briefly explain what might have triggered this feeling.
- Structure your story: Choose structuring questions from the list provided to help shape your narrative.
- Write your story: Put the pieces together. Give it a title. If possible, include a picture. Please use the next slide as a template and adapt it to your needs.
- Repeat and create more stories, if you like 😊

Step 1 included guidance on selecting a personal story:

Your story – Choosing circular actions:

Select any circular actions that are personally meaningful to you and that you would like to share with the CircleUp team. If possible, choose an action that you did recently, or is particularly memorable, or has had a lasting impact on you or others.

The range of actions can reflect

- your habits / how you developed new habits,
- actions taken together with others or alone,
- a single event or a series of events,
- creativity and/or problem solving,

Step 2 included the task to reflect on emotions and their causes, a list with positive emotions and definitions provided guidance, e.g.:

- happy: very pleased or filled with joy
- connected: feeling close to someone or part of a community

Step 3 included guidance on structuring the story:

Structure your story - Questions

Story Sequences

- What motivated you to take this action?
- What exactly did you do? Describe the steps you took.
- Did you face any challenges? If so, did you overcome them and how?

Reflections

- How do you feel about this action and why?
- What did you learn from this experience?
- What impact do you think your action had on you or on others?

Future

- Will you do it again / continue? Why or why not?
- What would make it easier for you to continue this behaviour?
- If you could improve or expand this action, how would you do it?

Missing a question? Feel free to create your own.

Step 4 included the deadline and a personal e-mail-adress to hand in the stories, accompanied with a template in MS-Powerpoint that should be used.

Procedure at the Workshop Day

The session began with a brief 15-minute introduction to the purpose and objectives of the workshop (see section goals) together with the theoretical underpinnings of storytelling. Three main aspects were outlined as follows:

Stories vs. Facts. Motivation to process facts depends on scientific literacy and prior beliefs. Facts may increase resistance, especially when challenging the worldview (Toomey 2023). On the other hand, stories trigger experiential rather than analytical processing, are less distant than facts and more relatable, and therefore reduce counter-arguing (Morris et al. 2019).

Stories, emotions and motivation. Climate emotions can be evoked by personal stories and motivate action by increasing emotional engagement (Brosch 2021). Negative climate emotions have been shown to be more arousing (Zaremba et al. 2024). On the other hand, positive emotions have been shown to expand people's thought-action repertoires, i.e. they increase creativity and solution seeking (Fredrickson 2001). The feeling of warm glow can also serve as an emotional reward for pro-social behaviour (Brosch 2021).

Stories – big or small. Small stories can be defined as "...stories in everyday life and as part of the fabric of social practices that ordinary people engage in" (Georgakopoulou 2017) whereas big stories "entail (...) reflection on either an episode, a portion of a life, an experience, are a step removed from those every-day goings-on" (Carù und Cova 2008). A prerequisite for creating big stories is introspection, which requires time and a certain psychological disposition. Both, small and big stories, contribute to form, maintain and communicate identity (Bamberg et al. 2011).

After the introduction, the group work of one hour was introduced. The 19 participants were divided into four groups of mixed nationality, gender and area of expertise by giving them numbers one to four in the order in which they were seated.

There were two tasks with a parallel structure. Task A focused on the similarities and differences of the stories and the motivation to respond, while task b focused more on the emotion part (see appendix). The guiding materials for task A were the structuring questions as outlined in step 3 of the preparation task. For task B, the

task was supported by a list of positive emotions and a list of negative emotions, each with short description, and a selection of emojis (see appendix).

The insights from the group work were summarised in a short presentation by each group.

Both groups worked with the printed out stories from the story pool and other supporting material such as post-its on whiteboards.

Results and Discussion from Preparation Task (Story Pool)

In total, 20 stories were created during the preparation phase, 17 by participants and 3 by the workshop leader (see next page; note that one story is continued on a second slide due to its length). One participant handed in three stories, i.e. stories from 15 participants were collected.

Spread over categories. The 17 (20) stories spreaded over the provided categories as follows:

- area: food = 4; textiles = 3 (6); electronics = 2; packaging = 3; other = 5
- people: by myself = 8; other people were involved = 8 (11); missing value = 1
- place: at home = 10 (11); in public sphere = 6 (7); at home \cap in public sphere = 4; at work = 1; missing value = 1
- theme: sharing = 4; repairing = 6 (8); reusing = 6; upcycling = 1; reducing? = 1; returning = 1; missing value = 2

Figure 9: Workshop 2, Pool of Circular Stories

The stories were fairly evenly spread across food, textiles, electronics, packaging and “other”, although the participants developed them independently, as the stories were made available for reading shortly before the workshop. Similarly, the choice in people involved was also even. When reading the stories’ content, the choice for the “by myself” category seemed to be quite subjective, for example in “Leftovers from school bistro” (wife involved), “Second life of electronics” (son involved), or “Intended bicycle theft” (thief involved). The offered options in people were obviously perceived as mutually exclusive, as no participant chose more than one. A different picture could be observed in place: Here, 4 stories were related to both “at home” and “in public sphere”. Overall, more stories were related to “at home” (10) than to “in public sphere” (6). One participant added “at work”. In terms of themes, repairing and reusing was chosen most often (6), in several cases both were chosen for the same story. The participants had difficulties in choosing themes for food stories, as out of four food stories one had a missing value and in one story “reducing?” was proposed as new category, which seems technically more correct than “reusing”. It should be discussed whether to include “reducing” as a theme, with the disadvantage that is quite broad and comes with hidden subjective assumptions that may not always be true in reality.

Description of emotions. The majority of the stories were related to three distinct emotions (n = 10), three stories were related to one emotion, and three to two emotions. One participant noted that “none of the suggested emotions apply”.

The positive emotions from the provided list were counted as follows (the number in brackets indicates the total count including the workshop leader’s stories):

happy	3	“Because I can please other kids”
excited	1	“When my sister got excited for free clothes”

surprised	1	“That my sister needed my stuff & the solution was to close to home”
empowered	0	
curious	0	
proud	4 (5)	“He (son) is able to fix things on his own”, “Because I learned a new skill + produced something pretty”
satisfied	10 (13)	“Because there is a problem that I can solve and this action solves this task”, “Saving food from being thrown away feels good”, “The jumpers look nice again”
at ease	1	„Less unnessary stuff at home”
pleased	5 (6)	“It was great that someone else could make use of a product we owned”
connected	3 (5)	“Involving my children in the decision-making process and seeing their willingness to give was a good feeling”
appreciated	0	
fulfilled	2 (3)	“Doing something good for not only myself”, “Having created a unique and costumized container handcraftet by yourself awakens a sense of pride”

“Satisfied” is the emotion that was most often associated with the stories (10), followed by “pleased” (5), “proud” (4), “happy” (3), “connected” (3) and “fulfilled” (2). “Excited”, “surprised” and “at ease” were used onces each. “Empowered”, “curious” and “appreciated” were also given as examples on the list but were not used by the participants. Further positive emotions added by participants were “content” and “fun”. Negative emotions added were “frustrated”, “grim”, “ambivalent” and “deceived”, all in connection with food stories. An emotion of unclear valence was also added to food: “feeling responsible”.

Discussion of the resulting stories. The story preparation task asked for a personal experience that could be chosen freely, and participants were also prompted to think of a good experience by a list of only positive emotions and a positive model story. The model story, which was about sending children's clothes to a friend with younger children, included a selection of three of the provided guiding questions with a text

section for each, some reflection on conflicting feelings, a picture with a box of clothes and a selection of three emotions with explanations of why. Because of the reflective elements it can be identified as a “big story”.

Although this story was initially only meant to illustrate how to fill in the story template, it quickly became clear that it was a powerful reference for the participants, as several of them commented in their e-mail when submitting their stories that they hoped their story would meet the expectations.

Both the model story and the list of only positive emotions nudged participants to create a story that included a sense of “warm glow”, defined as “an affective-emotional state, [that] captures the feeling of wellbeing related to the contribution to a good cause” (Hartmann et al. 2017). Emotions and anticipated affect play a crucial role as intrinsic motivators for sustainable action (Brosch 2021). They function both as outcomes of pro-environmental behavior (experienced warm glow) and as precursors to such actions (anticipated warm glow). This dynamic suggests a reinforcement mechanism whereby the warm glow experienced can inspire future pro-environmental behaviour.

The generated stories showed that recalling the feeling of warm glow is associated with stories involving problem-solving, creative actions, pro-social behaviour and contributing to a good cause. Stories involving feelings of warm glow occurred frequently in textiles and electronics (esp. sharing, repairing) as well in the category “other”, such as toys and furniture, but also with packaging (e.g. “content: at least a little bit contributing to reducing plastic or paper waste”). On the other hand, emotions related to food stories stood out as they were more diverse and included feelings of frustration, ambivalence or the feeling of responsibility for other’s lack of awareness. It seems that the food waste is more tangible and emotionally complex, as it is more directly related to personal habits and (conflicting) social norms.

Results and Discussion from Workshop Day

The results are based on the short group presentations given at the the end of the group work phase. The presentations were recorded and transcribed using app.read.ai. The full transcripts can be found in the appendix.

Table 8 shows the structured results of the group insights.

Table 8: Main results of Workshop 2 (Circular Stories)

	Motivating elements	Emotions	Structuring elements	General remarks
<u>Group 1</u>	authenticity, relatability, replicability, humour, creativity, practical value	Ambivalence in food-related stories: satisfaction vs. reluctance to eat leftovers. Nostalgia as both a motivator and barrier: can complicate the process of letting go of certain items.		Few stories about routines: We will have to find out what kind of stories fit to routines , how we can support the writing process and how can routine stories be made interesting and engaging . Model stories need to be brief as it's used on the smartphone, different kind of story types to meet the needs of different users.
<u>Group 2</u>	Stories triggered personal memories (e.g. food waste and sharing).	Negative emotions like shame and jealousy may inhibit storytelling. Some participants found the emotional reflection unnecessary or difficult .	Story simplicity and use of pictures and emojis were preferred by participants less inclined to write.	Importance of understanding the intended audience and building trust through community.
<u>Group 3</u>	Seeing others' stories was both inspiring and inhibiting. Inhibiting due to a sense of hesitation to write a story that felt too similar to one	Mixed emotions in food-related stories; satisfaction from repair or from learning a new skill. Difficulty engaging with emotions in relation to daily activities that don't necessarily feel emotional.	Prompt questions were helpful to structure stories but sometimes broke narrative flow.	We need to carefully consider which and how many example stories to provide to households - ensuring they are emotionally supportive, motivating, and legally appropriate. Raised concerns about legal and cultural

	already shared by someone else.	At times hard to pinpoint a specific emotion . Mixed experiences with the positive emotions list: some found it limiting.		variation across countries.
Group 4	Strong connection with short, relatable stories . Stories that inspire action or prompt reflection were found to be most impactful.	Stories that give us positive emotions motivate writing.		Suggested in-person kick-offs and influencer-like roles to increase trust . Acknowledged the influence of commercial story-telling and the need for well-crafted, high-quality model stories .

Motivating and Demotivating Elements in Circular Stories

In all four groups, participants reflected on the elements within stories that they found most motivating. Figure 10 shows an example of clustering stories from the story pool based on emotions. A strong consensus emerged around the value of authenticity, relatability, and practical relevance. Stories that felt real, reflected everyday life, or provided tangible ideas or life hacks were particularly valued. Participants highlighted that a story became more engaging and inspiring when it reflected their own experiences or presented actions that seemed replicable. Elements such as humour, creativity, and a touch of surprise were also valued for making stories more lively and memorable.

Figure 10: Example of clustering stories based on emotions

In contrast to the pool of stories derived in the workshop preparation, short and simple stories were discussed as being more accessible and effective, especially when read on a mobile device.

However, the discussions also revealed some demotivating factors. Several participants experienced a sense of emotional ambivalence particularly in relation to food stories (e.g. reluctance to repeatedly eat leftovers). Nostalgia was noted as both a motivator (encouraging care for cherished items) and a barrier (leading to hoarding). In some cases, stories evoked negative emotions such as shame or jealousy, which could inhibit the willingness to share or engage. For example, stories about repairing clothes triggered feelings of inadequacy in those who lacked the skills.

Additionally, some participants anticipated that they might feel discouraged when encountering stories that were too similar to their own, leading to a reluctance to contribute something that felt unoriginal. There was also concern that stories that were

too much focused on sharing emotions or that relied heavily on positive emotions might exclude those who are less reflective and more action-oriented.

In sum, motivating stories were those that were personal, practical, and emotionally resonant without being overly demanding. Demotivating factors often related to emotional discomfort, lack of perceived anticipated originality of the own personal story, or a sense that the expected stories would not fit one's own abilities or context.

Reflections on Structuring Elements in the Storytelling Process

Compared to other topics discussed in the workshop, structuring elements received relatively little attention in the group discussions. Nevertheless, some valuable insights emerged in relation to the guiding tools and prompts provided.

Several participants acknowledged that the guiding questions helped to structure their stories. However, participants also noted that this structure could sometimes be restrictive – particularly when someone already had a clear story in mind. In such cases, answering fixed questions could interrupt the natural flow of narration or lead to a sense of fragmentation.

Group 3 raised concerns that the emotion list, while useful for encouraging emotional reflection, was perceived as limiting by some. A few participants found it difficult to match their experiences with the predefined set of positive emotions, especially when their actions did not feel inherently emotional or fell somewhere between categories. This suggests that greater flexibility or a wider range of emotion descriptors might support a broader range of storytelling styles.

Furthermore, Group 1 discussed the importance of having a clear story arc—a narrative flow that carries the reader through a beginning, middle, and end—and noted that elements like surprise, creativity, and humour contributed to more engaging and memorable stories.

Overall, while structuring tools were seen as helpful for initiating the storytelling process, the discussions revealed the importance of maintaining flexibility and avoiding overly rigid formats, especially to accommodate different storytelling styles, comfort levels, and cultural backgrounds.

Reflections on model stories

The role and design of model stories emerged as a central topic in the group discussions. Participants agreed that model stories will be essential to kick-start engagement on the platform and to demonstrate what is meant by a “Circular Story.” They should serve as inspiration, guidance, and reassurance, particularly for users unfamiliar with storytelling or hesitant to share their own experiences.

Group 1 and 3 emphasised the importance of offering a balanced variety of story types. This includes both “small stories”—short, everyday narratives—and “big stories” that involve deeper reflection. Providing this range is essential to ensure that users with different communication styles and comfort levels feel represented and able to contribute. Concerns have been raised about the potential unintended effects of model stories. If examples are too polished or too emotionally demanding, they may discourage participation or suggest that only certain types of stories are welcome.

Group 1 stressed that model stories should be mobile-friendly and therefore brief in terms of text. To support users who prefer a less text-heavy format, visual elements such as photos, emojis, and minimal text were recommended.

Furthermore, groups highlighted the need to carefully select stories in terms of legal and cultural appropriateness, especially when the platform spans multiple countries.

Finally, participants acknowledged that to reach broader audiences and compete with commercial storytelling, model stories should be professionally supported and possibly co-created with the help of AI or communications experts. This would help craft engaging, trustworthy narratives that are able to stand out and foster lasting engagement.

Conclusion

The workshop confirmed the potential of storytelling as a powerful way to communicate circular actions, build community and inspire others. In summary, stories perceived as motivating were typically characterised by a personal relevance, practical applicability, and emotional resonance, while remaining accessible and easy to comprehend. In contrast, stories that elicited disengagement were often associated with emotional discomfort, concerns about a lack of originality, or a perceived

misalignment between the expected narrative and the individual's capabilities or contextual circumstances.

There was strong consensus that the storytelling format must remain flexible and accessible, accommodating both reflective and action-oriented users, and offering room for different levels of emotional depth.

The initial set of *model stories* should include a variety of formats and tones to reflect the diversity of user experiences and needs. They will serve to:

- Demonstrate what we mean by "Circular Stories"
- Show that everyone is capable of contributing their own story.
- Stories will be carefully selected and may be revised after further testing. The insights gathered will directly inform the development of story templates, support materials, and platform features aimed at lowering barriers and enhancing user engagement.

Furthermore, the workshop revealed that routine-based circular behaviours were largely underrepresented in the story pool. Yet, these everyday practices are very important for a sustained behaviour change. As participants could freely choose a story, such actions may not have felt “story-worthy”, as they are embedded in the ordinary and often lack a clear emotional or dramatic arc.

Further crafting of model stories should explore storytelling formats that offer ways to highlight routines in a meaningful and engaging way - for example, by focusing on the personal significance, problem-solving, or emotional ease that routines can bring.

Next steps should include expanding and concretising the story concept, for example by developing a range of distinct story types – such as picture stories, life-hack stories, circular adventure stories, and creative stories – each tailored to different user preferences and levels of engagement. Storytelling prompts and structuring aids should support both reflective and action-oriented users. Offering emojis/emotion should be optional. The aim is to ensure inclusivity, stimulate creativity, and lower the threshold for participation, making it easier for users to recognise and share circular actions in their everyday lives.

Based on these insights, the next section will present the current structure of the Circular Stories element.

2.4.3 The revised structure of the community building element - Circular stories embedded in a challenge-based approach

Based on the theoretical foundations and the insights from the workshops and the simulation, our community-building approach uses several of the mechanisms outlined above in the theoretical foundation of the community building approach.

We draw on the principle of recategorization (Gaertner et al. 1993) by introducing a sense of common fate (“Being part of the CircleUp project”) and shared tasks (taking part in the in great parts simultaneous challenges) as a means to foster a shared social identity. The challenges will comprise tasks with opportunities to collaborate. Here, small group interactions, both in the digital space and importantly, also in the real world, allow for the bottom-up formation of identity as highlighted by the Interactive Model of Social Identity Formation (Postmes et al. 2005).

This approach is implemented through a digital application and via real-world activities as follows (Figure 11):

Figure 11: Interplay of digital components and real-world activities towards the formation of a Circular Citizen Identity.

(1) Digital environment:

The app serves as a key interface, providing users with information, feedback, and opportunities to commit to specific actions. It includes an interactive learning tool that allows users to explore and experiment with how their individual behaviours influence the broader socio-ecological system. These features are designed to increase awareness and encourage behavioural change through personal reflection and system-level insight.

(2) Real-world settings:

The approach is complemented by face-to-face counselling and advisory services, community events, and support in discovering local infrastructure that facilitates circular practices. These activities aim to strengthen participants' engagement by embedding behaviour change in their immediate social and spatial context.

(3) Challenges as a structural element:

At the core of our concept are challenges presented via the app. These challenges are designed to prompt either individual action (e.g. habit change) or collaborative efforts. An example of such a challenge on the group level is organising a clothing swap event with friends as a way to reduce clothing consumption. Each challenge is structured in multiple stages (see section xxx on SSBC model).

(4) Circular Stories:

While elements such as information provision, feedback, and social support are typical of behavioural interventions, our approach introduces an additional, central component that is often overlooked: creative, emotional and imaginative aspects, in our approach transported through circular stories. Circular stories integrate elements of self-reflection and creativity – both in the circular solutions participants implement and in the stories they tell about them. Documenting personal actions through stories renders circular behaviours tangible and meaningful.

(5/6) Guided storytelling process:

As participants progress through the challenge's stages, they are prompted by the app to engage in a guided storytelling process. At several transition points in the app, they receive reminders to document their experience through notes, photographs, or emotion journaling. This culminates in a narrative summary that is completed at the end of the challenge as Circular Story.

(7) Story feed towards a circular citizen identity:

This challenge-based storytelling process contributes to the formation of a Circular Citizen Identity through two ways, reflecting the interactive ways of social identity formation as highlighted by Postmes et al. (2005):

- Top-Down: The story feed, visible to all users, showcases a diversity of lived experiences and circular solutions. By seeing the stories of others, participants

develop a diversified cognitive representation of circular actions on individual and group level.

- Bottom-Up: The story feed is shaped from the bottom-up by users' own actions and their stories about it in response to individual and group challenges, reinforcing the sense that they are part of a broader community engaged in circular transformation.

To illustrate how circular actions can be captured and shared through storytelling, the following two examples present different forms of *Circular Stories*. The first (figure 12) is a “small story”, documenting a circular practice that had just been performed and reflecting the feelings through a smiley and visual cues added to the image:

Figure 12: Example for a "small" Circular Story

The second example (figure 13) has characteristics of a “big story”, providing insights into personal development and reflecting emotions.

Introducing my „circular“ pets

These are my rabbits. My rabbits have taught me to see my garden with different eyes. Before I had them, I felt overwhelmed by the task of weeding my garden, which is too big to be well maintained in a working mum's life. The work never wanted to end as more blackberries, more dandelions, more grasses grew in every spot. Now that I have my rabbits, I'm happy to see the wild herbs growing and I like to harvest them because they are food for them. My rabbits also like to eat the kitchen scraps, which motivates me to cook "rabbit-friendly" dishes.

Realm 1 – task: Fresh and seasonal cooking
area: food; category: #thoughts #rethink

Figure 13: Example for a "big" Circular Story

Together, they demonstrate the diverse ways in which individuals can connect personal experience with circular values and how even small actions, when shared, can inspire wider change.

This narrative format integrates various attributes to ensure it is informative, interactive, and in line with the game's objectives:

- **Title***: Each circular story must have a clear and descriptive title that encapsulates its essence and draws the reader in.
- **Number of characters***: Each story must meet a specified minimum length, measured in characters, e.g. 200.
- **Inclusion of images***: Stories must include one or more images to help to illustrate key points and make the stories more engaging and easier to understand.
- **Authorship* and story links**: Stories are created by an author and can be linked to a story of another author, allowing for collaborative storytelling and a variety of perspectives.
- **Person links**: The author of a story can link one or more people to a story, which is essential for stories about group actions, where there is only one author.
- **Challenges**: Stories are linked to a challenge within the game, thus linking them to the material flow categories food, packaging, textiles, electronics. In addition, to allow for spontaneity and not limit the creativity of the players, stories can be created without a connection to a challenge.

- *Tags*: Stories can be tagged with relevant keywords (e.g., #restructuring-the-household, #sharing, #reselling, #circular-arts, #repairing). These tags help organize stories and make them easier to find and reference.
- *Likes and comments*: Other players can like and comment on stories, fostering a sense of community and allowing for interaction and feedback between players.
- *“Most relevant”, displayed first*: To ensure the quality of the stories, an algorithm could sort the stories based on an internal hidden rating by CircleUp admins and the number of likes and comments, the length of the text or other features.

The asterisk marks feature that cannot be left blank.

3. Stakeholder involvement (bottom-up process)

3.1 Specification of behaviours and first collection of concepts

In parallel to the literature review on circular economy and the environmental theories to explain consumer behaviour within a circular economy context, a stakeholder involvement process was started. During the first one year and a half, this was mainly within the project with the internal stakeholders (here specifically with the practice partners, who sit on extensive practical knowledge in the field from ongoing and previous activities). In a later stage of the project (from M18 onwards), the external stakeholders from the regions from our pilots will be involved.

During the first year of the CircleUp project, NTNU hosted three workshops as part of Work Package 2, aimed at developing a conceptual framework for the project. The three virtual workshops brought together the CircleUp partners and other stakeholders, resulting in in-depth discussions. The first two workshops focused on identifying key behaviours, barriers, drivers, and interventions essential for transitioning to a circular economy at the household level. The third workshop focused mainly on the involvement and input of stakeholders. ²

As a first step of this process during the kick-off meeting of the project, an excel sheet was presented to brainstorm and collect the existing knowledge of the partners. The aim of this arena for collection of ideas and assumptions was to stimulate a selection

² Part of this text has been published before in November 2024 as a blog post on the CircleUp LinkedIn page as part of the Dissemination and Communication working package of the project.

of specific key circular economy practices that CircleUp should focus on, define them, and create a first understanding of potential drivers and barriers for these behaviours, as well as intervention ideas to foster people's engagement with them.

In the proposal, the example behaviours displayed in Table 8 were identified in the four behavioural domains of CircleUp, distributed across the stages acquisition, use, and disposal. Based on this overview, the excel document was created that had one folder per domain and within each domain one line per behaviour. For each behaviour, members of the consortium were asked to answer the following questions:

- How can the behaviour be defined as exactly as possible?
- How can change in this behaviour be measured?
- Which drivers does this behaviour have?
- Which barriers does this behaviour have?
- Which interventions can we expect to have an impact on this behaviour?
- Why do we expect these interventions to work?
- Which characteristics do households need to have to do this?
- Which dimension would be interesting to compare across countries?
- Which technical features are necessary in the online platform?
- What do we need to know to model this behaviour in the system dynamics models?
- How does this behaviour strategy affect material flows (LCA)?

For several weeks, consortium members were motivated to fill the table and add additional behaviours if they wanted to. The engagement in this task was very high and a rich collection of inputs to the different questions was achieved. The full document is far too large to be included in a printed document like this, but it is uploaded to the project's Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/circleup>.

Table 9: Circular economy practices as named in the proposal

	Food	Packaging	Textiles	Electronics
Acquisition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Plan purchase to avoid food waste *Avoid buying too large packages of food 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Avoid packaging *Buy products with reduced packaging *Buy easily recyclable packaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Question the need *Buy durable and repairable textiles *Avoid returns with online orders *Buy second-hand clothes *Swap clothes with others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Question the need *Buy durable and repairable products *Buy second-hand electronics *Buy products with service options
Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Utilize leftovers in the kitchen *If too much purchased, give to neighbours *Know about “best before date” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Reuse packing (e.g., paper bags) *Use reusable containers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Repair damaged textiles *Reuse and upcycle *Recombine clothes to new outfits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Share products (e.g., drilling machine, lawn mowers) *Use rental /leasing offers *Repair damaged products *Update/Upgrade product
Disposal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Sort and dispose of used packaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Give to clothing collection *Give to friends and relatives *Resell *Sort and dispose damaged textiles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Give to electronics collection, friends and relatives *Resell

Overall, the following 48 partly overlapping behaviours in the different categories were listed in the excel sheet.

Food (14):

- Analyse current habits // assess status quo
- Plan purchases to avoid food waste
- Avoid buying too large packages of food / buy loose instead/ Single Item purchases
- Utilize leftovers in the kitchen
- If too much purchased, give to neighbours, or friends, family, community fridges
- Know about "best before date"
- Know about the "best before date-system"/ There are several steps/different kinds of dates (last date of consumption, best before, expiring date)
- Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting)
- Know about approx. CO₂ emissions of different food categories (e.g. meat, fresh vegetables, canned goods, ...)
- Shop - only buying what they need
- Cooking - only what they will eat
- Increased local food - food grown/produced near the consumer
- Increased seasonal food instead of importing from other continents
- Store foods correctly to increase their shelf-life

Packaging (8):

- Avoid packaging / avoid excessive packaging, double packaging
- Buy products with reduced packaging
- Buy products with recycled packaging (not just recyclable)
- Reuse packaging (e.g., paper bags)
- Use reusable containers // bags
- Sort and dispose of used packaging
- Reuse of plastic shopping bags
- Buy recycled products

Textiles (15):

- Question the need
- Buy durable and repairable textiles

- Avoid returns with online orders
- Buy second-hand clothes
- Swap clothes with others
- Take better care of textiles
- Repair damaged textiles
- Reuse and upcycle
- Recombine clothes to new outfits
- Give to clothing collections
- Give to friends and relatives
- Resell
- Sort and dispose damages textiles
- Renting clothes
- Encourage the use of real (washable) nappies

Electronics (11):

- Question the need // assess status-quo
- Buy durable and repairable products
- Buy second-hand electronics
- Buy products with service options
- Share products (e.g., drilling machine, lawn mowers)
- Use rental / leasing offer
- Repair damaged products
- Update/upgrade products
- Give to electronics collection, friends and relatives
- Resell
- Take care of products

For each of these behaviours the drivers, barriers, intervention ideas, etc. were collected in the excel sheet. This formed the input for the next step of the process.

3.2 Internal survey

To collect the input of as many consortium members as possible, an internal survey was designed to systematically gather the information necessary as input for the first internal workshop. 19 consortium members answered the survey, which corresponds

to 86% of all consortium members (excluding those having administrative functions only). All partners were represented with at least one answer.

In the first section of the survey, participants were asked for each of the four domains (food, packaging, textiles, and electronics) to assess the following aspects:

- How big is the environmental impact of this sector overall in the households? (very small – very large)
- How often do households make decisions in this area? (about every day – less than once a year)
- How easy do you think it is for households to change behaviour within this sector? (very difficult – very easy)
- How relevant is the behaviour from the perspective of the user partners? Consider what the mandate municipalities have, what focus NGOs might choose, etc. This question aims to select behaviours where the user partners actually feel that they are relevant for them. (out of scope – top priority)

All four questions were meant to frame the following decisions for which behaviours to prioritize on behaviours that are impactful for the environment, are performed often enough to be changeable within the time frame of the project, are not too difficult to change, and are within the mandate of the user-partners to address. As Figure 14 shows, so are primarily perceived behavioural frequency and difficulty the two dimensions which are perceived different. Whereas food and packaging related practices are basically performed on a daily basis and are therefore well suited for interventions in CircleUp, textile practices in general are rather perceived as a behaviour with a monthly frequency, and electronics related behaviours even lower. Difficulty is perceived negatively related to frequency, whereas changing food and packaging practices is perceived to be of medium difficulty, changing textile and electronic related practices appears to me more difficult. Environmental impact and priority from a user partner perspective were perceived more alike across the different domains. Then the participants were asked to prioritize one domain, based on the dimensions just assessed. Food (7 mentions) and Packaging (6 mentions) were clearly prioritised over Textiles and Electronics (both 3 mentions).

Figure 14: General assessment of the behavioural domains

In the next step, all named behaviours within each domain were listed and people were asked to select the three they considered most important from the perspective of the project (taking the dimensions just assessed in general into account). Overlapping mentions from the previous step were combined. Figure 15 shows how the behaviours were prioritised within the four sectors. Afterwards, each participant was asked the following questions for the three selected behaviours:

- **Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?** If not, which definition do you suggest? (all definitions given in the excel sheet for the specific behaviour were presented here).
- **How could the behaviour be measured?** All alternatives named in the excel sheet were listed to select (multiple answers possible). If “I have another idea” was selected, an open text box opened to write it down.
- **Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?** All alternatives named in the excel sheet were listed to select (multiple answers possible). If “other” was selected, an open text box opened to write it down.
- **Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?** All alternatives named in the excel sheet were listed to select (multiple answers possible). If “other” was selected, an open text box opened to write it down.

- **Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?** All alternatives named in the excel sheet were listed to select (multiple answers possible). If “other” was selected, an open text box opened to write it down.
- **Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?** If no was selected, a text box opened to specify which households can do it.

The answers to these questions for all behaviours can be found in the appendix. Please keep in mind that some behaviours have only been assessed by very few people.

Figure 15: Prioritised behaviours in the four domains (survey results, max three answers)

3.3 Focusing of behaviours

Based on the survey results, four prime target behaviours for each domain were chosen. This was done by the following rules: Select the most frequently selected behaviours from the survey within each of the behavioural category's “acquisition”, “use”, and “disposal” so that there is at least one in each category. Behaviours can be categorised in several of these categories. Some very similar categories were merged. Table 10 below shows the selected behaviours.

Table 10: Selected prime target behaviours for CircleUp

Behaviour		Acquisition	Use	Disposal
Food	Plan purchases to avoid food waste / only buy what is needed	X		
	Cooking – only what they will eat / Utilize leftovers in the kitchen		X	
	Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting)			X

	If too much is purchased, give to neighbours, friends, family, community fridges		X	X
Packaging	Use reusable containers / bags	X		
	Avoid packaging / buy products with reduced packaging	X		
	Reuse packaging (e.g., paper bags) / reuse of plastic shopping bags	X	X	
	Sort and dispose of used plastic			X
Textiles	Reduce buying clothes	X		
	Take better care of textiles / repair damaged textiles / buy durable and repairable textiles	X	X	
	Buy second hand clothes	X	X	
	Reuse and upcycle, recombine clothes to new outfits		X	X
Electronics	Share products (e.g., drills, lawn mowers, etc.)	X	X	
	Buy durable and repairable electronics / repair damaged electronics	X	X	
	Question the need of buying electronics / assess status quo	X		
	Give electronics to friends and family / other people			X

3.4 Workshop 1: Bottom-up framework models

On 22.04.2024 the first internal workshop to define the framework models bottom-up was organized by NTNU. 14 participants from all partners were represented in the meeting. After an introduction with some key survey results, the participants were split into even groups and worked in breakout rooms. In each of the rooms, participants worked with Miro boards on designing a framework model for the four selected behaviours of a specific domain (see Section 3.3). In these models they were asked to:

- Build a framework model
- Agree on a definition for each of the four behaviours
- Select the main drivers and barriers
- Select the key interventions and link them to specific drivers and barriers, with an assumption about the direction of their impact
- Select the most important measures to document the baseline and the change in behaviour

From the survey, the most frequently embraced drivers, barriers, measurements, and intervention ideas were selected and provided as post-it notes to be included in the models. Also all suggestions from open-ended questions were added, as these were not rated by everyone before. All definitions provided in the excel sheet (Section 3.1) and in the survey were also presented as a starting point for the discussion.

Food

Figures 16-19 display the results of the Miro board exercise for the food sector. The content of the post-its is summarised in Table 11. The full Miro board can be accessed here: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKR9VMeg=/>.

Figure 16: Bottom-up framework model for “Plan purchases to avoid food waste / only buy what is needed”

Figure 17: Bottom-up framework model for “Cooking – only what they will eat / Utilize leftovers in the kitchen”

Figure 18: Bottom-up framework model for “Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting)”

Figure 19: Bottom-up framework model for “If too much is purchased, give to neighbours, friends, family, community fridges”

Table 11: Summary of the workshop results for the food sector

	Plan purchases to avoid food waste / only buy what is needed	Cooking – only what they will eat / Utilize leftovers in the kitchen	Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting)	If too much purchased, give to neighbours, friends, family, community fridges
Definition	Plan purchases to avoid food waste / only buy what is needed: Plan: - e.g., make a shopping list before each purchase - e.g., make a weekly shopping list - e.g., make a list of you buy on a regular basis	People do portion planning, portion control, not overbuying at supermarkets/shops. Leftovers are stored properly and used up.	Residents use their home composter for unavoidable food waste which can be composted e.g. fruit, veg peelings, or even the whole food waste in some countries. They use the correct bin for disposing/recycling of food waste (and empty any gone off food from its	If the resident has bought too much food, can they pass it on to others who need it/can use it If the resident has bought too much food, can they pass it on to others who need it/can use it

	<p>- e.g., make a note of each spontaneous purchase and consider its possible place in future plans</p> <p>Food waste: - e.g., make a list of food products that you sometimes throw out - e.g., think about what you can change to avoid throwing these things out</p> <p>What is needed: - e.g., make a plan of what you would like to cook this week - e.g., make an inventory of your food supplies to see what needs to be bought in the next two weeks - e.g., think about what can be done with leftovers (including after the best before date)</p> <p>"Bonus" point - environmental impact of the foods: - e.g., learn about carbon footprint of the foods you consume - e.g., leant about water footprint of the foods you consume - e.g., consider alternatives</p>		<p>packaging into the food recycling bin).</p>	
<p>Drivers</p>	<p>Stable food purchase routines / Good planning abilities</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p>	<p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>Knowledge / skills / know how (recipe's, storage)</p>	<p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Having the opportunity (e.g., separate collection of</p>	<p>Social influence between households (social norms)</p> <p>positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)</p>

	Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	food waste; space for own compost)	If this can be made easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)
Barriers	<p>Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p> <p>Social influence between household members (social norms)</p> <p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p>	<p>Uncertainty/lack of information about safety of eating leftovers (e.g., after a certain time, when different ingredients are mixed)</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p> <p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p> <p>Taste preferences, preferences for variety of foods (not wanting to eat leftovers)</p>	<p>Hygiene concerns</p> <p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p> <p>Not perceived important enough</p> <p>No collection of organic waste</p> <p>No space for compost</p>	<p>negative emotions (e.g., embarrassment, stress)</p> <p>No system for communication or contact. Mismatch of supply and demand. Hard to adopt last-minute offers of food into weekly food plan.</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p> <p>Uncertainty about the quality/safety of food shared by others</p>
Interventions	<p>Feedback on own behaviour (change), e.g. by the game</p> <p>Material efficiency advisors</p> <p>Think of one change that would lead to less waste while meeting your hedonic goals equally well as the status quo</p> <p>Make a default shopping list on your phone, which can be consulted before each shopping trip</p> <p>Schedule a 30-minute discussion with your</p>	<p>Provide knowledge on how to store leftover food</p> <p>Point out that eating leftovers can lead to time savings and can require less effort</p> <p>Workshop and/or social game</p> <p>Encourage "left-over" dinners (maybe even regularly)</p> <p>Analyze current food habits / assess status quo</p> <p>Feedback on own behaviour (change)</p>	<p>Providing information on hygiene and smell of composting</p> <p>Providing information about collection of organic waste</p> <p>Normalizing the behaviour by showing other people do the same</p> <p>Providing equipment for home-composting</p> <p>Provide information on shared/community composting options in the vicinity of participants' home</p>	<p>Start by sharing with a friend or someone you are comfortable with, branch out later</p> <p>Social game</p> <p>Good overview of sharing options (e.g., through an app, possibility to claim the foods in the app)</p>

	<p>family about your food and shopping routines and think of one thing that everyone would agree to change</p> <p>Analyze current food habits / assess status quo</p> <p>Interviews about shopping practices</p> <p>Implementation intention</p>	<p>Think about how you can use leftovers to create a new dish (e.g., by combining with some additional ingredients, preparing the food differently, etc.)</p>		
Measurements	<p>Food waste diary (primary method)</p> <p>Weighing food waste (secondary method, which can partly validate accuracy of the food waste diary implementation conditional on feasibility in the project, do not implement if extra effort is required from participants)</p> <p>Shopping lists</p>	<p>Food diary (what has been prepared, what has been eaten, what has been stored, what has been thrown away)</p>	<p>Food waste diary (primary method)</p> <p>Weighing food waste (secondary method, which can partly validate accuracy of the food waste diary implementation conditional on feasibility in the project, do not implement if extra effort is required from participants)</p>	<p>Self-report on how much is given to/received from others</p> <p>Food diary (what has been prepared, what has been eaten, what has been stored, what has been thrown away)</p> <p>If implemented as part of the social game, perhaps can be tracked there as well</p>

Packaging

Figures 20-23 display the results of the Miro board exercise for the packaging sector. The content of the post-its is summarized in Table 12. The full Miro board can be accessed here: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKR8VI-0=. The group added another category (“Assumptions”) to the framework.

Figure 20. Bottom-up framework model for “Use reusable containers / bags”.

Figure 21. Bottom-up framework model for “Avoid packaging / buy products with reduced packaging”.

Figure 22. Bottom-up framework model for “Reuse packaging (e.g. paper bags), reuse plastic shopping bags”.

Figure 23. Bottom-up framework model for “Sort and dispose of used packaging”.

Table 12: Summary of the workshop results for the packaging sector

	Use reusable containers / bags	Avoid packaging / buy products with reduced packaging	Reuse packaging (e.g. paper bags), reuse plastic shopping bags	Sort and dispose of used packaging
Definition	Households use reusable bags or containers. Need to define what is "reusable" as opposed to single-use: probably quantity of use-phases. Especially to distinguish from behaviour 3	Households buy products with as little packaging as possible. Might need to consider which materials packaging is made from. It might be better to have a more packaged product with material that is completely recyclable/reusable than a less packaged product that will be waste.	Households reuse packaging, like boxes, shopping bags	Households sort packaging in the correct way for their waste separation system. In how far do we even want people to go beyond that, e.g. sort packaging for weighing different material streams even if the recycling system is not comprehensive?
Assumptions	Reuseable packaging will be used in scenarios where they would otherwise use single-use packaging. Purchasing products without packaging Example scenarios: food shopping with loose produce, takeaway coffee, packed lunch. Households don't accumulate an excess of reuseable containers (which often have a greater embedded environmental impact than single-use packaging)	Reduction in packaging will be connected to behaviour 1 i.e. if additional packaging is required, use reusable packaging instead of packing loose apples in a single-use bag.		

Drivers	<p>Social influence between household members (social norms)</p> <p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>Shops encourage the scheme with discounts</p> <p>positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)</p> <p>high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy</p> <p>Reusable system in place at shops (not something that has to be requested)</p> <p>Perception of improved hygiene</p> <p>Reusable object is nicer to use (than single use)</p> <p>Product attachment - can be personalised as an object</p>	<p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p> <p>Social influence between household members (social norms)</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Fits the self-concept / identity of the person (zero-waste lifestyle)</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p>	<p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)</p>	<p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p> <p>Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)</p>
Barriers	<p>Shyness / social concerns (being looked</p>	<p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p>	<p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p>	<p>Unclear sorting system / unsure what goes where</p>

	<p>down at), behaviour being not normal</p> <p>Not perceived important enough</p> <p>Does not fit with self-concept / identity</p> <p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p> <p>Reusable containers are more expensive (initially)</p> <p>Shops do not allow reusable containers (e.g., for hygiene rules)</p> <p>Forgetting the containers when going shopping, spontaneous shopping trip</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p> <p>viability of reusable food containers in supermarkets is too low.</p> <p>Aesthetic issues (bags or containers being crumpled/faded/scuffed etc.). Having to store these somewhere for future use.</p>	<p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p> <p>Not perceived important enough</p> <p>Preferred brands have only packaged products</p> <p>Unavailability of unpackaged product alternatives</p> <p>To buy the alternative with reduced packaging/recycled packaging is in conflict with other factors you find important such as locally produced, eco-label etc.</p> <p>Unpackaged products more expensive</p> <p>Lack of knowledge about the specific impact of the packaging of one product compared to another</p>	<p>Forgetting the packaging that one wants to reuse when for example going to the shop</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p>	<p>Lack of knowledge on how clean packaging needs to be</p> <p>Compound material makes sorting difficult</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p>
Interventions	<p>Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)</p> <p>Social game</p> <p>Consulting through advisors.</p>	<p>Consulting through advisors.</p> <p>Information about alternative products.</p> <p>make it easy to get unpackaged items - online shopping etc does not offer the</p>	<p>Suggestions of how to reuse packaging</p> <p>Triggering normative goals / framing</p> <p>Implementation intentions</p> <p>intervention (making mental cues that get</p>	<p>Providing information on what goes where and how to prepare</p> <p>Providing information on what is easy to recycle</p> <p>Organizing the personal space in a</p>

	<p>Feedback on own behaviour (change)</p> <p>Providing information on reusable containers</p> <p>Cheap offers for reusable bags or containers in shops.</p> <p>Give-away of reusable containers (coffee cups, bees wrap, steel containers), maybe personalized</p> <p>preparing infrastructure for wasteless shopping with advisers (shopping basket with reusable containers + bags); training wasteless shopping in groups</p> <p>Deposit systems for reusable packaging</p> <p>Significant portion of food items available in shops that can be purchased by using reusable bags or containers: concerted action with shops to inform households and to increase share of food items.</p> <p>Prompts for the door to remind to take containers to the shop</p> <p>Establishing routines to always have some containers in the bike bag/hand bag/car</p>	<p>choice, refill shops can require separate trips which can be difficult in time pressured lives, need space to store if purchase in bulk</p> <p>Feedback on own behaviour (change)</p> <p>Providing information about less packaged goods</p> <p>Providing information about alternative distribution channels</p>	<p>activated when going shopping)</p> <p>Stickers that can be put on the door to prompt people to remember their containers</p>	<p>way that makes it easy to sort where you are, e.g. with MEAs</p> <p>Prompts for the kitchen and other places where waste is produced.</p>
Measurements	Self-report (reuse diary)	<p>Self-report</p> <p>Description of thought process and</p>	Self-report (reuse diary)	Weighing waste (packaging) in the different fractions

	<p>Audit of reusable containers in the household</p> <p>Description of thought process and behaviour around reusable containers (interviews/session with advisors)</p> <p>Weighing waste (packaging), very imprecise way to measure this behaviour</p>	<p>behaviour around shopping habits? (interviews/session with advisors)</p> <p>Weighing waste (packaging)</p>	<p>Weighing waste (packaging)</p>	<p>Observation in the waste bins (material efficiency advisors)</p>
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Textiles

Figures 24-27 display the results of the Miro board exercise for the textiles sector. The content of the post-its is summarized in Table 13. The full Miro board can be accessed here: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKR8VI-0=/>.

Figure 24. Bottom-up framework model for “Reduce buying clothes”.

Figure 25. Bottom-up framework model for “Take better care of textiles / repair damaged textiles / buy durable and repairable textiles”.

Figure 26. Bottom-up framework model for “Buy second-hand clothes”.

Figure 27. Bottom-up framework model for “Reuse and upcycle, recombine clothes to new outfits”.

Table 13: Summary of the workshop results for the textile sector

	Reduce buying clothes	Take better care of textiles / repair damaged textiles / buy durable and repairable textiles	Buy second-hand clothes	Reuse and upcycle, recombine clothes to new outfits
Definition	People reduce the total number / amount of new clothes bought.	People repair textiles if possible to extend their lifetime.	Purchase second-hand clothing rather than buying new (not in addition to!)	Number of garments adapted or altered (and subsequent new purchases avoided)
Drivers	<p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Fits the self-concept / identity of the person (system criticism)</p> <p>what do i really save in the end: CO2 footprint</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>Social influence between household members (social norms)</p> <p>Dress code requirement from school/work</p>	<p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Interest in skills like sewing</p> <p>Emotional attachment to old clothes</p> <p>Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p>	<p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>Individuality rather than sticking to the current fashion</p> <p>positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)</p> <p>Used clothes are fashionable (vintage)</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p>	<p>Inspiration from social media</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)</p> <p>Interest in skills like sewing</p> <p>Creativity</p>

<p>Barriers</p>	<p>Lack of overview of the clothes you already have</p> <p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p> <p>Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)</p> <p>Expectational requirement to purchase certain product</p> <p>Status, want to be in fashion, which of course depends on the type. Keyword fast fashion.</p> <p>Social norms against the behaviour</p> <p>Desire for something new Buying new clothes often is not about the clothes but about getting dopamine. So, we have to tackle this issue somehow.</p> <p>Changes in fashion</p> <p>Marketing from the industry</p>	<p>Changes in fashion - would not wear even if repaired</p> <p>Desire for something new</p> <p>Lack of skills/equipment</p> <p>Time constraints</p> <p>Cost of repair services</p> <p>Lack of knowledge about repair services some brands offer</p> <p>Clothes have too low quality to justify repairing effort</p> <p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p>	<p>Not everything that is needed at a specific time is available second-hand at the right point in time</p> <p>Hygiene concerns</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p> <p>Second hand does not meet requirements (dress code etc)</p> <p>Not the social norm/ perception concerns</p> <p>Desire for something new</p>	<p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p> <p>Lack of skills / creativity</p> <p>Lack of equipment</p> <p>cost</p>
<p>Interventions</p>	<p>Information: Feedback about own behaviour (change) behaviour of other people (social norms)</p> <p>Information: Consulting through advisors</p>	<p>How do you recognize durable / repairable clothes</p> <p>Providing information about durability and repairing</p> <p>Blogs / social media / influencers showing diversity and sustainable</p>	<p>Action: Stimulating groups of young people to exchange clothes and buy second-hand, e.g., by a second-hand party.</p> <p>Information about how to wash clothes?</p>	<p>Information: details on where you can purchase upcycled fashion?</p> <p>Action: Courses for upcycling / recombining</p> <p>Action: Organizing upcycling workshops, making</p>

	<p>Information: Providing information on the impact of the clothing industry</p> <p>Activity for householder: Home mining challenge</p> <p>Activity for third party: Triggering normative goals / framing I think that for many people buying new clothes is like eating disorder or addiction and we have to deal with these deeply hidden issues.</p> <p>Activity for householder: No buying challenges</p> <p>Activity for householder: using renting/clothes libraries</p>	<p>styles/repared/upcycled clothes</p> <p>Activity: Courses for self-repair</p> <p>Activity: Visiting repair shops</p> <p>Information about repairing infrastructure</p> <p>Activity for Householder: Organizing repair workshops, making repairing a social event</p> <p>Possibility to loan equipment</p>	<p>Information: Feedback on own behaviour (change)</p> <p>Information: Apps/charity shops supporting access to second-hand clothes</p> <p>Information: Second-hand fashion blogs</p> <p>Information: Role models</p>	<p>upcycling a social event</p> <p>Action: Possibility to loan equipment</p>
Measurements	<p>Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought</p> <p>shopping receipts (do people have these? many shops do not provide as standard anymore)</p> <p>Self-report of where clothes were bought from</p> <p>Clothes diary what did you wear? where did you buy it from/how long have you had it?</p>	<p>Self-report in diary on repair of textiles (self-repair or by repair service).</p> <p>In the diary, it is noted whether any maintenance or repair work was carried out during a specified period of time.</p> <p>Measuring knowledge and skills for maintaining and repairing clothes</p> <p>Attendance at repair cafe/course</p>	<p>Purchase diary: Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought (both new and used)</p> <p>Report also the category the clothes are in (e.g. children, underwear, trousers, ...)</p> <p>Receipts of clothes purchases (both new and used) (could be difficult as shops are reducing what receipts are given as standard)</p>	<p>Purchase diary: Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought and upcycled / recombined</p> <p>Number of courses attended/skills acquired?</p> <p>Was equipment borrowed?</p>

	<p>Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought</p> <p>Self-report of origin and fibres of clothes bought (could be difficult)</p> <p>Questionnaire to fill in, what bought, where bought, when bought and if returned online; purchase receipts could help for details.</p>		Information provided by adviser (input measure not output)	
Comment		<p>Take better care of textiles - information based intervention</p> <p>Repair - Infrastructure and information based intervention</p> <p>Purchase durable - Information based intervention</p> <p>All have different drivers, barriers, measurements etc have chosen to focus on repair</p>		

Electronics

Figures 28-31 display the results of the Miro board exercise for the electronics sector. The content of the post-its is summarised in Table 14. The full Miro board can be accessed here: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKRDlvV0=/>.

Figure 28. Bottom-up framework model for “Share products (e.g., drills, lawn mowers)”.

Figure 29. Bottom-up framework model for “Buy durable and repairable electronics / repair damaged electronics”.

Figure 30. Bottom-up framework model for “Question the need of buying electronics / assess status quo”.

Figure 31. Bottom-up framework model for “Give electronics to friends and family / other people / give electronics to proper recycling”.

Table 14: Summary of the workshop results for the electronics sector

	Share products (e.g., drills, lawn mowers)	Buy durable and repairable electronics / repair damaged electronics	Question the need of buying electronics / assess status quo	Give electronics to friends and family / other people / give electronics to proper recycling
Definition	<p>People share products they only use occasionally rather than owning each their own copy.</p> <p>People seek to hire or borrow items from commercial sources or through community-led libraries of things</p>	<p>People make a purchase decision to invest more money in an item that should last longer...</p> <p>...and its possible to repair them.</p> <p>People repair or have damaged electronic products repaired.</p> <p>Extend the lifespan of products by...</p> <p>We spoke about leasing items too</p> <p>Buy second hand or refurbished product instead of new one.</p>	<p>People consider their needs and what they already own before buying something new (or used for that matter).</p>	<p>Residents give unwanted products to a charity, donation point, friends, relatives, etc.</p> <p>Resident gives damaged and unrepairable products to the proper recycling (e.g., return to shops).</p>

<p>Drivers</p>	<p>Fits the self-concept / identity of the person</p> <p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Together with social norms: Availability</p> <p>Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)</p> <p>Near-by possibilities for sharing, e.g. tool container for a settlement.</p> <p>Social event to share</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p>	<p>Product attachment</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Leasing an item for an extended period of time which can be repaired by the company, rather than buying (can be expensive)</p> <p>Pleasure of owning a high-quality product</p> <p>Savings in the future / investment</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>Annoyance with cheap products / programmed obsolescence</p>	<p>Annoyance with cheap products / programmed obsolescence</p> <p>Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p> <p>Self-concept</p> <p>Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)</p> <p>Economic benefits (saving money)</p>	<p>Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)</p> <p>Positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)</p> <p>Social influence from other households (social norms)</p>
<p>Barriers</p>	<p>Does not fit with self-concept / identity</p> <p>Strong habits for the old behaviour</p> <p>Not perceived important enough</p> <p>negative emotions: fear that sharing self-</p>	<p>Not perceived important enough</p> <p>Lack of infrastructure</p> <p>Inconvenience to get it repaired</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p>	<p>Low costs of many items</p> <p>Advertisement</p> <p>Social pressure to have newer models</p> <p>Lack of maintenance of the old product</p>	<p>Inconvenience to give it away</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p> <p>Data security concerns</p>

	<p>owned products might be damaged or not handled with care</p> <p>Diffusion of responsibility for maintenance</p> <p>Needs to be easy to get (located nearby), the right costs, and available when needed. needs to compete with the ability of Amazon to deliver next day</p> <p>Lack of common storage space</p> <p>Lack of infrastructure</p> <p>Time pressure / complications in everyday life</p>	<p>Insecurity how long the repaired item holds. Will it last? will it be updated? will it continue to work for the length of time I need or will i need to buy another? how much will a repair cost? how easy is it to repair?</p> <p>Lack of information on durability</p> <p>No repair index like in France.</p> <p>How do I know that an electronic good is really of higher quality. Only because it costs more its not automatically longer lasting than a cheaper product.</p> <p>No repairable products available</p> <p>Loosing the producer warranties when opening the product</p> <p>Higher initial costs / lack of funding</p> <p>High price in relation to value of the item</p> <p>Brand perception on quality</p> <p>Repairable products of lower quality / less fashionable (Fairphone)</p>	<p>(e.g., operating system)</p> <p>No updates available (computers, mobile phones, tablets)</p> <p>Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)</p>	
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Interventions	Normalizing the behaviour by presenting models	Feedback on own behaviour (change)	Suggestion by digital system not to buy?	Information about local donation points
	Feedback on own behaviour (change)	Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	Information about the impact of electronics production	Social game
	Information about formal sharing resources or legal agreements	Collaborative in-house inspection of status-quo	Collaborative in-house inspection of status-quo	Home-mining challenge
	Tasks on group or community level	Home mining challenge "finding the lost treasure"	Circular Story	Organizing a collection
	Circular stories game	Information about the impact of electronics production	Information on Support Possibilities, e.g. other operating systems	Information about secure deletion of data
	Social Game: Co-creation of a section "Virtual sharing library" in the CircleUp knowledge base to give participants the opportunity to offer their products for sharing within the CircleUp community	Information on where to find repairable product alternatives	Home mining challenge "finding the lost treasure"	
	Consulting through advisors.	Info on availability/cost of repair	Feedback on own behaviour (change)	
	Promoting community led sharing resources	Information on repair options	Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	
	Make it easy for people. information isn't enough to force a change, need the supporting infrastructure to be there	Information about legal rights / warranties	Fostering emotional attachment (stories from the life of the product)	
		Information on consumer rights, e.g. if shops are obliged to repair an item		
		Do it yourself workshops (where possible -> might be illegal for some products)		
		Information on durability of electronic products / guarantee		

		Concerted actions with households, craftsmen and repair cafés.		
Measurements	<p>Sharing diary</p> <p>Self-report of sharing</p> <p>Sharing diary but from the owner and not the leasers or renters</p> <p>Qualitative interviews</p> <p>"Circular Story"</p>	<p>Repair receipts, e.g. electronic shops</p> <p>Expenses for electronics / receipts</p> <p>Qualitative interviews, ask for past purchase decisions</p> <p>Measuring knowledge /motivation of how to repair</p> <p>Material efficiency advisor protocols (likely that investments are discussed in advisory sessions)</p> <p>Repair diary / self-report, ask for past purchase decisions</p> <p>Self-report might be useful here. "Buy durable and repairable electronics" refer to more expensive products which are not bought on a weekly basis.</p> <p>Shopping diary</p>	<p>Qualitative interviews</p> <p>Adviser protocols</p> <p>Inventory of existing electronics</p>	<p>Qualitative interviews</p> <p>Household's CE diary / self report</p>

3.5 Workshop 2: A solidified framework model across domains

On 03.09.2024, NTNU held a second workshop with about 20 members from the consortium. Similar to the first workshop, the aim was to consolidate the ongoing development of the framework model. Another objective was to develop concrete intervention strategies to integrate in the project to support and engage households. This was the agenda for the second workshop:

1. Status WP2
2. Theoretical framework: SSBC + intervention strategies
3. Groupwork: Miro board
4. Presentation from each group
5. Reflection: Questions; what's next?

Based on the literature study conducted at the beginning of the CircleUp project, we decided to adopt the stage model of self-regulated behavioural change (SSBC) created by Bamberg (2013) for developing and evaluating tailored interventions within the project. This model was chosen for its provided evidence across different environmental domains and its effectiveness in developing and evaluating tailored interventions aimed at changing people's environmental behaviour. The second workshop was dedicated to explaining this model to our partners and advancing the conceptual framework that had already been explored in the first workshop. During the workshop, we delved deeply into the SSBC model, making sure that all participants had a thorough understanding of its different stages and applications.

The primary activity of the second workshop was to match different interventions to the different stages of the SSBC model. Given the limited time available, we decided to focus on one main behaviour per domain, targeting food, textiles, packages and electronics. To facilitate discussions and brainstorming, the group was divided into smaller groups in breakout rooms, each focusing on one of these domains. Through intensive discussions, we realized that many of the developed interventions and strategies could be applied across different stages of the SSBC model. This insight led us to extend the conceptual framework to include not only our previously specified circular economy practices but also more general circular behaviours. This approach creates an adaptable framework that can be applied to a wider range of circular economy behaviours.

The participants were given the following tasks to work on during the workshop:

- Classify the interventions from workshop 1 in different stages (they were already written on post-it notes in Miro board) and make them more specific. It is recommended to create new intervention strategies since most of the existing interventions fit only the first stages.
We should motivate and engage people during all stages. Tip: Start with the third and fourth stages
- Try to develop interventions based on the theoretical framework: including information, feedback, commitment.
Questions to answer:
 - a. Which **feedback** shall we give to the households, how to give feedback, how often do the households need feedback, feedback from who?
 - b. Which general and tailored **information** shall we give to the households, how to give information, where shall we find information?
 - c. How to **commit** households to a behaviour? How to keep participants motivated in the project?
- Try to make a link with the social game³ for each intervention. F.ex. one post-it for each intervention and one post-it (other colour) for the link with the game
- Extra time? Decide whether the drivers and barriers are still fitting within the model

The results of the full Miro board for food can be accessed here:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKjoqR6Q=?share_link_id=667803165972

³ In the initial CircleUp project proposal and during the first year of the project, we planned to include a social game featuring different gamification elements such as difficulty levels, leaderboards, and badges. However, as the conceptual framework evolved, the game started aligning with the stages of the SSBC model, and most of the initial gamification elements were no longer included in the current model. Therefore, all materials and outcomes of workshops created during the first year of the project, still refer to the social game. However, since January 2025, we started to refer to the CircleUp app instead.

The results of the full Miro board for electronics can be accessed here:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKkC2YOg=?share_link_id=635852651920

The results of the full Miro board for packaging can be accessed here:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKkCuBC4=?share_link_id=629604155331

The results of the full Miro board for textiles can be accessed here:

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKkDb-fY=?share_link_id=469211304705

After the workshop, NTNU started to visualize the developed framework, which is visualized in figure 32. The visual model includes now multiple layers: general motivations to contribute to circular economy, the four domain-specific stages of the SSBC model, each with its drivers and barriers. Interventions are categorized as information, commitment, feedback or other types. We also identified the drivers and barriers. Furthermore, the model illustrates how the different interventions will be provided through the project (e.g., through the social game, counselling, system dynamics model, or other channels). Furthermore, behaviours are prioritized according to the R-hierarchy (also known as the R-strategies) from reduce, via reuse, and finally recycle⁴.

⁴ Part of this text has been published before in November 2024 as a blog post on the CircleUp LinkedIn page as part of the Dissemination and Communication working package of the project.

Figure 32. Framework model of the circular economy practices

Domain	Stage	Intervention	Category	Communicating channel	Affected barriers / drivers
			information, commitment, feedback, other	circular stories game, system dynamics model tool, circular counselling	
General circular practices	1	Feedback on own behaviour	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	B: Not perceived important enough B: Strong habits for the old behaviour
		Analyse current circular behaviour practices	Commitment	Circular stories game, counselling	B: Social influence between household members (social norms)
		Normalizing the circular behaviour practices by showing other people do the same	Information	Circular stories game	B: Negative emotions (e.g., embarrassment, stress)
		Information on general circular practices	Information	Circular stories game	D: Fits the person's normative goals (this is the right thing to do) D: Positive emotions (pride, warm glow)
	2	Information on legislation and regulation of circular economy	Information	Circular stories game	B: Hedonistic goals (more pleasure to do something else)
		Possibilities to perform circular economy practices	Commitment	Circular stories game, counselling	D: Economic benefits (saving money) D: Having the opportunity, possibilities to perform
	7	Foster repetition of circular economy actions	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Integrate practices in everyday life (by using prompts)	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Determine and change cues triggering old behaviour	Information	Circular stories game	
		Utilize network for social support	Other	Circular stories game	

		Utilize local stakeholders for social support	Other	Circular stories game	
Food	3f	Feedback on own behaviour: awareness of what food is currently wasted within the household	Feedback	Circular stories game	<p>B: Not perceived important enough</p> <p>B: Strong habits for the old behaviour</p> <p>B: Social influence between household members (social norms)</p> <p>B: Uncertainty/lack of information about safety of eating leftovers (e.g., after a certain time, when different ingredients are mixed)</p> <p>B: Negative emotions (e.g., embarrassment, stress)</p> <p>D: Fits the person's normative goals (this is the right thing to do)</p> <p>D : Uncertainty about the quality/safety of food shared by others</p>
		Analyse current food habits	Commitment	Circular stories game, circular counselling	
		Normalizing the behaviour by showing other people do the same	Feedback	Circular stories game	
	4f	Feedback on own behaviour: what behaviour causes the waste	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
		Schedule a 30-min discussion with your family about your food and shopping routines and think of one thing that everyone would agree to change	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Providing information on hygiene and smell of composting	Information	Circular stories game	
		Feedback on own behaviour: what behaviour causes the waste?	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
		Providing information about collection of organic waste	Information	Circular stories game	

		Provide information on shared/community composting options in the vicinity of participants' home	Information	Circular stories game	
5f-I		Check what food you have at home before going shopping	Commitment	Circular stories game	D: Good planning abilities D: Easy to implement
		Make a default shopping list on your phone	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Provide knowledge on how to store leftover food	Information	Circular stories game	
5f-II		Think about how you can use leftovers to create a new dish (e.g., by combining with some additional ingredients, preparing the food differently, ect)	Commitment	Circular stories game	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life D: Knowledge, skills, know how (recipes, storage)
		Workshop on how to cook new dishes (to use up leftovers)	Other	Circular stories game (info)	
		Encourage freezing food to prevent waste	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Encourage "left-over" dinners (maybe even regularly)	Commitment	Circular stories game	
5f-III		Start by sharing with a friend or someone you are comfortable with, branch out later	Commitment	Circular stories game	B: No system for communication or contact. Mismatch of supply and demand. Hard to adopt last-minute offers of food into weekly food plan. B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life
		Good overview of sharing options (e.g., through an app, possibility to claim the foods in the apps)	Information	Circular stories game	

	5f-IV	Providing information about the collection of organic waste	Information	Circular stories game	B: No space for compost B: No collection of organic waste
		Provide information on shared community composting options in the vicinity of participants' home	Information	Circular stories game	
		Providing equipment for home-composting	Other	Circular stories game	
	6f-I	Feedback on own behaviour change – what's the impact of the change	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	D: Stable food purchase routines
	6f-II	Share experience on social game	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Feedback on own behaviour change – what is the impact of change?	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
		Workshop: households share their behaviour change with each other/recipe swaps	Other	Counselling	
	6f-III	Share experience on social game	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Feedback on own behaviour change, what is the impact of change?	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
	6f-IV	Feedback on own behaviour change: what is the impact of the change?	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
Packaging	3p	Circular story plastic waste	Commitment	Circular stories game	B: Shyness
		Background information on plastic waste as a problem	Information	Circular stories game	B. Not perceived important enough B. Does not fit with self-identity
		Information on significant portion of food items available in shops that can be purchased by using reusable bags or containers	Information	Circular stories game	B: Strong habits for the old behaviour B: Reusable containers are more expensive B: Aesthetic issues

	Assessing the amount of plastic waste	Feedback	Circular stories game	<p>B: Lack of knowledge about the specific impact of the packaging of one product compared to another</p> <p>B: Unclear sorting system/unsure what goes where</p> <p>B: Lack of knowledge on how clean packaging needs to be</p> <p>D: Social influence between household members</p> <p>D: Social influence from other households</p> <p>D: Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")</p> <p>D: Positive emotions (pride, warm glow)</p> <p>D: Fits the self-concept/identity of the person (zero-waste lifestyle)</p>
	Feedback about behaviour of other people	Feedback	Circular stories game	
	Cheap offers for reusable bags or containers in shops	Other	Other	
	Organizing the personal space in a way that makes it easy to sort where you are, e.g. with MEAS	Other	Counselling	
4p	Information on legal possibilities, regulations, what are shops obliged to do?	information	Circular stories game	<p>B: Shops do not allow reusable containers</p> <p>B: Forgetting containers</p> <p>B: Preferred brands have only packaged products</p> <p>B: Unavailability of unpackaged product alternatives</p> <p>B: To buy the alternative with reduced packaging/recycled packaging is in conflict with other factors you find important such as locally produced, eco-label etc.</p> <p>B: Unpackaged products are more expensive</p> <p>D: Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control/self-efficacy)</p> <p>D: Personal environmental motivation/values (attitudes)</p> <p>D: Economic benefits (saving money)</p>
	Circular story on a wasteless product + social feedback	Commitment, feedback	Circular stories game	
	Set reachable goals in conversation with MEAs, offer low-threshold strategies, trying out shopping for certain products with reusable containers	Other	Counselling	
	information on wasteless alternatives, fun and shiny to hook people	Information	Circular stories game	
	Prompts for the kitchen and other places where waste is produced	Other	Circular stories game	

					<p>D: Shops encourage the scheme with discounts</p> <p>D: Reusable system in place at shops</p> <p>D: Perceptions of improved hygiene</p> <p>D: Reusable object is nicer to use</p> <p>D: Product attachment (personalised as an object)</p>
5p-I	Consulting through behaviours	Feedback	Counselling	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life	
	Providing information about alternative distribution channels	Information	Circular stories game		
	Information about alternative products	Information	Circular stories game		
	Providing information about less packaged goods	Information	Circular stories game		
	Make it easy to get unpackaged items-online shopping etc does not offer the choice, refill shops can require separate trips which can be difficult in time pressured lives, need space to store if purchase in bulk	Other	Other		
5p-II	Commit to do the action certain number of days in a row (resets if skip a day)	Commitment	Circular stories game	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life	
	Prompts	Other	Circular stories game		
	Consulting through advisors	Feedback	Counselling		
	Information on circular infrastructure	Information	Circular stories game		
	Deposit systems for reusable packaging	Other	Other		
	Providing information on reusable containers	Information	Circular stories game		

		Smart bin plastic	Other	Counselling	
		Give away reusable containers	Other	Other	
		Preparing infrastructure for wasteless shopping with advisors, training wasteless shopping in groups	Other	Other	
	5p-III	Suggestions of how to reuse packaging	Information	Circular stories game	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life B: Forgetting the packaging that one wants to reuse when for example going for shopping
		Stickers that can be put on the door to prompt people to remember their containers	Other	Counselling	
		Implementation intentions intervention (making mental cues that get activated when going shopping)	Other	Other	
	5p-IV	Providing information on what goes where and how to prepare	Information	Circular stories game	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life B: Compound material makes sorting difficult
		Providing information on what is easy to recycle	Information	Circular stories game	
	6p-I	Feedback on own behaviour (change)	Feedback	Circular stories game	
	6p-II	Commitment to use reusable containers for a certain period of time to advance in the social game	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Information about possible relapse situations + strategies	Information	Circular stories game	
		Feedback on own behaviour	Feedback	Circular stories game	

		Establish routines	Other	Counselling, circular stories game		
		Habit journal	Other	Counselling, circular stories game		
		MEA advice: deciding on mid-term goals for habitualizing	Other	Counselling		
		Social game challenges for habitualizing	Other	Circular stories game		
	6p-III	Triggering normative goals/framing	Other	Other		
	6p-IV					
Electronics	3e	Information about the impact of electronics production	Information	Circular stories game	B: Low costs of many items B: Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else) B: Does not fit with self-concept/self-identity B: Strong habits for the old behaviour B: Negative emotions: fear that sharing self-owned products might be damaged or not handled with care B: Diffusion of responsibility for maintenance B: Not perceived important enough B: Insecurity how long the repaired item holds. Will it last? Will it be updated? Will it continue to work for the length of time I need, or will I need to buy another? How much will a repair cost? How easy is it to repair?	
		Hint, tips, info provided by the game and other households	Information	Circular stories game		
		Info on availability/cost or repair	Information	Circular stories game		
		Information on repair options	Information	Circular stories game		
		Information about legal rights/warranties	Information	Circular stories game		
		Information on consumer rights e.g., if shops are obliged to repair an item	Information	Circular stories game		
		Information on durability of electronics products/guarantee	Information	Circular stories game		
		Information about the impact of electronics production	Information	Circular stories game		

		Information on where to find repairable product alternatives	Information	Circular stories game	<p>B: Lack of information on durability. How do I know that an electronic good is really of higher quality?</p> <p>Only because it costs more its not automatically longer lasting than a cheaper product.</p> <p>D: Fits the person's normative goals ("This is the right thing to do")</p> <p>D: Fits the self-concept/identity of the person</p> <p>D: Social influence from other households</p> <p>D: Personal environmental motivation/values</p> <p>D : Positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm, glow)</p> <p>D: Social influence from other households</p> <p>D: Inconvenience to give it away</p> <p>D: Economic benefits</p>
		Information about local donation points	Information	Circular stories game	
		Information about secure deletion of data	Information	Circular stories game	
	4e	Information on support possibilities, e.g., other operating systems	Information	Circular stories game	<p>B: Lack of maintenance of the old product (e.g., operating system)</p> <p>B: Data security concerns</p> <p>B: Needs to be easy to get (located nearby), the right costs, and available when needed</p> <p>B: No repair index like in France</p> <p>B: No repairable products available</p> <p>B: Higher initial costs/lack of funding</p> <p>B: High price in relation to value of the item</p> <p>B: Brand perception on quality</p> <p>B : Repairable products of lower quality/less fashionable (Fairphone)</p>
		Fostering emotional attachment (stories from the life of the product)	Information	Circular stories game	
		Personal examples provided by the game/advisor	Feedback	Circular stories game	
	Feedback about behaviour of other people	Feedback	Circular stories game		

					<p>D: Annoyance with cheap products/programmed obsolescence</p> <p>D: Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>D: Easy to implement</p> <p>D: Personal environmental motivation/values</p> <p>D: Availability</p> <p>D: Easy to implement</p> <p>D: Near-by possibilities for sharing, e.g. tool container for settlement</p> <p>D: Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>D: Product attachment</p> <p>D: Leasing an item for an extended period of time which can be repaired by the company, rather than buying (can be expensive)</p> <p>D: Pleasure of owning a high-quality product</p> <p>D: Savings in the future/investment</p>
5e-l	Collaborative in-house inspection of status-quo	Other	Counselling	B: No updates available (computers, mobile phones, tablets)	
	Home mining challenge “finding the treasure”	Commitment	Circular stories game		
	Circular story	Commitment	Circular stories game		
	Feedback about behaviour of other people	Feedback	Circular stories game		
	Suggestion by advisor not to buy	Other	Counselling		
	On the game, the householder can say that they need an item, and the game can suggest other ideas, and the advisor can help	Other	Circular stories game		

5e-II	Game provides householders with info where they can borrow the item from (who posts this, the community or the advisor?)	Information	Circular stories game	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life B: Lack of common storage space B: Lack of infrastructure
	Information about formal sharing resources or legal agreements	Information	Circular stories game	
	Feedback on own behaviour	Feedback	Counselling, Circular stories game	
	Consulting through advisors	Other	Counselling	
	Information on the person I will exchange/share the item with	Other	Circular stories game	
5e-III	Home mining challenge “finding the lost treasure”	Commitment	Circular stories game	B: Lack of infrastructure B: Inconvenience to get it repaired B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life B: Loosing the producer warranties when opening the product
	Collaborative in-house inspection of status-quo	Other	Counselling	
	Feedback about behaviour of other people	Feedback	Counselling, Circular stories game	
5e-IV	Home mining challenge	Commitment	Circular stories game	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life
6e-I	Home mining challenge “finding the lost treasure”	Commitment	Circular stories game	
	Circular story	Commitment	Circular stories game	
	Feedback on own behaviour	Feedback	Counselling, circular stories game	
6e-II	Promoting community led sharing resources	Other	Circular stories game	D: Social event to share
	Consulting through advisors	Other	Counselling	

		Could the householder set goals and targets for the game, for what they want to achieve (game is good for motivation)	Commitment	Circular stories game	
	6e-III	Do it yourself workshop: where possible? Might be illegal for some products	Other	Circular stories game	
		Concerted actions with households, craftsmen and repair cafes	Other	Circular stories game	
		Feedback on own behaviour (change)	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
	6e-IV	Feedback	Feedback	Circular stories game	
		Home mining-challenge	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		Organizing a collection	Other	Circular stories game	
Textiles	3t	Information consulting through advisors	Information	Counselling	B: Strong habits for the old behaviour B: Not the social norm/perception concerns B: Hedonistic goals (more pleasure to do something else) B: Status, want to be in fashion B: Social norms against the behaviour B: Lack of knowledge about repair services some brands offer B: Desire for something new B: Marketing from industry D: Social influence from other households D: Fits the person's normative goals D: Fits the self-concept/identity of the person
		Providing information on the impact of the clothing industry	Information	Circular stories game	
		Feedback about own behaviour, behaviour of others	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
		Triggering normative goals/framing	Information	Circular stories game	
		Feedback about own behaviour, how much is harmful?	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
		Information by role models	Information	Circular stories game	

					<p>D: Economic benefits</p> <p>D: Social influence between household members</p> <p>D: Dress code requirement from school/work</p> <p>D: Personal environmental motivation/values</p> <p>D: Emotional attachment to old clothes</p> <p>D: Information from social media</p> <p>D: Positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)</p>
4t	Consulting through advisors	Other	counselling	<p>B: Expectational requirement to purchase certain product</p> <p>B: Lack of skills/Creativity</p> <p>B: costs</p> <p>D: Personal environmental motivation/values</p> <p>D: Economic benefits (saving money)</p> <p>D: Interest in skills like sewing</p> <p>D: Creativity</p>	
	Feedback about own behaviour in comparison with possible alternatives (simulating alternative interventions)	Feedback	Circular stories game		
	Using renting or clothes libraries (simulating alternative interventions)	Commitment	Circular stories game		
	Information about repairing infrastructure	Information	Circular stories game		
	Providing information about durability and repairing	Information	Circular stories game		
	Possibility to loan equipment	Other	Circular stories game		
	Activity: visiting repair shops (simulating alternative interventions)	Other	Circular stories game		
	How do you recognize durable/repairable clothes	Information	Circular stories game		
	Action possibility to loan equipment	Other	Circular stories game		
	Details on where you can purchase upcycled fashion (map social game)	Information	Circular stories game		
	Second-hand fashion blogs	Information	Circular stories game		
Rôle models (map social game)	Information	Circular stories game			

	5t-I	Consulting through advisors (social game: reading stories from other players)	Other	Counselling	B: Lack of overview of the clothes you already have
		Feedback about own behaviour: how successful are the new actions (volume of reduction) (social game: liking of stories, interaction with other players)	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
		Use renting or clothes libraries	Other	Circular stories game	
		House mining challenge	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		No buying challenges (link social game)	Commitment	Circular stories game	
	5t-II	Blog, social media, influencers showing diversity and sustainable styles/Repaired/upcycled clothes	Information	Circular stories game	B: Time constraints
		Following courses for self-repair	Other	Circular stories game (info)	
		Visiting repair shops	Other	Circular stories game (info)	
		Organizing repair workshops, making repairing a social event (link social game badges, liking of stories, interaction with other players, reading stories from other players)	Other	Circular stories game (info)	
	5t-III	Information about how to wash clothes	Information	Circular stories game	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life
		Material advisors could support to try out digital alternatives: e.g., vinted (link social game: mapping second hand shops)	Commitment	Counselling	

	5t-IV	Follow courses for upcycling/recombining	Other	Circular stories game (info)	B: Time pressure/complications in everyday life B: Lack of equipment
		Consulting through advisors	Other	Counselling	
		Organizing upcycling workshops, making upcycling a social event (link social game)	Other	Circular stories game	
	6t-I	Feedback about own behaviour	Feedback	Circular stories game, counselling	
		House mining challenge	Commitment	Circular stories game	
		No buying challenge (social game)	Commitment	Circular stories game	
	6t-II	Organizing repair workshops, making repairing a social event (link social game badges, liking of stories, interaction with other players, reading stories from other players)	Other	Circular stories game (info)	
	6t-III	Information on apps/Charity shops supporting access to second-hand clothes	Information	Circular stories game	
	6t-IV	Action: Organizing upcycling workshops, making upcycling a social event (link social game: maybe in a different realm, going to public sphere; recombination challenge; challenge recombining clothes)	Other	Circular stories game (info)	

Legend: Category = information, commitment, feedback, other; communication channel = circular stories game, system dynamics model tool, circular counselling, other

3.6 Workshop 3: Stakeholder involvement in the framework development

On November 4th 2024, we hosted the third CircleUp, which was dedicated to engaging stakeholders to gather input on the CircleUp project and circular economy practices at the household level. The workshop was specifically designed for stakeholders interested in promoting circular economy practices at the household level. Our project partners played a crucial role in preparing a list of relevant stakeholders, ensuring that we reached out to a diverse group. We sent out invitations and followed up with reminders, emphasizing the importance of the participants' feedback and input to the success of the project. The workshop brought together a variety of 15 stakeholders from different fields who shared their views and experiences, enriching the discussion with a wide range of perspectives. The workshop also included dedicated time for input and questions, fostering an interactive and safe environment. We also provided updates on our project's progress and innovations and highlighted the importance of the social game as part of the intervention in CircleUp. This was the agenda for the third workshop:

1. CircleUp
2. Get to know each other
3. Social game
4. Input from stakeholders
5. Break
6. WP2 explained
7. Breakout rooms: group discussion in Miro boards
8. Q&A

In the first part of the workshop, we introduced the overall goal of CircleUp. To break the ice a bit, we organized a game to allow participants to learn more about each other. Afterwards, Beatrice Beitz from Prosperkolleg provided an explanation of the social game we planned to use in the project. She elaborated on the objectives of the game and the underlying principles. Afterwards, we invited the stakeholders to give some feedback and to provide input to the project. Prior to the workshop, the participants

were asked to reflect on a few questions that had been sent to them via e-mail. The idea was that this would make it easier to give some input during the workshop.

In the second part of the workshop, the conceptual framework as was already partially defined in the first and the second workshop, was further redefined. The external stakeholders and project partners were divided into breakout rooms, where they engaged in collaborative discussions using Miro boards. In the boards, participants had to think about additional circular economy practices on both individual and group level. Furthermore, households need access to knowledge and information to adopt the circular economy practices. Therefore, an additional goal in the Miro board was to think about this information and the sources giving this information. Participants came up with different types of sources such as blogs, existing maps, social media accounts etc., that could help households understand and implement circular economy practices. To help us improve our project, we sent out a short questionnaire after the workshop, asking stakeholders for feedback on what worked and what could be improved. The evaluation and the results will be explained in the following part. ⁵

The evaluation of the CircleUp stakeholders' workshop

To improve the CircleUp project and future workshops of CircleUp, we wanted to receive feedback from the stakeholders on the workshop through an evaluation survey. The survey aimed to:

- Get an overview of how satisfied attendees were regarding the workshop (content, structure, and the CircleUp project)
- Identify areas for improvement within the CircleUp project
- Identify areas for improvement within the workshop

On November 6th, 2024, all the participants from the stakeholders workshop received the following e-mail:

⁵ Part of this text has been published before in November 2024 as a blog post on the CircleUp LinkedIn page as part of the Dissemination and Communication working package of the project.

Dear participant,

I hope this email finds you well. Thank you for attending the CircleUp stakeholders' workshop on November 4th. We appreciate your participation and hope you found the workshop valuable.

To help us improve our project, we would like to receive your feedback. Could you please take a few minutes to answer the following questions?

Thank you!

*Best regards,
CircleUp Team*

We received 6 answers out of 14 invitations sent, resulting in a response rate of 43%. The survey, using Microsoft Forms, consisted of 8 open-ended questions and took a maximum of 5 minutes to complete. A reminder was sent on November 13th, 2024.

In the following section, you will find each survey question along with the participants' answers.

Question 1: What do you think of the structure of the workshop?

Ok
The structure was well planned.
I liked the teamwork on the board. But i felt real awkward in the part where we shuld introduce each other. I would have felt better if one just could introduce oneself to the others.
Was ok, just a bit too long for online workshop, but i get why it was like that.
Good and logical
The 1st part of the workshop was poorly planned: the way of presentation, the message to deliver to participants, presentation of the game

Question 2: Was the content of the workshop relevant and useful for you?

Partly
The topic is familiar, many things are known. But nuances make all the difference. It was a good opportunity to refresh things that were a bit forgotten.
I participated only as a guest so the usefulest part was the presentation about the project.
It was interesting but more because of discussions in smaller working groups
yes, I understand more what the outcome can be

Question 3: Where there any parts that were particularly challenging or unclear during the workshop?

No
No
Who are your target groups? How will you recruit the 100 families?
The idea of a social game remained unclear.
Knowing how our contribution will be used

Question 4: Are the project goals and objectives of CircleUp clear?

Question 5: What do you like about the CircleUp project?

Data collection
That solutions are being sought to change habits. Only if each of us invests, significant changes are possible.
The direct intervention in households
Can't tell from one meeting
the concrete interventions
Promising

Question 6: Where do you think the CircleUp project can improve?

Build on what's already there. Do not invent new circular maps.
Promote this project more to the public.
The problem of all projects is that it has only a short time but sustainable consumption is a topic that needs to be cared about for ages. Short lifetimed projects are not sustainable.
Can't tell from one meeting
The "why" for participants that are not very concerned

Question 7: Can you describe the most innovative part of CircleUp?

Direct contact with participants
Work in groups
Can't tell from one meeting
100 households with the same advice

Question 8: Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for us?

Have a good working power!

Based on the evaluation results, we can observe that, overall, participants were satisfied with the content of the workshop and the concept of CircleUp. However, individual differences in background, knowledge, and needs led to varied experiences.

Recognizing that there is always room for improvement, we identified several key takeaways for the further development of the project:

- Think about what's in a name for households to participate in CircleUp
- Make the innovative part of the project more clear, especially in communicating/disseminating with other stakeholders.
- Think about the sustainability of the project itself. What will happen with the concept, the game, the households after the project?
- Promote this project more to the public.
- Keep up the good work!

3.7 Workshop 4: Defining the challenges

During the CircleUp Oxford project meeting on March 6th 2025, NTNU organized another workshop as part of Working Package 2 to develop circular economy challenges for the CircleUp application. The workshop was divided into two parts:

Part 1: Developing challenges

The primary goal of the first part of the workshop was to develop 15 challenges, with 4 challenges per domain (food, textiles, packaging and electronics). Participants were asked to formulate these challenges at both the individual and the collective level.

Various circular economy actions and behaviours were generated in previous NTNU workshops for the CircleUp project. Table 15-18 show all these actions and behaviours per domain and were compiled into an Excel list for the workshop.

Table 15: List of behaviours within the food domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

FOOD
1. Plan purchases to avoid food waste
Individual level:
Only buy small portions of food with short durability
When shopping, use a food recipe
Meal plan a week in a time
Do the shopping on certain days of the week
Do not buy new food too soon, so that old vegetables/fruits are really eaten
Analyse current food habits
Schedule a 30-min discussion with your family about food and shopping routines and think of one thing that everyone would agree on to change
Check what food you have at home before going shopping
Make a default shopping list on your phone
Encourage freezing food to prevent food waste
Check a fridge before shopping
Start by sharing with a friend or someone you are comfortable with, branch out later
Use shopping lists
Buy expired food
Community level:

Organize a workshop on how to cook new dishes to use up leftovers
Organize a community dinner
2. Utilize leftovers in the kitchen
Individual level:
Create your recipes based on what you have already got in your fridge and only buy what you really need in addition
Use recipes from the previous generations
Become more creative in cooking
Freeze leftovers
Think about how you can use leftovers to create a new dish (e.g., by combining with some additional ingredients, preparing the food differently, ect)
Put leftovers in the fridge/freezer/on a balcony
Use glass containers for storage
Community level:
Organize a leftover cooking skill course
Organize a community event
Encourage “left-over” dinners (maybe even regularly)
Workshop: households share their behaviour change with each other/recipe swaps
3. Give leftovers to others
Individual level:
Share with farms, zoo
Community level:
Join a food sharing group in real life or online
Use public sharing spaces for food
Create a network of people who are willing to share leftover food
organize a food sharing group in real life or online

Introduce a neighbourhood group in a messenger app (such as Whats app, Signal etc.) where neighbours offer each other their food leftovers
4. Dispose leftovers correctly
Individual level:
Household pledge for consequent recycling + looking into bins with counsellors

Table 16: List of behaviours within the packaging domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

PACKAGING
1. Avoid packaging
Individual level:
Make it easy to get unpackaged items-online shopping etc does not offer the choice, refill shops can require separate trips which can be difficult in time pressured lives, need space to store if purchase in bulk
Preparing infrastructure for wasteless shopping with advisors, training wasteless shopping in groups
Habit journal
2. Use reusable containers/bags
Individual level:
Commitment to use reusable containers for a certain period of time to advance in the social game
Set reachable goals in conversation with MEAs, offer low-threshold strategies, trying out shopping for certain products with reusable containers
3. Reuse packaging
4. Sort and recycle properly

Table 17: List of behaviours within the electronics domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

ELECTRONICS
1. Reduce buying electronics
2. Share electronics
3. Repair electronics
4. Give electronics to others
Community level:
Collaborative in-house inspection of status-quo
Home mining challenge “finding the treasure”
Collaborative in-house inspection of status-quo
Organize a Do it yourself workshop: where possible? Might be illegal for some products
Concerted actions with households, craftsmen and repair cafes

Table 18: List of behaviours within the textile domain as defined before the workshop in Oxford

TEXTILES
1. Reduce buying textiles
Community level:
No buying challenges
Swap clothes instead of buying
2. Repair textiles
Repair your clothes
Community level:
Organizing repair workshops, making repairing a social event (link social game badges, liking of stories, interaction with other players, reading stories from other players)
Visiting repair shops
3. Buy second hand
4. Reuse and upcycle
Using renting or clothes libraries (simulating alternative interventions)
Possibility to loan equipment
Community level:

Follow courses for upcycling/recombining
Organizing upcycling workshops, making upcycling a social event
Use renting or clothes libraries

The task of the workshop was to design different overarching challenges. This task was divided into several steps:

The first part of the workshop started with a group discussion on the definition of a challenge. We came to the following criteria:

A challenge is an activity designed to be completed within a short period of time to maintain engagement and motivation (e.g., 3 weeks). It should be relevant and applicable to most households. The challenges should be possible to perform without making (high) financial investments. This will make the challenges feasible for all participants. Within the challenges, we should find a balance between being a bit but not too demanding. The difficulty will vary across the different challenges. Additionally, we need both collective challenges that can be undertaken within the neighbourhood and individual/household challenges.

Afterwards, the participants worked individually to formulate relevant behaviours or actions into overarching challenges for both the individual and collective level. They identified whether previously defined behaviours/actions needed to be discarded or rewritten and determined if additional challenges were needed. These challenges were written on post-its and placed on the table.

Participants then worked in pairs to discuss and match their challenges. They had to create a new list of four initial challenges per domain.

Participants placed all their post-its on four different whiteboards and visited each whiteboard in groups to rank the challenges. The four groups rotated between the whiteboards.

Part 2: Designing a challenge

Afterwards, participants selected one challenge and designed it in detail using the different stages of the SSBC model (Bamberg, 2013).

First, the four stages of SSBC model were briefly discussed and NTNU presented two examples of challenges in detail. Participants then answered the following questions for their selected challenge according to the SSBC stages:

Stage 1: Predecisional stage:

Question: WHY SHOULD I CARE ABOUT THE PROBLEM

Strategies to answer this question:

- a. How do other people behave? What is acceptable?
- b. Make people aware of the behaviour problem
- c. People should commit to the challenge

Stage 2: Preactional stage:

Question: WHAT CAN I DO INSTEAD

- a. What are other alternatives for the behaviour?
- b. What are the barriers and drivers for the alternatives?

Stage 3: Actional stage:

Question: HOW DO I IMPLEMENT THIS IN MY EVERYDAY LIFE?

- a. Help people with planning to implement the new behaviour

Stage 4: Postactional stage:

Question: HOW DO I PREVENT TO FALL BACK INTO OLD HABITS?

- a. Which strategies can people use to not fall back into old habits?

In the next step, the participants had to integrate the various CircleUp intervention tools into the development of the challenge during the different stages of the model. These tools included the LCA tool, the system modelling learning, the smart bin and the material advisor.

The main outcomes of the workshop:

1. Development of challenges

The participants, divided into four groups, successfully created 15 challenges, with 4 challenges per domain (food, textiles, packaging and electronics) at both individual and collective levels.

2. One challenge in detail

Each group designed one challenge in detail using the SSBC model, addressing

each stage and integrating various tools such as the LCA tool, system modeling learning, smart bins, and the material advisors. Although most groups did not finish all the stages by the end of the workshop, they gained a better understanding of how to develop a challenge in detail.

3. Experiencing the process of a challenge

Participants could experience the steps households will go through during a challenge.

All these outcomes could contribute to the further development and implementation of the CircleUp application.

The outline of the NTNU workshop organised in Oxford to finalise the challenges is included in Appendix b.

In Table 19-20, the challenges as defined by the four different working groups are outlined.

Table 19: Challenges created for FOOD in Oxford for WP2

<p>FOOD:</p> <p>Individual level</p>
Plan your weekly shopping; what will you cook and only buy what you need
Plan purchases for a week (month) and see how much food waste you are able to avoid
How much food is purchased in advance for a month and compare: How much food waste is avoided? Food purchase bills? (as opposed to not planning)
Plan your food purchase next week to avoid buying food that you will not use: Check what you have, find recipes
Plan and shop for five (or another number based on their routine) meals for a week - to reduce food waste
Reduce food waste by 1 kg/week (have reduce side of biowaste bin by 1/2 within 1 month)
Cut shopping bill by 20%
Do not go to the shops for X (3?) days
Try one new receipt for frozen leftovers per week
Pickle unused or close to expire vegetables

Have a use-up day - find or create a recipe for fresh food left in your fridge before you do your shop
Use a recipe generated/based on your food available at home during next week
Freeze leftovers: plan for one day a week that you eat something you have in your freezer
Manage leftovers well before they occur (cook ingredients separately, mix at your plate, not for all)
Used frozen leftovers (1x/week)
Check when your next food waste collection is, so you are ready
Manage leftovers straight away, i.e. put them in the fridge or freezer, develop suitable routines
Collect and try 5 new recipes
Create a purchase plan for the next week
Buy and use food from discount section with same day expiry
Cook one meal with leftovers and share a photo of your meal. Be creative
Use leftovers to make your lunch today
Visit one love food hate waste website for inspiration and recipes
FOOD:
Community level
Use whatsapp group to share recipes
Volunteer at your local community fridge/table... to help redistribute food and save waste
gardening season: set up whatsapp group etc to share garden fruits and vegetables
Find your nearest community fridge
Leftover putlock once a week in community
Community food waste diner: meet and bring what is close to expire, cook together
Organized 1 community dinner per month
One thematic community dinner per month, e.g., tomato evening, potato evening, cucumber evening
After a celebration: plan a leftover celebration
After a celebration: give the food to other organizations
Campaign the narrative of only taking what you need in canteens, buffets

Locate a community fridge or other food sharing initiative to donate surplus food to
Invite friends and ask everyone to bring 3 food items they have at home (no new purchases allowed). Create a meal out of it
Share more, waste less: Find one option to share your food this week
#bagabargain: visit your local community garden + bag a bargain and reduce food waste

Table 20: Challenges created for PACKAGING in Oxford for WP2

PACKAGING:
Individual level
Try to organize a practice where you buy from local markets, farmers
Try one week so that you buy only refill. Is that possible in your town?
Find five products in local shops that you normally buy packaged where you could replace with loose products
Ask you supermarket for options to buy unpackaged food
Reduce packaging by 0.5 kg/week
Visited no-package shop once a week
Purchase shampoo and conditioner bars/dry shampoo to reduce packaging waste
Unsure on what to do with an item? Check the waste wizard (UK)
Plan to take your plastic film to the supermarket this week
Take lunch to work in a reusable plastic container to prevent purchase of packaged food
Take a reusable water bottle + coffee cup with you when heading out
Use one 'give me tap' website to find out where you can refill your water bottle
Buy a reusable food bag for vegetables and fruits to avoid plastic waste
Use a reusable bag for shopping
Find your closest re-fill shop
Only buy unpackaged fresh produced fruit and vegatbles and dont use supermarket plastic bags
Track when you purchase and how long it takes to plan your trip to refill store
Get unpacked items
Try to include one zero packaging practice in your everyday life

Avoid buying things in plastic bags, reuse the plastic bags, buy loose fruit
Visit a refill shop to reduce the amount of plastic waste generated. You could refill household cleaning products like detergent or dry goods like rice
PACKAGING:
Community level
Team up with neighbours to organize purchase of large quantities of basic food/organize a distribution next week
Buy together to reduce packaging
Buy in bulk with friends and neighbours to reduce packaging, i.e., large sack of flour
Neighbourhood shopping
Have organised 1 package reuse event at community level
Organized one event based on youtube DIY advices for packaging reuse

Table 21: Challenges created for TEXTILES in Oxford for WP2

TEXTILES:
Individual level
Participate in a clothes swap event
Refrain from buying new clothes for a month (unless replacing damaged), ask friends for a swap
Have not bought any new clothes within two months
Have developed two sets of capsule wardrobe for each season
Before buying new clothes, look in local second hand/charity shops to see if you can purchase there
Find your nearest second hand shop
Thrift rather than buy for new for 6 months
Find your nearest charity shops and secondhand shops and visit these first before buying new and spot on the map
Swap or donate three items a year
Next time your clothes need repairing look online to see if you can learn to repair them yourself. You can find good videos here.
Look on YouTube for how to repair a hole in a pair of jeans, sew a button

During next month, not buy any items of clothes
Shopp less, create new: Take an old clothing piece and style it new. Share a photo and be creative
Avoid buying new clothes for defined period of time (a month) or have a budget for it
Re-order your wardrobe and put clothes you wear and waste on the right hand side. After 6 months, consider donating items on the left that you havent worn
Make a revision in your wardrobe
Find clothes to give away
Repair a piece of clothing
Go to secondhand shop if you need more clothes
Make a list of what you need before clothes shopping
Carry out a clothes audit. Try and identify 1 item to repair, 1 item to wear more. 1 item to give away. If you need more clothes this month buy only second hand.
Weigh your clothes and compare kg/tonnes
TEXTILES:
Community level
Reduce social pressure of purchases of new textiles
Organize a clothes swap event with your friends
Organize a clothes swap event with children clothes
Invite friends and family to a clothes swap party
Organize a friend's clothes swap day or group to continue swapping
Organize a clothes swap with neighbours or friends
Organize a textile/repair cafe event to showcase your (new) skills and help others mend their clothes
Have organized one upcycling social event
Capsule wardrobe event (exchange of clothing to combine gaps)
Organize a rental system for clothes etc
Upcycling workshop for textiles: two groups of people: people who can share their skills, people want to learn how to use sewing machine, apply 1 week
Upcycling workshop for textiles: From organisation team: meat and plan event and do event

Table 22: Challenges created for ELECTRONICS in Oxford for WP2

ELECTRONICS:
Individual level
Find your nearest repair cafe
Have repaired at least one electronic unit in 1 month
Learn 1 advice on how to fix electronic unit from youtube
Buying second-hand electronics
Next time you find something you want to buy-consider borrowing it instead, visit a library of things
Find your nearest library or things
Sort through your cupboard and sell, donate or recycle old electrical items
Check what old electronics you have (old phones) and sell or recycle
Make a list of nearby repair shops and use them when you need
Search for old electricals in your house. Donate, sell, repair or recycle all unwanted items
Try to repair some broken electronics you have by yourself, by repair cafe, by professional repairer
Find repair services in your area and commit to use these before buying new
Find a repair shops or place where to leave used electronic items
Visit a repair cafe next time something breaks, over 60% of the items taken to a repair cafe can be fixed. Will yours be one of them?
Find your nearest repair cafe
Share or care: Share or rent electronics instead of buying a new one or using it alone
Go through your electronics not used anymore: Give them to friends or recycle
ELECTRONICS:
Community level
Set up a whatsapp group or similar with neighbours and friends to list tools and other items you own to lend, borrow and share when needed
Sharing items
Share with neighbours
If you plan on buying a new electronic, ask a friend or neighbour first

Arts workshop for electronics that will never be used again
Have a movie night using a rented projector
Volunteer at your local repair cafe to help more things be fixed
Electronic swap
Community raffle
Repair at household level yard
Make an inventory of the electronic devices you own that you would share with others. Ask your neighbours to do the same. Create a sharing system.
Organize a neighbour marked for swapping, give away, sharing
Non time bound electronic challenges: visit a lot next time you need something, look on blackmarket/second hand next time you need something, visit a repair cafe next time

4. List of final challenges

After the workshop in Oxford, NTNU reviewed all the challenges and proposed a final list of 15 challenges. The project partners all agreed on the following challenges, outlined in Table 23.

Table 23: List of final challenges for CircleUp

Behaviour	Alternative behaviour for the challenge
FOOD	
1. Plan purchases to avoid food waste	Use a shopping list (ind. level) Use a meal plan (ind. level)
2. Reuse leftovers	Make a leftovers meal (ind. level) Store leftovers properly (ind. Level)
3. Give away leftovers	Organize a leftovers dinner (collective level)
4. Share your leftover management skills with others	Share your food waste skills with others such as how to store food, freeze leftovers, and understand date labels (collective level)
ELECTRONICS	

1. Reduce buying electronics	<p>Audit of your electronic devices (ind. level)</p> <p>Audit of your electronic devices and give away to others at least one unused item (coll. level)</p> <p>Maintain your electronic devices (ind. level)</p>
2. Repair broken electronics	Repair one of your broken electronics (ind. level)
3. Reuse electronics	<p>Organize a community sharing system for electronic devices (collective level)</p> <p>Organize a swap electronic event (collective level)</p>
TEXTILES	
1. Reduce textiles	<p>Wardrobe audit (ind. level)</p> <p>Not buying any clothes (ind. level)</p>
2. Buy second-hand clothes	Buy second-hand (ind. level)
3. Reuse, repair, upcycle clothes	<p>Organize a repair textile event (collective level)</p> <p>Organize an upcycle textile event (collective level)</p> <p>Organize a cloth swap event (collective level)</p>
PACKAGING	
1. Avoid packaging (refuse, reduce)	<p>No packaging (ind. level)</p> <p>Less packaging (ind. level)</p>
2. Reuse packaging	<p>Use reusable bags (ind. level)</p> <p>Use reusable containers (ind. level)</p> <p>Use a reusable coffee cup (ind. level)</p> <p>Use a reusable lunch box (ind. level)</p>
3. Avoid packaging together	Buy in bulk together (collective. level)

5. Guidelines for the CircleUp app

By the end of January 2025, NTNU suggested a more comprehensive concept of the CircleUp app based on the Bottrop simulation presented during one of the consortium meetings, the current version of the conceptual framework, and the previous discussions held in the bi-weekly meetings. All the consortium partners decided together to adopt this app concept for the further development of the project.

5.1 The ambition of the app

The participants should be motivated to use the app regularly. Therefore, the app needs to be meaningful and engaging, which we will achieve through both in-app assistance and support from the CircleUp team. The app will feature feedback mechanisms, reminders, and challenges to keep the users engaged.

The app will also serve as a platform for building a social community, both within the app and in the real world. Therefore, all the challenges are based on the individual but also on the community level such as sharing food in the neighbourhood or organizing local repair events. The app will also include some fun / motivating gamification elements which at the same time foster a sense of community. To make the app more sustainable, the app should be usable and customizable by future stakeholders, e.g. communities, schools or universities. Therefore, the concept should be modular and be possible to use for different user groups. Furthermore, the app will be available to participating households, who will receive full functionality. Additionally, other users can be invited to join the app as well.

5.2 The intervention strategies within the app

Within the app, different intervention strategies are included such as the circular stories, the challenges, the waste bins, and links to the external surveys and the diaries. The app will also contain a section on the LCA analyses. The app will give direct feedback on the effect of finished challenges (LCA), based on short questionnaires. Participants who are not from the target households can skip the LCA questionnaires. Furthermore, the app will include links to the interactive learning tool (system modelling). The interactive learning tool will also be linked to specific stages in the challenges. The app includes support tools supporting the challenges. Furthermore, habit trackers will be included. The app will give continuous feedback from the smart bin next to tailored feedback. The app will have a section with a

progress tracker of the challenge. Furthermore, we will include circular stories which has to be written after each challenge. With the circular stories, we will stimulate personal reflection on the participants' "Circular Journey" of the challenge.

5.3 The circular stories concept

Central to our community-building strategy is the integration of Circular Stories, a narrative-based component designed to foster emotional engagement, creativity, and reflection (see in more detail in section 2.4). Circular Stories add a distinctive dimension by rendering circular actions personally meaningful and socially visible.

As participants engage in challenges, structured around individual or collaborative circular practices, they are guided through a storytelling process embedded in the app. At key transition points, users are prompted to document their experiences through notes, photographs, or emotion journaling, i.e. through emojis. These individual contributions culminate in a Circular Story, which captures both the action taken and the personal reflections surrounding it. Circular stories can look very different for different participants, leaving room for varying personal skills and personality types.

This storytelling element is not only a reflective tool, but also a communication interface to allow for a two-way process of social identity formation (Postmes et al. 2005). The stories are published in a shared feed, which functions on two levels:

- Top-down, by presenting what it means to act as a Circular Citizen through the story feed that shows a diverse collection of circular practices and solutions
- Bottom-up, by allowing users to actively shape the content of the Circular Citizen Identity represented in the story feed through their own stories, reinforcing a sense of belonging and agency with the CircleUp community.

In doing so, Circular Stories support the development of a Circular Citizen Identity, enabling individuals to see their behaviours as part of a broader collective transformation, while giving visibility to the real-world impact of their actions.

5.4 The challenges within the app

The challenges will be launched simultaneously for all participants within each country, where possible, with a set time limit (e.g., 3 weeks). The challenges are domain specific covering areas such as food, packaging, clothes, and electronics. Participants

can invite other users from the same country to join the challenge. Some challenges will focus on individual actions, while others will encourage collaborative actions that encourage team building. The challenges follow a generic structure over all countries but will be localized. Figure 34 shows how each challenge will follow the different stages of the SSBC model. Several challenges are launched at the same time to give people some freedom of choice.

The primary focus will be behaviours with measurable impacts, assessed through life cycle assessment. Some challenges aim to inspire personal reflection, (everyday) creativity and citizenship behaviours, addressing the emotional dimension. These enrich the circular stories and strengthen social identification with CircleUp/ the circular citizen but their impact may be less measurable. Figure 33 shows the different functionalities of the overall app.

CircleUp App-Functionalities (overview)

Overall concept

The app has the following main functionalities:

- The **circular stories** section is an interactive feed of stories about changes in circular practices where the participants should post their experiences and tell others about what they did and how. This can also include posts by the material advisors (tips, shared personal experiences) and the research team to create a critical mass of activities (especially important in the beginning). Since the circular stories part plays an important role in the app, they ideally appear on the main screen when the app is opened by the player (next to the challenges part).
- The **challenges** part gives the participants series of tasks per domain in a time limited way (e.g., for 3 weeks). The challenges have different steps designed following the stage model of behaviour change developed in WP2. Challenges connect to the external surveys (baseline), give input to (and potentially retrieve info from) the LCAs, link to the information database of the app, refer to the system modelling learning tool at specific points, may use information from the smart bins to give feedback, and feed at the end of the challenge into the circular stories. The challenges are designed as story lines. To offer people some agency and allow them to build intrinsic motivation, several challenges within one domain (food, packaging, clothes, electronics) are started at the same time. Challenges follow a generic storyline which will be localized by the teams. Challenges cover both individual and collaborative actions. As challenges run in parallel with the achievements publicly displayed on the impact board, they frame individual actions as collective ones. Some of the challenges will be created as "real-life" outdoor social activities. People can team up with other users to do challenges together and create an extra "social boost".
- The **external surveys** section may send people invitations to the external surveys (implemented in for example "nettskjema") at selected points in time (baseline, midways, end of intervention, follow up). This should be done by push messages. Ideally, the app would generate a token in the invitation link that can link the answers of the survey to the person using the app.
- The **LCA** part is mostly a background module that uses input from the short surveys answered in the app after completing a challenge to assess the impact of the action. This has to be on a rather generic level to not overburden the participants. Participants from outside the households may hop over the surveys. This information will be used in the feedback to the participants.
- The **information** section collects all links, material, maps of local circular economy opportunities, etc. that the material advisors and the researchers identify as relevant. To sections of this database will be referred to specifically in the earlier stages of the challenges, but the database should also be searchable independently (and maybe even extendable by the participants).
- The **learning tool** is meant to give the participants a feeling for the potential impact of their changes. This is especially relevant in the "what" stage of the stage model and will be used in the challenges accordingly. However, it might also be accessible directly, if people want that.
- The **smart bins** section administers the waste bins and displays the achieved changes in weight of waste fractions. People can get feedback about their daily waste weights in a dedicated section of the app.
- The **progress tracker** visualizes progress participants have made in each challenge. In addition, there will be a collective impact board with all achievements the households in one country created together. As a key gamification element, this feedback mechanism should be designed to encourage cooperation/collaboration and a sense of community and might be accompanied by badges. The decision about the visualization of progress in the challenges (closing circles, growing plants, something else) will be taken together with the designer.

Figure 33. Overview of the CircleUp app functionalities

Figure 34. Challenges flow of the CircleUp app

6. Matching the interventions to the conceptual framework

Following the SSBC model, the first stage or the pre-decisional stage, involves a person becoming aware of the consequences of his or her current behaviour and evaluating it. This awareness can lead to the formation of a goal intention. The goal intention is influenced by different socio-psychological factors such as the awareness of consequences, feeling responsible for making changes, and social norms.⁶ A goal intention typically follows the structure “For the next three weeks, I will try to reach goal X” where X relates to a specific personal goal to which the individual feels committed (Bamberg, 2013). The formation of a goal intention marks the transition into the second stage.

In the second stage, an individual must select the most suitable behavioural strategy to achieve the desired goal. Once the goal intention is established, the individual enters the pre-actional stage and begins to choose an alternative behaviour. This stage involves preparing the person for the change, leading to the behavioural intention. This intention represents a self-commitment to adopt the alternative behaviour. Attitudes such as liking or not liking the alternatives and perceived behavioural control (i.e. perceived ability to shift to the alternative behaviour) are two socio-psychological factors that play a role in the formation of the behavioural intention. The behavioural intention reflects an individual’s self-commitment to the chosen behaviour (Bamberg, 2013; Wang et al. 2023). A person has to weigh the pros and cons of possible alternative behavioural strategies resulting in a behavioural intention reflecting an individual’s self-commitment to one of these behavioural strategies (Bamberg, 2013). The structure of a behavioural intention has the structure of “During the next three weeks, I will perform option Y”, marking the transition from the preactional to the actional stage (Bamberg, 2013).

In the actional stage, the individual implements the necessary actions to make the behavioural change, guided by the implementation intention. Concrete planning abilities and the ability to overcome psychological barriers such as action and coping

⁶ See section 2.3 for a more detailed explanation of the socio-psychological factors included in the stage model.

planning are important to form the implementation intention. This leads to the post-actional stage.

In the post-actional stage, the individual evaluates what he or she has achieved and decides whether he or she wants to maintain the new behaviour. Self-efficacy is crucial to maintain the new behaviour. This is the possibility to maintain the new behaviour and resume the new behaviour after a relapse (Bamberg, 2013).

Table 24 explains the purpose of the various intervention strategies, also referred to as building blocks, used at different stages of the SSBC model. These building blocks are based on the theoretical framework of the CircleUp project (see section 1) and follow the structure of the stage model by Bamberg (2013). The strategies aim to help people change their behaviour. Figures 34 and 35 show the structure of the different building blocks included in each stage.

Table 24: Building blocks following the SSBC model

Building block	Challenge
Stage 1	
I01: Information provision (why current behaviour is problematic)	Purpose: With this building block, we aim to briefly introduce the problem of the current behaviour and raise awareness about the negative impacts. As a result, people in the first stage start to reflect on their current behaviour and the associated consequences.
I02: Videos	Purpose: This building block aims to simplify the content from the previous information provision strategy, making information more understandable. Some people find it more difficult to grasp information by only text. The videos help in making the content more engaging and easier to understand.
I01: Information provision (on what others already do)	Purpose: This building block helps people see that change in behaviour is not only possible but already happening among others, making it socially accepted. It reduces uncertainty, builds social proof, and offers concrete ideas at different societal levels that individuals and communities can adopt or adapt in their own lives. People can be influenced by information showing how other people behave (differently), which is related to the perceiving of social norms.

E02: Experiential learning task	Purpose: This building block is designed to give individuals direct, hands-on experience of the impact of their current behaviour. It aims to be motivating and encouraging and give individuals a feeling of self-efficacy. Furthermore, they will include a reflective component which they have to incorporate in the social story task.
E04: Smart bin analysis	Purpose: This building block provides households with a concrete, data-driven experience of their current behaviour by offering continuous and tailored feedback through a smart bin system. By visually and quantitatively showing how much plastic and food waste is being discarded over time, this tool raises awareness of the consequences of overconsumption.
E05: LCA assessment	Purpose: This building block helps individuals understand the full environmental impact of their behaviours by calculating their footprint and comparing this with others in the country. This tool traces the entire life cycle of plastic products, food waste, electronics and textiles, from raw material extraction, manufacturing and transportation to usage and end-of-life disposal. It provides detailed impact data on global warming potential, resource depletion, water use, and toxicity, increasing awareness of consequences and showing that change is not only necessary but feasible and measurable, thus strengthening motivation and goal clarity.
E03: Quiz	Purpose: Participants can engage in the quiz building block that asks questions related to the information provision strategy. It checks if participants have understood key information and makes the challenges more engaging and fun.
Commitment	Purpose: Participants will be asked to commit themselves to the challenge, which helps in developing a goal intention. The commitment will be asked at the end of stage 1.
Stage 2	
I01: Information provision	Purpose: The aim of this building block is to inform individuals about the alternatives to their current behaviour, including both the advantages and the disadvantages of each behaviour.

I02: Videos	Purpose: This building block aims to simplify the content from the previous information provision strategy, making information more understandable. Some people find it more difficult to grasp information by only text. The videos will help in making the content more engaging and easier to understand.
E01: Interactive learning environments	Purpose: This building block will allow participants to explore “what-if” scenarios regarding their behaviour changes and their environmental impact.
E03: Quiz	Purpose: The aim of this building block is to assess the participants' understanding of specific alternative behaviours to their current behaviour and habits. By asking questions related to practical actions like choosing products with less packaging or bringing reusable containers, the quiz reinforces the provided knowledge.
Stage 3	
I01: Information provision	Purpose: The aim is to provide clear, actionable guidance on how individuals can implement the new behaviour in their daily routines. By offering practical steps, tips, and resources on how to implement their new alternative behaviour, this building block supports action planning.
I02: Videos	Purpose: This building block aims to simplify the content from the previous information provision strategy, making information more understandable. Some people find it more difficult to grasp information by only text. The videos will help in making the content more engaging and easier to understand.
I03: Map	Purpose: The aim is to provide individuals with specific, localised information about where they can take action related to the challenge, such as locations for bulk stores, local or farmers' markets, refill stations, or where to buy durable packaging options. By offering a visual guide to nearby resources, this building block supports action planning by helping individuals identify convenient places to engage in sustainable practices.
E06: Tutorials	Purpose: The aim of this building block is to present the participants with a hands-on, step-by-step tutorial for the alternative behaviour(s).

E03: Quiz	Purpose: Participants can engage in the quiz building block that asks interactive questions about how to plan sustainable actions. It checks if participants have understood key information and makes the challenge more engaging and fun.
T02: External tools	Purpose: The purpose of this building block is to link the participants to external planning tools like shopping lists, apps, recipe generators, and other resources to support individuals in action planning by providing structured and practical assistance.
Stage 4	
E04: Smart bin analysis	Purpose: This building block provides households with a concrete, data-driven experience of their current behaviour by offering continuous and tailored feedback through a smart bin system. By visually and quantitatively showing how much plastic and food waste is being discarded over time, this tool raises awareness of the consequences of overconsumption.
E05: LCA assessment	Purpose: We aim to quantify the environmental impact of household actions, offering a clearer understanding of how behaviour changes, such as reducing packaging and reducing food waste can contribute to broader sustainability goals. By providing tangible data on factors like carbon emissions, resource use, and waste reduction, the LCA tool can boost motivation and improve self-efficacy, helping individuals see that their efforts matter and that meaningful change is within their control.
T01: Habit tracker	Purpose: By tracking progress, we aim to support the formation of sustainable habits. The tool reinforces routine and keeps motivation high. This repetition is key to turning sustainable actions into long-term habits that are embedded in daily life.
S04: Circular story task	Purpose: Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge. They are encouraged to reflect on the barriers, motivations, and possible outcomes of their new behaviour. In addition, they can give tips to other participants. Including pictures and emotions will make it more personal.

Archetypical individual challenge

Figure 35. Model of the building blocks following the individual challenge

Archetypical collective challenge

Figure 36. Model of the building blocks following the collective level

7. The 15 challenges following the building blocks based on the SSBC model ⁷

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AI was used for some parts of the challenges development. It has been used for generating key summaries of information texts. Additionally, AI also supported the development of quiz questions. All AI-generated content was reviewed and edited by the authors of this document to ensure accuracy and correctness.

Table 25: Framework for the individual food challenges

<p>Building block</p>	<p>Challenge 1 individual: Plan purchases to avoid food waste</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Use a shopping list b. Use a meal plan 	<p>Challenge 2 individual: Reuse leftovers to avoid food waste</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Make a leftovers meal b. Store leftovers properly
<p>Questions for the stage analysis</p>	<p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about planning your purchases to avoid food waste?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -I am not sure why I should plan purchases to avoid food waste (stage 1) -I know why it is important to plan purchases to avoid food waste, but I do not know what I can do exactly (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already using meal plans before grocery shopping (stage 4) 	<p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about reusing your leftovers to avoid food waste?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -I am not sure why I should reuse leftovers to avoid food waste (stage 1) -I know why it is important to reuse leftovers to avoid food waste, but I do not know what I can do exactly (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already making leftover meals regularly (stage 4) -I already store my leftovers properly (stage 4)

	-I am already using shopping lists while grocery shopping (stage 4)	
Stage 1		
	<p>Welcome to the food challenge! First, you will read a text about how food waste affects our planet, the economy and how it contributes to social inequality.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>	
I01: Information provision (why current behavior is problematic)	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food waste accounts for 8-10% of global greenhouse gas emissions and is a major contributor to climate change. • Worldwide, approximately 1.3 billion tonnes of food are wasted every year, resulting in huge economic losses. • Food waste is an ethical paradox, as 870 million people are hungry while tonnes of food are wasted. • Leftover management plays an important role in reducing household food waste. • Planning food purchases helps in reducing household food waste. <p>What is the problem?</p> <p>One-third of our world's food production is wasted for various reasons. This means an estimated 1.3 billion tonnes of food are wasted every year. In the European Union alone, around 90 million tonnes of food are wasted every year, creating a financial burden. On an individual level, the average person throws away about</p>	

37 kilograms of food every year with the majority being fruit and vegetables followed by bread and baked goods.

What is food waste?

When talking about food waste, it is important to distinguish between food loss and food waste. Food loss occurs during the supply chain process. With food loss, the food intended for consumption is damaged or destroyed before it reaches retailers or consumers. Food waste refers to discarding edible food, often due to retailer or consumer behaviour.

The impact of food waste

Food waste is a pressing global issue with far-reaching economic, environmental, and social consequences. Around 8-10% of all global greenhouse gas emissions come from uneaten food, including emissions coming from production, transport and landfill decomposition.

Economic impact

Economically, the waste of 1.3 billion tonnes of food per year results in immense losses for producers, retailers and consumers. Food waste also undermines global food security. The more food we waste, the higher the demand, especially for staple crops such as wheat or maize. This demand drives up food prices worldwide, affecting the poorer countries the most.

Environmental impact

Food waste is not just an economic problem – it is also a serious environmental issue. According to the IPCC, 8-10% of global greenhouse gas emissions come from wasted food. The production and transport of uneaten food uses a lot of energy, water, and land and releases more than three gigatonnes of greenhouse gases into

	<p>the atmosphere. Wasting food also means using fertilisers and pesticides unnecessarily, further polluting the environment.</p> <p>Ethical concerns</p> <p>Despite this enormous waste, more than 870 million people worldwide are hungry. From an ethical perspective, this contradiction is hard to ignore, as it highlights serious inequalities in the food distribution. The global food production is enough to feed 12 billion people, which is much more than our current world population, yet millions of people go hungry.</p> <p>Food waste at the household level</p> <p>As highlighted above, food waste has huge implications for our economy, environment, and society. Understanding these impacts can help us make more informed choices and take greater responsibility at various levels. However, research indicates that the majority of food waste in the EU comes from households. Common reasons for food waste at the household level include buying too much, storing food incorrectly, and misunderstanding 'best before' or 'use by' dates. Leftovers are also a major contributor to households' food waste. Whether leftovers are reused depends on different factors such as time, personal values, and kitchen infrastructure.</p>
	<p>You're done reading, good job! Hopefully, you have gained some new information.</p> <p>You're now invited to watch some interesting videos on the topic to further deepen your knowledge.</p>

<p>I02: Videos (why current behavior is problematic)</p>	<p>Videos will be provided by the project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
	<p>We're facing big challenges! Have you ever wondered how people and organisations all over the globe are addressing these challenges? Let's take a closer look.</p>
<p>I01: Information provision (on what others already do)</p>	<p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supermarkets offer “ugly” or imperfect vegetables and fruit at lower prices • People share leftovers through community fridges or food sharing platforms • Retailers provide additional food date labels such as “Best before, often good after” <p>Retailers, supermarkets, and individuals within communities are already taking some initiatives to reduce food waste.</p> <p>Supermarkets and retailers</p> <p>Not every vegetable or fruit looks perfect, and that is a good thing! More and more supermarkets are taking initiatives to ensure that crooked, small, or misshapen food also finds its way into our kitchens, because the taste is exactly the same. These imperfect food products are sold at more favorable prices, benefiting both</p>

	<p>the environment and consumers. In Norway for instance, some food products are labelled with “Best before, often good after”, helping consumers using their senses more carefully, rather than just discarding food when they reach their expiration date. Additionally, supermarkets often reduce the price of food products approaching their expiration date, offering discounts for items nearing their best-before date. These products are typically placed at a specific section in the supermarket. Some supermarkets are also collaborating with local organisations to collect and redistribute surplus food.</p> <p>Food sharing initiatives</p> <p>In many cities, community fridges are installed where surplus but still edible food can be shared with others. The concept is simple: anyone can put something in or take something out without having to exchange or pay for it. This not only strengthens your community but also saves food.</p> <p>There are also (online) food sharing platforms such as Too good to go or OLIO. These platforms collect food products from individuals, local stores or restaurants which would otherwise be discarded and distribute the food to individuals who want to consume them.</p>
	<p>You as an individual have the capacities to change a lot in this world. Let’s get active now and take part in an “experimental learning task”!</p> <p>The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don’t feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!</p>

<p>E02: Experimental learning task</p> <p>S02: Circular story preparation task</p>	<p>Task:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Take a moment to look at the food items from your most recent grocery shopping trip. You can use your paper receipt or check your online shopping app. If you don't have the receipt, postpone the task and remember to keep the receipt next time. 2. Look at the products and identify any items you didn't really need to buy. 3. Reflect on why you bought these unnecessary items. Was it due to impulse buying, attractive discounts, or shopping while hungry? 4. What did you do with the unnecessary food items you purchased? Did you eat them? Or did you throw them away? 4. Write down your reflections or create a drawing to better understand your shopping behaviour. 5. If you still have them, take also a picture of the food items you bought but didn't really need. Upload the picture here. Save the pictures and your 	<p>Task:</p> <p>For the following task, you have two different options to choose from. Pick the one that seems the most interesting for you or challenge yourself and try both.</p> <p>Option 1</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. When preparing your next meal (whether it is breakfast, lunch, or dinner), take a picture of any edible food you have thrown away during and after finishing your meal. 2. Reflect and write a short note by using some of the following questions. Remember, you don't have to answer all the questions one by one. We want to give you some starting points to help guide your reflection. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What did you cook, and was any edible food wasted? • How did you deal with leftovers? • How did you feel about throwing away the food? • Why did you end up with leftovers? Did you cook too much? Were you not as hungry as you
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	<p>reflections or drawings for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>	<p>thought? Do you dislike eating leftovers? Did you prepare your meal? Are there different eating preferences among family members?</p> <p>3. Save the pictures and your reflections for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p> <p>Option 2</p> <p>1. Browse through your fridge, freezer, and cupboards and look for any food that has expired and is no longer edible. Use your senses to make this decision: look, smell, taste.</p> <p>2. Reflect and write a short note, make a drawing, or make a video on why the food has been ending up being bad. Take a picture of the food.</p> <p>3. Save the pictures and your reflections for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>
	<p>Thank you for participating in this task. We hope that you have learned much about your own behaviour. It's quickly happening that you lose track on the consequences of your own behaviour. How much food does your household actually waste? Let's measure this with one of our smart bins.</p>	

E04: Smart bin analysis	The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their food waste.
	What is the impact of your consumer choices? Let's take a look at the lifecycle of some of your daily products.
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
	Congratulations on your progress so far. We are confident that you have gained lots of knowledge! Would you like to test this knowledge? Let's move on to a short quiz!
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What percentage of global greenhouse gas emissions come from food waste?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) 2-4% b) 5-8% c) 8-10% <p>Question 2.</p> <p>How many tons of food are wasted globally each year?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) 500 million tons b) 1 billion tons c) 1.3 billion tons

Question 3.

Which of the following is *not* a major cause of food waste in households?

- a) Insufficient grocery shopping
- b) Improper food storage
- c) Improper packaging of food in supermarkets**
- d) Poor meal planning

Question 4.

Which of the following is one of the solutions to reduce food waste?

- a) Throw away leftovers
- b) Freeze leftovers**
- c) Buy food in larger quantities
- d) Buy more food products in discount

Question 5.

How much food waste occurs approximately due to confusion about expiration dates?

- a) 10%
- b) 15%
- c) 20%**

Question 6.

What is a practical tip to reduce food waste at home?

- a) Only buy food in bulk.

b) Use a shopping list to avoid impulse purchases and waste.

c) Freeze everything immediately after purchasing.

Question 7.

How does proper food storage contribute to reducing food waste?

a) It helps extend the shelf life of food and reduces spoilage.

b) It reduces the amount of food needed in a household.

c) It increases food waste by encouraging larger portion sizes.

Question 8.

What is one way to handle leftovers at home?

a) Store leftovers for a few days and throw away any uneaten food.

b) Reuse leftovers creatively by turning them into new dishes, such as soups or salads.

c) Only store leftovers if they are not too much.

Question 9.

What is one key benefit of using meal kits?

a) They help reduce packaging waste.

b) They reduce food waste by providing pre-portioned ingredients.

c) They increase food waste by offering excess ingredients.

Question 10.

What is one method of turning leftovers into new meals?

	<p>a) Discard them after reheating.</p> <p>b) Combine leftover vegetables, rice, and beans into a soup or stew.</p> <p>c) Feed the leftovers to your pets.</p>	
Commitment to the challenge:	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to plan purchases to avoid food waste:</p> <p>a. yes</p> <p>b. no</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to reuse leftovers to avoid food waste:</p> <p>a. yes</p> <p>b. no</p>
Stage 2		
	<p>What can you do to make a difference? Let's have a look at different alternatives you have for addressing food waste.</p>	
I01: Information provision (alternative behaviours, advantages and disadvantages)	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning meals with similar ingredients increases efficiency and reduces costs. • Using a shopping list helps avoid impulse purchases, reduces waste, and saves money, but requires some discipline and extra planning. • Portion size adjustments help reduce waste 	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using leftover such as processing them into new meals or freezing them, will reduce waste, though it can require some extra time and a bit of creativity in the beginning. • Good storage techniques (e.g. refrigeration, correct packaging) extend the shelf life of food and prevent spoilage.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Best before" dates indicate quality, not safety. Sensory testing often confirms edibility beyond the date. • Using the FIFO (First In, First Out) method and proper labelling can help in using older foods first. <p>Food waste is a major problem with environmental, economic, and social impacts. The good news is that there are many ways to reduce food waste at home, from shopping and storage practices to smart use of leftovers. In this part, we will tell you a bit more about effective strategies on how to plan your food purchases.</p> <p>Shopping list</p> <p>A shopping list is simply a list of items you need and use while shopping. Using a shopping list helps prevent impulse purchases and ensures that you only buy the products you need. This does not only reduce food waste but also saves you money. Using shopping lists requires some planning and a bit of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freezing leftovers is a very easy and effective technique if you don't want to eat the same meal two days in a row. <p>Food waste is a major problem with environmental, economic, and social impacts. The good news is that there are many ways to reduce food waste at home, from shopping and storage practices to smart use of leftovers. In this part, we will tell you a bit more about effective strategies on how to use your leftovers.</p> <p>Some people find eating leftovers less tasty or appetizing. If you are one of them, consider exploring the other food challenge to learn how to portion your meals better and minimize leftovers.</p> <p>Reusing leftovers</p> <p>Leftovers can be seen as any remaining food that you have not eaten by the end of your meal. Instead of throwing away your leftovers, you can turn them into new meals. Leftovers can be turned into new dishes such as soups, salads, or stir-fries. Using your leftovers into new meals requires some creativity and new</p>
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	<p>discipline, especially in the beginning. But since shopping lists are a great tool for keeping both your shopping and expenses under control, they are worth using.</p> <p>Meal plan</p> <p>Meal planning means organizing and preparing meals in advance. This reduces waste, saves time, and reduces the stress of daily meal choices families often have. However, it may require some time and effort in the beginning and can limit some spontaneity.</p> <p>Start by checking the ingredients you already have at home. This will help you create a shopping list based on what you already have and prevents impulse and over buying. Taking a photo of the fridge, freezer or cupboards before grocery shopping is super-efficient when you have little time. Choose frequently used ingredients that can be used for several meals. You can also look for</p>	<p>cooking skills, especially in the beginning. Fortunately, there are already many leftover recipes available on the internet (for free!). To give you some ideas: Leftover roasted vegetables, beans and rice can be turned into soups or stews; grilled meats and cooked vegetables can become salads; and stir-fries or casseroles can be made with a mix of leftover grains and proteins. Overripe fruit can be made into smoothies, muffins or banana bread, while vegetable peels and bones can be saved for broths.</p> <p>Storing leftovers</p> <p>Are you concerned about the safety of eating leftovers? Proper storage is crucial for extending the shelf life of food in general, but also of leftovers. Refrigerating food and using the correct packaging prevents spoilage and waste, though it requires some knowledge and available storage space. Fresh tomatoes for instance, should not be stored in the fridge to preserve their flavour, while potatoes should be kept in a cool, dark place to avoid sprouting. Meat and cheese last longer when they are stored in airtight containers or beeswax wraps. But</p>
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	<p>recipes that use often thrown away food items such as overripe bananas or wilted vegetables.</p> <p>Adjusting portion sizes</p> <p>Adjusting portion sizes can also help in avoiding leftovers. Using portion size guides or apps can help you with this. Did you know there are tools available to measure perfect portions of pasta and rice?</p> <p>Food date labels</p> <p>Before you go grocery shopping, checking your cupboards for items that are about to expire can help you to prioritise the food you have. Make sure you understand the different food date labels. The 'use by' date indicates safety, especially for perishable items such as minced meat or fresh fish and must be followed more strictly. In contrast, the 'best before' date refers to quality and should be seen as a guideline, not safety - many foods remain safe and edible after this date if stored properly.</p> <p>Look, smell and taste</p> <p>Use the "look, smell, feel, and taste" method to</p>	<p>again, on the internet you will find a lot of information on how to store leftover food in the fridge and freezer.</p> <p>Don't you like to eat the same meal two days in a row? Freezing leftovers is an easy solution for this and will extend the life of your leftovers. You can also freeze food items nearing expiration date. Keep in mind that this requires some extra freezer space.</p> <p>To help you keep an overview of your freezer, foods should be labelled with date and contents, portioned into meal-sized portions and stored properly. Techniques such as blanching or steaming vegetables before freezing or using ice cube trays for herbs in oil offer both preservation and convenience. Vacuum or airtight packaging also prevent freezer burn and helps to keep the freshness of the food.</p> <p>Despite good intentions, leftovers often get forgotten in an unorganized and messy fridge. To avoid this, try to organize your fridge. You could for instance keep a (part of a) specific shelf or section in your fridge or freezer for all your stored leftovers.</p>
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	<p>check the freshness of the food. If food looks normal, smells good, and tastes normal after a small test, it is usually safe to eat. Keep in mind; due to microbial safety risks, this method should not be used for products with a 'use by' date.</p> <p>FIFO method</p> <p>Additionally, the FIFO "First in, First out" method ensures that older products are used before newer ones. This means you have to place the oldest items at the front of your fridge or cupboard, and adding newer food products behind them.</p> <p>To sum up</p> <p>Better planning, proper storage and creative use of leftovers are key to reducing food waste and promoting sustainability at home. Implementing these strategies and turning them into a habit will take some extra time, knowledge, and creativity. But it is worth its effort and by doing so, you will be helping reduce food waste, which will benefit both the environment and your wallet.</p>	<p>To sum up</p> <p>Creative use of leftovers is key to reducing food waste and promoting sustainability at home. Implementing these strategies and turning them into a habit might take some extra time, knowledge, and creativity in the beginning. But it is worth its effort and by doing so, you will be helping reduce food waste, which will benefit both the environment and your wallet.</p>
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	Want to learn more about behavioural alternatives? Let's watch some short and fun videos.	
I02: Videos (alternative behaviours, advantages and disadvantages)	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
E01: Interactive learning environments	Link the participants to ILE based on system model.	
	Feels like you are expert now, right? Let's test your knowledge with a short test.	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one advantage of using a shopping list?</p> <p>a) It allows for spontaneous meal choices</p> <p>b) It reduces waste and saves money</p> <p>c) It encourages bulk buying</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is another key benefit of creating a shopping</p>	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What could be a barrier of transforming leftovers into new dishes?</p> <p>a) It requires creativity and some cooking skills</p> <p>b) It makes meals less varied</p> <p>c) It leads to more food waste</p>

<p>list?</p> <p>a) It increases impulse buying</p> <p>b) It ensures that only necessary items are purchased</p> <p>c) It encourages purchasing in bulk</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>Why should you take a photo of your fridge before shopping?</p> <p>a) To compare prices in the store</p> <p>b) To check which foods you have, and which food needs to be replaced</p> <p>c) To see which brands you have</p> <p>Question 4.</p> <p>What does the “best before” date indicate?</p> <p>a) The date at which food becomes unsafe to eat</p> <p>b) The manufacturer’s quality guarantee</p> <p>c) The latest date for purchasing the product</p> <p>Question 5.</p> <p>Why is portion control important?</p> <p>a) It helps reduce food waste</p>	<p>Question 2.</p> <p>How does proper food storage help reduce waste?</p> <p>a) It prevents spoilage and extends shelf-life</p> <p>b) It eliminates the need to check expiration dates</p> <p>c) It allows all foods to be stored at the same temperature</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>Why might freezing leftovers not always be an ideal solution?</p> <p>a) It requires adequate freezer space and proper labelling</p> <p>b) It makes food spoil faster</p> <p>c) It increases cooking time</p> <p>Question 4:</p> <p>Which of the following is an example of creatively reusing leftovers?</p> <p>a) Throwing overripe fruit in the compost</p> <p>b) Turning leftover rice and vegetables into a stir-fry</p> <p>c) Storing uncooked vegetables in the fridge</p>
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	<p>b) It makes meals more expensive</p> <p>c) It encourages overcooking</p>	<p>Question 5:</p> <p>What is one challenge of proper food storage at home?</p> <p>a) It requires you to eat more food</p> <p>b) It demands some extra storage space</p> <p>c) It eliminates the need for grocery shopping</p>
Commitment to the challenge	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to:</p> <p>a. Use a shopping list to avoid food waste</p> <p>b. Use a meal plan to avoid food waste</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to:</p> <p>a. Make leftover meals to avoid food waste</p> <p>b. Store my leftovers properly</p>
Stage 3		
	<p>You feel like you're still missing hands-on advice? How to actually turn these solutions into reality. Learn more about practical applications through the next block.</p> <p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>	
I01: Information provision (helping with planning)	Key takeaways:	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using leftovers creatively in new dishes like soups or salads can reduce waste.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a detailed shopping list based on what you already have at home to avoid buying too much. • Plan your meals for the week and use a shopping list to avoid impulse buying and food waste • Limit impulse buying and encourage sustainable food choices. • Mindful consumption means serving smaller portions and understanding food date labels to avoid unnecessary waste. • Practical skills, such as food preservation techniques, can reduce waste in the kitchen. <p>For this challenge, you have decided you want to use a shopping list and/or plan your meals in advance. We will help you plan your new behaviour.</p> <p>Before the shopping</p> <p>A smart grocery shopping routine starts before</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning leftovers in your meal plan helps reduce food waste and saves time • Optimal storage techniques can extend the shelf life of perishable foods and reduce spoilage, while freezing methods help preserve leftovers. • Proper food storage extends shelf life and ensures freshness. • Smart organisation in the kitchen supports efficient food use and reduces spoilage. <p>For this challenge, you have decided you want to use your leftovers. We will help you plan your new behaviour.</p> <p>Managing your leftovers</p> <p>Make sure you store your leftovers as soon as possible. Keep them in the fridge if you plan to eat them within the next few days. If you don't like to eat the same meal twice, you can put your leftovers in the freezer to save them for later. Try to create a routine that suits your</p>
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	<p>entering the grocery store. Take stock by checking what is already in your fridge, freezer, and cupboards to plan your meals for the upcoming week. Keep a list of the items you have at home, either on a simple piece of paper or with an app. Use this inventory to create your shopping list and only buy the food you need. If you have little time, you can simply take a photo of your fridge, freezer, or cupboards before leaving your house. Organising your list by category—such as fresh produce, dairy, or dry goods—will save you time in the store and avoids impulse buying. With writing a shopping list while taking inventory, you will avoid buying the same food products again. Organize your food by expiration date and use the older food items first. Plan your meals using similar ingredients that can be used across different meals. Do not forget to plan simple meals planned for busier days. You can also include (frozen) leftovers into your meal plan—such as using old bread for croutons or using cooked vegetables into soups.</p>	<p>household needs. This will reduce some stress around planning, shopping, and cooking at the same time.</p> <p>Need inspiration?</p> <p>If you are lacking inspiration, you can find numerous leftover recipes online. Some dishes are easier than others to make with leftovers, such as salads, pasta dishes, and one-pan recipes. Try to come up with different combinations like pizza, fried rice, salad, tacos, or quiche.</p> <p>Take leftovers for lunch the next day at work to avoid buying food at the cafeteria or eating bread all the time. You might even inspire your colleagues to do the same!</p> <p>You can also prepare extra dinners to save time on meal prepping for the rest of the week. By cooking larger portions at once, you can freeze them and just reheat them on busy days.</p> <p>Keep track of your leftovers</p> <p>When you plan to freeze your leftovers, it is a good idea to freeze them in smaller portions (depending on your household size). Use a marker or sticker to label what is</p>
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<p>During the shopping</p> <p>During your shopping trip itself, sticking to your shopping list is key. Many grocery stores offer promising and attractive discounts. Try to only buy these products if you really need them. Checking expiration dates in the store and choosing products at varying stages of ripeness can help ensure that the products remain usable throughout the whole week.</p> <p>CircleUp tip: Many stores have a discount section for products nearing their expiration date. If you plan to eat the food the same day, take advantage of these deals. Instead of using it the same day, you can also freeze it straight away to extend its shelf-life.</p> <p>Furthermore, choosing seasonal and local food products not only supports sustainability but often results in fresher, longer-lasting food. Opting for longer-lasting alternatives, like cabbage instead of lettuce, can further reduce spoilage.</p>	<p>in your container. Don't forget to add the date.</p> <p>Following the "first in, first out" method to make sure that you eat the older food first and that food is eaten and not hidden or forgotten in the back of the fridge or freezer.</p> <p>Safety</p> <p>Regularly check the temperature of your fridge and freezer to make sure the food is stored safely. You can also look at websites to find tips and tricks on how to freeze and defrost food safely. Be extra careful with uncooked meat and fish.</p>
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	<p>After the shopping</p> <p>At home, the way food is stored is just as important. If available, check the storage instructions on the food package itself. Store the right food in the fridge or freezer so that it lasts longer. If you want to freeze some of your food, remember to divide larger portions of food into smaller portions so that you only defrost the portions you need. Don't forget to check the temperature of your fridge and freezer regularly. Furthermore, a lot of information is available on the internet about what food products can and cannot be stored in your fridge, how to freeze products and for how long, how to defrost them afterwards and many more tips. Remember to store your leftovers visible and in the front of your fridge so they don't get lost.</p>	
<p>I02: Videos (helping with planning)</p>	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p>	

	<p>UK: ...</p> <p>Latvia: ...</p>	
	<p>Great, now you already know a lot about how to find solutions to environmental challenges. But how can you turn this into reality? Where can you find helpful resources in your hometown? Let's take a look at this map.</p>	
I03: Map	<p>Participants and project partners will locate places on the map.</p>	
	<p>Let's get active and participate in a hands-on tutorial!</p>	
E06: Tutorials	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>In this tutorial, we will show you how you can create a shopping list and plan your meals to avoid food waste. You can write your shopping list on a piece of paper, on your notes on your phone, or use a special app.</p> <p>Step 1: Preparation before shopping</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check your fridge, freezer, and cupboards. • Make a note of what food needs to be used first (near expiration date). Make sure you understand the food date labels. 	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>In this tutorial, we will show you how you can create your leftovers into meals and store them properly afterwards.</p> <p>Step 1: Take stock</p> <p>Open your fridge, freezer, and cupboards.</p> <p>Make a note of the items you have stored.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooked leftovers (e.g. rice, pasta, vegetables, meat) • Vegetables or fruit

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think ahead: What ingredients can be reused for several meals? • Decide if you want to plan your meals for the next few days or the whole week • Use ingredients you already have in your recipes. • Plan easy meals for busy days. • Include leftovers in your meal plan. Plan at least one "leftovers meal" a week. <p>➔ Make a shopping list</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write down any missing items on your list. • Organise your items by categories (e.g. fruit & vegetables, dairy, dry groceries) to save time in the shop. Many shops have integrated apps that offer this functionality. • If you are planning to shop in different stores, you can also decide to group the items by the store. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opened sauces, broths, cheese, etc. • Food with an expiration date <p>Step 2: Plan your meal creatively</p> <p>Ask yourself:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do I have a base? <p>Cooked rice/pasta/potatoes are perfect for stir-fries or oven dishes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do I have any vegetables? <p>Shriveled vegetables are great for soups, curries or stews</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do I have protein? <p>Boiled egg, leftover meat, tofu or leftover cheese are good to add to the pan or casserole</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do I have a sauce/thickening? <p>Tomato sauce, cream, stock, an egg or cheese can hold everything together</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't forget to write down the quantities next to each item. <p>CircleUp tip: Take a picture of your fridge, freezer, and cupboards before your shopping trip when you are in a hurry.</p> <p>Step 2: Grocery shopping</p> <p>The most important: Stick to your shopping list!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buy only what is on your shopping list to avoid impulse buys. • Use discounts wisely and buy them only if they fit into your meal plan. • Check expiration dates • Choose fresh produce wisely - buy fruit and vegetables at different stages of ripeness to spread the use in your meal plan • Choose local and seasonal produces since these are often more sustainable and fresher. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which spices go well? <p>If you prefer Asian: soy sauce, ginger, garlic</p> <p>If you prefer Mediterranean: oregano, olive oil, lemon</p> <p>Collect and try different leftover recipes. You can find online leftover apps to find more recipes and inspiration. You will notice that you automatically become more creative with leftovers the more often you prepare them.</p> <p>Step 3: Store leftovers correctly</p> <p>Seal well: Use (glass) containers, tins or beeswax cloths.</p> <p>Labelling: Write the date and contents on the container.</p> <p>Optimise storage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fridge: max. 3-4 days for cooked food • Freezer: up to 3 months (e.g. bread, cooked rice, vegetables) • Place older food in front of the fridge so that you won't forget it.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If possible, choose alternatives for perishable foods (e.g. cabbage lasts longer than lettuce). <p>Step 3. Store your food properly after shopping</p> <p>Organise your fridge and cupboards using the "first in, first out" rule: put older items in the front and newer items in the back.</p> <p>Store food properly. Try to reduce plastic and use (glass) containers, tins or beeswax cloths instead.</p> <p>Divide food into smaller portions before freezing</p> <p>Consistency is key! By repeating these steps every time you shop, you will not only reduce waste, but also make grocery shopping a smoother, less stressful routine. Over time, this can even lead into a habit!</p> <p>Step 4. Take a picture of your shopping list and meal plan and keep it for the circular story</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start creating a shopping list and a</p>	<p>Step 4: Use leftovers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan 1-2 'leftover days' per week. • Freeze small leftovers - including stock, tomato puree or herbs in ice cube molds. • Keep leftovers (vegetables, herbs, bones) to make stock. • You can also choose to make extra portions while cooking to have leftovers. This saves you time and gives you ready-to-eat meals on a busy day. • Instead of preparing a meal to eat at home, try making a lunch with your leftovers that you can bring to work the next day. This might inspire some of your colleagues to do the same. <p>Step 5. Take a picture of your leftover meal(s) and keep it for the circular story</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to use and store your leftovers. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We</p>
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	<p>meal plan. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>	<p>encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>
<p>After finishing this tutorial, you contributed to circularity in a meaningful way, that's amazing! Would you like to test your knowledge in a final quiz? Click here.</p>		
<p>E03: Quiz</p>	<p>Question 1. Why is it important to take inventory before shopping? a) To check which food products need to be used soon b) To buy more food than necessary just in case c) To spend extra money on new ingredients</p> <p>Question 2. What is an effective way to reduce impulse purchases when grocery shopping? a) Buying in bulk, even if not needed b) Using a shopping list and planning meals in</p>	<p>Question 1. Why is it important to organise food by expiration dates? a) To ensure older items are used first and avoid spoilage b) To make the fridge look neat c) Because food expires faster when disorganised</p> <p>Question 2. What is a good way to use up overripe fruit? a) Blending it into smoothies or using it in baking</p>

<p>advance</p> <p>c) Choosing discounted items, regardless of necessity</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>Which of the following is a correct food storage practice?</p> <p>a) Keeping potatoes and onions together to save space</p> <p>b) Storing leafy greens in airtight containers to prolong freshness</p> <p>c) Keeping tomatoes in the fridge for longer shelf life</p> <p>Question 4.</p> <p>How can you effectively manage frozen food?</p> <p>a) Label and date frozen food to track storage times</p> <p>b) Freeze all leftovers without checking portion sizes</p> <p>c) Store frozen food without considering temperature settings</p>	<p>b) Throwing it away to avoid eating soft fruit</p> <p>c) Keeping it in the fridge indefinitely</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>How can you use leftover pasta sauce?</p> <p>a) Use it into a new dish with other vegetables</p> <p>b) You cannot reheat it for a second time so throw it away</p> <p>c) Freeze it for your next spaghetti meal</p> <p>d) Use the sauce as a dip for chips or roasted vegetables</p> <p>Question 4.</p> <p>Why would you make extra portions to save as leftovers when preparing and making dinner?</p> <p>a) This is generally bad advice that no one should follow</p> <p>b) This will save you time when you have a busy day</p> <p>c) This will save you time when meal planning</p> <p>d) This is not a good idea when you don't like using leftovers</p>
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Question 5.

What is the best way to organize a shopping list?

a) Write down items randomly as they come to mind

b) Organize items by category (fruits & vegetables, dairy, dry goods, etc.)

c) Only write down a few items and buy the rest spontaneously

Question 6.

How can you reduce food waste when meal planning?

a) Plan meals using ingredients you already have and incorporate leftovers

b) Only cook large meals and throw away the leftovers

c) Buy extra ingredients for future meals without checking your inventory

Question 7.

What is a good strategy when buying fresh produce?

	<p>a) Buy all fruits and vegetables at the same ripeness level</p> <p>b) Choose local and seasonal produce and buy them at different ripeness levels</p> <p>c) Buy only exotic fruits to try something new every week</p>	
<p>We have collected some useful material for you in the following step.</p>		
<p>T02: External tools</p>	<p>Shopping lists</p> <p>Using shopping lists helps you to only buy what you need and can contribute to the reduction of food waste. As you have learned, you can write a shopping list on a piece of paper or use the notes app on your phone. But there are also different apps available that help you create your own shopping lists. Some of these apps allow you to share your shopping list with others within your household and with certain apps you can create shopping lists based on recipes. Some supermarket apps come with integrated shopping lists, making it easier to navigate through their stores. Many of these apps also come with automatic categorization of food products. A lot of these apps have free versions, but some features require subscription costs.</p> <p>Recipes for leftovers</p> <p>There is already a lot of information and inspiration out there on the internet, also on how to use leftovers creatively. A lot of websites provide recipes on how to utilize leftovers into a meal. Here are some of them:</p> <p><i>Input from partners:</i></p> <p>Norway: Matvett.no</p>	

	<p>Germany: Latvia: UK: www.lovefoodhatewaste.com</p> <p>Are there some stickers available from the partners to put on the fridge/freezer showing which products can and cannot be in the fridge or freezer?</p> <p>Storing food</p> <p>Furthermore, there exist different websites on how to store food products:</p> <p><i>Input from partners:</i></p> <p>Norway: Naturvernforbundet.no: Slik kaster du mindre mat</p> <p>Germany: Latvia: UK:</p> <p>Measurement tools</p> <p>There are also useful tools available to help you measure the right amount of food. Such as how much spaghetti, rice, or pasta one person usually eats. Using this tool will help you avoid cooking too much food and reduce waste.</p>
Stage 4	
E04: Smart bin analysis	The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their food waste and on the changes in food waste since the start of the challenge.

E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
T01: Habit tracker	<p>Will be provided if available and useful.</p> <p><i>... Input from the partners</i></p> <p><i>Loop Habit via Playstore, Aurora Store or FDroid Store (Android only), open source</i></p>
	<p>Wow, you nailed it! You finished an entire challenge of the CircleUp project! What did you learn? What was interesting or challenging? Reflect on your experiences in the Circular story task and inspire others.</p>
S04: Circular story task	<p>Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge. They are encouraged to reflect on the barriers, motivations, and possible outcomes of their new behaviour. In addition, they can give tips to other participants.</p>
Sources used for this challenge ⁸ :	<p>European Commission. (2023, October). <i>Food waste: The EU is taking action to reduce food waste and promote sustainable food systems</i> [Factsheet]. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/attachment/876207/Factsheet_Food%20Waste_EN.pdf</p> <p>Statista. (2024). <i>Lebensmittelverschwendung – Statistiken und Daten</i> [Food waste – Statistics and data]. https://de.statista.com/statistik/studie/id/78401/dokument/food-waste/</p>

⁸ We have decided to keep the reference list for the deliverable separate (see section 8. References) from the references used for the development of the challenges. This makes it easier for the reader to distinguish which sources have been used for the challenges and which were used for the rest of the document.

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Table 26: Framework for the community food challenges

<p>Building block</p>	<p>Challenge 1 community: Give away leftovers</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <p>a. Organize a leftover dinner</p>	<p>Challenge 2 community: Share your leftover management skills with others</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <p>a. Talk with others on how to store leftovers properly b. Talk with others on how to read food labels (e.g., best before or use-by date)</p>
<p>Questions for the stage analysis</p>	<p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about doing things together to avoid food waste?</p> <p>-I am not sure why I should share/give away leftovers (stage 1)</p> <p>-I know why it is important to share/give away leftovers but I do not know what to do (stage 2)</p> <p>-I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3)</p> <p>-I am already organizing leftover dinners with others (stage 4)</p>	<p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about doing things together to avoid food waste?</p> <p>-I am not sure why I should share my leftover management skills with others to avoid food waste (stage 1)</p> <p>-I know why it is important to share my leftover management skills with others to avoid food waste but I do not know what to do (stage 2)</p> <p>-I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3)</p>

		<p>-I am already talking with other people on how to store leftovers properly (stage 4)</p> <p>-I am already talking with other people on how to read food labels (stage 4)</p>
Stage 1		
	<p>Welcome to the community food waste challenge! Are you motivated to address food waste-related challenges together with others in your community? Then you're in the right place! Let's get started with a short introduction.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>	
I01: Information provision (why current behavior is problematic)	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food waste accounts for 8-10% of global greenhouse gas emissions and is a major contributor to climate change. • Worldwide, approximately 1.3 billion tonnes of food are wasted every year, resulting in huge economic losses. • Food waste is an ethical paradox, as 870 million people are hungry while tonnes of food are wasted. • Leftover management plays an important role in reducing household food waste. • Planning food purchases helps in reducing household food waste. 	

What is the problem?

One-third of our world's food production is wasted for various reasons. This means an estimated 1.3 billion tonnes of food are wasted every year. In the European Union alone, around 90 million tonnes of food are wasted every year, creating a financial burden. On an individual level, the average person throws away about 37 kilograms of food every year with the majority being vegetables, fruit, bread and baked goods.

What is food waste?

When talking about food waste, it is important to distinguish between different terms. Food loss occurs during the supply chain process. With food loss, the food intended for consumption is damaged or destroyed before it reaches retailers or consumers. Food waste refers to discarding edible food, often due to retailer or consumer behaviour.

The impact of food waste

Food waste is a pressing global issue with far-reaching economic, environmental, and social consequences. Around 8-10% of all global greenhouse gas emissions come from uneaten food, including emissions coming from production, transport and landfill decomposition.

Economic impact

Economically, the waste of 1.3 billion tonnes of food per year results in immense losses for producers, retailers and consumers. Food waste also undermines global food security. The more food we waste, the higher the demand, especially for staple crops such as wheat or maize. This demand drives up food prices worldwide, affecting the poorer countries the most.

Environmental impact

Food waste is not just an economic problem – it is also a serious environmental issue. According to the IPCC, 8-10% of global greenhouse gas emissions come from wasted food. The production and transport of uneaten food uses a lot of energy, water, and land and releases more than three gigatonnes of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Wasting food also means using fertilisers and pesticides unnecessarily, further polluting the environment.

Ethical concerns

Despite this enormous waste, more than 870 million people worldwide are hungry. From an ethical perspective, this contradiction is hard to ignore, as it highlights serious inequalities in the food distribution. The global food production is enough to feed 12 billion people, which is much more than our current world population, yet millions of people go hungry.

Food waste at the household level

As highlighted above, food waste has huge implications for our economy, environment, and society.

Understanding these impacts can help us make more informed choices and take greater responsibility at various levels. However, research indicates that the majority of food waste in the EU comes from households. Common reasons for food waste at the household level include buying too much, storing food incorrectly, and misunderstanding 'best before' or 'use by' dates. Leftovers are also a major contributor to households' food waste. Whether leftovers are reused depends on different factors such as time, personal values, and kitchen infrastructure.

	<p>You're done reading, good job! Hopefully, you have gained a lot of new information.</p> <p>You're now invited to watch some interesting videos on the topic to further deepen your knowledge.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
	<p>As you have seen, food waste is a pressing problem. What has already been done to address this issue? This is what you'll find out through reading the next text.</p>
I01: Information provision (on what others already do)	<p>Key Takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supermarkets offer “ugly” or imperfect vegetables and fruit at lower prices • People share leftovers through community fridges or food sharing platforms • Retailers provide additional food date labels such as “Best before, often good after” <p>Retailers, supermarkets, and individuals within communities are already taking some initiatives to reduce food waste.</p>

	<p>Supermarkets and retailers</p> <p>Not every vegetable or fruit looks perfect, and that is a good thing! More and more supermarkets are taking initiatives to ensure that crooked, small, or misshapen food also finds its way into our kitchens, because the taste is exactly the same. These imperfect food products are sold at more favorable prices, benefiting both the environment and consumers. In Norway for instance, some food products are labelled with “Best before, often good after”, helping consumers using their senses more carefully, rather than just discarding food when they reach their expiration date. Additionally, supermarkets often reduce the price of food products approaching their expiration date, offering discounts for items nearing their best-before date. These products are typically placed at a specific section in the supermarket. Some supermarkets are also collaborating with local organisations to collect and redistribute surplus food.</p> <p>Food sharing initiatives</p> <p>In many cities, community fridges are installed where surplus but still edible food can be shared with others. The concept is simple: anyone can put something in or take something out without having to exchange or pay for it. This not only strengthens your community but also saves food.</p> <p>There are also (online) food sharing platforms such as Too good to go or OLIO. These platforms collect food products from individuals, local stores or restaurants which would otherwise be discarded and distribute the food to individuals who want to consume them.</p>
	<p>Good job with reading the texts! Now, after gaining all this knowledge, let’s get active with an “experimental learning task”.</p>

	<p>The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don't feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!</p> <p>In the previous sections, you have seen that food waste is a global problem. Even if you have become aware of the problem, that does not mean that others have.</p>	
<p>E02: Experimental learning task</p> <p>S02: Circular story preparation task</p>	<p>Task:</p> <p>Start a discussion with others on reusing leftovers</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify some people (an individual or a group of people) you would like to discuss the topic of reusing leftovers with. This could be family members outside your household, friends, colleagues, or neighbours. 2. If you need more information on this topic, we advise you to go through the first challenge on food waste for additional insights. 	<p>Task:</p> <p>Start a discussion with others on how to storage food properly</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify some people (individual or a group of people) you would like to discuss the topic of storing food with. This could be family members outside your household, friends, colleagues, or neighbours. 2. If you need more information on this topic, we advise you to go through the XXX challenge on food waste for additional insights. 3. Think about topics you want to discuss.

	<p>3. Think about topics you want to discuss.</p> <p>Some tips to make the discussion more engaging and get started:</p> <p>Share something you learned recently about reusing leftovers.</p> <p>Share your own experiences with reusing leftovers.</p> <p>Discuss advantages/disadvantages of reusing leftovers</p> <p>Exchange tips and recipes for reusing leftovers</p> <p>4. Have a short reflection afterwards and write them down. Remember that you also make a video or make a drawing to express your reflections.</p> <p>How did it go? What surprised you in the discussion?</p> <p>Did anyone experience resistance or discomfort by the topic?</p> <p>5. Save your reflections for the circular story and ongoing discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>	<p>Some tips to make the discussion more engaging and get started:</p> <p>Share something you learned recently about food storage.</p> <p>Share your own experience with storing food.</p> <p>Discuss advantages/disadvantages of storing food.</p> <p>Exchange tips for storing food.</p> <p>4. Have a short reflection afterwards and write them down. Remember that you also make a video or make a drawing to express your reflections.</p> <p>How did it go? What surprised you in the discussion? Did anyone experience resistance or discomfort by the topic?</p> <p>5. Save reflections for the circular story and ongoing discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>
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	Are you interested in your own waste footprint? Let's measure your households' waste with one of our smart bins.
E04: Smart bin analysis	The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their food waste.
	What are the environmental consequences of each of our actions? Where does our food waste actually come from and where does it go? These are the questions that can be answered with a so-called "life-cycle assessment". Let's dive into this further.
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
	<p>Are you ready to take a quiz? Let's go and test your knowledge.</p> <p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>How many tons of food are wasted globally each year?</p> <p>a) 500 million tons</p> <p>b) 1 billion tons</p> <p>c) 1.3 billion tons</p>

Question 2.

What is one of the main causes of food waste in households?

- a) Too much cooking oil
- b) Improper food storage**
- c) Lack of grocery stores
- d) Too many vegan options

Question 3.

Which of the following is a suggested solution to reduce food waste?

- a) Throw away leftovers
- b) Freeze leftovers**
- c) Buy food in larger quantities

Question 4.

How much food waste occurs due to confusion about expiration dates?

- a) 10%
- b) 15%
- c) 20%**

Question 5.

What is one major environmental consequence of food waste?

a) Increased energy production.

b) A rise in greenhouse gas emissions from food production, transportation, and decomposition.

c) Reduced water usage in food production.

Question 6.

How much global food waste contributes to greenhouse gas emissions?

a) 5-7%.

b) 8-10%.

c) 15-20%.

Question 7.

What is one ethical issue caused by food waste?

a) Lower food prices globally.

b) Unequal food distribution, while 870 million people suffer from hunger.

c) Reduced food variety for consumers.

Question 8.

Which is a key cause of food waste in households?

a) Overbuying food that is not consumed in time.

b) Storing food in eco-friendly packaging.

c) Consuming food immediately after purchase.

	Congratulations on finishing the quiz.	
Commitment to the challenge	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to avoid food waste together with others and give away leftovers</p> <p>a. yes b. no</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to avoid food waste together with others by sharing my leftover management skills with others</p> <p>a. yes b. no</p>
Stage 2		
	Do you want to inspire others to take action to reduce their food waste? We will tell you a bit more about it in the next step.	
I01: Information provision (alternative behaviour, advantages and disadvantages)	<p>Going beyond the individual level</p> <p>Reducing food waste requires a collaborative effort from different groups of people in our society, including individual consumers, restaurants, retailers, food producers, but also governments. Each group has a role to play in creating a more justice and environmental food system, from a local to a global level. Households can make a change by planning meals, storing food properly, and reuse their leftovers creatively. Restaurants can allow customers to pay for what they eat, offer doggy bags, and manage their food orders more efficiently. Policymakers can come up with stricter regulations and support campaigns to reduce food waste.</p>	

During this challenge, we encourage you to go a step further and inspire others to take action by engaging with the community.

There are different ways to engage within your broader community:

Raising awareness:

Raising awareness about food waste doesn't have to be complicated. Simple conversations and visible actions can make a meaningful difference. The goal is to help others understand the problem and inspire them to take small steps in their own lives.

Start by bringing the topic into everyday conversations. Whether it's over dinner with your family or during a coffee break with friends or colleagues, discussing the social, economic, and environmental impacts of food waste can plant seeds for change among others.

Keep your message relevant with simple solutions, such as using shopping lists or meal plans. People are more likely to act when the information feels applicable and accessible to their daily lives.

In today's digital world, social media is a powerful tool. Share your own progress: Maybe you've already started using your leftovers. Talk about it. These small stories can be inspiring for others. Visuals help, too: post photos of how much waste you collected or avoided. For people who aren't yet aware, this kind of concrete example makes the issue more real.

	<p>Finally, remember that not everyone is motivated in the same way. While environmental reasons are powerful for some people, for others, financial incentives work better. So, highlight the personal benefits too. This can be saving money by using your leftovers or planning your meals in advance. When you connect the problem to real-life advantages, you make change feel not only important, but achievable.</p> <p>Educate people:</p> <p>Organizing workshops or events is a powerful way to educate people about food waste. These can be hands-on sessions where the participants learn practical skills such as using their leftovers. Workshops can also include demonstrations that show how to organize your fridge, cupboards, or freezer. By bringing people together and organizing workshops and events, you can educate and empower people with skills. This could be the start of a bigger change. At the end of a workshop or event, you can collect ideas for future activities.</p> <p>Community engagement:</p> <p>By carrying out practices in the local community, you can empower other individuals or groups of people in our society to take action. Try to get into dialogue with other people. You can join local initiatives such as setting up a community garden, a food sharing program or a community fridge where community members can exchange surplus food. You can also collaborate with local organizations such as NGOs working towards a more sustainable world. You can be part of a public event focusing on food waste or setting up a food waste campaign. Finally, you can engage with the local government by starting petitions to initiate policy changes or participate in forums or public consultations. Let your voice be heard.</p>
	<p>Do you want to learn more about behavioural alternatives? Let's watch some short and fun videos.</p>

I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
E01: Interactive learning environments	<p>Link the participants to ILE based on system model.</p>
	<p>Ready to take another quiz? We are sure you learned enough through the past blocks to successfully pass this test!</p> <p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1:</p> <p>Who is responsible for reducing food waste?</p> <p>a. Individual consumers, restaurants, retailers, food producers, and policymakers</p>

	<p>b. Only individual consumers c. Only governments d. Only individual consumers and governments</p> <p>Question 2. What can you do to motivate others to help reduce food waste?</p> <p>a. Talk about it during everyday conversations b. Involve other people in organizing activities to reduce food waste c. Host an event focusing on reducing food waste d. Express yourself</p> <p>Question 3. What can you do to take the topic of food waste to a higher level?</p> <p>a. Start or sign a petition including the topic of food waste b. Write letters to policymakers c. Take part in local decision making d. Ignore the topic and be silent</p>	
Choice of action	<p>During the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>a. Organize a leftover dinner with other people from my neighbourhood</p>	<p>During the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>a. Talk to others on how to store leftovers to prevent food waste (e.g, freezing leftovers)</p>

		b. Talk to others on how to read and understand the food date labels (use-by dates, best before dates, ...)
Stage 3		
	<p>You feel like you're still missing hands-on advice? How to actually turn these solutions into reality. Learn more about practical applications through the next block.</p> <p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>	
I01: Information provision (helping with planning)	<p>In this challenge, you will try to promote and encourage positive changes among others. You will bring people together with the same values. Being a part of a group of like-minded people is a great way to stay motivated.</p> <p>You decided to organize a leftover dinner with your neighbours. During this event, you will prepare a meal together by using leftovers. Organizing a leftover dinner is not only a fun and interactive way to spend time with your neighbours but it will also raise awareness on the importance of reducing food waste.</p>	<p>You decided to share your food waste skills on how to tackle food waste at home. During this activity you can talk about different topics such as freezing food of leftovers or understanding food date labels (use-by dates and best before dates). You can also combine both topics if you want.</p> <p>Topic 1: Freezing food and leftovers</p> <p>In this talk you can discuss which foods freeze well, such as fruit, vegetables, bread, and cooked meals, and which</p>

	<p>Think about</p> <p>Start by agreeing the basics such as the date, the venue (whether it will be at your home or in a community space) and the number of people who can attend. Do not forget to invite people in advance.</p> <p>Encourage people to bring food from home that is about to expire or that they will unlikely use.</p> <p>You could also contact local supermarkets or bakeries to see if they have any surplus food they would be willing to donate you. This is a great way to involve the wider community.</p> <p>Additional step:</p> <p>Menu planning (2-3 days in advance)</p> <p>A few days before the dinner, you could also ask guests to send you a list of what they plan to bring, which will help with the next step - planning the menu.</p> <p>Once you have gotten a rough idea of the ingredients available, start grouping and brainstorm recipes. A group chat or shared online document can help</p>	<p>don't (such as high-water-content vegetables or creamy sauces).</p> <p>Topics to take into account:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to pack food and leftovers correctly, using airtight containers, freezer bags and food date labelling. • How long frozen foods and leftovers will keep, e.g. bread (up to 3 months), cooked meals (2-3 months) and meat (up to 6 months). • How to organise the freezer, using clear labelling and the 'first in, first out' principle to avoid forgotten leftovers. <p>Topic 2: Understanding food date labels</p> <p>In this talk you can discuss what the food date labels exactly mean, why they exist, and how we should interpret them.</p>
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	<p>everyone post what they are bringing, allowing for collaborative meal planning. Try to be flexible since ingredients can change at the last minute, so choose recipes that can be easily adapted.</p> <p>Dinner Day</p> <p>Prepare the meal together with your guests. This not only creates a sense of community but also makes the issue of food waste more personal and accessible.</p> <p>Here are some menu ideas to get you started:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starter: Bread crisps made from old bread, paired with dips made from leftover vegetables. • Main course: A colourful stir-fry with a variety of vegetables, a leftover quiche or a soup. • Dessert: A fruit salad with overripe fruit or banana bread made from soft bananas. • Drinks: Ripe fruit smoothies or homemade lemonade. 	<p>The best before and use by date labels are the most widely used types of date labeling on food in Europe. By understanding and paying attention to the different labels, we can reduce our food waste considerably.</p> <p>Best before date?</p> <p>This label tells us more about the quality of the food Use sense: look, smell, taste.</p> <p>It is difficult to say how long it can be eaten after the best before date since it depends on the product. You can also follow the packaging recommendations.</p> <p>Use by date?</p> <p>This label tells us more about the safety of the food If you store the product properly and in hygienic conditions, it can be used safely until its use by day If you freeze it before the use by date, it can be used beyond expiration date Some supermarkets offer discounts when the product is close to use by date. This is an opportunity to buy</p>
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	<p>If you want to make a bigger impact, you might start the evening with a short introduction about why food waste matters - how much food is thrown away each year and how creative solutions such as leftover dinners can make a difference. Throughout the evening, encourage your guests to share their own tips, experiences and challenges with food storage, leftovers and waste prevention.</p> <p>Right after the meal</p> <p>Ask participants to bring a container with them for the leftovers. Alternatively, you can freeze any leftover food or use it into future meals.</p> <p>Gather also some feedback from the guests. This can be in a informal conversation or in a follow-up e-mail afterwards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What did people enjoy most about the event? • Was there anything that surprised them? • Would they consider trying this at home? 	<p>cheaper food when it is close to use by date. Freeze it before the use by date when not using it directly</p> <p>Are you going to eat the food product shortly after buying it? Take the item in the supermarket closest to expiration date. Leave the items with longer expiration date for other people who might need it.</p>
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- Would they consider organizing a leftover dinner themselves?
- Could this become a regular event within the neighbourhood?

After the dinner

After the dinner, you can encourage the participants to share their personal tips and leftover-friendly recipes.

You could create a new group on social media platforms such as WhatsApp or Facebook to facilitate the sharing. Alternatively, as the organizer, you could compile a leftover recipe book and collect recipes for often wasted food products (e.g. bread, vegetables, bananas) and create a small digital or printed recipe booklet for your community.

You can also think together with the guests about how you can make your own community more sustainable (f.ex. a permanent food sharing box)

A food waste dinner is more than just a meal - it is a statement. It brings people together, encourages sustainable consumption and turns what might have

	gone in the bin into something delicious. With a little planning, your dinner could be a memorable event with a lasting impact.	
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
	Where can you find the resources you need in your hometown? Find out about local stores in the map.	
I03: Map	Participants and project partners will locate places on the map themselves.	
	Let's get active and participate in a hands-on tutorial!	
E06: Tutorials	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to reduce food waste by organizing a leftover dinner in your neighbourhood.</p> <p>Planning:</p>	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>If you want to go a step further and you want to make a bigger impact. You could share your food waste skills with more people in your neighbourhood. You can think about organizing an event to raise awareness and motivate others to engage.</p>

	<p>Invite your neighbours - by message or in person.</p> <p>Agree on a time and place (e.g. community room, office kitchen, garden).</p> <p>Ask everyone to bring leftovers (or other products) that are still good but close to expire.</p> <p>Organisation:</p> <p>Collect tables, chairs, plates, glasses, cutlery, napkins. To make it easier, you can also ask people to bring their own plate, cutlery, and glass.</p> <p>Provide water or other drinks. Again, to make it easier, you can also ask people to bring a drink to share.</p> <p>Provide a cooker if needed.</p> <p>Collect all the leftovers on a table, sort the food and decide together what to make with it.</p> <p>Brainstorm or improvise some recipes.</p> <p>Cook, serve and enjoy together!</p>	<p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organize an event where you share your own food waste management skills: Freeze smarter</p> <p>Introduction: Introduce the topic of food waste. Use an icebreaker or ask an easy question such as: "Have you ever frozen food - and if so, what?"</p> <p>Key topics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why food waste matters • The power of freezing • Understanding labels on frozen food <p>Step 2: Show participants what can be frozen and how to do it properly.</p> <p>How to do it: Discuss common foods and whether they freeze well (e.g. bread, cucumbers?).</p> <p>Demonstrate good freezing practices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use airtight containers or freezer bags. • Label everything with contents and date.
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	<p>Ask the participants to bring empty containers with them so that leftovers can be taken away.</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start organizing a leftover dinner. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise the freezer according to the FIFO principle (first in, first out) • Share a handy freezer chart: how long typical foods last (e.g. berries: 6 months, cooked meals: 2-3 months). <p>CircleUp tips to share with others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freeze only the portions you're going to use. • Flatten bags of soup or sauces to save space. • Use paper clips or pens to mark dates clearly. <p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organize an event where you share your own food waste management skills: Freeze smarter. Read labels better.</p> <p>Introduction: Understanding Food date Labels Help participants confidently identify food date labels using their senses: look, smell, taste.</p>
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		<p>Group discussion: What's the difference between 'use by' and 'best before'?</p> <p>If you have the capacities, you can include a hands-on activity: Show real food - such as yoghurt, bread and tins - and guide the participants: Smelling, inspecting and checking for signs of spoilage.</p> <p>Decide if the food is still safe to eat.</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start organizing an event on sharing your food waste skills. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>
	<p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>	

<p>E03: Quiz</p>	<p>Question 1: What is the purpose of asking guests to bring food that is about to expire or leftovers? A) To test their cooking skills B) To creatively use food that would otherwise go to waste C) To ensure there is enough food for the host</p> <p>Question 2: When should the menu ideally be planned? A) On the day of the dinner B) 2–3 days before the dinner C) A month in advance</p> <p>Question 3: What is one suitable starter for a Food Waste Dinner? A) Fresh sushi from the supermarket B) Bread chips made from stale bread with vegetable dips C) A frozen ready meal</p> <p>Question 4: Why should you encourage guests to share their experiences during the dinner? A) To raise awareness about food waste and promote new habits</p>
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	<p>B) To make the dinner longer</p> <p>C) To find out who brought the best dish</p> <p>Question 5:</p> <p>What should be done with leftover food after the event?</p> <p>A) Throw it away to avoid storing it</p> <p>B) Leave it behind for the host to manage</p> <p>C) Let guests take food home, freeze it, or reuse it creatively</p>
	We have collected some useful material for you in the following building block.
T02: External tools	<p>Partners can include helpful links to support people in organizing workshops or events focusing on food waste prevention, food storage, organizing leftover dinners</p> <p><i>NO:</i></p> <p><i>Germany:</i></p> <p><i>UK:</i></p> <p><i>Latvia:</i></p>
Stage 4	
E04: Smart bin analysis	The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their food waste and on the changes in food waste since the start of the challenge.
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
T01: Habit tracker	Will be provided if available and useful.

	<p>... <i>Input from the partners</i></p>
<p>S04: Circular story task</p>	<p>Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge. They are encouraged to reflect on the barriers, motivations, and possible outcomes of their new behaviour. In addition, they can give tips to other participants.</p>
<p>Sources used for this challenge</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · https://www.canr.msu.edu/news/keep_food_safe_by_implementing_the_fifo_system · https://www.verbraucherzentrale.de/tipps-zur-haltbarkeit-und-lagerung-von-lebensmitteln-59515 · https://www.verbraucherzentrale.nrw/wissen/lebensmittel/auswaehlen-zubereiten-aufbewahren/lebensmittelverschwendung-folgen-fuer-umwelt-ressourcen-welternahrung-59565 · https://www.verbraucherzentrale.nrw/wissen/lebensmittel/auswaehlen-zubereiten-aufbewahren/politik-von-der-lebensmittelverschwendung-zur-wertschaetzung-59547 · https://www.verbraucherzentrale.de/wissen/lebensmittel · https://www.stopfoodwasteday.com/en/recipes-and-top-tips/sfwd-cookbook.html · https://www.zerowastescotland.org.uk/resources/how-to-meal-plan · https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/prevention-and-reduction-food-waste <p>Aloysius, N., Ananda, J., Mitsis, A., & Pearson, D. (2023). Why people are bad at leftover food management? A systematic literature review and a framework to analyze household leftover food waste generation behavior. <i>Appetite</i>, 186, 106577.</p>

	<p>Boulet, M., Hoek, A., & Raven, R. (2021). The gaze of the gatekeeper: Unpacking the multi-level influences and interactions of household food waste through a video elicitation study. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i>, 171, 105625.</p> <p>Gustavsson, J., Cederberg, C., Sonesson, U., van Otterdijk, R., & Meybeck, A. (2011). Global food losses and food waste: Extent, causes and prevention food and agriculture organization of the united nations. <i>Rome: Italy</i>.</p> <p>Koivupuro, H. K., Hartikainen, H., Silvennoinen, K., Katajajuuri, J. M., Heikintalo, N., Reinikainen, A., & Jalkanen, L. (2012). Influence of socio-demographical, behavioural and attitudinal factors on the amount of avoidable food waste generated in Finnish households. <i>International journal of consumer studies</i>, 36(2), 183-191.</p> <p>Mbow, H.-O. P., Reisinger, A., Canadell, J., & O'Brien, P. (2017). Special Report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems (SR2). <i>Ginevra, IPCC</i>, 650.</p> <p>Ramos, G. J., Borges, J. A. R., Domingues, C. H. d. F., & van Herpen, E. (2024). Reducing food waste by simply measuring it: insights from interventions to reduce household food waste. <i>British Food Journal</i>, 126(2), 812-833.</p> <p>Roe, B. E., Bender, K., & Qi, D. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on consumer food waste. <i>Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy</i>, 43(1), 401-411.</p> <p>Russell, S. V., Young, C. W., Unsworth, K. L., & Robinson, C. (2017). Bringing habits and emotions into food waste behaviour. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i>, 125, 107-114.</p> <p>Schanes, K., Dobernig, K., & Gözet, B. (2018). Food waste matters-A systematic review of household food waste practices and their policy implications. <i>Journal of cleaner production</i>, 182, 978-991.</p> <p>States, A. O. o. t. U. (2013). <i>The state of food insecurity in the world 2013: The multiple dimensions of food security</i>. Fao.</p> <p>Thomas, A., & Garland, R. (2004). Grocery shopping: list and non-list usage. <i>Marketing Intelligence & Planning</i>, 22(6), 623-635.</p>
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Table 27: Framework for the individual packaging challenges

Building block	Challenge 1 individual: Challenge: Avoid packaging Alternative behaviour: Buy food with no packaging Alternative behaviour: Buy food with less packaging	Challenge 2 individual: Challenge: Reuse packaging Alternative behaviour: Use reusable bags/containers Alternative behaviour: Use reusable cups/takeaway box
Questions for the stage analysis	Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about avoiding packaging? -I am not sure why I should avoid packaging (stage 1) -I know why it is important to avoid packaging, but I do not know which alternatives I have (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already buying a lot of things with no packaging (stage 4) -I am already buying a lot of things with less packaging (stage 4)	Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about reusing packaging? -I am not sure why I should reuse packaging (stage 1) -I know why it is important to reuse packaging, but I do not know which alternatives I have (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already using reusable bags (stage 4) -I am already using reusable containers (stage 4) -I am already using reusable coffee cups (stage 4) -I am already using reusable takeaway boxes (stage 4)
Stage 1		

	<p>Welcome to the packaging challenge! First of all, you will read a text about how plastic pollution affects our planet and our health.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>
<p>I01: Information provision (why current behavior is problematic)</p>	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plastic packaging harms animals, pollutes ecosystems, and threatens our health. • Production is skyrocketing, driven by rising demand. • Microplastics are now a global problem — impacting crops, oceans, animals, and people. • Avoiding and reducing packaging, especially single-use plastics, is one of the most impactful steps individuals and communities can take to protect the environment and each other. <p>Plastic, the material that wraps, protects, and preserves our products, is made primarily from fossil fuels like crude oil and natural gas. Its production consumes vast amounts of energy, water, and raw materials, releasing high levels of greenhouse gases and contributing to climate change. This is especially concerning given the massive and growing demand for plastic, much of which is used for short-lived packaging.</p> <p>Environmental impact</p> <p>Once released into the environment, plastic enters a long-lasting and destructive cycle. Approximately 8 million tons of plastic waste flow into the oceans every year, where it poses a severe threat to marine life and ecosystems. On land, packaging waste fills landfills, takes centuries to decompose, and leaves behind toxic</p>

traces that pollute the soil and water systems. Over time, plastic breaks down into tiny fragments called microplastics, which now contaminate rivers, oceans, and even the air we breathe.

Impact on wildlife

This pollution has a devastating impact on wildlife. Animals often mistake plastic packaging for food, leading to ingestion that causes internal injuries, intestinal blockages, starvation, and, frequently, death. On British shores, every single animal examined after washing up was found to have plastic in its stomach. Discarded packaging like plastic bags and abandoned fishing gear also entangle wildlife, trapping and injuring sea turtles, seals, and seabirds. The accumulation of packaging waste degrades natural habitats, making it harder for species to survive, reproduce, and maintain ecological balance.

Impact on water systems

The effects don't stop at animals and landscapes. Water systems suffer greatly from packaging waste. As plastic degrades, microplastics infiltrate marine ecosystems and agricultural soils. These particles can interfere with critical biological processes, such as photosynthesis in marine algae and crops. In fact, exposure to microplastics has been shown to reduce staple crop yields by as much as 12%, posing a direct threat to global food security.

Impact on health

Humans are not immune to these consequences. Microplastics have already been found in our drinking water, in the food we eat, and even in human organs. While the full health implications are still being studied, early research links microplastic exposure to inflammation, hormonal disruption, and other health risks. At the same time, the carbon emissions from the production and incineration of packaging materials continue to accelerate climate change, creating knock-on effects that further threaten public health, agriculture, and ecosystems.

	<p>To sum up</p> <p>The problem is vast and growing. As plastic production surges, so too does the risk it poses to our environment and ourselves. Packaging is often unnecessary, used once, and discarded - yet its environmental impact lasts for centuries.</p>	
	<p>You're done reading, good job! Hopefully, you have gained a lot of new information.</p> <p>You're now invited to watch some interesting videos on the topic to further deepen your knowledge.</p>	
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
	<p>We're facing big challenges! Have you ever wondered how people and organisations all over the globe are addressing these challenges? Let's take a closer look.</p>	
I01: Information provision (on what others already do)	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The European Union is actively addressing plastic pollution. 	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many people are already adopting zero-waste lifestyles.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the main strategies is a ban on commonly littered items, for example plastic plates, cutlery and straws. <p>Across Europe, governments, businesses, and communities are taking bold steps to combat plastic pollution and reduce unnecessary packaging. By learning from these actions, individuals and local groups can feel empowered to do the same.</p> <p>EU's response</p> <p>One major example is the European Union's comprehensive response to single-use plastics. As part of its directive to reduce plastic waste, the EU has banned commonly littered single-use plastic items since 2021 such as plastic plates, cutlery, straws, balloon sticks, and cotton buds. These items, often used just once, have been found in oceans, beaches, and natural habitats, harming wildlife and ecosystems. Their removal from the market marks a shift toward more sustainable consumption.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reusable bags, containers, and jars are used, for example at bulk stores. • Workplaces and schools are also embracing reusables. • It is important that large events also shift to reusable systems. • Since online communities are growing in which ideas in DIY are shared, it makes it easier for everyone to be part of a change. <p>All over the world, individuals, businesses and communities are rethinking the way we use packaging and reusing it instead of throwing it away. For example, many people try to live without purchasing any new plastics. By seeing what others already do, we can find practical inspiration and realise that a more sustainable lifestyle is not only possible, but already underway.</p> <p>Reusable practices</p> <p>In many cities, people bring their own reusable bags, containers, and jars when shopping at refill stores or</p>
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	<p>Additionally, the EU has introduced regulations in 2024 requiring that plastic bottle caps remain attached to bottles, a small but powerful change aimed at preventing cap littering and improving recycling rates. Producers are also being encouraged or required to design packaging that is easier to recycle, creating a stronger circular economy for plastic.</p> <p>Supermarkets</p> <p>On the ground, practical changes are already visible. In many European supermarkets, wooden spoons have replaced plastic ones in yogurt containers, and more products are being packaged in compostable or refillable formats. These are not just symbolic steps, they reflect a growing commitment to redesign systems, reduce waste, and make reuse the norm.</p> <p>These efforts show that change is possible and already underway.</p>	<p>zero-waste shops. At local or farmers markets, customers skip the plastic and carry fresh produce in cloth or mesh bags. More and more cafés are welcoming customers who bring reusable cups and lunch boxes, often offering discounts as a reward.</p> <p>Workplaces and schools</p> <p>Workplaces and schools are also adapting: employees pack meals in reusable lunch containers, and refill stations are being introduced for cleaning supplies and toiletries. Some households go a step further by organizing neighborhood refill groups, buying in bulk and sharing large quantities of goods to reduce both costs and waste.</p> <p>Large events</p> <p>Even at events and festivals, reusable cup deposit systems are replacing single-use plastics, showing that reusability can scale up to large gatherings.</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>Social media is filled with communities sharing tips,</p>
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		<p>photos, and creative solutions, from DIY beeswax wraps to stylish portable cutlery kits.</p> <p>These real-life examples show that reusing packaging is not a far-off goal but a growing movement. With a little planning and creativity, anyone can be part of it.</p>
	<p>You as an individual have the capabilities to change a lot in this world. Let's get active now and take part in an "Experiential learning task"!</p> <p>The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don't feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!</p>	
<p>E02: Experimental learning task</p> <p>S02: Circular story preparation task</p>	<p>Task:</p> <p>Have a look at your own plastic use. Track (and analyze) one type of plastic usage over a week. Select one type of plastic usage from the list below or choose another item you frequently use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. plastic shopping bags b. thin plastic bags for vegetables, fruit, potatoes c. aluminium foil/tinfoil for wrapping food in the kitchen 	<p>Task:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collect your single-use coffee, tea cups or take-away single use boxes over a week and store them in one designated place. 2. At the end of the week, sum up the total number of items that you have used. 3. Take a photo of these items.

	<p>Task:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collect the used items (if possible) and store them in a designated place. 2. At the end of the week, count the total number of items used. 3. Take a picture of the collected items at the end of the week. 4. Upload the picture here. 5. Save the picture for the Circular story and potential future CircleUp challenges or discussions. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Upload it here in this app. Save the picture for the Circular story and potential future CircleUp discussions. 5. Reflect on your usage. These questions can help as a guideline. Remember, you don't have to answer all the questions one by one. We want to give you some starting points to help guide your reflection. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is there a specific location where you use many single-use items, e.g. at work? - What are the reasons for this usage, e.g. convenience? - Think of solutions for changing your behaviour. This includes using reusable items, such as food containers, beeswax wraps and reusable cups.
	<p>Thank you for participating in this task. We hope that you have learned a lot about your own behaviour.</p> <p>It's quickly happening that you lose track on the consequences of your own behaviour. How much waste does your household actually produce? Let's measure this with one of our smart bins.</p>	
E04: Smart bin analysis	<p>The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their plastic packaging.</p>	

	<p>What is the impact of your consumer choices? Let's take a look at the lifecycle of some of your daily products.</p>
E05: LCA assessment	<p>Link the participants to the LCA questions.</p>
	<p>Congratulations on finishing the last building block. We are confident that you have gained lots of useful knowledge!</p> <p>Would you like to test this knowledge? Let's move on to a short quiz!</p>
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one of the EU's main strategies to reduce plastic pollution?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Encouraging people to buy more plastic items b) Banning commonly littered single-use plastic items c) Promoting the export of plastic waste d) Giving free plastic bags at supermarkets <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is one of the goals of EU packaging regulations for producers?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) To reduce food prices b) To promote plastic exports c) To design packaging that is easier to recycle d) To eliminate all types of packaging

Question 3.

What types of single-use plastic items were banned under the EU directive?

- a) Plastic bags only
- b) Plastic furniture and toys
- c) Plates, cutlery, straws, balloon sticks, and cotton buds**
- d) Plastic water bottles and wrappers

Question 4.

Which statement is true?

- a) Europe is banning all plastic immediately
- b) Positive change is already happening and individuals can be part of it**
- c) Plastic pollution is impossible to solve
- d) Only governments can make a difference

Question 5.

What is one of the main motivations for individuals adopting zero-waste lifestyles?

- a) Spending more money on groceries
- b) Following social media trends
- c) Reducing plastic waste and environmental impact**
- d) Getting more free products

Question 6.

What do refill groups typically do?

- a) **Share bulk-bought goods to reduce waste and cost**
- b) Refill plastic bottles at home
- c) Sell second-hand plastic bags
- d) Recycle paper and metal

Question 7.

Why is it important that large events adopt reusable systems?

- a) They often serve expensive food
- b) They typically have many waste bins
- c) **They often generate a lot of single-use plastic waste**
- d) They attract media attention

Question 8.

You are preparing your shopping trip to a zero-waste store or refill station, what should you bring?

- a) Nothing
- b) Plastic wrap
- c) Plastic bags
- d) **Reusable bags, jars, and containers**

Commitment to the challenge:	For the next three weeks, I will try to reduce packaging: a. yes b. no	For the next three weeks, I will try to reuse packaging: a. yes b. no
Stage 2		
What can you do to make a difference? Let's have a look at different alternatives you have for addressing packaging waste.		
I01: Information provision (alternative behaviour, advantages and disadvantages)	Key takeaways: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoiding packaging starts with mindful shopping, like choosing loose fruits instead of wrapped ones. • Not every store offers these options, but these stores might be convinced by your behaviour. • Local or farmers markets and organic stores often offer unpacked food. • Choose compostable or minimal packaging when 100% plastic-free is not available and possible. • Bulk buying can save you money and reduce waste. 	Key takeaways: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Switching to reusable packaging is an effective way to reduce plastic waste. • Impactful solutions are reusable shopping bags, bringing your own containers to refill stations, and reusable lunch boxes or coffee cups for eating and drinking on the go. • At home, you can use different kinds of containers and beeswax wraps. • Reusable options only become more sustainable than single-use options once they are used several times, so consistency is important.

	<p>Avoiding and reducing packaging waste starts with making more mindful choices in your daily routine.</p> <p>Avoid packaging</p> <p>One simple way is to choose food products with no packaging at your local grocery store. Choose loose fruits and vegetables instead of plastic or paper wrapped ones. This helps reduce packaging waste and gives you more control over how much you buy. While you might need reusable bags and containers, and some extra cleaning at home, it is a straightforward and an impactful change.</p> <p>Buy loose products</p> <p>Support stores that offer loose fruit and vegetables. If your local store doesn't, you can start sharing your concerns and ask if they are willing to reduce their plastic packaging. Although speaking up might feel uncomfortable or time-consuming at first, your effort can create a positive change in the end. Avoid buying multi-packs as they often lead to food waste.</p>	<p>Switching to reusable packaging is a simple, yet impactful way to reduce waste and protect the environment. By replacing single-use plastics with reusable options, you can lower your environmental footprint while building more sustainable habits. There are many alternatives to traditional packaging, each with its own set of advantages and potential challenges.</p> <p>Bring containers with you</p> <p>Using your own containers at stores with bulk sections or refill stations helps you avoid unnecessary packaging while buying exactly what you need. Though it may require some planning and upfront investment, reusable containers can be used for years, reducing both waste and costs over time.</p> <p>Reusable shopping bags</p> <p>When shopping, bring your own reusable shopping bags with you to reduce single-use plastic bags. Cloth, mesh, or durable tote bags are perfect for carrying groceries and can easily be folded and kept in your car, backpack, or purse to ensure you always have one on hand. While</p>
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	<p>Buy fresh products</p> <p>Another great option is to buy fresh products without plastic wrapping, which is common at local or farmers markets. These markets help you buy food with minimal environmental impact, while also supporting local farmers. Organic stores also often offer products with less plastic. However, they can sometimes be more expensive or less accessible depending on where you live.</p> <p>Look for less or compostable packaging</p> <p>When non-packaging options are not available in your neighbourhood, look for items with less packaging, or compostable packaging. This reduces immediate waste and encourages retailers to prioritize sustainable options. Even though this is not the perfect solution, it still reduces the waste you generate. Choose cardboard containers or boxes when available, as they are easier to recycle and often come with less environmental impact.</p>	<p>remembering to bring them might take some time, many people find that it quickly becomes second nature.</p> <p>On the go</p> <p>When eating or drinking on the go, bringing a reusable coffee cup, water bottle, and food container helps avoid disposable takeout packaging. Many cafés and restaurants now support "bring-your-own" options, with some even offering discounts. These alternatives help reduce single-use plastics like cups, cutlery, and takeaway containers that often end up in landfills or oceans. Additionally, bringing your own reusable utensils when dining out, helps reduce the reliance on single-use cutlery.</p> <p>Storing food at home</p> <p>At home, alternatives to single-use plastics are equally important. Consider using glass containers, silicone bags, or beeswax wraps instead of plastic foil and disposable storage bags. These options not only reduce plastic waste but also help keep food fresher for longer. Though they require cleaning and a small upfront cost,</p>
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	<p>Refill shops</p> <p>Refill shops offer another great solution, where you can purchase products like grains, nuts, and spices without packaging. By shopping at refill shops, you only buy what you need, which creates less food waste at the same time. Shopping at refill shops ask a bit more planning in advance because you need to bring your own containers and it might not be an option in your neighbourhood, however, many people find that this can become a rewarding habit over time. To make bulk buying more efficient and prevent food waste, consider sharing items with friends or family. While this requires a bit of coordination, it can be more economical and environmentally friendly in the long run.</p> <p>To sum up</p> <p>These alternatives not only reduce your ecological footprint but also help shift the marketplace towards more sustainable practices, contributing to a cleaner planet. While some alternatives may require more</p>	<p>they are sturdy, long-lasting, and better for both you and the environment.</p> <p>Don't forget:</p> <p>It should be taken into account that reusable packaging is designed for multiple uses and is only more environmental than its single-use equivalent after the reuse of several times. The same counts for reusable bags.</p> <p>To sum up</p> <p>While some of these alternatives may take a bit more time or effort, the benefits like less waste, saving money, and healthier habits, make it worth it. By using reusable containers, bags, and other sustainable solutions, you can help reduce packaging waste and support a greener lifestyle.</p> <p>By reducing packaging, avoiding single-use plastics, and supporting reuse and bulk alternatives, individuals and communities can play a powerful role in addressing this global challenge.</p>
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	<p>planning or investment, the long-term benefits for both you and the environment are well worth it.</p> <p>By reducing packaging, avoiding single-use plastics, and supporting reuse and bulk alternatives, individuals and communities can play a powerful role in addressing this global challenge.</p>	
	<p>Want to learn more about behavioural alternatives? Let's watch some short and fun videos.</p>	
<p>I02: Videos</p>	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	

E01: Interactive learning environments	Link the participants to ILE based on system model.	
	Feels like you are an expert now, right? Let's test your knowledge with a short test.	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one simple way to reduce packaging waste when grocery shopping?</p> <p>a) Buying canned goods in bulk</p> <p>b) Choosing loose fruits and vegetables</p> <p>c) Purchasing pre-packed meals</p> <p>d) Using plastic bags for produce</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>Which of the following is a benefit of shopping at farmers markets?</p> <p>a) All produce is plastic-wrapped</p> <p>b) Products are available year-round regardless of season</p> <p>c) You support local farmers and reduce packaging</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>What is one suggested way to reduce packaging when</p>	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one main benefit of bringing your own containers to refill stations?</p> <p>a) You get to shop faster</p> <p>b) You avoid all food waste</p> <p>c) You reduce packaging waste and buy only what you need</p> <p>d) You receive government rewards.</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is a potential disadvantage of using reusable containers?</p> <p>a) They are too small to use for shopping.</p> <p>b) They cannot be reused</p> <p>c) They are only accepted in organic stores</p> <p>d) They require cleaning and initial investment</p>

	<p>buying in bulk?</p> <p>a) Share purchases with friends or family</p> <p>b) Eat all the food immediately</p> <p>c) Freeze everything regardless of need</p> <p>d) Only buy packaged goods</p>	<p>Question 4.</p> <p>What type of bag is recommended for carrying groceries sustainably?</p> <p>a) Cloth, mesh, or tote bags</p> <p>b) Thin plastic bags</p> <p>c) Paper bags only</p> <p>d) Aluminium foil wraps</p>
Choice of action	<p>For the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>a. Buy food with no packaging</p> <p>b. Buy food with less packaging</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>a. Use reusable bags/containers</p> <p>b. Use reusable cups/lunch box</p>
Stage 3		
	<p>You feel like you're still missing hands-on advice? How to actually turn these solutions into reality. Learn more about practical applications through the next block.</p> <p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>	

<p>I01: Information provision (helping with planning)</p>	<p>How to avoid packaging in daily life?</p> <p>Goal: Plan concrete steps to avoid single-use packaging in everyday life - and put them into practice!</p> <p>Why take part?</p> <p>Plastic packaging harms animals, the environment and health - and is often completely unnecessary.</p> <p>Packaging is usually only used once and then pollutes our oceans, soil and air for centuries. But you can make a difference - right when you shop!</p> <p>Your challenge - step by step:</p> <p>1. Planning is everything: create your unpackaged strategy</p> <p>Make a shopping list for the week.</p> <p>Tick it off: What can you buy unpackaged or with less packaging?</p> <p>Plan: When will you visit a weekly market or an unpackaged shop, for example?</p>	<p>How to reuse packaging in daily life?</p> <p>Goal: Plan concrete steps to reuse single-use packaging in everyday life – and put them into practice!</p> <p>Reusable bags</p> <p>Bringing reusable bags for grocery shopping, as well as for bread, fruit and vegetables. Bringing your own bags is one of the simplest ways to reduce plastic packaging.</p> <p>Use a reusable linen bag or cloth to store your bread.</p> <p>Many stores and bakeries allow their customers to bring their own bags, so don't hesitate to ask. For extra freshness, choose breathable fabric bags that keep your bread fresh. You can also use these bags or containers for other bakery items such as pastries.</p> <p>Reusable produce bags are an easy and effective way to shop for plastic free groceries. They are often made from eco-friendly materials and are perfect for carrying fruits, vegetables or other loose items without relying on plastic. They are lightweight and convenient, making them easy to carry in your larger reusable grocery bags.</p>
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	<p>2. Actively use alternatives</p> <p>Buy fruit and vegetables loose, not in plastic nets or film.</p> <p>Choose products with less packaging - e.g. large packs instead of lots of small ones.</p> <p>Bring your own bags, containers and tins.</p> <p>Avoid packaged snacks, yoghurt in plastic or to-go food in disposable boxes.</p> <p>3. Rethink at home</p> <p>Store food in reusable containers instead of cling film.</p> <p>Use beeswax cloths or screw-top jars, for example.</p> <p>Take stock: Which products can you refill or buy in different packaging in the future (e.g. bars of soap, refill packs)?</p> <p>4. Reflect and carry on.</p> <p>How much packaging did you manage to avoid?</p> <p>What came as a surprise — either positive or negative?</p> <p>What would you like to maintain or improve?</p>	<p>The most challenging part about reusable bags is remembering to take them with you! Keep them in your car, bike bag or by your door so you don't forget. This simple habit not only reduces waste but also saves you money.</p> <p>Reusable containers</p> <p>Most grocery stores have sections where you can buy fresh meat, fish, or cheese. These sections often allow you to bring your own containers, so they can put the food directly into your reusable container instead of using their own packaging. To make the most of this habit, plan ahead. Avoid impulse shopping trips when you don't have your containers with you. If you usually drive to the store, keep a couple of reusable containers in your car. Place a reminder, like a post-it note, on your dashboard or in the back of your car so you don't forget your containers. Additionally, consider investing in a variety of reusable containers that suit different types and sizes of food. You can also use jars, that you already have, i.e. screwtop-jars used for vegetables.</p>
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	<p>Your goal: buy at least five products per week without packaging, or with significantly less of it, and realise how good it feels!</p> <p>Tip: You save waste and often money, and inspire those around you to do the same.</p> <p>Less rubbish. Less cost. More future. Join in and show that change is possible!</p>	<p>Reusable cup</p> <p>Being a coffee or tea lover and reducing single-use packaging can go hand in hand. Reusable coffee cups have a much lower environmental impact compared to single-use cups. But to maximize the benefits, you should use your reusable cup between 20 and 100 times to have lower emissions than disposable cups. Make it a habit to pack your reusable coffee cup whenever you leave the house. If you forget it, try to enjoy your drink inside the café instead. Wash your cup between uses and use it for as long as possible. When it reaches the end of its life, be sure to recycle it properly.</p> <p>Reusable takeaway container</p> <p>Avoiding single-use takeaway packaging will help you reduce your packaging. The most important step is to bring your own container with you to get your meal. Before you leave the house, consider whether you will be buying a takeaway breakfast, lunch, or dinner or if you will eat somewhere that only serves food in single-use packaging. Make it a daily habit to pack reusables next to your other essential items such as keys, wallet, and</p>
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		<p>phone before leaving the house. Don't forget other reusables for the day such as bags or containers.</p> <p>CircleUp tip: Make sure your container is clean, which means washed and dried completely. Metal or glass containers are preferable as they look cleaner over time compared to plastic containers.</p> <p>Different containers work for different types of food. Think about what you will be asking to put into your reusable container. If it is the first time you use your reusable container, start with something simple and easy to pack.</p> <p>By including these habits into your shopping routines, you will not only reduce your environmental footprint but might also inspire others to do the same.</p>
I02: Videos	Videos are provided by project partners if available.	

	<p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
	<p>Great, now you already know a lot about how to find solutions to environmental challenges. But how can you turn this into reality? Where can you find helpful resources in your hometown? Let's take a look at this map.</p>	
I03: Map	<p>Participants and project partners will locate places on the map.</p>	
	<p>Let's get active and participate in a hands-on tutorial!</p>	
E06: Tutorials	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>One example tutorial:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Choose one product that is sealed in plastic and you think that there are equivalent alternatives of the same product without packaging (e.g. fruits with plastic cover) 2. Think about where and how to get this alternative product. This can simply be choosing an 	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>One example tutorial:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Go through your fridge and cupboards consciously: Where have you used wrapping or packages to store leftovers? Which of them could be replaced by sustainable options, such as glass containers, silicone storage bags, jars or bottles.

	<p>alternative product in the same store or visiting the farmers market, refill store etc. and get the product there.</p> <p>3. Take a picture from the last time you bought the product with packaging. With that, you can visualise how much packaging you were able to save.</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start buying products with no or less packaging. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>	<p>2. If you don't have them already, purchase them (this can easily be done in various stores, such as IKEA, or even second hand).</p> <p>3. Change your way of storing items, now you don't need to use single-use packaging again</p> <p>Tutorial for making an own beeswax wrap (more difficult one)</p> <p>How have you wrapped your sandwich in the past? You have probably fought with annoying saran wrap or used quite some amount of aluminum foil, right? Beeswax wraps are a healthy and chemical-free alternative to conventional methods of covering foods and they can be used all over again. Today, we will make some by ourselves:</p> <p>All you need is two things: beeswax and fabric. Beeswax will be melted onto the fabric. The waxy surface will then seal your food.</p> <p>Buy this in advance:</p>
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		<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Fabric, ideally 100% cotton. You can find some nice fabric in thrift stores.2. A block of beeswax or beeswax pellets3. Baking sheet (or other utility sheet that you use for arts and crafts)4. Paintbrush to spread the wax5. Pinking shears (if you want to cut the fabric nicely) <p>Steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Heat the oven to 180 °C.2. Cut the fabric and place it face down on the baking sheet3. Spread the beeswax evenly. Rather take a bit too less than too much because you can always heat up more later.
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		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Place it in the oven for 1-2 minutes. Watch carefully until the wax is melted. 5. Spread the wax evenly with a paint brush. 6. Cool and dry the fabric. 7. Ready to use! <p>How to use the beeswax wrap?</p> <p>Place the wrap over the food you need to cover and press around the edge of the container with your hands. The heat from your hands will warm the wax and allow it to stick to the container sealing it to protect the food.</p> <p>How to clean the beeswax wrap?</p> <p>Use cool, soapy water and a non-abrasive sponge, if needed (no warm water because this will melt the wax). Just wipe them clean and hang them dry.</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start using reusable products. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We</p>
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		<p>encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>
	<p>After finishing the tutorial, you contributed to circularity in a meaningful way, that's amazing!</p> <p>Would you like to test your knowledge in a final quiz? Click here!</p>	
	<p>We have collected some useful material for you in the following building block.</p>	
<p>T02: External tools</p>	<p>There are different existing apps that can help you minimize your plastic usage in different domains such as in the bathroom or kitchen. Some apps also calculate your plastic footprint and provide you with more sustainable alternatives.</p> <p>There are also apps available which detect microplastics in your products by scanning the barcode of the items.</p> <p>There is already a lot of information out there on the internet. Here are some of them:</p> <p><i>Norway:</i></p> <p>BeeOrganic.no</p> <p>Svanemerket.no : The official ecolabel of the Nordic countries. The date label wants to make people aware about the environmental impact from production and consumption of products so they can choose the environmental alternative instead.</p> <p>Guppyfriend to wash with less microplastics</p> <p>Reko Ringen</p>	

	<p>Kaffebrenneriet and Baker Hansen gives a reduction when you take your own cup with you</p> <p>Hold Norge Rent</p> <p><i>Germany:</i></p> <p><i>Latvia:</i></p> <p><i>UK:</i></p>
Stage 4	
E04: Smart bin analysis	The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their plastic packaging
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
T01: Habit tracker	<p>Will be provided if available and useful.</p> <p><i>... Input from the partners</i></p>

	<p>Wow, you nailed it! You finished an entire challenge of the CircleUp project! What did you learn, what was interesting or challenging? Reflect on your experiences in the “Circular story task”.</p>
<p>S04: Circular story task</p>	<p>Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge. They are encouraged to reflect on the barriers, motivations, and possible outcomes of their new behaviour. In addition, they can give tips to other participants.</p>
<p>Sources used for this challenge</p>	<p>Sources:</p> <p>https://supplychain.edf.org/resources/sustainability-101-packaging-waste-the-problem/</p> <p>https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2025/mar/16/the-guardian-view-on-microplastics-harmful-pollution-must-be-curbed</p> <p>https://atlantic.ca/the-case-against-overpackaging-why-less-is-more/</p> <p>https://www.keepbritaintidy.org/get-involved/support-our-campaigns/plastic-challenge/impact-wildlife</p> <p>Everything you should know about single-use plastic - Greenpeace Africa</p> <p>https://www.greenpeace.org/aotearoa/story/plastic-pollutions-devastating-impact-on-wildlife/</p> <p>Scientific sources:</p> <p>Miao, X., Magnier, L., & Mugge, R. (2023). Switching to reuse? An exploration of consumers’ perceptions and behaviour towards reusable packaging systems. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i>, 106972.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.106972</p>

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Table 28: Framework for the community packaging challenges

<p>Building block</p>	<p>Challenge 3 community: Avoid packaging together</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <p>Buy bulk together</p>
<p>Questions for the stage analysis</p>	<p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about avoiding packaging together?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -I am not sure why I should avoid packaging together (stage 1) -I know why it is important avoid packaging together but I do not know exactly what I can do (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already regularly buying bulk together (stage 4)
<p>Stage 1</p>	
	<p>Welcome to the community packaging challenge! Are you motivated to address a packaging-related challenge together with others in your community? Then you're in the right place! Let's get started with a short introduction.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>

<p>I01: Information provision (why current behavior is problematic)</p>	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plastic packaging harms animals, pollutes ecosystems, and threatens our health. • Production is skyrocketing, driven by rising demand. • Microplastics are now a global problem — impacting crops, oceans, animals, and people. • Avoiding and reducing packaging, especially single-use plastics, is one of the most impactful steps individuals and communities can take to protect the environment and each other. <p>Plastic, the material that wraps, protects, and preserves our products, is made primarily from fossil fuels like crude oil and natural gas. Its production consumes vast amounts of energy, water, and raw materials, releasing high levels of greenhouse gases and contributing to climate change. This is especially concerning given the massive and growing demand for plastic, much of which is used for short-lived packaging.</p> <p>Environmental impact</p> <p>Once released into the environment, plastic enters a long-lasting and destructive cycle. Approximately 8 million tons of plastic waste flow into the oceans every year, where it poses a severe threat to marine life and ecosystems. On land, packaging waste fills landfills, takes centuries to decompose, and leaves behind toxic traces that pollute the soil and water systems. Over time, plastic breaks down into tiny fragments called microplastics, which now contaminate rivers, oceans, and even the air we breathe.</p> <p>Impact on wildlife</p> <p>This pollution has a devastating impact on wildlife. Animals often mistake plastic packaging for food, leading</p>
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to ingestion that causes internal injuries, intestinal blockages, starvation, and, frequently, death. On British shores, every single animal examined after washing up was found to have plastic in its stomach. Discarded packaging like plastic bags and abandoned fishing gear also entangle wildlife, trapping and injuring sea turtles, seals, and seabirds. The accumulation of packaging waste degrades natural habitats, making it harder for species to survive, reproduce, and maintain ecological balance.

Impact on water systems

The effects don't stop at animals and landscapes. Water systems suffer greatly from packaging waste. As plastic degrades, microplastics infiltrate marine ecosystems and agricultural soils. These particles can interfere with critical biological processes, such as photosynthesis in marine algae and crops. In fact, exposure to microplastics has been shown to reduce staple crop yields by as much as 12%, posing a direct threat to global food security.

Impact on health

Humans are not immune to these consequences. Microplastics have already been found in our drinking water, in the food we eat, and even in human organs. While the full health implications are still being studied, early research links microplastic exposure to inflammation, hormonal disruption, and other health risks. At the same time, the carbon emissions from the production and incineration of packaging materials continue to accelerate climate change, creating knock-on effects that further threaten public health, agriculture, and ecosystems.

To sum up

The problem is vast and growing. As plastic production surges, so too does the risk it poses to our

	<p>environment and ourselves. Packaging is often unnecessary, used once, and discarded - yet its environmental impact lasts for centuries.</p> <p>By reducing packaging, avoiding single-use plastics, and supporting reuse and bulk alternatives, individuals and communities can play a powerful role in addressing this global challenge.</p>
	<p>Great job with making it through the text. Let's continue with some fun videos.</p>
<p>I02: Videos</p>	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
	<p>As you have seen, plastic pollution is a pressing problem. What has already been done to address this issue? This is what you'll find out through reading the next text.</p>
<p>I01: Information provision (on what others already do)</p>	<p>Across Europe, governments, businesses, and communities are taking bold steps to combat plastic pollution and reduce unnecessary packaging. By learning from these actions, individuals and local groups can feel empowered to do the same.</p>

	<p>One major example is the European Union’s comprehensive response to single-use plastics. As part of its directive to reduce plastic waste, the EU has banned commonly littered single-use plastic items such as plastic plates, cutlery, straws, balloon sticks, and cotton buds. These items, often used just once, have been found in oceans, beaches, and natural habitats, harming wildlife and ecosystems. Their removal from the market marks a shift toward more sustainable consumption.</p> <p>Additionally, the EU has introduced regulations requiring that plastic bottle caps remain attached to bottles, a small but powerful change aimed at preventing cap littering and improving recycling rates. Producers are also being encouraged or required to design packaging that is easier to recycle, creating a stronger circular economy for plastic.</p> <p>On the ground, practical changes are already visible. In many European supermarkets, wooden spoons have replaced plastic ones in yogurt containers, and more products are being packaged in compostable or refillable formats. These are not just symbolic steps, they reflect a growing commitment to redesign systems, reduce waste, and make reuse the norm.</p> <p>By sharing what is already being done - from EU-level policies to small innovations in everyday products - we can inspire and guide further action. These efforts show that change is possible and already underway.</p>
	<p>Good job with reading the texts! Now, after gaining all this knowledge, let’s get active with an “Experiential learning task”.</p>

	<p>The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don't feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!</p>
<p>E02: Experiential learning task S02: Circular story preparation task</p>	<p>In the previous sections, you have seen that plastic pollution is a global problem. Even if you have become aware of the problem, that does not mean that others have. With this learning task, we aim to share global awareness.</p> <p>Go on a clean-up in your neighborhood with some friends and family. If you don't think that you can find any trash in your neighborhood area, choose another place. Often, you can find these items at places where people like to hang out, e.g. lakesides, parks etc. Now reading this, you might think that you live in a clean environment, but keep your eyes open, you'll find something!</p> <p>Here's how you do it:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Choose 3-5 friends or family members and invite them to the clean-up. Choose a nice day for a walk outside to make this an enjoyable activity. 2. Prepare some equipment, such as bags to put the trash in and gripping pliers and/or gloves to touch some trash. 3. Determine an area or route and go for a 1-2 hours walk. Look closely.

	<p>4. Optional: On the walk, share the information that you have learned in the previous sections. Exchange knowledge and opinions with others.</p> <p>5. After the clean-up, take a look into your bags and see how much you have collected.</p> <p>Take a photo and save the pictures and your reflection or drawing for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p> <p>7. And finally: Enjoy the rest of the day with having in mind that you have done something good for our environment!</p>
	<p>Are you interested in your own waste footprint? Let's measure your households' waste with one of our smart bins.</p>
<p>E04: Smart bin analysis</p>	<p>The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their plastic packaging.</p>
	<p>What are the environmental consequences of each of our actions? Where does our packaging waste actually come from and where does it go? These are the questions that can be answered with a so-called "Life-cycle assessment". Let's dive into this further.</p>
<p>E05: LCA assessment</p>	<p>Link the participants to the LCA questions.</p>
	<p>Do you feel ready to take a quiz? Let's go and test your knowledge.</p>

	<p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one of the EU’s main strategies to reduce plastic pollution?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Encouraging people to buy more plastic items b) Banning commonly littered single-use plastic items c) Promoting the export of plastic waste d) Giving free plastic bags at supermarkets <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is one of the goals of EU packaging regulations for producers?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) To reduce food prices b) To promote plastic exports c) To design packaging that is easier to recycle d) To eliminate all types of packaging <p>Question 3.</p> <p>What types of single-use plastic items were banned under the EU directive?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Plastic bags only

- b) Plastic furniture and toys
- c) Plates, cutlery, straws, balloon sticks, and cotton buds**
- d) Plastic water bottles and wrappers

Question 4.

Which statement is true?

- a) Europe is banning all plastic immediately
- b) Positive change is already happening and individuals can be part of it**
- c) Plastic pollution is impossible to solve
- d) Only governments can make a difference

Question 5.

What is one of the main motivations for individuals adopting zero-waste lifestyles?

- a) Spending more money on groceries
- b) Following social media trends
- c) Reducing plastic waste and environmental impact**
- d) Getting more free products

Question 6.

What do refill groups typically do?

- a) Share bulk-bought goods to reduce waste and cost**
- b) Refill plastic bottles at home

	<p>c) Sell second-hand plastic bags d) Recycle paper and metal</p> <p>Question 7. Why is it important that large events adopt reusable systems?</p> <p>a) They often serve expensive food b) They typically have many waste bins c) They often generate a lot of single-use plastic waste d) They attract media attention</p> <p>Question 8. You are preparing your shopping trip to a zero-waste store or refill station, what should you bring?</p> <p>a) Nothing b) Plastic wrap c) Plastic bags d) Reusable bags, jars, and containers</p>
<p>Commitment to the challenge:</p>	<p>During the next three weeks, I will try to avoid packaging together:</p> <p>a. yes b. no</p>
<p>Stage 2</p>	

	<p>Congratulations on finishing the quiz. How can you as an individual make a difference? Read about this topic in the following building block.</p>
<p>I01: Information provision (alternative behaviours, advantages and disadvantages)</p>	<p>Going beyond the individual level</p> <p>Reducing plastic waste requires a collaborative effort from different groups in our society, including individual consumers, manufacturers, retailers, packaging companies, but also governments. Each group has a role to play in creating a more just and environmentally sound packaging system, from a local to a global level.</p> <p>Households can make a change by choosing products with minimal or recyclable packaging and reusing containers. Manufacturers can design packaging that is easier to recycle and reduce the amount of plastic used. Policymakers can implement stricter regulations and support campaigns and companies reducing plastic waste.</p> <p>During this challenge, we encourage you to go a step further and inspire others to take action by engaging with the community.</p> <p>There are different ways to engage within your broader community:</p> <p>Raising awareness:</p> <p>Raising awareness about plastic waste doesn't have to be complicated. Simple conversations and visible actions can make a meaningful difference. The goal is to help others understand the problem and inspire them to take small steps in their own lives.</p>

Start by bringing the topic into everyday conversations. Whether it's over dinner with your family or during a coffee break with friends or colleagues, discussing the social, economic, and environmental impacts of plastic waste can plant seeds for change among others.

Keep your message relevant with simple solutions, such as using reusable bags or containers. People are more likely to act when the information feels applicable and accessible to their daily lives.

In today's digital world, social media is a powerful tool. Share your own progress: Maybe you've already started using reusable coffee cups. Talk about it. These small stories can be inspiring for others. Visuals help, too: post photos of how much plastic waste you collected or avoided. For people who aren't yet aware, this kind of concrete example makes the issue more real.

Finally, remember that not everyone is motivated in the same way. While environmental reasons are powerful for some people, for others, financial incentives work better. So, highlight the personal benefits too. This can be saving money by buying in bulk or reusing your bags over and over again. When you connect the problem to real-life advantages, you make change feel not only important, but achievable.

Educate people:

Organizing workshops or events is a powerful way to educate people about **packaging** waste. These can be hands-on sessions where the participants learn practical skills such as how to store all your reusables.

Workshops can also include demonstrations that show how to make your own beeswax wraps for instance.

By bringing people together and organizing workshops and events, you can educate and empower people with skills. This could be the start of a bigger change. At the end of a workshop or event, you can collect ideas for future activities.

People are already finding creative ways to reuse packaging and reduce reliance on single-use materials through collaboration and smarter shopping.

One powerful approach is forming bulk buying teams. Members of the community come together to order large quantities of staples like rice, beans, flour, or oil directly from suppliers. By splitting the goods and the costs, everyone saves money and avoids unnecessary packaging in the process. However, coordinating orders and storage space can be a challenge, especially for those with limited space or irregular working schedules.

Another alternative is setting up a sharing or refill system. In this model, one person buys in bulk and serves as a kind of “refill station” for the others. Community members bring their own jars or containers and collect what they need. This not only reduces packaging but also fosters a stronger sense of local connection and cooperation. On the downside, the success of such a system depends on trust, availability, and consistent participation, which may not always be easy to maintain.

For those with access to farms or small-scale producers, buying directly from the source is another excellent way to cut down on packaging. Many farmers offer produce, dairy, or pantry items with minimal or no packaging. These options may not be feasible for people without access to a car or people living in rural

	<p>areas, and the timing of availability might not suit everyone's needs. If the location is far, teaming up and sharing the ride in one car helps keep both emissions and costs low.</p> <p>These alternative approaches show how reusing packaging can become part of a shared routine - one that benefits both people and the planet. With a little coordination, it's easy to turn sustainable practices into social, rewarding, and practical habits.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
E01: Interactive learning environments	<p>Link the participants to ILE based on system model.</p>
	<p>Ready to take another quiz? We are sure you learned enough through the past blocks to successfully pass this test!</p>

<p>E03: Quiz</p>	<p>Question 1. What is one of the main benefits of forming bulk buying teams? a. It helps individuals avoid going to the store. b. It reduces food variety. C. It increases single-use packaging usage. D. It allows members to save money and reduce packaging waste.</p> <p>Question 2. In a local refill system, what role does one person often play? a. They collect used packaging for recycling. b. They organize composting activities. c. They act as a refill station for the community. d. They deliver groceries door to door.</p> <p>Question 3. What can be a challenge associated with buying from farms? A. The food is usually over-packaged. B. Transportation and accessibility may be difficult. C. Farms only sell non-organic products. D. Farms operate only in winter</p>
<p>Choice of action</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will</p>

	a. Buy bulk together
Stage 3	
	<p>You feel like you're still missing hands-on advice? How to actually turn these solutions into reality. Learn more about practical applications through the next block.</p> <p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>
I01: Information provision (helping with planning)	<p>Bulk buying: a smart way to shop and protect the environment!</p> <p>Bulk buying is more than a clever shopping strategy – it's a growing movement rooted in community, sustainability, and mindful consumption. Whether you're stocking up on pasta, rice, or everyday essentials, buying in bulk can help reduce packaging waste, save money, and build stronger local networks.</p> <p>At its core, bulk buying means purchasing larger quantities of goods, often together with others. It's particularly common for non-perishable items like grains, legumes, nuts, flour, or even cheese and eggs.</p> <p>When several households share these purchases, there are several benefits: fewer single-use packages, reduced transport emissions, and lower costs per unit.</p>

Across neighbourhoods, friend groups, and eco-conscious communities, people are increasingly turning to bulk buying as a practical step toward reducing waste. The idea is simple: buy larger packages at once, split it fairly, and cut down on both packaging and unnecessary shopping trips.

Why is it effective?

Because most everyday products are typically sold in smaller quantities, each individually wrapped, they contribute significantly to the overall volume of packaging waste. Bulk purchasing not only eliminates many of these smaller packages but also allows for more efficient transportation and storage. Since you're often dealing with staple foods or household items that last, it's easy to plan ahead.

Some groups coordinate bulk buys informally, others set up neighbourhood chats or use digital tools to stay organised. In rural areas or cities with farmers' markets and refill shops, it's often possible to access large-format goods with minimal packaging or even none at all. Some farms and zero-waste stores actively support this model by offering discounts for bulk purchases or encouraging community-led refilling systems.

Beyond the products themselves, bulk buying is a way to:

- Share resources and strengthen community ties
- Make shopping more intentional and reduce impulse buying
- Support local suppliers and eco-conscious retailers
- Reduce reliance on plastic packaging and lower your carbon footprint

	<p>Of course, bulk buying isn't without its challenges. It requires a bit more planning, storage space, and coordination between participants. Some items are easier to split than others, and bulk formats may not be available everywhere. Still, many who try it find the benefits far outweigh the effort.</p> <p>Ultimately, bulk buying shows that small collective actions, such as teaming up with friends and people from your neighbourhood, can have a meaningful impact. It's not about doing everything perfectly, but about taking practical steps toward less waste, more community, and smarter consumption.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
	<p>Where can you find the resources you need in your hometown? Find out about local stores in the map.</p>
I03: Map	<p>Participants and project partners will locate places on the map.</p>
	<p>Let's get active and participate in a hands-on tutorial!</p>
E06: Tutorials	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p>

In this tutorial, we will get an overview about how we reduce packaging together by buying in bulk as this is reducing the total amount of packaging per person. You have got an overview of your own packaging footprint during the last sections by documenting your own packaging waste. With these experiences in mind, do the following:

1. Choose an item for which bulk buying makes sense. This can be quite individual. Often, dry products are good items to be shared among several people: pasta, flour, rice or cereal. You can also think about products, such as cheese or eggs, as they are usually much cheaper when bought in bulk.
2. Organize a bulk buying group: Find people in your community who would like to share products with you. If desired, you can also organize a shared bulk buying trip to decide on the products together. Otherwise, one household does grocery shopping.
3. After shopping, share the products and split the money. Be cautious about how you store these split-ups, e.g. bring containers to put pasta, rice etc. in after opening the big package.
4. Document the bought product(s) with a photo and upload it in the app.

Reflect on your experiences with others from the community. These questions can be guidelines. Remember, you don't have to answer all the questions one by one. We want to give you some starting points to help guide your reflection.

- What was surprisingly easy or difficult to find products that are suitable for bulk buying and share them with others?

	<p>- Compare your packaging waste in previous grocery trips with the one now: Did the amount of packaging decrease? For this, collect the overall packaging waste and estimate the total amount per person.</p> <p>- Bulk buying also offers financial advantages. When splitting the bill per person or household, can you spot a difference between single grocery trips and bulk buying? Take note of this financial difference.</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start buying in bulk together. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>
	<p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one of the main benefits of bulk buying?</p> <p>a. It increases individual packaging waste</p> <p>b. It reduces total packaging waste per person</p> <p>c. It limits your food options</p> <p>d. It makes shopping trips longer</p>

	<p>Question 2.</p> <p>Which types of products are typically well-suited for bulk buying?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Frozen meals and soda b. Fresh herbs and snacks c. Dry items like rice, pasta, or cereal d. Cosmetics and ready-to-eat salads <p>Question 3.</p> <p>What is one advantage of bulk buying besides packaging reduction?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Less space in your shelf b. Reduced food choices c. Financial savings when splitting costs d. Easier shopping for luxury items
	<p>We have collected some useful material for you in the following building block.</p>
<p>T02: External tools</p>	<p>Partners can include helpful links to support people buying in bulk together</p> <p><i>Norway:</i></p> <p><i>Germany:</i></p> <p><i>Latvia:</i></p>

	UK:
Stage 4	
E04: Smart bin analysis	The purpose of this building block at this stage is to provide individuals with real-time feedback on their plastic packaging.
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants the LCA questions.
T01: Habit tracker	Will be provided if available and useful. <i>... Input from the partners</i>
	We can't believe you finished this big community challenge on packaging, you are amazing! Would you like to share your story? What have you learned? Have there been moments that were challenging? Reflect on your experience in the next and last task.
S04: Circular story task	Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge. They are encouraged to reflect on the barriers, motivations, and possible outcomes of their new behaviour. In addition, they can give tips to other participants.
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Table 29: Framework for the individual electronic challenges

Building block	Challenge 1 individual Challenge: Reduce buying electronics Alternative behaviour: a. Audit of your electronic devices b. Maintain your electronic devices	Challenge 2 individual Challenge: Repair broken electronics Alternative behaviour: a. Repair one of your broken electronics
Question for the stage analysis	Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about reducing buying electronics? -I am not sure why I should reduce buying electronics (stage 1) -I know why it is important to reduce buying electronics, but I do not know exactly what I can do (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already doing regular audits of my electronic devices (stage 4)	Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about repairing your broken electronics? -I am not sure why I should reuse my electronics (stage 1) -I know why it is important to reuse my electronics, but I do not know exactly what I can do (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already repairing my broken electronics (stage 4)

	-I am already maintaining the electronic devices I have (stage 4)	
Stage 1		
	<p>Welcome to the electronics challenge! First; you will read a text about e-waste and how e-waste affects not only our planet but also people, particularly in the Global South.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>	
I01: Information provision (why current behavior is problematic)	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-waste refers to discarded electronic devices, categorized into Used Electrical and Electronic Equipment (UEEE), which is functional or repairable and Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), which is non-functional waste. • In 2022, the EU had 14.4 million tonnes of electronics on the market, with 5 million tonnes of e-waste collected. • Incorrect e-waste disposal releases toxic and harmful materials, polluting the environment and posing health risks, especially in the Global South. • A huge amount of WEEE is illegally exported to the Global South. 	

- Due to fast technological advancements, devices that are still functional are often replaced by consumers. As a result, a lot of smaller electronic devices are stored at home or thrown away instead of being repaired or recycled.

Electronic waste, or e-waste refers to discarded electronic devices such as computers, phones, televisions and other electronics used by consumers. These devices can be categorized into two types:

Used Electrical and Electronic Equipment (UEEE), devices that are still functional or need minor repairs before reuse

Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), devices that no longer work and are considered waste

Some statistics

In 2022, the European Union had 14.4 million tonnes of electronics on the market. Out of this, 5 million tonnes of e-waste were collected, which is an average of 11.3 kg per person. Furthermore, e-waste is the world's fastest-growing waste stream. Only about 15% of the world's e-waste is recycled, leading to illegal dumping.

Risks of e-waste

Many people don't know the risks of improper e-waste disposal and often discard items that could be reused or repaired. E-waste can cause serious problems due to its impact on the environment and health. Improper disposal of WEEE releases toxic and harmful materials like heavy metals and toxic chemicals, which pollute the environment such as the soil and water and accumulate in living organisms, affecting our ecosystems. Additionally, e-waste also releases greenhouse gases during the manufacturing and disposal processes.

	<p>Informal recycling practices such as open burning and acid bathing remain widespread and harmful, especially in the Global South. Workers are exposed to toxic and harmful substances, leading to severe health issues such as respiratory problems, neurological damage, and cancers.</p> <p>Illegal export</p> <p>Furthermore, WEEE is often illegally exported to the Global South to avoid disposal costs. The fast-changing technology drives consumers to replace electronic and electrical equipment (EEE) even when they are still working perfectly.</p> <p>Stored at home</p> <p>Many replaced small EEE devices are stored at home because people think they might need them again or in case a device breaks, instead of being reused by others or recycled. Small EEE devices, are rarely repaired and often discarded immediately when they break.</p> <p>Overconsumption at households</p> <p>Household electronics affected by overconsumption include kitchen appliances (coffee machines, blenders, toasters, microwaves, air fryers), entertainment devices (TVs, gaming consoles, smart speakers, tablets), cleaning devices (vacuum cleaners, robotic cleaners, air purifiers), personal use items (hairdryers, electric toothbrushes, shavers, straighteners), but also smart home devices (smart lights, digital assistants, smart thermostats).</p>
	<p>You're done reading, good job! Hopefully, you have gained a lot of new information.</p> <p>You're now invited to watch some interesting videos on the topic to further deepen your knowledge.</p>

<p>I02: Videos</p>	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
<p>I01: Information provision (on what others already do)</p>	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many household items are used only occasionally and can be shared instead of owned. • Items can be shared informally among neighbours or via organised online platforms. • Ethical brands support long-term use and fair production. • Companies offer short-term rentals for expensive or rarely used items, though sustainability may vary. <p>Ethical brands</p> <p>Supporting ethical brands offering electronic devices can make a big difference. These companies focus on modular, repairable designs, fair working conditions, and sustainable materials, helping reduce e-waste while promoting responsible consumption.</p> <p>Sharing</p> <p>Many everyday items are only used occasionally. Instead of buying and storing them, more and more people</p>

are turning to the idea of sharing. While shared mobility (e.g. car or bike sharing) is already well established, the sharing of household items is still less common but slightly gaining popularity.

Privately, sharing often happens in neighbourhoods, on campsites, in student housing, or through local libraries. People lend each other tools, games, sports gear, or electronics—usually for free or a small fee. Sometimes a deposit is required, which is refunded upon return of the item in good condition.

Online platforms are also making it easier to share. Websites and classified ads allow individuals to rent out items like hiking gear, e-bikes, or drones for a fee. These platforms offer a wide selection and flexible rental periods, though users must handle agreements directly with the lender.

Commercial providers have also entered the market, offering rental models for high-cost electronics like smartphones or cameras. This allows users to test or use expensive items for a short time without buying them. Some companies even offer the option to purchase the item after renting. However, these models often prioritise profit over sustainability, as damaged items are quickly replaced with new ones, which can undermine the environmental benefits of sharing.

To sum up

Sharing everyday items—whether privately, via platforms, or commercially—can save money, reduce clutter, and support more sustainable consumption habits. If you have old electronic devices you no longer use, there are several platforms where you can either sell or share them, helping to reduce e-waste and promote reuse.

Good job with reading the texts! Now, after gaining all this knowledge, let's get active with an “experimental learning task”.

The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don't feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!

<p>E02: Experiential learning task</p> <p>S02: Circular story preparation task</p>	<p>Task:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have a look at your kitchen. 2. Select one kitchen device that you use frequently within your household (e.g., a blender, a coffee machine, a toaster) 3. Inspect the device carefully for any signs of damage 4. Find the manual. No worries if you have lost it or thrown it away, you often find them online. If you cannot find the manual, choose another device. 5. What maintenance does your device need? Clean and take care of your device according to the manufacturer's instructions to ensure it lasts longer. 	<p>Task:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have a look at your cupboards and collect all the phones/computers you have stored at home. 2. Take a picture of them <p>Take a few minutes to think about the following questions. Write down your thoughts and discuss them with your family members. Remember, you don't have to answer all the questions one by one. We want to give you some starting points to help guide your reflection.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Why do you buy new phones/computers? Is it because your phone/computer is broken? Is it because your phone/computer is outdated? Are you easily influenced by new features or trends?
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	<p>6. Reflect on this task by answering some of the following questions. Remember, you don't have to answer all the questions one by one. We want to give you some starting points to help guide your reflection.</p> <p>Have you ever looked at the instructions before? Do you regularly take care of your devices? If yes, how? If not, why not?</p> <p>7. Take a picture of the device you maintained during this task. If cleaning made a real difference even taking "before" and "after"-pictures might be fun.</p> <p>8. Save your reflections for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>	<p>How?</p> <p>Are you influenced by friends or family? How?</p> <p>4. How often do you buy a new phone/computer?</p> <p>5. What do you do with the old phone/computer? Recycle, sell or store it at home?</p> <p>6. What changes are you willing to make in your family to be more sustainable when it comes to buying new phones/computers? Can you extend the life of your current phone/computer by repairing it when it breaks? Do you know where to repair it? Are you willing to buy a refurbished phone/computer? Are you willing to recycle your phone/computer properly? If yes, find out where to recycle them in your neighbourhood.</p> <p>7. Save your reflections for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>
E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the electronic challenge.	

E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>How much e-waste was collected in the EU in 2022?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) 14.4 million tonnes b) 11.3 million tonnes c) 5 million tonnes <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is a major environmental risk of improper e-waste disposal?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Loss of electronic components b) Release of toxic substances like heavy metals and chemicals. c) Increased resource recovery <p>Question 3.</p> <p>Which country is the largest destination for global e-waste?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) India b) China c) USA <p>Question 4.</p> <p>Which of the following is a consequence of informal e-waste recycling?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) It contributes to efficient recycling processes.

	<p>b) It reduces the amount of e-waste shipped overseas.</p> <p>c) It exposes workers to harmful substances, leading to health risks.</p>	
Commitment to the challenge	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to reduce buying electronics:</p> <p>a. yes</p> <p>b. no</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to repair (one of) my broken electronics</p> <p>a. yes</p> <p>b. no</p>
Stage 2		
I01: Information provision (alternative behaviours, advantages and disadvantages)	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain existing devices to extend the life of a product and reduce waste and resource consumption. • Reuse devices to extend their lifespan and reduce the amount of e-waste generated, promoting a more sustainable economy • Choose high-quality, durable electronics that have a longer lifespan and are less likely to need frequent replacement. 	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling e-waste recovers valuable metals and plastics, reducing the need for mining and lowering the environmental footprint • Recycling processes can be expensive and require a significant amount of energy, which may hinder widespread implementation • Recycling prevents the release of hazardous substances into the environment, safeguarding ecosystems and human health

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use multi-purpose devices (e.g., using an oven instead of buying an air fryer) to reduce the number of electronics needed. • Engage in electronic-sharing platforms, such as tool libraries or borrowing from neighbours, to minimize the need for personal ownership of rarely used devices. • Purchase refurbished or second-hand electronics instead of new ones to extend the life cycle of existing products and reduce e-waste. <p>There are different strategies for consumers to reduce the purchase of electronic devices:</p> <p>Keep and use electronics</p> <p>The best thing to do is to keep and use your electronics for as long as possible. By maintaining and take care of your existing devices, you will extend the life of a product, reduce waste and conserve resources.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe recycling practices prevent workers from being exposed to toxic chemicals and heavy metals • Repairing devices extends their lifespan and reduces the amount of e-waste generated, promoting a more sustainable economy <p>Recycle and reuse</p> <p>Recycling and reusing electronic devices can extend their lifespan and reduce e-waste, supporting a more circular economy. Proper recycling practices also protect workers from exposure to toxic and harmful chemicals and heavy metals, ensuring their health and safety. Furthermore, recycling e-waste helps recover valuable materials, reducing the need for mining and preventing harmful substances from entering the environment.</p> <p>Repairing</p> <p>Repairing electronic devices prevents them from becoming e-waste which reduces the amount of e-waste ending up in landfills. By repairing and reusing</p>
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	<p>Buy high-quality and durable products Investing in high-quality, durable products can also help extend their lifespan, reducing the need for frequent replacements of electronics.</p> <p>Be creative and use multi-purpose devices Using multi-purpose devices, such as an oven instead of an air fryer, minimizes the need for multiple electronics in your household.</p> <p>Sharing electronics Participating in electronic-sharing platforms, like tool libraries or borrowing from neighbours, saves money on rarely used devices and reduces the need for storage space.</p> <p>Second-hand electronics Choosing refurbished or second-hand electronics is another effective strategy. It is cheaper than buying new devices, extends the product lifespan, and has a lower environmental impact.</p>	<p>the electronic devices we have, we reduce the need for new raw materials, which conserves natural resources and reduces the impact of mining. Furthermore, we reduce the carbon emissions when producing new electronics.</p> <p>Challenges of repairing Despite the clear benefits of repairing electronics, some challenges exist. Professional repair services can be expensive for some devices. Unfortunately, replacing a product is sometimes more convenient and cheaper than repairing it. Furthermore, not all devices are designed to be repairable and there might be limited access to spare parts.</p>
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	<p>Be aware</p> <p>It is important to be aware of the influence of social media on the purchase intentions of customers. Fear of missing out (FOMO) on new technology creates pressure, especially through social media.</p>	
	<p>Want to learn more about behavioural alternatives? Let's watch some short and fun videos.</p>	
<p>I02: Videos</p>	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
<p>E01: Interactive learning environments</p>	<p>Link the participants to ILE based on system model.</p>	
	<p>Ready to take another quiz? We are sure you learned enough through the past blocks to successfully pass this test!</p>	

<p>E03: Quiz</p>	<p>Question 1. What is a key benefit of repairing and maintaining existing devices? a) It increases electronic waste. b) It extends the product's lifespan and reduces waste. c) It always costs more than buying new.</p> <p>Question 2. What is the potential downside of using electronic-sharing platforms? a) It eliminates the need for agreements with others. b) It always guarantees product availability. c) It might require organization and responsibility for repairs.</p> <p>Question 3. What is a common feature of Fairphone and Shiftphones? a) They are designed for long-term use and repairability.</p>	<p>Question 1: What is a key benefit of repairing and maintaining existing devices? a) It increases electronic waste. b) It extends the product's lifespan and reduces waste. c) It always costs more than buying new.</p> <p>Question 2. What is the potential downside of using electronic-sharing platforms? a) It eliminates the need for agreements with others. b) It always guarantees product availability. c) It might require organization and responsibility for repairs.</p>
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	<p>b) They are disposable and hard to repair.</p> <p>c) They do not focus on sustainability.</p>	
Choice of action	<p>For the next three weeks, I will reduce buying electronics by:</p> <p>a. Doing an audit of my electronic devices</p> <p>b. Maintain my electronic devices</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>a. Try to repair one of my broken electronics</p>
Stage 3		
	<p>You feel like you're still missing hands-on advice? How to actually turn these solutions into reality. Learn more about practical applications through the next block.</p> <p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>	
I01: Information provision (helping with planning)	<p>To conduct an electronics audit, you can make a list or a picture of all or some of the electronic devices in your household. To keep control it is useful to note the year of purchase, the frequency of use, the condition of the device, and the reason for disuse.</p>	<p>Intro</p> <p>Repairing electronic devices plays a key role in reducing e-waste and support a more environmental lifestyle.</p>

	<p>Furthermore, you can identify electronic devices in your household that can be sold, donated, shared, or recycled.</p> <p>If you want to buy a new electronic device, you can make use of the Five W's of Consumer Decision-Making:</p> <p>Who?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who in my household will use it? <p>What?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do I need? • What alternatives exist (e.g., repairing, renting, second-hand, doing without)? • What are the environmental and social impacts of this product? <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where is the most ethical or sustainable place to buy it? 	<p>Repair cafes</p> <p>Repair cafes are community spaces where people come together to repair. The good think about a repair café is that the tools and materials available, so you don't have to take them with you. Repair cafes often work with volunteers, who are often experts in repairing small appliances are available to assist you when needed. Try to find out where your nearest repair café is.</p> <p>Repair yourself</p> <p>With the help of different websites and Youtube videos, you can get access to knowledge to get a better understanding of how your electronic devices work, how to maintain them, and even how you may fix some basic repairs yourself. However, keep in mind that repairing your own devices comes with a risk. Always unplug the electronic device beforehand and make sure you are well-informed. If you are not an expert and the issue seems to complicated, try to seek advice from others with more experience, visit a repair café, or call</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where can I find a high-quality second-hand or refurbished option? • Where will I store this device at home—do I even have space for it? • Where will it go when I no longer need it (e.g., recycling, donation, landfill)? <p>When?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When will I use this device, and how often? • When did I last buy a similar product, and do I really need an upgrade? <p>Why?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why do I need to buy this, and is it necessary? • Do I feel pressured to buy this (advertising, social trends, FOMO)? • Can I wait few weeks and see if I still feel the need to buy it? 	<p>in a professional to repair items that are not produced for home repair.</p> <p>Professional repairer</p> <p>There are many professional repairers who can fix both your smaller and larger broken electronic appliances. Ask your friends, neighbours, or community website where to find a reliable and local professional repairer. In addition, professional repairers often sell replacements parts when you want to repair something yourself.</p>
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	By asking these questions, you can make a more thoughtful and sustainable choice, reducing the impulse to buy new electronics and contributing to a decrease in e-waste.	
	Want to learn more about behavioural alternatives? Let's watch some short and fun videos.	
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
	Where can you find the resources you need in your hometown? Find out about local stores in the map.	
I03: Map	Places on the map are provided by participants and project partners.	
	Let's get active and participate in a hands-on tutorial!	
E06: Tutorials	**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**	**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**

	<p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to reduce buying electronics.</p> <p>Goal: Reduce unnecessary electronic purchases by conducting an electronics audit, questioning new purchases, and extending the life of existing devices.</p> <p>Step 1: Conduct an Electronics Audit (Inventory)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Make a List: Create a list or collection of all or some of your electronic devices in your household, including phones, laptops, kitchen appliances, etc. 2. Note Details: Select one or more items, and try to remember the year of purchase, frequency of use, condition (working, partly broken, unused), and the reason for disuse (if any). 3. Identify Redundancies: Identify duplicate or rarely used items that can be sold, donated, or shared. 	<p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to repair electronics.</p> <p>Goal: Extend the life of your equipment by repairing it yourself - to save money, reduce e-waste and support sustainability.</p> <p>Step 1: Take stock of what you have</p> <p>Go through your home and collect broken or unused items such as phones, headphones, remote controls and kitchen appliances.</p> <p>Choose 2-3 items to start with.</p> <p>Look for problems such as frayed cables, weak batteries or inoperable buttons.</p> <p>Step 2: Clean before repair</p> <p>Use a microfibre cloth and a little isopropyl alcohol to clean surfaces.</p> <p>Clean vents and connections with a small brush or compressed air.</p> <p>Remove battery corrosion with vinegar or a baking soda paste.</p>
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	<p>Step 2: Apply the Five W's Before Purchasing a New Item</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Who Needs It: Determine who in your household will use this device and consider if you could borrow or share it instead. 2. What do I need: Assess what problem the device solves, explore alternatives like repairing or buying second-hand, and evaluate the long-term benefits and drawbacks. 3. Where to Buy: Find the most ethical or sustainable place to purchase the device, look for refurbished options, and consider the labour conditions where it was manufactured. 4. When to Buy: Reflect on when you will really use the device, whether you truly need it now 5. Why Buy: Question the necessity of the purchase, whether it's driven by external 	<p>Step 3: Get ready Gather the essentials: a set of screwdrivers, a multimeter and small trays for screws. Use iFixit for tools, parts and device-specific repair guides.</p> <p>Step 4: Set up your work area Use a clean, well-lit table with plenty of space. Lay out the tools and parts you will need. Use bowls or trays to keep screws and components organised. Consider taking photos during disassembly to help with reassembly.</p> <p>Step 5: Start repairing - step by step Start with simple repairs such as replacing batteries, cables or plugs. Use a multimeter to check that power is flowing. Follow iFixit's step-by-step guides.</p> <p>Step 6: Finish and document Test the unit to make sure it works. Put it back together and tighten all the screws.</p>
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	<p>pressures such as advertising and consider waiting a few weeks to reassess the need.</p> <p>Step 3: Raise Awareness and Build Habits</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Share Your Audit: Discuss your electronics audit with family or friends to raise awareness about consumption habits. 2. Discuss Influences: Talk about the impact of advertising, planned obsolescence, and the environmental consequences of e-waste at home. 3. Set a Rule: Implement a 30-day waiting period before making any non-essential tech purchases to avoid impulse buying. <p>By following these steps, you can make a more informed decision, reduce unnecessary electronic purchases, and contribute to a more sustainable lifestyle.</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to reduce buying electronics. While</p>	<p>Make a note of what worked and what did not, what equipment is now functional, and what should be recycled or kept for parts.</p> <p>Step 7: Final notes</p> <p>If a repair is not possible, dispose of the equipment at an e-waste centre.</p> <p>Share your repair successes with friends.</p> <p>Keep your tools well organised for next time.</p> <p>By following these steps, you can effectively repair and maintain your electronic equipment, reduce e-waste and promote sustainability.</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start creating a shopping list and a meal plan. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>
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	<p>our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>	
<p>E03: Quiz</p>	<p>Question 1. What is one key benefit of repairing electronic devices instead of discarding them? a) It increases the need for new products. b) It reduces the need for new products and decreases e-waste. c) It leads to faster technological advancements.</p> <p>Question 2. What should consumers do to ensure their e-waste is handled in an environmentally responsible way? a) Dispose of it in regular trash bins. b) Send it to certified recycling centres. c) Sell it to non-certified scrap dealers.</p> <p>Question 3. What is an important question to ask when</p>	<p>Question 1. What is the main goal of iFixit? a) Selling new electronic devices b) Encouraging repair to reduce e-waste c) Promoting disposable technology</p> <p>Question 2. Why should you clean electronic devices before repairing them? a) To improve ventilation and avoid damage from dust or corrosion b) To make them look nicer after the repair c) To remove fingerprints for better grip</p> <p>Question 3. Which tool is commonly used to check if a device has an electrical issue?</p>

	<p>considering purchasing a new electronic device?</p> <p>a) How much will this device cost me in the long run?</p> <p>b) Can I share or borrow this device from someone else instead of buying it?</p> <p>c) What are the sales and discounts available for this product?</p> <p>Question 4.</p> <p>Which of the following is a key consideration when evaluating the environmental and social impacts of a product?</p> <p>a) Where was this product manufactured, and what are the labour conditions?</p> <p>b) What is the total weight of the device?</p> <p>c) What is the device's colour or design?</p>	<p>a) Hammer</p> <p>b) Glue gun</p> <p>c) Multimeter</p> <p>Question 4.</p> <p>What should you do if a device cannot be repaired?</p> <p>a) Keep it for spare parts or dispose of it properly</p> <p>b) Throw it in the regular household waste</p> <p>c) Store it indefinitely without deciding what to do</p>
T02: External tools	Partners can include helpful links to support people in how to repair electronic devices, where to find repairers, how to take care of electronic devices	

	<p><i>Norway:</i> Naturvernforbundet.no : ta være på det du her Naturvernforbundet.no: Finn en reparatør</p> <p><i>Germany:</i></p> <p><i>Latvia:</i></p> <p><i>UK:</i></p>
Stage 4	
E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the electronic challenge.
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
T01: Habit tracker	Will be provided if available and useful. <i>... Input from the partners</i>
	Wow, you nailed it! You finished an entire challenge of the CircleUp project! What did you learn, what was interesting or challenging? Reflect on your experiences in the “Circular story task”.

S04: Circular story task	Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge
Sources used for this challenge	<p>An, J., & Ahn, J. (2025). the role of customer fear of missing out on purchase intention. <i>Current Issues in Tourism</i>, 28(6), 863-870.</p> <p>Cheshmeh, Z. A., Bigverdi, Z., Eqbalpour, M., Kowsari, E., Ramakrishna, S., & Gheibi, M. (2023). A comprehensive review of used electrical and electronic equipment management with a focus on the circular economy-based policy-making. <i>Journal of cleaner production</i>, 389, 136132. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136132</p> <p>Pérez-Belis, V., Braulio-Gonzalo, M., Juan, P., & Bovea, M. D. (2017). Consumer attitude towards the repair and the second-hand purchase of small household electrical and electronic equipment. A Spanish case study. <i>Journal of cleaner production</i>, 158, 261-275. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.04.143</p> <p>Ramírez Restrepo, A., & Baars, R. (2025). A comprehensive systematic review in e-waste studies: themes beyond metrics. <i>International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology</i>, 1-28.</p> <p>Sonego, M., Echeveste, M. E. S., & Debarba, H. G. (2022). Repair of electronic products: Consumer practices and institutional initiatives. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i>, 30, 556-565. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.12.031</p>

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| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/waste-electrical-and-electronic-equipment-weee_en• https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c4gvq1rd0geo• https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en/topics/waste-resources/product-stewardship-waste-management/electrical-electronic-waste#current-problems-• https://shop.fairphone.com/• https://shop.shiftphones.com/• https://frame.work/de/de• https://www.verbraucherzentrale.de/wissen/umwelt-haushalt/abfall/elektroschrott-diese-geraete-und-gegenstaende-gehoren-ins-recycling-12861• https://www.ifixit.com/ |
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Table 30: Framework for the community electronics challenges

Building block	Challenge 1 community:	Challenge 2 community:
Questions for the stage analysis	<p>Reuse electronics:</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <p>Organize a community sharing system for electronic devices</p> <p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about organizing activities with others to reuse electronics?</p> <p>-I am not sure why I should do things together with others to reuse electronics (stage 1)</p> <p>-I know why it is important to do things together with others to reuse electronics, but I do not know what to do (stage 2)</p> <p>-I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3)</p> <p>-I am already organizing a community sharing system for electronic devices (stage 4)</p>	<p>Reuse electronics:</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <p>Organize an electronic swap event</p> <p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about organizing activities with others to reuse electronics?</p> <p>-I am not sure why I should do things together with others to reuse electronics (stage 1)</p> <p>-I know why it is important to do things together with others to reuse electronics, but I do not know what to do (stage 2)</p> <p>-I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3)</p> <p>-I am already organizing an electronic swap event with others (stage 4)</p>

	<p>Welcome to the community electronics challenge! Are you motivated to address e-waste related challenges together with others in your community? Then you're in the right place! Let's get started with a short introduction.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>	
Stage 1		
	<p>Welcome to the electronics challenge! First, you will read a text about e-waste and how e-waste affects not only our planet but also people, particularly in the Global South.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>	
I01: Information provision (why current behaviour is problematic)	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-waste refers to discarded electronic devices, categorized into Used Electrical and Electronic Equipment (UEEE), which is functional or repairable and Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), which is non-functional waste. • In 2022, the EU had 14.4 million tonnes of electronics on the market, with 5 million tonnes of e-waste collected. • Incorrect e-waste disposal releases toxic and harmful materials, polluting the environment and posing health risks, especially in the Global South. 	

- A huge amount of WEEE is illegally exported to the Global South.
- Due to fast technological advancements, devices that are still functional are often replaced by consumers. As a result, a lot of smaller electronic devices are stored at home or thrown away instead of being repaired or recycled.

Electronic waste, or e-waste refers to discarded electronic devices such as computers, phones, televisions and other electronics used by consumers. These devices can be categorized into two types:

Used Electrical and Electronic Equipment (UEEE), devices that are still functional or need minor repairs before reuse

Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), devices that no longer work and are considered waste

Some statistics

In 2022, the European Union had 14.4 million tonnes of electronics on the market. Out of this, 5 million tonnes of e-waste were collected, which is an average of 11.3 kg per person. Furthermore, e-waste is the world's fastest-growing waste stream. Only about 15% of the world's e-waste is recycled, leading to illegal dumping.

Risks of e-waste

Many people don't know the risks of improper e-waste disposal and often discard items that could be reused or repaired. E-waste can cause serious problems due to its impact on the environment and health. Improper disposal of WEEE releases toxic and harmful materials like heavy metals and toxic chemicals, which pollute

the environment such as the soil and water and accumulate in living organisms, affecting our ecosystems. Additionally, e-waste also releases greenhouse gases during the manufacturing and disposal processes.

Informal recycling practices such as open burning and acid bathing remain widespread and harmful, especially in the Global South. Workers are exposed to toxic and harmful substances, leading to severe health issues such as respiratory problems, neurological damage, and cancers.

Illegal export

Furthermore, WEEE is often illegally exported to the Global South to avoid disposal costs. The fast-changing technology drives consumers to replace electronic and electrical equipment (EEE) even when they are still working perfectly.

Stored at home

Many replaced small EEE devices are stored at home because people think they might need them again or in case a device breaks, instead of being reused by others or recycled. Small EEE devices, are rarely repaired and often discarded immediately when they break.

Overconsumption at households

Household electronics affected by overconsumption include kitchen appliances (coffee machines, blenders, toasters, microwaves, air fryers), entertainment devices (TVs, gaming consoles, smart speakers, tablets), cleaning devices (vacuum cleaners, robotic cleaners, air purifiers), personal use items (hairdryers, electric toothbrushes, shavers, straighteners), but also smart home devices (smart lights, digital assistants, smart thermostats).

	<p>You're done reading, good job! Hopefully, you have gained a lot of new information.</p> <p>You're now invited to watch some interesting videos on the topic to further deepen your knowledge.</p>
<p>I02: Videos</p>	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
	<p>As you have seen, e-waste is a pressing problem. What has already been done to address this issue? This is what you'll find out through reading the next text.</p>
<p>I01: Information provision (on what others already do)</p>	<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many household items are used only occasionally and can be shared instead of owned. • Items can be shared informally among neighbours or via organised online platforms. • Ethical brands support long-term use and fair production. • Companies offer short-term rentals for expensive or rarely used items, though sustainability may vary.

Ethical brands

Supporting ethical brands offering electronic devices can make a big difference. These companies focus on modular, repairable designs, fair working conditions, and sustainable materials, helping reduce e-waste while promoting responsible consumption.

Sharing

Many everyday items are only used occasionally. Instead of buying and storing them, more and more people are turning to the idea of sharing. While shared mobility (e.g. car or bike sharing) is already well established, the sharing of household items is still growing but slightly gaining popularity.

Privately, sharing often happens in neighbourhoods, on campsites, in student housing, or through local libraries. People lend each other tools, games, sports gear, or electronics—usually for free or a small fee. Sometimes a deposit is required, which is refunded upon return of the item in good condition.

Online platforms are also making it easier to share. Websites and classified ads allow individuals to rent out items like hiking gear, e-bikes, or drones for a fee. These platforms offer a wide selection and flexible rental periods, though users must handle agreements directly with the lender.

Commercial providers have also entered the market, offering rental models for high-cost electronics like smartphones or cameras. This allows users to test or use expensive items for a short time without buying them. Some companies even offer the option to purchase the item after renting. However, these models often prioritise profit over sustainability, as damaged items are quickly replaced with new ones, which can undermine the environmental benefits of sharing.

	<p>To sum up</p> <p>Sharing everyday items—whether privately, via platforms, or commercially—can save money, reduce clutter, and support more sustainable consumption habits. If you have old electronics you no longer use, there are several platforms where you can either sell or share them, helping to reduce e-waste and promote reuse.</p>	
	<p>Good job with reading the texts! Now, after gaining all this knowledge, let's get active with an “experimental learning task”.</p> <p>The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don't feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!</p>	
<p>E02: Experimental learning task</p> <p>S02: Circular story preparation task</p>	<p>Task:</p> <p>1. Think about an electronic appliance that you are planning to buy in the near future (e.g. a blender, power bank, or speakers).</p>	<p>Task:</p> <p>1. Have a look at your electronic devices and remove one old or rarely used device from your household, such as a toaster, power bank, or headphones.</p>

	<p>2. Research a sharing platform or neighbourhood solution in your country.</p> <p>3. Imagine you will borrow or rent the item</p> <p>4. How would that feel for you?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will it be easy? • Will you save money or space? <p>5. Save the pictures and your reflection or drawing for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>	<p>2. Decide whether you want to keep it or pass it on. Consider the following questions: Is the device still working or does it need to be repaired? Do you have some sentimental attachment to it, or is it just taking up space in your house or apartment? Would you prefer to get money from it and sell it?</p> <p>3. Try to find an online platform to give it away, share, or sell your appliance with someone from the neighbourhood.</p> <p>4. Take a picture from the appliance (and the new owner).</p> <p>5. Save the pictures and your reflection or drawing for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>
E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the electronic challenge	

E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.	
	We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What does e-waste refer to?</p> <p>a) Devices that are no longer in use but can be repaired.</p> <p>b) Only electrical appliances such as fridges and microwaves.</p> <p>c) Discarded electronic devices, which can be either functional or non-functional.</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>How much e-waste was collected in the EU in 2022?</p> <p>a) 14.4 million tonnes</p> <p>b) 11.3 million tonnes</p> <p>c) 5 million tonnes</p>	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What are the six categories of e-waste for effective recycling?</p> <p>a) Household, mobile, IT equipment, lighting, consumer, and recycling tools.</p> <p>b) Large appliances, IT equipment, communication devices, lighting, small appliances, and tools.</p> <p>c) Large household appliances, small household appliances, IT and telecommunications equipment, consumer equipment, lighting, and electrical tools.</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is a key benefit of proper e-waste disposal?</p> <p>a) It helps to manufacture more devices.</p>

	<p>Question 3. What is a major environmental risk of improper e-waste disposal?</p> <p>a) Loss of electronic components b) Release of toxic substances like heavy metals and chemicals. c) Increased resource recovery</p> <p>Question 4. Which country is the largest destination for global e-waste?</p> <p>a) India b) China c) USA</p>	<p>b) It reduces pollution and recovers valuable materials. c) It encourages the development of new e-waste management companies.</p> <p>Question 3. What is a disadvantage of proper e-waste recycling?</p> <p>a) It can be costly and energy intensive. b) It leads to more environmental harm than benefits. c) It makes electronics harder to repair.</p> <p>Question 4. Why is repairing electronics considered a sustainable action?</p> <p>A) It increases the product's resale value B) It extends the product's life and reduces waste C) It makes electronics look newer and more modern</p>
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Commitment to the challenge:	For the next three weeks, I will try to share electronic devices with others and organize an electronic swap event. a. yes be. no	For the next three weeks, I will try to share electronic devices with others and organize a repair event or café. a. yes be. no
Stage 2		
	Do you want to inspire others to take action to reduce buying electronic devices? We will tell you a bit more about it in the next step.	
I01: Information provision (alternative behaviours, advantages and disadvantages)	<p>Going beyond the individual level</p> <p>Reducing e-waste requires a collaborative effort from different groups in our society, including individual consumers, electronics manufacturers, retailers, recycling companies, and governments. Each group has a role to play in creating a more just and environmentally sound system, from a local to a global level.</p> <p>Households can make a change by properly disposing of broken electronics, repair instead of buying, and support recycling programs. Retailers can offer recycling services, and encourage people to buy eco-friendly and ethical products. Finally, policymakers can make stricter regulations to manage e-waste, support recycling initiatives, and raise awareness through big campaigns.</p>	

During this challenge, we encourage you to go a step further and inspire others to take action by engaging with the community.

There are different ways to engage within your broader community:

Raising awareness:

Raising awareness about e-waste and the environmental and health risks and the importance of recycling and reusing electronics doesn't have to be complicated. Simple conversations and visible actions can make a meaningful difference. By understanding the consequences of improper e-waste management, people can make informed decisions that support sustainability and reduce ecological harm. The goal is to help others understand the problem and inspire them to take small steps in their own lives. Start by bringing the topic into everyday conversations. Whether it's over dinner with your family or during a coffee break with friends or colleagues, discussing the social, economic, and environmental impacts of e-waste can plant seeds for change among others.

Keep your message relevant with simple solutions, such as maintaining the electronic devices you have or recycling them at the end of their life-cycle instead of storing them at home. People are more likely to act when the information feels applicable and accessible to their daily lives.

In today's digital world, social media is a powerful tool. Share your own progress: Maybe you've already started repairing your electronic devices. Talk about it. These small stories can inspire others.

Finally, remember that not everyone is motivated in the same way. While environmental reasons are powerful for some people, for others, financial incentives work better. So, highlight the personal benefits as well. This can be saving money by taking care of your devices or sharing some electronics with others. When you connect the problem to real-life advantages, you make change feel not only important, but achievable.

Educate people:

Organizing workshops or events is a powerful way to educate people about e-waste. These can be hands-on sessions where the participants learn practical skills such as taking care of their devices. Workshops can also include demonstrations. By bringing people together and organizing workshops and events, you can educate and empower people with skills. This could be the start of a bigger change. At the end of a workshop or event, you can collect ideas for future activities.

Community engagement:

By carrying out practices in the local community, you can empower other individuals or groups to take action. Try to get into dialogue with other interest groups. You can join local initiatives, that are i.e. setting up an electronic sharing program where community members can exchange electronics for the garden for instance. You can also collaborate with local organizations such as NGOs working towards a more sustainable world. You can be part of a public event focusing on e-waste. Finally, you can engage with the local government by starting petitions to initiate policy changes or participate in forums or public consultations. Let your voice be heard.

I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
E01: Interactive learning environments	Link the participants to ILE based on system model.	
	<p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is a potential drawback of using electronic-sharing platforms?</p> <p>a) Saves money on rarely used devices</p>	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is a key benefit of repairing and maintaining existing devices?</p> <p>a) It increases electronic waste.</p> <p>b) It extends the product's lifespan and reduces</p>

	<p>b) No need for storage space</p> <p>c) Availability might be limited</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is an advantage of buying refurbished or second-hand electronics?</p> <p>a) Unlimited warranty</p> <p>b) Lower environmental impact</p> <p>c) Wider selection of models compared to new devices</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>What is the potential downside of using electronic-sharing platforms?</p> <p>a) It eliminates the need for agreements with others.</p> <p>b) It always guarantees product availability.</p> <p>c) It might require organization and responsibility for repairs.</p>	<p>waste.</p> <p>c) It always costs more than buying new.</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>Which of the following is NOT a benefit of repairing electronic devices instead of replacing them?</p> <p>a) Extends the product's lifespan</p> <p>b) Reduces waste and resource consumption</p> <p>c) Always costs less than buying new</p>
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Choice of action	During the next three weeks: I will organize an electronic swap event.	During the next three weeks: I will organize a repair event or café.
Stage 3		
	<p>You feel like you're still missing hands-on advice? How to actually turn these solutions into reality. Learn more about practical applications through the next block.</p> <p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>	
I01: Information provision (helping with planning)	<p>How to Organise a Group Electronics Swap Event</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan and prepare: Choose a suitable space, inform participants, and set clear expectations. • Organise and label: Clearly mark the condition of each device and group them by type. 	<p>How to Organise a Repair Challenge:</p> <p>Repairing instead of replacing is not only environmentally friendly—it's also empowering and often cost-effective. Hosting a Repair Challenge is a great way for groups to learn new skills, reduce e-waste, and promote sustainability in a hands-on way. Here's how to get started:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wrap up and reflect: Recycle or donate leftovers and gather feedback for future improvements. <p>Organising a local electronics swap or repair café is straightforward, and the benefits are clear. It helps reduce e-waste, saves participants money, and strengthens your community.</p> <p>Step 1: Plan and invite</p> <p>Pick a public space such as a schoolyard, community centre or library. Invite neighbours, friends, and local groups. Make it clear that only working or repairable devices should be brought along. No sales – just sharing!</p> <p>Step 2: Organise and label</p> <p>Group items by type (phones, chargers, laptops, etc.). Label the devices: is it working, does it need repairing, and what is missing? Add signs and power strips so that devices can be tested on the spot.</p>	<p>Plan a Repair Café: repair together, save money and protect the environment!</p> <p>A Repair Café is a great opportunity to repair broken electrical appliances together instead of throwing them away. This saves money, conserves valuable resources, and strengthens the neighbourhood.</p> <p>Location and preparation</p> <p>Choose a location that is easily accessible, such as a community centre, library or school playground. Invite neighbours, friends, and local groups. Everyone should bring one or two broken but repairable devices, such as smartphones, laptops or kitchen appliances.</p> <p>Tip: Creating a good atmosphere helps to build trust – with music, coffee and small snacks, the event will feel much cosier!</p> <p>2. Repair and learn from each other!</p> <p>Invite experienced tinkerers or repair café volunteers to provide on-site assistance. Participants can lend a hand or get help, even if they have no prior knowledge.</p>
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	<p>Step 3: Swap or repair. Participants can exchange devices or get help fixing them. Invite local tinkerers or Repair Café volunteers. Everyone leaves with something useful without spending a penny.</p> <p>Step 4: Wrap up and recycle. Donate or recycle what's left. Gather feedback to help you improve next time. Want to go further? Add a small information stand about sustainable living.</p> <p>A swap or repair event is about more than just cleaning up; it's a step towards smarter consumption, shared resources and a healthier planet. Reuse more. Spend less. Connect locally.</p> <p>By following these steps, your group can create a meaningful, low-cost event that not only reduces waste but also strengthens community ties.</p>	<p>Online platforms such as iFixit or YouTube tutorials can also help.</p> <p>Advantages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Save money instead of buying new. • Feel a real sense of achievement through DIY! • Learn new skills <p>You can reuse electronics instead of disposing of them.</p> <p>Upcycling and recycling:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not everything can be saved, but many things can still be used. • Obtain spare parts. • Get creative with upcycling (e.g. turn a keyboard into a pen holder). • Recycle professionally together. <p>4. Exchange and outlook At the end: Get feedback, share ideas and plan the next dates. This may develop into a regular Repair</p>
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		<p>Café or a local repair group.</p> <p>A Repair Café offers a practical approach to resource protection. It connects people, extends the lifespan of appliances, and demonstrates that repairing is not only sustainable, but also fun and a great way to save money and strengthen our community.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
I03: Map	<p>Places on the map are provided by participants and project partners.</p>	
	<p>Let's get active and participate in a hands-on tutorial!</p>	
E06: Tutorials	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p>	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p>

	<p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organize an electronic swap event in your community</p> <p>Goal: Reduce electronic waste by swapping unused but functional devices within your community.</p> <p>Step 1: Set the Time and Place</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose a location that suits your group—indoors for weather protection or outdoors for more space and visibility. • Ensure there are enough tables, bar tables, or blankets to display items. • Create clear sections for different categories like kitchen appliances, small electronics, or accessories. • Put up signs such as "Working Devices", "Needs Repair", and "Accessories" to help participants navigate easily. <p>Step 2: Inform Participants</p>	<p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organise a repair café in your community</p> <p>Repairing instead of replacing is not only environmentally friendly—it's also empowering and often cost-effective. Hosting a Repair Challenge is a great way to learn new skills, reduce e-waste, and promote sustainability in a hands-on way.</p> <p>Step 1: Arrival & Introduction</p> <p>Welcome Participants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greet everyone and introduce the purpose of the event. • Set a positive, collaborative tone. <p>Why Repair?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talk about the environmental impact of e-waste. • Explain how repairing extends the life of devices and reduces landfill waste. <p>Tools & Safety</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invite neighbours, friends, and family—and encourage them to bring others. • Clearly communicate expectations: • Only bring devices that are functional or repairable. • There are no guarantees—items are exchanged at your own risk. • Everyone is responsible for the items they bring and take home. <p>Step 3: Set the Rules</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use a simple 1:1 swap principle or a points system if you prefer more flexibility. • Make it clear: once someone takes an item, they accept full responsibility—no returns or complaints. <p>Step 4: Run the Event</p> <p>Set-up & Registration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present the tools available. • Go over basic safety rules: • Do not open devices with visible electrical damage. • Use tools properly and wear safety gear if needed. <p>Step 2: Repair Session</p> <p>Bring Your Devices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each participant brings 1–2 broken devices and their cable box. • If possible, bring your own tools or spare parts. <p>Work in Groups</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Form small teams—those with experience (e.g. soldering) can help others. • Encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing. <p>Use Online Guides</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants set up their devices on the tables. • Each item should be labelled with: • Its condition (working, needs repair) • Missing accessories (if any) • Known issues or repair needs • Consider grouping items into small “market stalls” by category (e.g. smartphones, kitchen gadgets, cables). <p>Swap Phase</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Let participants browse and swap freely. • If a device isn’t claimed, suggest donating it to a local repair initiative or recycling centre. <p>Leftover Devices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide in advance what to do with unclaimed items: • Bring them to a future Repair Day 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit iFixit for step-by-step repair instructions. • Watch tutorials on DIY Perks YouTube Channel. <p>If It Can’t Be Repaired</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don’t worry! Move on to creative alternatives like upcycling or reusing parts. <p>Step 3: Sharing Ideas</p> <p>Reflect Together</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What worked well? • What challenges did you face? <p>What to Do with Non-Repairable Devices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donate working parts or tools. • Upcycle: e.g. turn an old keyboard into a pencil holder. • Recycle responsibly—plan a group trip to the recycling centre! <p>Step 4: Open Discussion & Next Steps</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donate to local charities or recycling centres <p>Step 5: Follow Up</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle or donate any leftover devices responsibly. • Reach out to local electronics recycling centres or charitable organisations. • If some items are repairable, store them for the next community repair event. • Collect feedback from participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What worked well? • What could be improved? • Should this become a regular event? <p>By organizing this activity, your group can create a meaningful, low-cost event that promotes sustainability, reduces waste, and strengthens community connections.</p>	<p>What's Next?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Would you like to do this again? • Could this become a regular event? • Are there local Repair Cafés or sustainability groups to connect with? <p>Keep the Momentum Going</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the right to repair movement. • Choose repairable and ethical products in the future. <p>Good to Know</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bring your own tools or spare parts if you have them. • Never open devices with exposed wiring or severe damage. • Even broken parts can be reused—get creative! <p>By organizing this activity, your group can create a meaningful, low-cost event that promotes sustainability,</p>
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		reduces waste, and strengthens community connections
	We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1. What should you do before the electronics swap event?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Label your devices with information about their condition b) Test all devices before bringing them c) Only bring electronics that are in perfect working condition <p>Question 2. What should you clarify with participants during the event?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) That each participant is responsible for the functionality of their own device b) Who will be responsible for repairs after the 	<p>Question 1. What should you do if a device cannot be repaired at a repair café?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Throw it away immediately b) Consider upcycling, reusing parts, or recycling c) Keep it at home indefinitely <p>Question 2. What is a key safety rule in repair sessions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Always repair alone without supervision b) Do not open devices with severe electrical damage c) Use any available tool, even if unsure how to handle it

	<p>event</p> <p>c) That devices can be returned if not functioning properly</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>What happens to leftover devices after the event?</p> <p>a) They should be recycled or donated</p> <p>b) They are stored for future swaps</p> <p>c) They should be sold for a profit</p>	<p>Question 3.</p> <p>What could be an additional activity at the end of the session?</p> <p>a) Selling the repaired devices</p> <p>b) Eating, networking, and discussing future sessions</p> <p>c) Buying new devices to replace broken ones</p>
T02: External tools	<p>Sell Your Electronics</p> <p>You can sell your used devices like smartphones, tablets, or laptops through second-hand marketplaces and buyback platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Germany: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kleinanzeigen – local classifieds Rebuy – buyback and resale Back Market – refurbished electronics marketplace • Norway: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finn.no – Norway’s largest classifieds site 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UK: Decluttr – sell tech and media BuyBackWorld – trade in electronics ItsWorthMore – sell used devices for cash • Latvia: ... <p>Share or Rent Electronics</p> <p>If you prefer to share or borrow instead of buying, these platforms offer community-based options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Olio (Germany, UK): Share or give away electronics and household items for free within your local community. • Peerby (Germany, UK, Norway): Borrow and lend household items, including electronics, from neighbours. • Nextdoor (Germany, UK, Latvia, Norway): A neighbourhood social network with features for lending and borrowing items like electronics. <p>These platforms make it easy to give your devices a second life, whether by selling them or sharing them with others.</p>
Stage 4	

E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the electronic challenge.
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
T01: Habit tracker	<p>Will be provided if available and useful.</p> <p>... <i>Input from the partners</i></p>
S04: Circular story task	Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge. They are encouraged to reflect on the barriers, motivations, and possible outcomes of their new behaviour. In addition, they can give tips to other participants.
Sources used for this challenge	<p>An, J., & Ahn, J. (2025). The role of customer fear of missing out on purchase intention. <i>Current Issues in Tourism</i>, 28(6), 863-870.</p> <p>Cheshmeh, Z. A., Bigverdi, Z., Eqbalpour, M., Kowsari, E., Ramakrishna, S., & Gheibi, M. (2023). A comprehensive review of used electrical and electronic equipment management with a focus on the circular economy-based policy-making. <i>Journal of cleaner production</i>, 389, 136132. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136132</p> <p>Pérez-Belis, V., Braulio-Gonzalo, M., Juan, P., & Bovea, M. D. (2017). Consumer attitude towards the repair and the second-hand purchase of small household electrical and electronic equipment. A Spanish case</p>

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- <https://www.finn.no/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.prisjakt.no/ • https://www.decluttr.com/ • https://www.buybackworld.com/ • https://www.itsworthmore.com/sell • https://olioapp.com/en/ • https://www.peerby.com/en-nl • https://www.verbraucherzentrale.de/umwelt-haushalt/neu-denken-statt-neu-kaufen-kaputte-elektrogeraete-nachhaltig-ersetzen-86138 • https://about.nextdoor.com/ • https://shop.shiftphones.com/ • https://shop.fairphone.com/ • https://frame.work/de/de • https://de.ifixit.com/ • https://www.youtube.com/@DIYPerks • https://www.repaircafe.org/en/visit/
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Table 31: Framework for the individual textiles challenges

<p>Building block</p>	<p>Challenge 1 individual:</p> <p>Reduce buying clothes</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <p>a. wardrobe audit</p> <p>b. not any buying clothes during the challenge</p>	<p>Challenge 2 individual:</p> <p>Reduce buying new clothes</p> <p>Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge:</p> <p>a. buying second hand clothes</p>
<p>Questions for the stage analysis</p>	<p>Which of the following sentences describes best how you feel about reducing buying clothes?</p> <p>-I am not sure why I should reduce buying clothes (stage 1)</p> <p>-I know why it is important to reduce buying clothes, but I do not know exactly what I can do (stage 2)</p> <p>-I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3)</p> <p>-I am already not buying clothes for a longer period (stage 4)</p> <p>-I am already doing regular wardrobe audits (stage 4)</p>	<p>Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about reducing buying new clothes?</p> <p>-I am not sure why I should reduce buying new clothes (stage 1)</p> <p>-I know why it is important reduce buying new clothes, but I do not know exactly what I can do (stage 2)</p> <p>-I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3)</p> <p>-I am already regularly buying second hand clothes (stage 4)</p>

Stage 1	
	<p>Are you ready to question your shopping habits and turn your wardrobe upside down? Welcome to the textile challenge! Let's get started.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>
<p>I01: Information provision (why current behavior is problematic)</p>	<p>Some statistics</p> <p>The textile industry has become one of the most resource-intensive and most polluting sectors in the world. Each year, 85% of all textiles end up being discarded, with a staggering 87% of used clothes either incinerated or sent to landfill. Globally, the fashion industry generates around 92 million tons of textile waste annually, while also contributing an estimated 2–8% of total global carbon emissions. Furthermore, on a global scale, only 1% of all the used clothes are recycled into new garments, meaning nearly all clothing waste is lost as a resource, making it also an economic problem.</p> <p>If nothing changes, this impact is set to grow dramatically. At its current pace, the fashion industry could consume up to 26% of the global carbon budget by 2050, making it one of the biggest climate challenges ahead. And it's not just carbon, the production of textiles is estimated to cause about 20% of global clean water pollution, mainly due to toxic dyes and chemical finishing processes.</p> <p>In Europe, the problem of fast fashion is extremely visible. The average person uses around 26 kilos of textiles annually, and discards about 11 kilos, while much of it is still wearable.</p>

	<p>Looking at personal wardrobes, the scale becomes even more relatable. In the UK, the average adult owns 118 items of clothing, but roughly a quarter of them (around 31 pieces) haven't been worn in the last year. This highlights a massive potential to reduce unnecessary consumption.</p> <p>In addition to the environmental concern, the fashion industry has significant social impacts, particularly in low-income countries where garments are often produced. Many workers face unsafe conditions, long hours, and wages below the living standard, with exposure to toxic chemicals and poor ventilation posing serious health risks over time.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
	<p>You have seen the consequences of fast fashion and how consumer behaviour harms our planet and our health. How are other people addressing this problem? Read about possible solutions in the following text.</p>

<p>I01: Information provision (on what others already do)</p>	<p>Sustainable behaviours within the clothing sector are already practiced by many individuals, communities, and organizations. When people see that others are already making eco-friendly choices, this targets social norms and increases their own willingness to take similar steps. Rethinking how we buy, use, and dispose of clothing is a key step. Reducing the number of new clothes we purchase, extending the life of the ones we already have and passing on unused garments to others are powerful actions with real environmental benefits. When we donate, sell, or swap items instead of throwing them away, we not only keep clothing in circulation longer but also help others avoid the need to buy new. This contributes to a more circular and sustainable fashion system.</p> <p>Examples of these practices are becoming more common: clothing swap events are held in many cities; second-hand and vintage shops are thriving; and online platforms like Vinted, Depop, or local Facebook groups make it easier than ever to give garments a second life. Repair cafés and upcycling events offer communities a chance to learn how to mend their clothes together, sharing both skills and social connection. These actions not only reduce waste and demand for new materials but also empower individuals to be part of a larger cultural shift. By making more conscious fashion choices and joining others in doing so, people are helping to create a fashion culture that values durability, reuse, and creativity over constant consumption. Now is a great time to explore these alternatives, because the more people join in, the more normal and rewarding these sustainable habits become.</p> <p>That's why it's so important to rethink how we buy, use, and dispose our clothing. Reducing the number of new clothes we purchase, extending the life of the ones we already have, and passing on unused garments</p>
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	<p>to others are powerful steps. When we donate, sell, or swap items instead of throwing them away, we not only save valuable resources but also help others avoid the need to buy new, contributing to a more circular and sustainable fashion system.</p>	
	<p>Good job with reading the texts! Now, after gaining all this knowledge, let's get active with an "experimental learning task".</p> <p>The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don't feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!</p>	
<p>E02: Experiential learning task</p> <p>S02: Circular story preparation task</p>	<p>Task:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Think about your latest clothing purchase <p>This can be any clothing or accessory item bought online, in-store, new or second-hand</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Have a look at the item 3. Document your observations. Use these questions as a guideline: <p>What item was bought (or considered)?</p>	<p>Task:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Invite a friend or family member to join you on a second-hand shopping trip. If you prefer to go alone, no problem. But it is probably more fun to do it together. 2. Inform yourself about second-hand stores nearby 3. Select one clothing item that you need in the (near) future (or one of your children if you have any)

	<p>Why did you want or need it? Did you really need it?</p> <p>What material and dyeing is it made of?</p> <p>Was it new, second-hand, or sustainably sourced?</p> <p>Can you backtrack to its origin?</p> <p>Where was it produced?</p> <p>What are the consequences of this production, e.g. working conditions, environmental destruction?</p> <p>4. Take a photo of the item</p> <p>5. Reflect on some of the questions. Remember, you don't have to answer all the questions one by one.</p> <p>We want to give you some starting points to help guide your reflection.</p> <p>What types of materials were involved (e.g., polyester, cotton, recycled fabrics)?</p> <p>What triggered your purchase or desire (e.g., need, trend, sale, influenced by others, boredom)?</p>	<p>4. Select one item from your wardrobe that you almost never use. Take a picture of it and take it with you on your shopping trip.</p> <p>5. Visit different secondhand shops and keep looking for the specific clothing item you have in mind. Take a picture of the item you found.</p> <p>6. Decide If you really feel you need to buy the item you found in the secondhand shop. If it is not very urgent, wait a bit before you buy it. You can always come back later.</p> <p>6. Think about sustainable options for the item you no longer need, e.g. giving it to friends, donating it to the secondhand shop you visited, taking it to a swap event, selling it in a second-hand shop or via the internet. Only if not usable anymore, donate it to a textile container.</p> <p>8. Reflect on your experience. Remember, you don't have to answer all the questions one by one. We want</p>
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	<p>How sustainable was your choice?</p> <p>6. Save the picture of the item and your reflection or drawings for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>	<p>to give you some starting points to help guide your reflection.</p> <p>Was it easy or difficult to find the piece? How many stores did you visit? How much fun was it? How did you feel when you gave your old item a new life?</p> <p>9. Save the pictures and your reflection or drawing for the circular story and discussions on the CircleUp platform.</p>
E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the textile challenge.	
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.	
	<p>Great job with reading the texts and completing the last tasks. Are you now ready to test your knowledge? Let's check what you have learned!</p>	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What percentage of clothes gets recycled?</p>	

	<p>a) 1%</p> <p>b) 5%</p> <p>c) 8-10%</p> <p>d) 15%</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What are the main impacts of the fashion industry on the environment?</p> <p>a) Development of big landfills</p> <p>b) Increase in carbon emissions</p> <p>c) Degradation of clean water</p> <p>d) All of the above</p>	
Commitment to the challenge:	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try not to buy any clothes:</p> <p>a. yes</p> <p>b. no</p>	<p>For the next three weeks, I will try to only buy second-hand clothes:</p> <p>a. yes</p> <p>b. no</p>
Stage 2		
	<p>Good progress so far! In the next block, we would like to learn something about practical alternatives to fast fashion and extensive clothing consumption – something that each of us can do!</p>	

<p>I01: Information provision (alternative behaviours, advantages and disadvantages)</p>	<p>The environmental, economic, and social impacts of the fashion industry highlight the urgent need for more sustainable consumption patterns and show the importance of exploring circular solutions. To reduce the impact of the fashion industry, alternatives like buying second-hand, repairing clothes, renting, swapping, and choosing sustainably made garments offer practical and more environmentally friendly options.</p> <p>Mindful shopping</p> <p>Start by asking yourself a few key questions before making a purchase: <i>Do I really need this? Will I wear it at least 30 times?</i> If you're unsure, wait a day or two before buying - often, that initial urge fades, and you realize you didn't need it after all.</p> <p>Capsule wardrobe</p> <p>Another powerful strategy is to build a capsule wardrobe. Choose clothing that sticks to a consistent color palette and timeless cuts, so your outfits easily</p>	<p>The environmental, economic, and social impacts of the fashion industry highlight the urgent need for more sustainable consumption patterns and show the importance of exploring circular solutions. To reduce the impact of the fashion industry, alternatives like buying second-hand, repairing clothes, renting, swapping, and choosing sustainably made garments offer practical and more environmentally friendly options.</p> <p>If you really need something new, make second-hand your first stop, you will often find unique, high-quality pieces while saving resources and money. Switching to second-hand clothing is one of the most impactful steps you can take to reduce your fashion footprint. The good news is, there are multiple ways to do it, each with its own advantages. Whether you're on a budget, looking for unique pieces, or simply want to shop more sustainably, second-hand options offer something for everyone.</p>
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	<p>match, and you don't feel the need to constantly buy new items to "complete" your look.</p> <p>Take care</p> <p>Taking care of the clothes you already own also makes a huge impact. Wash them gently, repair them when needed, and store them properly. Extending the life of your garments delays the need to replace them and reduces your environmental footprint. Better quality items will last longer and stay in better shape than fast fashion products.</p> <p>Sustainable options</p> <p>If you really need something, explore more sustainable options like renting or swapping clothes, especially for special occasions. It keeps your wardrobe fresh without contributing to waste.</p> <p>Rethink</p> <p>Of course, choosing to buy fewer clothes may come with some downsides, such as limited variety or needing to invest more time in maintenance and</p>	<p>Shops</p> <p>Thrift stores and charity shops are great places to start. They offer affordable prices, a wide variety of styles, and the satisfaction of supporting charitable causes. You can also try clothes on immediately, which helps ensure a good fit. However, quality may vary, and depending on the shop, it can take time to browse through everything to find what you want.</p> <p>Online</p> <p>For those who prefer convenience, online second-hand platforms offer a huge selection of items at your fingertips. You can filter by size, brand, or condition, making it easier to find exactly what you're looking for. The downside? You'll often have to pay shipping costs, and there's always the risk that an item may not look or feel as expected - plus, you can't try it on before buying.</p> <p>Swapping</p> <p>If you're looking for a more social and zero-cost experience, clothing swaps and community exchanges</p>
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	<p>repairs. It can also be difficult if fashion plays a big role in your identity or social life and you may not always find the right item easily and quickly. But many people find that reducing clothing consumption leads to a greater sense of creativity, confidence, and appreciation for the items they do own. Lastly, rethink how shopping fits into your life. Unsubscribe from fast fashion newsletters that tempt impulse buys, and challenge the idea that shopping is a hobby. By shifting your habits, you're not just buying clothes, you're choosing a more thoughtful, responsible way to engage with fashion.</p>	<p>are a fun alternative. They're free, eco-friendly, and offer a chance to refresh your wardrobe while connecting with others. That said, these events usually have a limited selection and require a bit of planning or participation to organise or attend.</p> <p>Each of these second-hand options has its strengths and trade-offs, but all contribute to a more circular and conscious way of consuming fashion. Mixing and matching these methods can help you build a wardrobe that's not only stylish and affordable but also good for the planet.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	

E01: Interactive learning environments	Link the participants to ILE based on system model.	
You think you can score 100% on the following quiz? Let's see!		
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is the most sustainable option when it comes to clothing?</p> <p>A) Buying secondhand clothes B) Swapping clothes with friends C) Buying from sustainable brands D) Not buying new clothes at all</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>What is the main advantage of a capsule wardrobe?</p> <p>A) It allows you to follow fast fashion trends B) It makes choosing outfits easier and reduces unnecessary shopping C) It encourages buying expensive designer pieces D) It means you have to wear the same outfit every day</p>	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one of the biggest benefits of switching to second-hand clothing?</p> <p>a) Clothes are always brand new b) It helps reduce your fashion footprint c) It guarantees the latest fashion trends d) It eliminates all shopping costs</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>Which of the following is not a downside of shopping in thrift stores?</p> <p>a) High shipping costs b) Limited variety c) Time needed to browse for items d) Ability to try clothes on</p>

	<p>Question 3.</p> <p>If you want a “new” outfit without buying anything, what is the best option?</p> <p>A) Browse fast fashion sales for cheap deals</p> <p>B) Buy a trendy item and donate an old one</p> <p>C) Borrow, swap, or style existing clothes differently</p> <p>D) Wait for a new collection from a sustainable brand</p>	<p>Question 3.</p> <p>What is a common advantage of clothing swaps and community exchanges?</p> <p>a) Items are usually designer brands</p> <p>b) They are often free and social</p> <p>c) They offer guaranteed sizing</p> <p>d) You can return items after use</p>
Choice of action	<p>During the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>a. Organize a wardrobe audit</p> <p>b. Not buying any clothing</p>	<p>During the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>Buy secondhand clothes if I need to buy something</p>
Stage 3		
	<p>You feel like you’re still missing hands-on advice? How to actually turn these solutions into reality. Learn more about practical applications through the next block.</p>	

	<p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>	
<p>I01: Information provision (helping with planning)</p>	<p>A wardrobe audit</p> <p>Taking a closer look at your own wardrobe is a powerful way to connect with the impact of your clothing choices. A wardrobe audit encourages you to reflect on what you actually own, wear, and value. Often, we find that many items remain unworn or forgotten, which highlights opportunities to reduce overconsumption and waste.</p> <p>What is a wardrobe audit?</p> <p>Through this reflection, many people discover the benefits of building a capsule wardrobe: a thoughtful collection of garments, timeless pieces that can be mixed and matched easily. A capsule wardrobe focuses on quality over quantity, helping you to streamline your closet and simplify daily outfit choices while reducing impulse buying.</p>	<p>The benefits of second-hand shopping</p> <p>Second-hand shopping is a practical way to save money, but it's also a meaningful act that supports a circular and sustainable fashion economy. When you buy second-hand, you are giving clothes a new lease on life, helping to reduce demand for new textile production and its associated environmental costs.</p> <p>If you need more variety</p> <p>The variety of second-hand options, from thrift shops and online marketplaces to clothing swaps, offers a solution for everyone, whether you're looking for unique vintage pieces, affordable basics, or a fun social activity. This approach not only keeps garments out of landfills but also celebrates individuality and creativity in style.</p>

	<p>By identifying the items you truly love and wear frequently, you can make more intentional decisions about repairing, repurposing, or passing on clothes that no longer fit your style or needs. This mindful approach encourages sustainability and helps align your wardrobe with your values.</p> <p>A wardrobe audit combined with the capsule wardrobe concept is not about restriction but about creating a more satisfying, functional, and sustainable way of dressing. How can your wardrobe reflect values that matter to you? Can we recombine clothes to create new styles? Do your clothes already tell a story?</p> <p>Of course, you can also make a wardrobe audit without going for a capsule wardrobe. You may rediscover pieces that you can wear next season and get an overview of what you already have. Going more circular regarding fashion does not mean you're</p>	<p>Choosing second-hand clothing challenges the fast fashion cycle and encourages a more thoughtful way of consuming. It invites us to appreciate quality and longevity over quantity, transforming the way we think about what it means to own and wear clothes.</p>
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	limited to a certain kind of style. It's as diverse as people are.	
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
	<p>You already made it very far in this challenge, congratulations!</p> <p>Are you interested in local resources that enable you to shop sustainably? Let's check out the map!</p>	
I03: Map	Participants and project partners will locate places on the map themselves.	
	A challenge is supposed to be fun – and it is especially fun when you can turn everything that you have learned so far into practical actions. Let us continue with a tutorial in which you learn how to build up a sustainable wardrobe.	
E06: Tutorials	**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**	**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**

	<p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organize a wardrobe audit.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Take everything out of your closet. Even though this seems to be effortful, it will help you to throw as many unwanted clothes out as possible. 2. Pick up each item separately and evaluate it. Does it fit? Do I like it? Will I wear it within the next year? 3. Create three piles: 1. Definitely keep, 2. Unsure, 3. Thrown out. Further divide the “Thrown out” pile with into “Donate/Sell” and “Discard” based on the condition of the clothes. Assign each piece to one pile based on these questions. 4. Take the “Keep” pile and move the clothes into your wardrobe. Do this in an organised way (by category or color) and make sure that it stays organised in the future. 	<p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organize a successful second-hand trip.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Preparation: Know your wardrobe well enough, think about what you need and what you want to buy second-hand, set a budget for your trip 2. Store: Choose the right place that matches your style and budget, also consider online second-hand shops, flea markets and swaps 3. Quality of items: Check the fabric, seams and stitching, check for potential damages such as holes 4. Time: Take your time, thrifting requires more patience than fast fashion, but you may find very unique pieces
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	<p>5. Find solutions for the pieces that you've thrown out: selling online and in stores, places to donate, given to friends and family if they are interested.</p> <p>6. For the future, keep track of what you got: Which pieces match together? Which items do I have too many of? Which items do I need, which ones should be replaced?</p> <p>How to organize a capsule wardrobe?</p> <p>A capsule wardrobe is a wardrobe full of clothes that can easily be combined and mixed in many different ways. It is designed to maximize the number of outfits while decreasing the number of pieces at the same time. It saves you time when it comes to the question what to wear, money and it's sustainable.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decide on a color palette. Something that you like and you already have a lot of pieces of. 2. Audit your current wardrobe. Pick your favourite pieces. They serve as a reference 	<p>5. Customise: If something does not fit perfectly, but still seems to be a nice piece, you might consider some upcycling or small alterations, e.g. in size</p> <p>Have fun!</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start second-hand shopping. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>
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	<p>point and help you define the style and colors.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">3. Remove the items that will not be part of the capsule wardrobe and find sustainable solutions for them.4. Once you have picked your capsule pieces, choose additional items that have a similar style to fill up what you need. An average capsule wardrobe contains of 20-40 pieces. Get these items from thrift stores, either in-town or online. <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start creating a wardrobe audit and capsule wardrobe. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>	
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	<p>Great job on the tutorial! Keep going!</p> <p>Here, we offer you the opportunity to test the practical knowledge that you have just learned in a final test.</p>	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>How can you refresh your style without buying new clothes?</p> <p>A) Borrow or swap clothes with friends B) Restyle existing outfits in new ways C) Repair or upcycle old clothing D) All of the above</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>Which of these is a common mistake when trying to buy less clothing?</p> <p>A) Keeping a wish list for planned purchases B) Decluttering too quickly and rebuying similar items C) Investing in high-quality staple pieces D) Learning to mix and match outfits</p> <p>Question 3.</p> <p>Which of the following is NOT a benefit of a capsule wardrobe?</p>	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>Which of the following is NOT a common place to shop second-hand?</p> <p>a) Thrift stores and charity shops b) Flea markets c) Fast fashion retail stores d) Clothing swaps</p> <p>Question 2.</p> <p>Why does second-hand shopping require more patience compared to fast fashion?</p> <p>a) Because you often have to go through many items to find unique pieces b) Because you need to compare frequently changing prices c) Because stores are always far away d) Because clothes need washing before buying</p>

	<p>A) Reducing decision fatigue B) Saving money by shopping less C) Always following the latest fashion trends D) Creating a more sustainable wardrobe</p> <p>Question 4. What does NOT make me buy less?</p> <p>A) Unsubscribing from fashion brand emails and newsletters B) Browsing online stores "just to look" C) When buying, considering if this fits the style of my current wardrobe D) Creating a capsule wardrobe with versatile, timeless pieces</p>	<p>Question 3. What is a good idea if a second-hand item doesn't fit perfectly but you like it?</p> <p>a) Throw it away b) Consider upcycling or making small alterations c) Ignore it and leave it behind d) Sell it online as is</p>
T02: External tools	<p>Input from the partners: Useful links to support people finding local events for repairing clothes, websites to sell or buy second hand clothes, rent clothing etc</p> <p>Norway: klesbyttearrangementer (Naturvernforbundet.no) Tise.no</p>	

	<p>Finn.no Brukt klær i klesbutikker (Polarn og Pyret) Reli.no Hygglo.no Hvorfor ikke leie en bunad eller bryllupsklær? Naturvernforbundet has a lot of nice tutorials on fixing clothes: Hvordan sy på nye knapper på 1-2-3? Ny glidelås til bukse Fiske og reparere hull i bukse</p> <p><i>Germany:</i> <i>Latvia:</i> <i>UK:</i></p>
Stage 4	
E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the textile challenge.
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.
T01: Habit tracker	Will be provided if available and useful.

	<p>... <i>Input from the partners</i></p>
	<p>You did a brilliant job! Looking back at all the information you received and the tasks you completed, it can be helpful to reflect on your own experiences. We encourage you to take part in the last task, the “Circular story task” which is wrapping up the challenge.</p>
<p>S04: Circular story task</p>	<p>Participants are encouraged to share a circular story based on the finished challenge. They are encouraged to reflect on the barriers, motivations, and possible outcomes of their new behaviour. In addition, they can give tips to other participants.</p>
<p>Sources used for this challenge</p>	<p>Aguiar, G. J. A., Almeida, L. R., Fernandes, B. S., Gavazza, S., Silva, G. L., & Machado Santos, S. (2023). Use of life cycle assessment as a tool to evaluate the environmental impacts of textile effluents: a systematic review. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i>, 30(31), 76455-76470. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-27785-6</p> <p>Chequer, F. M. D., de Oliveira, G. A. R., Ferraz, E. R. A., Cardoso, J. C., Zanoni, M. V. B., & de Oliveira, D. P. (2013). Textile dyes: dyeing process and environmental impact. In <i>Eco-friendly textile dyeing and finishing</i>. IntechOpen. https://doi.org/10.5772/53659</p> <p>Islam, T., Repon, M., Islam, T. et al. Impact of textile dyes on health and ecosystem: a review of structure, causes, and potential solutions. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> 30, 9207–9242 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-24398-3</p> <p>Joanes, T., Geiger, S. M., & Gwozdz, W. (2025). Think Twice—An Intervention Strategy to Reduce Personal Clothing Consumption. <i>Environment and Behavior</i>. https://doi.org/10.1177/00139165251315563</p>

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<https://www.genevaenvironmentnetwork.org/resources/updates/sustainable-fashion/>
<https://www.wrap.ngo/media-centre/press-releases/nations-wardrobes-hold-16-billion-items-unworn-clothes-people-open-new>

Table 32: Framework for the community textiles challenges

Building block	Challenge 3 community: Reuse textiles Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge: Organize a clothes swap	Challenge 4 community: Repair/upcycle textiles Alternative behaviour to choose from in the challenge: a. Organize a repair textiles event b. Organize an upcycling event
Questions for the stage analysis:	Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about reusing clothes together? -I am not sure why I should reuse clothes together (stage 1) -I know why it is important to reuse clothes together but I do not know exactly what I can do (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already organizing clothes swaps in my neighbourhood (stage 4)	Which of the following sentences describe best how you feel about repairing or upcycling clothes together? -I am not sure why I should repair or upcycle clothes together (stage 1) -I know why it is important to repair/upcycle clothes together but I do not know exactly what I can do (stage 2) -I have decided what I want to do to, but I am still figuring out how to do it (stage 3) -I am already organizing repair textiles or upcycling activities in my neighbourhood (stage 4)
Stage 1		

	<p>Welcome to the communal textile challenge! In the following, we will address the global textile issue together. You can look forward to swapping clothes, repairing and upcycling them and much more.</p> <p>We have also included short bullet points for those who prefer a quick read over a longer text.</p>
<p>I01: Information provision (why current behavior is problematic)</p>	<p>Some statistics</p> <p>The textile industry has become one of the most resource-intensive and polluting sectors in the world. Each year, 85% of all textiles end up being discarded, with a staggering 87% of used clothes either incinerated or sent to landfill. Globally, the fashion industry generates around 92 million tons of textile waste annually, while also contributing an estimated 2–8% of total global carbon emissions.</p> <p>If nothing changes, this impact is set to grow dramatically. At its current pace, the fashion industry could consume up to 26% of the global carbon budget by 2050, making it one of the biggest climate challenges ahead. And it's not just carbon: the production of textiles is estimated to cause about 20% of global clean water pollution, mainly due to toxic dyes and chemical finishing processes.</p> <p>In Europe, the problem is especially visible: the average person uses around 26 kilos of textiles annually, and discards about 11 kilos, much of it still wearable. Shockingly, only 1% of used clothing is recycled into new garments, meaning nearly all clothing waste is lost as a resource.</p> <p>Looking at personal wardrobes, the scale becomes even more relatable. In the UK, the average adult owns 118 items of clothing, but roughly a quarter of them (around 31 pieces) haven't been worn in the last year. This highlights a massive potential to reduce unnecessary consumption.</p> <p>That's why it's so important to rethink how we buy, use, and dispose of clothing. Reducing the number of new clothes we purchase, extending the life of the ones we already have, and passing on unused</p>

	<p>garments to others are powerful steps. When we donate, sell, or swap items instead of throwing them away, we not only save valuable resources but also help others avoid the need to buy new, contributing to a more circular and sustainable fashion system.</p> <p>In addition to the environmental concern, the fashion industry has significant social impacts, particularly in low-income countries where garments are often produced. Many workers face unsafe conditions, long hours, and wages below the living standard, with exposure to toxic chemicals and poor ventilation posing serious health risks over time.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
I01: Information provision (on what others already do)	<p>Sustainable behaviours within the clothing sector are already practiced by many individuals, communities, and organizations. When people see that others are already making eco-friendly choices, this targets social norms and increases their own willingness to take similar steps. Rethinking how we buy, use, and dispose of clothing is a key step. Reducing the number of new clothes we purchase, extending the life of</p>

the ones we already have and passing on unused garments to others are powerful actions with real environmental benefits. When we donate, sell, or swap items instead of throwing them away, we not only keep clothing in circulation longer but also help others avoid the need to buy new. This contributes to a more circular and sustainable fashion system.

Examples of these practices are becoming more common: clothing swap events are held in many cities; second-hand and vintage shops are thriving; and online platforms like Vinted, Depop, or local Facebook groups make it easier than ever to give garments a second life. Repair cafés and upcycling events offer communities a chance to learn how to mend their clothes together, sharing both skills and social connection.

These actions not only reduce waste and demand for new materials but also empower individuals to be part of a larger cultural shift. By making more conscious fashion choices and joining others in doing so, people are helping to create a fashion culture that values durability, reuse, and creativity over constant consumption.

Now is a great time to explore these alternatives, because the more people join in, the more normal and rewarding these sustainable habits become.

That's why it's so important to rethink how we buy, use, and dispose our clothing. Reducing the number of new clothes we purchase, extending the life of the ones we already have, and passing on unused garments to others are powerful steps. When we **donate, sell, or swap items** instead of throwing them

	<p>away, we not only save valuable resources but also help others avoid the need to buy new, contributing to a more circular and sustainable fashion system.</p>	
	<p>Good job with reading the texts! Now, after gaining all this knowledge, let's get active with an "experimental learning task".</p> <p>The following task involves a bit more effort. We will ask you to take a piece of paper and a pencil, but you can use anything you can make notes on. If this feels too time-consuming or you are not a big fan of writing, you can also make a short movie or a drawing to express your thoughts. Don't feel obliged or stressed; we want you to enjoy the task!</p>	
<p>E02: Experiential learning task</p>	<p>Purpose: This building block is designed to give individuals direct, hands-on experiences with solutions for environmental problems in their own lives. They should be motivating and encouraging and give individuals a feeling of self-efficacy.</p> <p>Regarding "I want to buy less clothes for the next three weeks." (then, it's similar to challenge individual 1)</p> <p>In this task, we ask you to be mindful about your clothing purchases for the next three weeks.</p>	<p>Purpose: This building block is designed to give individuals direct, hands-on experiences with solutions for environmental problems in their own lives. They should be motivating and encouraging and give individuals a feeling of self-efficacy.</p> <p>Believe it or not: There is usually at least one item in your wardrobe that is not properly in shape anymore. This might be the reason why you are wearing this item less often – or you are even thinking about throwing this away. In this experiential learning task, we aim to raise</p>

	<p>1. Whenever you feel the need of a new item, you find yourself in a store or online shopping, ask yourself the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How is this item produced? Where can I find information on this? Based on previous information in this app, how do I imagine the environmental impact to be? <p>2. Ask yourself: Do I really need this item, e.g. for a special occasion or to replace something that is worn out? A good threshold is the “30-times” question asking yourself if you are going to wear this item at least 30 times. Then, it might be worth the purchase.</p> <p>3. These strategies should help you to reflect on your consumption behaviour and reduce the overall number of new clothes. Compare the</p>	<p>awareness about how to bring these pieces back to life!</p> <p>Here’s how to do it:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Choose one item out of your wardrobe that is broken or not usable anymore in any kind of way, that can be a hole, something that has become too small or big, or a missing button 2. Find a way to repair this item properly (see also examples in the next stages in this app). 3. Get the necessary material, that can be fabric, needles etc. If you don’t have a sewing machine, but know how to sew, try to rent a sewing machine. If you don’t know how to sew, ask friends and family members for support. 4. You can make a collaborative project out of it: Invite friends, everyone brings one item they would like to repair and you can do it together – that’s more fun! 5. And finally: Be happy about the freshly repaired piece that is now ready to be worn again!
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	number of bought clothes within these three weeks to a time period before that with a similar length.	
E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the textile challenge.	
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions	
	<p>It's time for a quiz! Let's test your knowledge in the following test.</p> <p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>	
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one of the benefits of participating in a repair textile event?</p> <p>a) It helps reduce textile waste and promotes sustainability</p> <p>b) It allows you to learn some clothing repair skills</p> <p>c) You can come in contact with other like-minded people in my community</p>	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one of the biggest benefits of participating in a clothing swap?</p> <p>a) It helps reduce textile waste and promotes sustainability.</p> <p>b) It allows you to buy brand-new designer clothes.</p> <p>c) It ensures you always wear the latest fashion trends.</p> <p>d) It is more expensive than traditional shopping.</p>

	<p>d) It will be cheaper than buying a new clothing item</p> <p>Question 2. Which of the following is a good tip for organizing a successful repair textile event?</p> <p>a) Set rules about the amount of clothing items people can take with them to repair</p> <p>b) Ask an entrance fee to participate c) Only accept clothes that are difficult to repair</p> <p>Question 3. What should you do before attending a repair textile event yourself?</p> <p>a) Bring as many damaged clothes as possible b) Look for the event's guidelines and select an appropriate item to repair</p> <p>d) Buy repairing tools in advance such as a sewing kit</p>	<p>Question 2. Which of the following is a good tip for organizing a successful clothing swap?</p> <p>a) Only allow people to bring new clothes with tags. b) Set rules about the condition of clothing items.</p> <p>c) Charge people high entrance fees to participate. d) Only accept clothes from luxury brands.</p> <p>Question 3. What should you do before attending (or organising) a clothing swap?</p> <p>a) Bring as many clothes as possible, regardless of the condition. b) Research the event's guidelines and select items in good condition.</p> <p>c) Buy new clothes to swap with others. d) Avoid bringing any clothes, just take what you like.</p>
Commitment to the challenge	For the next three weeks, I will try to repair or upcycle my clothes together with others:	For the next three weeks, I will try to share clothes with others:

	a. yes b. no	a. yes b. no
Stage 2		
	Do you want to inspire others to take action to reduce their textiles? We will tell you a bit more about it in the next step	
I01: Information provision (alternative behaviour, advantages and disadvantages)	<p>Going beyond the individual level</p> <p>Reducing fast fashion requires a collaborative effort from different groups in our society, including individual consumers, retailers, manufacturers, but also governments. Each group has a role to play in creating a more just and sustainable fashion system, from a local to a global level.</p> <p>Households can make a change by buying fewer items, higher-quality and fair items, repairing clothes they have and donating to others. Retailers can offer sustainable clothes, promote secondhand shopping, and manage their inventory of clothes more efficient. Policymakers can develop stricter regulations and support campaigns to encourage sustainable practices in the fashion industry. Furthermore, they can play a more prominent role in combating greenwashing.</p> <p>During this challenge, we encourage you to go a step further and inspire others to take action by engaging with the community.</p>	

There are different ways to engage within your broader community:

Raising awareness:

Raising awareness about fast fashion doesn't have to be complicated. Simple conversations and visible actions can make a meaningful difference. The goal is to help others understand the problem and inspire them to take small steps in their own lives.

Start by bringing the topic into everyday conversations. Whether it's over dinner with your family or during a coffee break with friends or colleagues, discussing the social, economic, and environmental impacts of fast fashion can plant seeds for change among others.

Keep your message relevant with simple solutions, such as buying secondhand or choosing sustainable brands. People are more likely to act when the information feels applicable and accessible to their daily lives.

In today's digital world, social media is a powerful tool. Share your own progress: Maybe you've already started buying your clothes secondhand. Talk about it. These small stories can be inspiring for others.

Visuals help, too: post photos of how you repaired your clothing or which item you have swapped on a swap event. For people who aren't yet aware, this kind of concrete example makes the issue more real.

Finally, remember that not everyone is motivated in the same way. While environmental reasons are powerful for some people, for others, financial incentives work better. So, highlight the personal benefits too. This can be saving money by buying less clothing or planning to buy your next item second hand. When you connect the problem to real-life advantages, you make change feel not only important, but achievable.

Educate people:

Organizing workshops or events is a powerful way to educate people about fast fashion. These can be hands-on sessions where the participants learn practical skills such as sewing a whole. Workshops can also include demonstrations that show how to do a clothing audit. By bringing people together and organizing workshops and events, you can educate and empower people with skills. This could be the start of a bigger change. At the end of a workshop or event, you can collect ideas for future activities.

Community engagement:

By carrying out practices in the local community, you can empower other individuals or groups to take action. One popular and effective community practice is clothing swaps. These events bring people together to exchange clothes they no longer wear in a fun and social setting, allowing everyone to refresh their wardrobes without buying new items. Clothing swaps reduce textile waste, save money, and strengthen community bonds by encouraging sharing and reuse. They're also a great way to discover unique styles and inspire sustainable fashion habits. Try to get into dialogue with other groups in our society. You can join local initiatives such as setting up a textile sharing program where community members can exchange clothing. You can also collaborate with local organizations such as NGOs

	<p>working towards a more sustainable world. You can be part of a public event focusing on fast fashion. Finally, you can engage with the local government by starting petitions to initiate policy changes or participate in forums or public consultations. Let your voice be heard.</p>
I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners if available.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>
E01: Interactive learning environments	<p>Link the participants to ILE based on system model.</p>
	<p>We want to challenge you to find others to take the quiz with. These could be family members, friends, neighbours. If you are up to it, you can even challenge some of your colleagues by asking some of the questions during lunch or at the end of a meeting. These questions might create room for discussions and perhaps even even motivate others to join you in the CircleUp challenge?</p>
E03: Quiz	<p>Question 1.</p> <p>What is one effective way for individuals to raise awareness about fast fashion in their everyday life?</p>

- a) Avoid discussing environmental issues with friends
- b) Talk about the impact of fast fashion during everyday conversations**
- c) Only share statistics without context

Question 2.

How can social media help in encouraging sustainable fashion practices?

- a) By criticising people who buy fast fashion
- b) By sharing personal stories and visuals of sustainable actions**
- c) By only reposting professional campaigns

Question 3.

What is one role policymakers can play in reducing fast fashion?

- a) Enforcing stricter regulations and combating greenwashing**
- b) Promoting fast fashion brands to boost the economy
- c) Reducing taxes on imported clothing

Question 4.

What is a key benefit of community activities about fast fashion?

	<p>a) They provide free clothes to participants b) They promote fashion trends c) They teach practical skills and empower people to take action</p> <p>Question 5. What is an example of community engagement to fight fast fashion?</p> <p>a) Hosting a fashion show with new collections b) Encouraging people to shop online c) Setting up a local textile sharing programme</p>	
Choice of action	<p>During the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>a. Organize a textiles repair event b. Organize an upcycling event</p>	<p>During the next three weeks, I will:</p> <p>Organize a cloth swap event</p>
Stage 3		
	<p>Many people are aware of environmental problems, but how do we take action? How do we implement these actions in our daily life? Let's take a closer look at this in the following block.</p> <p>You might feel like you are receiving a lot of information. Our goal is to inspire you and give you some helpful guidelines if you are unsure on how to proceed with the challenge. Feel free to use it in a way that supports you best.</p>	

<p>I01: Information provision (helping with planning)</p>	<p>Upcycling of your clothes is a creative and sustainable way to refresh your wardrobe by transforming old or unused garments into something new and unique. Instead of discarding clothes, upcycling helps reduce textile waste while adding a personal touch to your style.</p> <p>Start simple</p> <p>Starting with simple projects, you can easily turn worn-out jeans into shorts or convert an old t-shirt into a trendy tote bag or pencil case. If your clothes feel plain, small additions like patches, embroidery, or fabric paint can make a big difference. Techniques such as tie-dye or bleach-dye add bold patterns and colour variations to otherwise dull items.</p> <p>For the more advanced once's</p> <p>For those who enjoy more hands-on creativity, combining different fabrics into patchwork</p>	<p>Clothing swaps have become an increasingly popular way for communities to tackle the environmental challenges posed by fast fashion. Rather than buying new clothes, swapping allows people to refresh their wardrobes by exchanging garments they no longer wear. This practice not only reduces textile waste but also helps save money and supports a healthier planet.</p> <p>What is a clothing swap?</p> <p>At its core, a clothing swap is a collective event where participants bring clean, gently used clothing and trade items with others. Swaps can take many forms—from informal gatherings among friends to large community events hosted in public spaces. The flexibility and inclusivity of clothing swaps make them accessible to a wide range of people and lifestyles.</p> <p>Benefits of clothing swaps</p> <p>One of the main benefits of clothing swaps is the reduction of unnecessary consumption. By reusing existing garments, swaps prevent perfectly wearable clothes from ending up in landfills or incinerators,</p>
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	<p>designs can mix textures and colours, creating truly one-of-a-kind pieces. You can also alter clothes to fit your needs better, like resizing a waistband, shortening sleeves, or reshaping garments for a fresh look.</p> <p>Benefits of upcycling clothes</p> <p>Upcycling is not just about saving money or materials; it's about building a stronger connection to the clothes you wear. This approach reduces dependence on fast fashion and encourages sustainable consumption habits. With a little imagination and effort, every piece of clothing has the potential to come up as something new and valuable.</p> <p>Repairing your clothes is a practical and sustainable way to extend the life of your clothes. Instead of discarding clothes that are damaged or worn out, repairing helps reduce textile waste.</p>	<p>helping to lessen the fashion industry's massive environmental footprint. They also offer a financial advantage, allowing people to update their wardrobes without spending money on new items.</p> <p>Moreover, clothing swaps can strengthen community ties by creating opportunities for people to meet, share stories, and exchange ideas about sustainable living. These social connections are vital in building a culture that values mindful consumption and resource sharing.</p> <p>Challenges of clothing swaps</p> <p>While clothing swaps are generally positive experiences, some challenges exist. Organising a successful swap requires coordination, a shared understanding of guidelines (such as ensuring items are clean and in good condition), and a plan for managing leftover clothes. However, many communities find that the benefits far outweigh these logistical considerations.</p>
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	<p>Start simple</p> <p>Starting with simple repairs, you can easily fix small holes or sewing a button using basic sewing techniques. You can use needle and thread, or iron patches.</p> <p>For the more advances one's</p> <p>There are many resources available to get better in repairing your own clothes. Have a look at online tutorials, community workshops, or even sewing classes.</p> <p>Benefits of repairing clothes</p> <p>Repairing clothes is not just about saving money or materials; it's about building a stronger connection to the clothes you wear. This approach reduces dependence on fast fashion and encourages sustainable consumption habits. With a little imagination and effort, every damaged piece of clothing has the potential to come up as something new and valuable.</p>	<p>Overall, clothing swaps represent a practical and engaging way to embrace circular fashion principles. They show how collective action can reduce textile waste, save money, promote sustainability, and foster stronger community connections</p>
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I02: Videos	<p>Videos are provided by project partners.</p> <p><i>Input from the partners:</i></p> <p><i>No: ...</i></p> <p><i>Germany: ...</i></p> <p><i>UK: ...</i></p> <p><i>Latvia: ...</i></p>	
I03: Map	<p>Participants and project partners will locate places on the map.</p>	
	<p>You've already made it so far in this challenge, keep up the good work!</p> <p>Sustainable action can be a lot of fun – something that we want to emphasise for the following tutorials. They will provide you with hands-on expertise on how to organize a clothes swap or fix your clothes by yourself. That's cool, isn't it? Let's keep going!</p>	
E06: Tutorials	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organize a repair textile event.</p>	<p>**Check if there are existing tutorials from the partners**</p> <p>A step-by-step tutorial on how to organise a clothes swap event.</p> <p>Plan the event in advance: Choose a date, timeslot and venue, e.g. at home, somewhere in your neighbourhood</p>

	<p>Plan the event: Choose a date, timeslot, and accessible venue such as a community centre or local library</p> <p>Create an invitation and some guidelines if necessary</p> <p>Gather necessary tools: needles, thread, scissors, patches, sewing machines (if available)</p> <p>Invite skilled volunteers or local tailors to assist participants</p> <p>Create and share simple repair guides for common fixes (e.g., sewing buttons, patching holes)</p> <p>Promote the event through local social media, community boards, and word of mouth</p> <p>Ask participants to bring clothes needing repair</p>	<p>Create an invitation and guidelines (e.g. how many pieces per person)</p> <p>Define rules (e.g. let everyone look and try at first, then choose)</p> <p>Promote the event, invite people from your neighbourhood</p> <p>Exchange system: e.g. one-on-one system or free-to-take garments</p> <p>Sort clothes, e.g. by type or by size</p> <p>Prepare the venue: fitting area, mirrors, hangers, possibly have music, a photo area and snacks/drinks</p> <p>Think in advance about the options for leftover clothes: charity donations or upcycling</p>
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	<p>Set up workstations with enough space and lighting for repairs</p> <p>Provide hands-on support and encourage participants to help each other</p> <p>Offer refreshments and a comfortable atmosphere to foster community spirit</p> <p>After the event: Share success stories and gather feedback for future events</p> <p>Plan options for leftover materials or tools, such as donations or communal sharing</p> <p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to start organizing a textile repair event. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional</p>	<p>In this tutorial, we want to give you some basic advice on how to organize a clothes swap. While our tutorial will get you started, a lot of other people have created very good and detailed tutorials available online. We encourage you to explore YouTube videos for additional guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>
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	<p>guidance and share the videos you like and are most helpful with others.</p>	
<p>E03: Quiz</p>	<p>Question 1. What is the main purpose of a clothes swap? a) To buy new clothes at a discount b) To exchange clothes with others to refresh your wardrobe sustainably c) To donate clothes to charity d) To throw away old clothes</p> <p>Question 2. Which of the following is important to decide before organising a clothes swap? a) The venue and date b) The number of pieces each person can bring c) Rules for trying on and selecting clothes d) All of the above</p> <p>Question 3. What can you do with leftover clothes after a</p>	<p>Question 1. Which of the following is an example of upcycling? a) Donating your old clothes to charity b) Turning a t-shirt into a tote bag c) Selling clothes on a second-hand app d) Throwing away clothes with holes</p> <p>Question 2. What is one creative upcycling idea for jeans? a) Cutting them into shorts or a patchwork bag b) Washing them in cold water c) Ironing them more often d) Turning them into compost</p> <p>Question 3. What is the main difference between recycling and upcycling in fashion? a) Recycling creates higher quality items</p>

	swap event? a) Donate to charity b) Upcycle or repurpose them c) Throw them in the trash d) Both a and b	b) Upcycling is less eco-friendly c) Recycling is only for clothes d) Upcycling adds value to old pieces
T02: External tools	Partners can include helpful links to support people in organizing a repair textile event and a clothes swap event. <i>Norway:</i> <i>Latvia:</i> <i>Germany:</i> <i>UK:</i>	
Stage 4		
E04: Smart bin analysis	The smart bin will not be used for the textile challenge.	
E05: LCA assessment	Link the participants to the LCA questions.	
T01: Habit tracker	Will be provided if available and useful.	

	... <i>Input from the partners</i>
	It's a wrap – you successfully made it through all the task of the community textile challenge. What an achievement! Are you ready to reflect on your experiences? This will also benefit others in the CircleUp community.
S04: Circular story task	Participants are encouraged to write a circular story based on the finished challenge.
Sources used for this challenge	<p>Aguiar, G. J. A., Almeida, L. R., Fernandes, B. S., Gavazza, S., Silva, G. L., & Machado Santos, S. (2023). Use of life cycle assessment as a tool to evaluate the environmental impacts of textile effluents: a systematic review. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i>, 30(31), 76455-76470. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-27785-6</p> <p>Chequer, F. M. D., de Oliveira, G. A. R., Ferraz, E. R. A., Cardoso, J. C., Zanoni, M. V. B., & de Oliveira, D. P. (2013). Textile dyes: dyeing process and environmental impact. In <i>Eco-friendly textile dyeing and finishing</i>. IntechOpen. https://doi.org/10.5772/53659</p> <p>Footprint, F. W. (2013). <i>Food wastage footprint: impacts on natural resources: summary report</i>. Food & Agriculture Organization of the UN (FAO).</p> <p>Islam, T., Repon, M., Islam, T. et al. Impact of textile dyes on health and ecosystem: a review of structure, causes, and potential solutions. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> 30, 9207–9242 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-24398-3</p> <p>Joanes, T., Geiger, S. M., & Gwozdz, W. (2025). Think Twice—An Intervention Strategy to Reduce Personal Clothing Consumption. <i>Environment and Behavior</i>. https://doi.org/10.1177/00139165251315563</p>

	<p>Madhav, S., Ahamad, A., Singh, P., & Mishra, P. K. (2018). A review of textile industry: Wet processing, environmental impacts, and effluent treatment methods. <i>Environmental Quality Management</i>, 27(3), 31–50. https://doi.org/10.1002/tqem.21538</p> <p>McEachern, M.G., Middleton, D. & Cassidy, T. (2020) Encouraging Sustainable Behaviour Change via a Social Practice Approach: A Focus on Apparel Consumption Practices. <i>Journal of Consumer Policy</i> 43, 397–418. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10603-020-09454-0</p> <p>Resta, B., & Dotti, S. (2015). Environmental impact assessment methods for textiles and clothing. In <i>Handbook of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of textiles and clothing</i> (pp. 149-191). Woodhead publishing. https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100169-1.00008-3</p> <p>Ribeiro, P. R., Batista, P., Mendes-Palma, F., Pintado, M., & Oliveira-Silva, P. (2023). Consumers' Engagement and Perspectives on Sustainable Textile Consumption. <i>Sustainability</i>, 15(22), 15812. https://doi.org/10.3390/su152215812</p> <p>van Duin, D. (2021). Using Behavioural Insights to Increase Textile Recycling in Urban Households: Testing Two Nudging Interventions. https://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:039b61b3-8723-4d01-a828-f19b5e14c9d4</p> <p>You, S., Cheng, S., & Yan, H. (2009). The impact of textile industry on China's environment. <i>International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education</i>, 2(1), 33–43. https://doi.org/10.1080/17543260903055141</p>
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9. Appendices

9.1 Appendix a. Outline of the NTNU workshop organized to finalize the challenges

CircleUp project meeting in Oxford, March 6-7, 2025

Workshop organized by NTNU

Goal of today: Design household challenges in detail according to the SSBC stages

Within this workshop, we will create circular economy challenges for the households across the four different domains at both individual and community level. We have already defined various actions/behaviours before, which are now grouped together in one Excel table. Today's task is to design some overarching challenges and prepare them in more detail.

Needed: post-its, 4 grouped tables, 4 flip charts, markers, Excel table printouts with all behaviours/actions (one for each person)

To do: Place post-its, markers, flip charts, Excel table printouts with all the behaviours/actions on the four different tables, each table representing one domain (food, textiles, packaging, electronics)

23 participants (5-6 persons per group)

Step 0. Introduction (20 min)

Step 1. Individual work (15 min)

Task:

Formulate relevant behaviours/actions into overarching challenge(s)

Identify any behaviours/actions that need to be discarded or rewritten

Determine if additional challenges are needed and create new ones

Instructions:

Each participant works individually at their table

Use the post-its to write down challenges and place them on the table

Output:

A set of initial challenges for each domain

Step 2. Partner work (25 min)

Task and instructions:

Pair up with someone from your table (another country)

Discuss the challenges you designed briefly

Identify differences and try to match them

Is it possible to classify the challenge both at the individual level/household level and the community level? Discuss and try to design the challenges for individual level + community level

Output:

A new list of initial challenges for each domain

Step 3. Table discussion (60 min)

Task and instructions:

Form a group at your table and find one challenge you will be working on

Try to answer the questions in detail according to the SSBC stages:

Stage 1: Predecisional stage:

- a. How to make social and personal norms salient?
- b. How to enhance problem awareness?
- c. How to enhance goal setting and goal attachment?

Stage 2: Preactional stage:

- a. Which information about pros and cons of different behavioural alternatives is needed?

Stage 3: Actional stage:

- a. How to offer specific planning information?

Stage 4: Postactional stage:

- a. Develop strategies against temptation and relaps
- b. Provide behavioural feedback

Output:

Questions answered for the different stages for all the challenges

Step 4. Group discussion (30 min)

Task and instructions:

Each team presents the challenge in more detail with flip chart

Time for questions and feedback

Example of a Challenge:

Food: Avoid food waste (individual level)

No food waste during one week

Stage 1: Predecisional stage:

WHY SHOULD I CARE ABOUT THE PROBLEM?

Part a

a. Make social and personal norms salient:

Share some stories of households successfully avoiding food waste

Share average food waste per household (per country)

Share successful public campaigns (e.g., wrap UK)

Share some stories about restaurants taking steps to reduce food waste

Share some stories about people bringing leftovers to work for lunch

b. Enhance problem awareness:

Environmental impact of food waste: food waste contributes to greenhouse emissions

Producing food uses different resources such as water, energy and land use

Economic impact of food waste

Food security of food waste

Show the amount of food that is thrown away or wasted: up to 30% of food is wasted, +- 70% comes from households

Show how food waste varies between countries

Think about: Make use of graphs and pictures

c. Enhance goal setting and goal attachment:

-Commitment: Accepting the challenge

What should be reached in the end of the stage? Goal intention=commitment, accepting the food waste challenge

We should ask one diagnostic question every now and then to define the stage.

Example of the question: I will try to not have food waste for one (two or three) week

Part b

Think about the integration of the tools in every stage (in different forms):

*LCA tool

People answer LCA questions about what and how much food they wasted per day.

Using LCA to evaluate the environmental impact of different kind of food waste: in terms of greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, energy consumption

*System modelling learning

Use the model to run simulations under different scenarios. Stimulate the impact of improved food storage technique, impact of costs by reducing food waste

*Smart bins

Gives constant feedback

*Material advisor

No visit of material advisor in stage 1

*Information

(look at b in part a)

Stage 2: Preactional stage

WHAT CAN I DO INSTEAD?

Part a

a. Provide information about pros and cons of reducing food waste

Food waste is not a concern of people in top 5 among UK citizens (youtube wrap)

Show people the drivers and barriers of reducing food waste:

drivers: costs

barriers: being more prepared, take some time, cultural norms, food not looking good

b. Enhance perceived behavioural control

Learn about how to use leftovers in dishes to reduce food waste

Suggest alternatives: freezing food, become more creative in cooking

What should be reached in the end of the stage? Behavioural intention: I intent to use my leftovers in dishes

Part b

Think about the integration of the tools in every stage (in different forms):

*LCA tool

People answer LCA questions about what and how much food they wasted per day.

Using LCA to evaluate the environmental impact of different kind of food waste: in terms of greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, energy consumption

*System modelling learning

Use the model to run simulations under different scenarios. Stimulate the impact of improved food storage technique, impact of costs by reducing food waste

*Smart bins

Gives constant feedback

*Material advisor

No visit of material advisor in stage 2

*Information

Stage 3: Actional stage:

HOW DO I IMPLEMENT THIS IN MY EVERYDAY LIFE?

Part a

a. Offer specific planning information:

-Knowledge base questions offered in a quiz with true or false questions on storing food

Offer tips on how to avoid food waste:

How to plan, buy, store, or prepare food to help reduce the amount that gets thrown away

How to plan?

make a meal plan for the week ahead

check what you already have in the fridge and freezer before shopping

make a detailed shopping list for daily or monthly shopping

How to buy?

not buying too much food

avoid impulse shopping (e.g., tempted by special offers)

Storage and management:

Learn about food storage management

keep track of food in the fridge/freezer

Learn about labels (best before date) and check labels for storage information (e.g., where and how long)

using up food before it goes past its use by/best before date

Label your products before storing them in fridge or freezer

keep track of items that have been opened

Prepare food:

Making a meal by combining foods/random ingredients

Don't cook too much. Think about portion sizing

using up leftovers as part of another meal

batch cooking (making several portions to store for later)

Implementation intention: I have made plans when, where and what I will buy and how I will store it

Part b

Think about the integration of the tools in every stage (in different forms):

*LCA tool

People answer LCA questions about what and how much food they wasted per day.

Using LCA to evaluate the environmental impact of different kind of food waste: in terms of greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, energy consumption

*System modelling learning

Use the model to run simulations under different scenarios. Stimulate the impact of improved food storage technique, impact of costs by reducing food waste

*Smart bins

Gives constant feedback

*Material advisor

The material advisor can visit the household in stage 3 and help with the planning.

*Information

Stage 4: Postactional stage

HOW DO I PREVENT TO FALL BACK INTO OLD HABITS?

part a

a. Develop strategies against temptation and relapse:

don't buy food in excessive amounts due to special offers, talk with others about preferences for freshness, variety

At the end of the challenge: Reflect on how this challenge made you feel and the difficulties you encountered. This will provide valuable insights into how you can continue to reduce your food waste beyond the challenge.

b. Provide behavioural feedback

part b

Think about the integration of the tools in every stage (in different forms):

*LCA tool

People answer LCA questions about what and how much food they wasted per day. Using LCA to evaluate the environmental impact of different kind of food waste: in terms of greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, energy consumption

*System modelling learning

Use the model to run simulations under different scenarios. Stimulate the impact of improved food storage technique, impact of costs by reducing food waste

*Smart bins

Gives constant feedback

*Material advisor

The material advisor will not visit the households in stage 4

*Information

Example of a challenge: Share electronics

Electronics: Share electrical devices with others from your close neighbourhood

Start a database and share 3 electronics you would otherwise buy with people from the neighbourhood

No SSBC stages

9.2 Appendix b. Results from the internal survey

Rapport

Internal_CircleUp

Innhold

Which partner do you represent?	17
How big do you think the environmental impact of this sector overall in the households?	18
How often do households make decisions in this area?	18
How easy do you think it is for households to change behaviour within this sector?	19
How relevant of the behaviour from the perspective of user partners?	19
Overall, which of the four sectors we look at do you consider the most important for CircleUp taking these dimensions into account?	19
Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?	20
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	21
Which definition do you suggest?	21
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	21
How else can this behaviour be measured?	21
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	22
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	22
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	23
Which other barriers do you see?	23
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	24
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	24
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	24
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	24
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	25
Which definition do you suggest?	25
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	25
How else can this behaviour be measured?	25
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	26
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	26
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	27
Which other barriers do you see?	27
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	28
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	28
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	28
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	29
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	29
Which definition do you suggest?	29
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	29
How else can this behaviour be measured?	29
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	30
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	30

Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	31
Which other barriers do you see?	31
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	32
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	32
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	32
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	32
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	33
Which definition do you suggest?	33
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	33
How else can this behaviour be measured?	33
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	34
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	34
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	35
Which other barriers do you see?	35
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	35 - 36
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	36
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	36
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	37
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Which definition do you suggest?	37
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How else can this behaviour be measured?	37
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Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	38
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	39
Which other barriers do you see?	39
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	40
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	40
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	40
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	41
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	41
Which definition do you suggest?	41
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	41
How else can this behaviour be measured?	41
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	42
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	42
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	43
Which other barriers do you see?	43
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	44

Which other intervention ideas do you have?	44
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	44
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	45
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Which definition do you suggest?	45
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Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	46
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	46
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	47
Which other barriers do you see?	47
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	48
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	48
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	48
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	48
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	49
Which definition do you suggest?	49
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How else can this behaviour be measured?	49
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	49 - 50
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	50
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	50 - 51
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Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	66
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	66 - 67
Which other barriers do you see?	67
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	67
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	68
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	68
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	68
Is there anything else you want to say for the food sector?	68
Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?	69
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	69

Which definition do you suggest?	69
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Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	85 - 86
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Which other intervention ideas do you have?	99
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	99
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	99
Is there anything else you want to say for the packaging sector?	99
Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?	99 - 100
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	100
Which definition do you suggest?	100 - 101
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How else can this behaviour be measured?	101
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Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	102
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	102 - 103
Which other barriers do you see?	103
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Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	106
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	106 - 107
Which other barriers do you see?	107

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Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	110
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	110 - 111
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Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	112
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How else can this behaviour be measured?	117
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Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	118
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	118 - 119
Which other barriers do you see?	119
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	120
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	120
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	120

Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	120
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	120 - 121
Which definition do you suggest?	121
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	121
How else can this behaviour be measured?	121
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	121 - 122
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	122
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	122 - 123
Which other barriers do you see?	123
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	123 - 124
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	124
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	124 - 125
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	125
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	125
Which definition do you suggest?	125
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	125
How else can this behaviour be measured?	125 - 126
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	126
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	126
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	126 - 127
Which other barriers do you see?	127
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	127 - 128
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	128
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	128
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	128 - 129
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	129
Which definition do you suggest?	129
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	129
How else can this behaviour be measured?	129
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	129 - 130
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	130
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	130 - 131
Which other barriers do you see?	131
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	131 - 132
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	132
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	132
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	132
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	132 - 133
Which definition do you suggest?	133

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	133
How else can this behaviour be measured?	133
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	133 - 134
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	134
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	134 - 135
Which other barriers do you see?	135
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	135 - 136
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	136
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	136
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	136
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	136
Which definition do you suggest?	136 - 137
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	137
How else can this behaviour be measured?	137
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	137 - 138
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	138
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	138 - 139
Which other barriers do you see?	139
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	139 - 140
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	140
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	140
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	140
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	140 - 141
Which definition do you suggest?	141
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	141
How else can this behaviour be measured?	141
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	141 - 142
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	142
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	142 - 143
Which other barriers do you see?	143
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	143 - 144
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	144
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	144
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	144
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	144
Which definition do you suggest?	144 - 145
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	145
How else can this behaviour be measured?	145
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	145 - 146

Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	146
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	146 - 147
Which other barriers do you see?	147
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	147 - 148
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	148
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	148
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	148
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	148 - 149
Which definition do you suggest?	149
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	149
How else can this behaviour be measured?	149
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	149 - 150
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	150
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	150 - 151
Which other barriers do you see?	151
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	151 - 152
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	152
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	152
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	152
Is there anything else you want to say for the clothing sector?	152 - 153
Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?	153
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	154
Which definition do you suggest?	154
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	154
How else can this behaviour be measured?	154
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	154 - 155
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	155
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	155 - 156
Which other barriers do you see?	156
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	156 - 157
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	157
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	157
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	157
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	158
Which definition do you suggest?	158
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	158
How else can this behaviour be measured?	158
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	158 - 159
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	159

Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	159 - 160
Which other barriers do you see?	160
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	160 - 161
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	161
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	161
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	161
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	162
Which definition do you suggest?	162
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	162
How else can this behaviour be measured?	162
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	162 - 163
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	163
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	163 - 164
Which other barriers do you see?	164
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	164 - 165
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	165
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	165
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	165
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	165 - 166
Which definition do you suggest?	166
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	166
How else can this behaviour be measured?	166
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	166 - 167
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	167
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	167 - 168
Which other barriers do you see?	168
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	168 - 169
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	169
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	169
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	169
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	169
Which definition do you suggest?	169 - 170
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	170
How else can this behaviour be measured?	170
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	170 - 171
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	171
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	171 - 172
Which other barriers do you see?	172
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	172 - 173

Which other intervention ideas do you have?	173
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	173
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	173 - 174
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	174
Which definition do you suggest?	174
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	174
How else can this behaviour be measured?	174
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	174 - 175
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	175
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	175 - 176
Which other barriers do you see?	176
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	176 - 177
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	177
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	177
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	177
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	177 - 178
Which definition do you suggest?	178
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	178
How else can this behaviour be measured?	178
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	178 - 179
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	179
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	179 - 180
Which other barriers do you see?	180
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	180 - 181
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	181
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	181
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	181
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	182
Which definition do you suggest?	182
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	182
How else can this behaviour be measured?	182
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	182 - 183
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	183
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	183 - 184
Which other barriers do you see?	184
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	184 - 185
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	185
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	185
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	185

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	185 - 186
Which definition do you suggest?	186
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	186
How else can this behaviour be measured?	186
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	186 - 187
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	187
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	187 - 188
Which other barriers do you see?	188
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	188 - 189
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	189
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	189
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	189
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	189 - 190
Which definition do you suggest?	190
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	190
How else can this behaviour be measured?	190
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	190 - 191
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	191
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	191 - 192
Which other barriers do you see?	192
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	192 - 193
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	193
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	193
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	193
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	193 - 194
Which definition do you suggest?	194
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	194
How else can this behaviour be measured?	194
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	194 - 195
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	195
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	195 - 196
Which other barriers do you see?	196
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	196 - 197
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	197
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	197
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	197
Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?	197 - 198
Which definition do you suggest?	198
How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?	198

How else can this behaviour be measured?	198
Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?	198 - 199
Which other drivers do you consider relevant?	199
Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?	199 - 200
Which other barriers do you see?	200
Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?	200
Which other intervention ideas do you have?	200 - 201
Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?	201
Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?	201
Is there anything else you want to say for the electronics sector?	201

Internal survey to prepare the selection / definition of target behaviours for CircleUp

Dear partners,

On 22nd April, we will have the first internal workshop in WP2 of CircleUp. To prepare the exercise, I ask you to answer the following survey. It will take a bit of your time, but I hope that it will make the workshop more substantial and more structured.

Thank you for answering until the **18th of April**.

To structure the survey here and to limit the time you spend on the survey, you will be asked in every section first, which three behaviours within this area you consider most relevant and then be asked to answer further questions only for them.

☑ Which partner do you represent?

Antall svar: 19

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Riga Technical University	2	10.5%	10.5%
Norwegian University of Science and Technology	3	15.8%	15.8%
Hochschule Ruhr West	2	10.5%	10.5%
Conservation Education and Research Trust	1	5.3%	5.3%
Verbraucherzentrale NRW	2	10.5%	10.5%
Prosperkolleg e.V.	2	10.5%	10.5%
Naturvernforbundet (Friends of the Earth Norway)	1	5.3%	5.3%
Latvian Rural Forum	2	10.5%	10.5%
Oxfordshire County Council	3	15.8%	15.8%
NOVA School of Science and Technology University Lisbon	1	5.3%	5.3%

Assessing the relevance of the four sectors overall

The impact of our interventions depend on several factors. Overall, I first ask you to give an assessment of the following impact dimensions of the general sectors on the following dimensions:

☰ How big do you think the environmental impact of this sector overall in the households?

Rader	● very small	● small	● medium	● large	● very large
Food	0	1	1	9	8
Packaging	0	4	6	1	8
Textiles	0	1	6	6	6
Electronics	0	1	7	8	3

☰ How often do households make decisions in this area?

Rader	● about every day	● about once a week	● about once a month	● about once a year	● less than once a year
Food	18	1	0	0	0
Packaging	17	2	0	0	0
Textiles	0	4	14	1	0
Electronics	0	0	7	11	1

☰ How easy do you think it is for households to change behaviour within this sector?

Rader	● very difficult	● difficult	● neither/nor	● easy	● very easy
Food	1	6	5	5	2
Packaging	2	5	5	6	1
Textiles	2	8	6	2	1
Electronics	3	9	4	3	0

☰ How relevant of the behaviour from the perspective of user partners?

Rader	● Out of scope	● Low importance	● medium importance	● high importance	● Top priority
Food	1	0	3	12	3
Packaging	1	1	4	9	4
Textiles	1	0	6	9	3
Electronics	1	0	8	9	1

☑ Overall, which of the four sectors we look at do you consider the most important for CircleUp taking these dimensions into account?

Antall svar: 19

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Food	7	36.8%	36.8%
Packaging	6	31.6%	31.6%
Textiles	3	15.8%	15.8%
Electronics	3	15.8%	15.8%

Now we go more into detail for the Food sector

In the matrix on the CircleUp server, you have entered a list of behaviour regarding circular economy behaviour in the food sector. Here you can find a structured overview of what has been collected. In the following, you are asked to select three of these behaviours that you consider particularly interesting for our project and there we go into detail with some follow-up questions.

☑ Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?

Antall svar: **19** Randomisert: **Ja**

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Analyze current food habits / assess status quo	7	36.8%	36.8%
Plan purchases to avoid food waste / only buy what is needed	11	57.9%	57.9%
Avoid buying too large packages of food	2	10.5%	10.5%
Buying loose food	1	5.3%	5.3%
Cooking - only what they will eat / Utilize leftovers in the kitchen	7	36.8%	36.8%
If too much purchased , give to neighbours , friends, family, community fridges	4	21.1%	21.1%
Know about "best before date"	0	0%	0%
Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting)	4	21.1%	21.1%
Know about approx. environmental impact of different food categories (e.g. meat, fresh vegetables , canned goods, ...)	10	52.6%	52.6%
Buy local food	7	36.8%	36.8%
Buy seasonal food	2	10.5%	10.5%
Store foods correctly to increase their shelf-life	2	10.5%	10.5%

The following question regard "Analyze current food habits / assess status quo"

✓ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	4	57.1%	57.1%
No, I propose to change the definition.	3	42.9%	42.9%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
Self-reflection and shopping list Planning a week of grocery shopping. What is bought and consumed. And analyse the shopping at the beginning; how much meat, how many vegetables, organic content, etc. I also think families plan their shopping per week, singles are more likely to go shopping every day. The Smart Bins are used to measure waste and what they have thrown away.
People should also consider/learn about more eco-friendly alternatives that could replace what they eat currently. People should learn about the different benefits and costs of specific food consumption decisions (including side benefits e.g. for one's health). An algorithm that would summarize those benefits and costs and options for change would be cool to have to minimize effort on the participant's side.
Add information about changing/improving food preparation habits, incl. acquiring new skills and information about new food recipes etc.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Making a list of food items thrown away in a specific time span	6	85.7%	85.7%
During the home visit: Check the freezer / fridge / storage facilities	3	42.9%	42.9%
I have an idea for further measures	2	28.6%	28.6%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Self-reflection and shopping list; before, inbetween and at the end. I don't think we should start in the fridge, but when they make their decision and they do that when they write the shopping list (considered buying) and when they go to the supermarket (affect buying). If we start here, changing behaviour is easier from my point of view.
It would be important to understand the quantity of food purchased during a specific time span (receipts) + information about household size and meals at home or eating habits (for example, if both parents work from home, they may have lunch at home, while children - at school).

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	4	57.1%	57.1%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	7	100%	100%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	3	42.9%	42.9%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	28.6%	28.6%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	5	71.4%	71.4%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	6	85.7%	85.7%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	6	85.7%	85.7%
Not perceived important enough	5	71.4%	71.4%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	14.3%	14.3%
Negative emotions (does not feel good)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Needs consistency in behaviour	2	28.6%	28.6%
Other barriers	1	14.3%	14.3%

☰ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
financial pressure

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 7 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Diary / list of foods thrown away from fridge	4	57.1%	57.1%
Social game ("home mining challenge" for fridge, freezer, kitchen storage)	3	42.9%	42.9%
Mock competition for who owns the oldest piece of stored food	1	14.3%	14.3%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	6	85.7%	85.7%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Triggering normative goals / framing	3	42.9%	42.9%
Other intervention ideas	2	28.6%	28.6%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

The things on the list are all right. I would in the first place like to see a usable/professional recommender algorithm that would be based on my habits recommend possible changes and credibly quantify benefits and costs of those changes.

Additional features could include things from the list (e.g., gamification).

The first one could be expanded to include not only a list of thrown away but also the financial losses.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	6	85.7%	85.7%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	14.3%	14.3%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

To find a motivation why to do it.

The following question regard "Plan purchases to avoid food waste / only buy what is needed"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 11

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	6	54.5%	54.5%
No, I propose to change the definition.	5	45.5%	45.5%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 5

Svar
In addition include meal planning and list writing. I've seen some guidance that suggests for a weekly shop, planning for 5 of 7 days' meals creates capacity for changes of plan (possibly a meal out) and also a "leftovers day". Recent data from UK resource charity WRAP suggests 39% of edible food waste is food bought but not eaten in time https://wrap.org.uk/sites/default/files/2024-01/WRAP-Food-Surplus-and-Waste-in-the-UK-Key-Facts%20November-2023.pdf
Create a weekly plan, i.e. prepare a meal plan and the associated shopping list for the entire week; a portion planner helps with planning. Based on this write a list of the foods and ingredients you need throughout the week, thereby look at what you have in your fridge or cupboards; leftovers can be used creatively (food upcycling); food after the "best before date" might still be usable. Once a week, do a bulk purchase to buy all the food that you can stock up on for a week with correct storage. Eating together is good for the family atmosphere and for implementing the plan.
It does not only matter that the right quantity of foods is purchased, but also what types of foods.
Meal plan to purchase what you needed, allow for spontaneity (takeaway, eating out etc) by utilising freezer etc
In addition to current definition some sense of planning purchases to correspond to particular meals or recipes rather than just purchasing random ingredients.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 11

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Monitoring monthly / weekly spendings on food	6	54.5%	54.5%
Shopping lists	4	36.4%	36.4%
I have an idea for further measures	1	9.1%	9.1%
Weighing food waste	4	36.4%	36.4%
Food waste diary	10	90.9%	90.9%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Interviews about shopping practices

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 11

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	9	81.8%	81.8%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	2	18.2%	18.2%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	5	45.5%	45.5%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	5	45.5%	45.5%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	7	63.6%	63.6%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	8	72.7%	72.7%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	4	36.4%	36.4%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	7	63.6%	63.6%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	7	63.6%	63.6%
Other drivers	1	9.1%	9.1%
Liking to find creative solutions	0	0%	0%
Valuing food	7	63.6%	63.6%
Being a role model	1	9.1%	9.1%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Stable food purchase routines Good planning abilities

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 11

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	7	63.6%	63.6%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	9.1%	9.1%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	8	72.7%	72.7%
Not perceived important enough	7	63.6%	63.6%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	6	54.5%	54.5%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	2	18.2%	18.2%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	2	18.2%	18.2%
Negative emotions (does not feel good)	2	18.2%	18.2%
Needs consistency in behaviour	1	9.1%	9.1%
Other barriers	2	18.2%	18.2%
Lack of planning capacity	8	72.7%	72.7%
Lack of knowledge / skills	7	63.6%	63.6%
Do not know what is at home when shopping	6	54.5%	54.5%
Offers in store feel like one is saving money (e.g., get 3 for 2)	9	81.8%	81.8%
No plan for what to cook	10	90.9%	90.9%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Having small children with unpredictable food consumption
family situation - young children etc

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 11 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	8	72.7%	72.7%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	5	45.5%	45.5%
Triggering normative goals / framing	4	36.4%	36.4%
Other intervention ideas	2	18.2%	18.2%
Providing information	5	45.5%	45.5%
Shopping lists / templates	6	54.5%	54.5%
Recipies for left-overs	5	45.5%	45.5%
Give-aways like containers for buying loose quantities	3	27.3%	27.3%
Portion planning tool	6	54.5%	54.5%
Implementation intention "next time I am in the supermarket and find something nice in the "close to expiry date fridge" I will only buy it if it replaces something else that I planned to buy so that I do not buy more food.	4	36.4%	36.4%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Probably covered in the information section but advice on storage/freezing of leftovers and fresh produce that is approaching use-by date
Concerted action with shops to support customers in buying loose quantities, better planning the next purchase and exchanging leftovers with other households.
Social game.
Consulting through advisor.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 11

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	10	90.9%	90.9%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	9.1%	9.1%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

They need cooking skills and planning skills. And they have to have interest in changing their habits.

The following question regard "Avoid buying too large packages of food"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	1	50%	50%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	50%	50%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

The main issue with bulk buying large packages of food relates to fresh produce with a relatively short-shelf life. Contrastingly, large packages of food that can be stored for long periods can create a positive outcome by saving money per kg and reducing the relative weight of the packaging

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Making a list of food items thrown away in a specific time span	2	100%	100%
Interview / survey: self-report of food leftovers gone bad	2	100%	100%
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Food purchases (self-report)	2	100%	100%
Food purchases (receipts)	1	50%	50%
Weighing food waste	1	50%	50%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	2	100%	100%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	50%	50%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	100%	100%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	2	100%	100%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	50%	50%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	50%	50%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	1	50%	50%
Other drivers	1	50%	50%

☰ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Frugality

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	50%	50%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	50%	50%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	2	100%	100%
Not perceived important enough	2	100%	100%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	50%	50%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	50%	50%
Negative emotions (does not feel good)	0	0%	0%
Needs consistency in behaviour	1	50%	50%
Other barriers	1	50%	50%
Feeling to save money when buying larger quantities	2	100%	100%
Lack of knowledge	2	100%	100%
No plan for the consumption during the week	2	100%	100%
Recommendation to have a food stock at home for emergencies	1	50%	50%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Unclear food consumption of family members (young children, teenagers, unclear who will be there for dinner, ...) Culture for having plenty of food available (e.g., at parties)

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	50%	50%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	2	100%	100%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	100%	100%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	50%	50%
Other intervention ideas	1	50%	50%
Consulting through advisor (knowledge)	1	50%	50%
Meal / portion planning session / knowledge on meal sizes / recipies	2	100%	100%
Give-aways (shopping list templates ; meal plans)	1	50%	50%
Calculator to show how much money is lost by buying "cheaper" large packages and not using them	2	100%	100%
Wrap food waste action	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
prompts (stickers to put on phone or shopping bag) TOTE bag with "only buy as much as you can eat" or something more fun with the same message

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	2	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Buying loose food"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 1

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	1	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Loose food purchases in relation to packaged (self-report)	1	100%	100%
Loose food purchases in relation to packaged (receipts)	0	0%	0%
Food purchase diary	1	100%	100%
weighing food waste	0	0%	0%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 1 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	100%	100%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	100%	100%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	100%	100%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	100%	100%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	100%	100%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 1 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	100%	100%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (does not feel good)	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	1	100%	100%
Feeling to save money when buying larger quantities	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge	0	0%	0%
Shorter shelf life of unpackaged products	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns	0	0%	0%
Lack of access to loose food items	1	100%	100%
More complicated shopping (need to go to several shops)	1	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
No reusable bags or boxes available in the store.

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	100%	100%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	1	100%	100%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	1	100%	100%
Consulting through advisor (knowledge)	1	100%	100%
Meal / portion planning session / knowledge on meal sizes / recipies	0	0%	0%
Give-aways (containers for purchase of loose food items)	1	100%	100%
Calculator to show how much money is lost by buying "cheaper" large packages and not using them	0	0%	0%
Wrap food waste action	0	0%	0%
Provide knowledge on how to store unpackaged food	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Selling of reusable bags or containers in the shop for a cheap price.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 1

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	1	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Cooking - only what they will eat / Utilize leftovers in the kitchen"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	7	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Food diary (what has been prepared, what has been eaten, what has been stored, what has been thrown away)	5	71.4%	71.4%
weighing food waste	3	42.9%	42.9%
Weighing the amount of edible food leftovers within the food waste	2	28.6%	28.6%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	6	85.7%	85.7%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	42.9%	42.9%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	4	57.1%	57.1%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	14.3%	14.3%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	3	42.9%	42.9%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Attractivity of employing 'traditional knowledge'; creativity + improvisation	3	42.9%	42.9%
Knowledge / skills / know how (recipies, storage)	6	85.7%	85.7%
Ability to make decisions	2	28.6%	28.6%
Hygiene knowledge	1	14.3%	14.3%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	5	71.4%	71.4%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	14.3%	14.3%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	6	85.7%	85.7%
Not perceived important enough	5	71.4%	71.4%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	14.3%	14.3%
Negative emotions (does not feel good)	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge about portion sizes	3	42.9%	42.9%
Hygiene concerns	1	14.3%	14.3%
Not planning cooking and eating	5	71.4%	71.4%
Negative side effects (warm food in the fridge might have negative environmental effects)	0	0%	0%
Amount of leftovers is not known before which might interfere with food planning	3	42.9%	42.9%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	28.6%	28.6%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	3	42.9%	42.9%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Triggering normative goals / framing	2	28.6%	28.6%
Other intervention ideas	1	14.3%	14.3%
Consulting through advisor (knowledge)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Meal / portion planning session / knowledge on meal sizes / recipes	4	57.1%	57.1%
Give-aways (containers for storage of leftover food items)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Provide knowledge on how to store unpackaged food	3	42.9%	42.9%
Tools to measure ingredients	1	14.3%	14.3%
Nudges (Stickers on the fridge "Hello, we are here") "Eat me first" box	2	28.6%	28.6%
Encourage "left-over" dinners (maybe even regularly)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Recipes for leftovers (apps like Big Oven)	2	28.6%	28.6%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Information on being able to use some of the leftovers even after the "best before date".

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	6	85.7%	85.7%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	14.3%	14.3%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Mental capacity to make decisions and plan etc.

The following question regard "If too much purchased, give to neighbours, friends, family, community fridges"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	2	50%	50%
No, I propose to change the definition.	2	50%	50%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

Also that households look to take up and use things offered by other households or restaurants (definition needs to be two-way)

If too much purchased, give to neighbours, friends, family, community fridges. This can be Done using social media and different platforms.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 4

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	25%	25%
Food diary (what has been prepared, what has been eaten, what has been stored, what has been thrown away)	2	50%	50%
weighing food waste	1	25%	25%
Weighing the amount of edible food leftovers within the food waste	1	25%	25%
Self-report on how much is given to others	4	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Short documentation with a picture of what has been given away. Food diary as suggested seems to be too time consuming to me.

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	25%	25%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	75%	75%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	3	75%	75%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	25%	25%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	50%	50%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	25%	25%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	3	75%	75%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	2	50%	50%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	1	25%	25%
Has a positive social side-effect	2	50%	50%
Knowledge / skills / know how (recipies, storage)	0	0%	0%
Ability to make decisions	1	25%	25%
Hygiene knowledge	1	25%	25%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

As this behavior is highly dependend on the social structures and also on the spatial arrangements (e.g. living in a tower block, living in a rural neighborhood, the living environment should be considered (influences percieved behavioral control).

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	25%	25%
Social norms against the behaviour in the neighbourhood (awkwardness)	3	75%	75%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	4	100%	100%
Not perceived important enough	2	50%	50%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	25%	25%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	2	50%	50%
Negative emotions (embarrassing , shyness)	1	25%	25%
Other barriers	1	25%	25%
Hygiene concerns	1	25%	25%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

No system for communication or contact. Mismatch of supply and demand. Hard to adopt last-minute offers of food into weekly food plan.

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	4	100%	100%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	1	25%	25%
Triggering normative goals / framing	2	50%	50%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Consulting through advisor (knowledge)	1	25%	25%
Give-aways (containers for storage of leftover food items)	2	50%	50%
Provide knowledge on how to store unpackaged food	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste to show the amount of the problem	0	0%	0%
Pointing out community fridges / places for food sharing	4	100%	100%
Making agreements between neighbours removing the awkwardness	2	50%	50%
Providing people with "conversation starters" about sharing	2	50%	50%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	3	75%	75%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	25%	25%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Ability to carry/transport food to different places (they may have food deliveries if they are not capable of visiting shops themselves, which makes it difficult to take uneaten food elsewhere)

The following question regard "Know about 'best before date'"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Self-report of number of items used after "best before"	0	0%	0%
weighing food waste	0	0%	0%
Testing knowledge of people about the different concepts	0	0%	0%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Ability to make decisions	0	0%	0%
Hygiene knowledge	0	0%	0%
Confidence in ability to detect food gone bad	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (feels uncomfortable)	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns	0	0%	0%
Lack of ability to decide if food is still good (smell test, visual test)	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Normalizing the behaviour by showing other people do the same	0	0%	0%
Providing information about the best before date	0	0%	0%
Providing information on hygiene and food security	0	0%	0%
Fridge magnets	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Dispose leftovers correctly (e.g., composting)"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	3	75%	75%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	25%	25%

☒ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
For Oxfordshire we would want to refer to "recycling" rather than "disposing" of food waste as we have close to 100% coverage of separate food waste collections. Recent studies suggest unopened food that has gone off is most likely to be disposed of in general waste even where the household already recycles some of their food. Add the words "Empty any gone off food from its packaging into the food recycling bin" For leftovers, having an option to allow them to be re-invented into a new dish if still edible.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	25%	25%
weighing food waste correctly disposed	2	50%	50%
Weighing food waste in the wrong bins (e.g., residual waste) depending on the local system	2	50%	50%
Waste disposal diary	3	75%	75%

☒ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
If weights can be attributed specifically to the type of food wasted that would be useful but this may become onerous and beyond the scope of what we are asking. Some food waste is unavoidable and may come from using fresh rather than pre-prepared produce (peelings etc) the diaries and any weighing system need to recognise this difference

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	3	75%	75%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	25%	25%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	25%	25%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	2	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	50%	50%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	3	75%	75%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	25%	25%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	3	75%	75%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	3	75%	75%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Ability to make decisions	1	25%	25%
Confidence in ability to detect food gone bad	2	50%	50%
Having the opportunity (e.g., separate collection of food waste; space for own compost)	4	100%	100%
Good sorting habits / routines	3	75%	75%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	4	100%	100%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	25%	25%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	3	75%	75%
Not perceived important enough	4	100%	100%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	25%	25%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	25%	25%
Negative emotions (feels uncomfortable)	1	25%	25%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns	2	50%	50%
No collection of organic waste	3	75%	75%
No space for compost	3	75%	75%
Concern about smell	4	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	25%	25%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	2	50%	50%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	3	75%	75%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	25%	25%
Other intervention ideas	1	25%	25%
Normalizing the behaviour by showing other people do the same	3	75%	75%
Providing information about collection of organic waste	4	100%	100%
Providing information on hygiene and smell of composting	3	75%	75%
Providing equipment for home-composting	3	75%	75%
Bin stickers showing food items and where they should be sorted	3	75%	75%
Home composting social network page for sharing tips	2	50%	50%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

We have found residents are interested to know "how" the food waste we collect is recycled

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	3	75%	75%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	25%	25%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

They need to have access to space for composting (but there could be a kitchen composter, but then you need to be able to do something with the soil you produce) or a collection scheme for organic waste.

The following question regard "Know about approx. environmental impact of different food categories (e.g. meat, fresh vegetables, canned goods, ...)"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 10

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient .	7	70%	70%
No, I propose to change the definition .	3	30%	30%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

Raise the resident's awareness of the carbon cost of food, food miles, shopping local and in season, including the water, energy and land consumption.

same as above but i would add human rights and social fairness in food production especially in the poorer producing countrys.

Maybe it would be good to rather point this into habit change, instead of knowledge: "adopt a planetary health diet" or "eat more plant-based" or else

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 10

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	10%	10%
Measuring knowledge in questionnaire / quiz	8	80%	80%
Environmental footprint calculator tool	7	70%	70%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

kitchen diaries; shopping lists/receipts

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 10

Randomisert: Ja

☰ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

As in the cases of previous and subsequent long lists of factors, possibly there might be correlations with any of these. Also, whether a factor plays a role or not is likely going to be individual and situation specific.

health reasons; perceiving vegetarian/vegan foods as fashionable or normal

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 10

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	7	70%	70%
Social norms against the behaviour	2	20%	20%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	8	80%	80%
Not perceived important enough	3	30%	30%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	4	40%	40%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	2	20%	20%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	6	60%	60%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	2	20%	20%
Insufficient information on environmental footprint of products	5	50%	50%
Some food types (e.g., meat) are highly ideologically charged	5	50%	50%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

Comment: Knowledge is not a behavior, it might be a prerequisite for relevant behaviors. It might serve as a foundation for informed decision-making and discussion. In my point of view even well-educated individuals that have an interest in the environment may lack awareness of the environmental footprint associated with various products.

potential cost of changing diet etc

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 10

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	4	40%	40%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	3	30%	30%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	7	70%	70%
Triggering normative goals / framing	6	60%	60%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Providing information about environmental footprints of food products	6	60%	60%
The footprint calculator itself is an intervention	5	50%	50%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 10

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	8	80%	80%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	2	20%	20%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

Households may need the budget to eat produce which is in season, and some produce may be more expensive - with the cost of living crisis, we need to do due diligence of creating and identifying diet/food shopping ideas that don't break the bank - so can be adapted and used in the future by different demographics

Interest in this issue.

The following question regard "Buy local food"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	4	57.1%	57.1%
No, I propose to change the definition.	3	42.9%	42.9%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
i would consider local food depending on the relative distance of transportation. Local food is produced in the (e.g.) top 10% of the nearest farming facilities. In my opinion, environmental impact also depends on factors that are not related to locality of food and so, locality should not be exclusively be explained by environmental impacts. Maybe local food production is much worse than other because the plants need to be warmed or cooled down.
Include also definition of what is local.
... and also because they support local farmers and producers

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Percentage of local food in total purchases (self-report / diary)	7	100%	100%
Percentage of local food in total purchases (receipts)	3	42.9%	42.9%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	3	42.9%	42.9%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	6	85.7%	85.7%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	6	85.7%	85.7%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	28.6%	28.6%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	14.3%	14.3%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about transporting food too far)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	1	14.3%	14.3%
Supporting local businesses	4	57.1%	57.1%
Food safety / security	1	14.3%	14.3%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Easy availability of local foods. Local markets aren't sufficient for people working in a regular job. Local foods need to be available in local supermarkets all days.

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	6	85.7%	85.7%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	3	42.9%	42.9%
Not perceived important enough	2	28.6%	28.6%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Insufficient information on origin of products	3	42.9%	42.9%
Economic barriers (more expensive)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Insufficient info on environmental footprint of local vs. non-local food	3	42.9%	42.9%
Lack of access to local produce	4	57.1%	57.1%
More complicated shopping (need to go to several places)	6	85.7%	85.7%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	14.3%	14.3%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	3	42.9%	42.9%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	14.3%	14.3%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Information about local food distributors	6	85.7%	85.7%
Information on labelling of local produce	4	57.1%	57.1%
Information about environmental footprints of local vs. non-local food	5	71.4%	71.4%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	6	85.7%	85.7%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	14.3%	14.3%

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

might depend on types of food.
exotic fruits might not be available in any of the countries we scope.

The following question regard "Buy seasonal food"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	1	50%	50%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	50%	50%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
this is just additional to the definition: we might add examples.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	50%	50%
Percentage of seasonal food in total purchases (self-report / diary)	2	100%	100%
Percentage of seasonal food in total purchases (receipts)	1	50%	50%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
I think we'll need both, diary and receipts, as seasonal food may be bought in places that doesn't give receipts, e.g. weekly markets. Also, buying seasonal food is highly associated with the amount of fresh food in total purchases, so we might measure that as well.

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	50%	50%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	50%	50%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	50%	50%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	100%	100%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Supporting local businesses	0	0%	0%
Food safety / security	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	2	100%	100%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	50%	50%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	50%	50%
Not perceived important enough	1	50%	50%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	50%	50%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	50%	50%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	2	100%	100%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Insufficient information on seasonality of products	1	50%	50%
Economic barriers (more expensive)	0	0%	0%
Insufficient info on environmental footprint of seasonal vs. un-seasonal food	1	50%	50%
Lack of access to seasonal produce	1	50%	50%
More complicated shopping (need to go to several places)	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	50%	50%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	1	50%	50%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	100%	100%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	50%	50%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Providing information about environmental footprints of food products	1	50%	50%
Information about seasonal food / season calendar as give away	2	100%	100%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	2	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Store foods correctly to increase their shelf-life"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	2	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Kitchen diaries	2	100%	100%
Advisers take a look into peoples fridges and kitchens in general	2	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	50%	50%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	100%	100%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	50%	50%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about wasting food)	2	100%	100%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Appreciation of food	1	50%	50%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	50%	50%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	50%	50%
Not perceived important enough	1	50%	50%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	50%	50%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge	2	100%	100%
Complexity of the task	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	2	100%	100%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	50%	50%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Providing information about correct storage and how to "refresh" food	2	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	2	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☰ Is there anything else you want to say for the food sector?

Antall svar: 5

Svar
I think we should cover something from avoid, reuse/reduce, to recycle.
Ich glaube nicht, dass wir damit anfangen sollten, wenn sie ihre Entscheidung treffen. Das tun sie, wenn sie die Einkaufsliste schreiben (Kaufüberlegungen) und wenn sie in den Supermarkt gehen (Kaufentscheidungen). Wenn wir hier ansetzen, ist es aus meiner Sicht einfacher, das Verhalten zu ändern.
Giving information isn't enough to make people do things - we need to make it easy for them
A special focus in the food segment should be given to the reduction of animal based products and hightening plant based foods due to the big climate impact of meat and milk products.
I think the food sector is the one where behaviour change can go a long way, while other areas, especially ICT and technology, require more action by other stakeholders (esp. regulatory). But there are also a lot of players in Germany who already work on this issue. So its worth discussing whether we want to make CE in food consumption our priority.

Now we go more into detail for the Packaging sector

In the matrix on the CircleUp server, you have entered a list of behaviour regarding circular economy behaviour in the packaging sector. Here you can find a structured overview of what has been collected. In the following, you are asked to select three of these behaviours that you consider particularly interesting for our project and there we go into detail with some follow-up questions.

☑ Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?

Antall svar: 19 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Avoid packaging	14	73.7%	73.7%
Buy products with reduced packaging	8	42.1%	42.1%
Buy easily recyclable packaging	3	15.8%	15.8%
Buy products with recycled packaging (not just recyclable)	5	26.3%	26.3%
Reuse packaging (e.g., paper bags), reuse of plastic shopping bags	8	42.1%	42.1%
Use reusable containers // bags	14	73.7%	73.7%
Sort and dispose of used packaging	4	21.1%	21.1%
Buy recycled products made from packaging	0	0%	0%

The following question regard "Avoid packaging"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 14

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	9	64.3%	64.3%
No, I propose to change the definition.	5	35.7%	35.7%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 5

Svar
I suggest separating between buying less packaged products and using reusable containers. These are two behaviours.
People alter their shopping habits to use stores and markets that sell loose produce
People buy less packaged products. People use reusable bags or containers for example for food purchases.
additionally: people know where to get products with little/no packaging
Avoid packning materials of unknown origin or the mix of materials in same product.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste (packaging)	10	71.4%	71.4%
Self-report	12	85.7%	85.7%

☒ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	5	35.7%	35.7%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	21.4%	21.4%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	5	35.7%	35.7%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	6	42.9%	42.9%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	7	50%	50%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	11	78.6%	78.6%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person (zero-waste lifestyle)	9	64.3%	64.3%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	8	57.1%	57.1%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about unnecessary packaging)	3	21.4%	21.4%
Other drivers	3	21.4%	21.4%

☰ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

Cheap offers for reusable bags or containers in shops and discount in take-aways.
Easily available possibilities to buy loose food in shops and take-aways.
High tax on plastic food packaging.

Most products are overpacked and reusable packaging is not available in most cases. So it's not the consumer but the producers that need to change the offer.

I believe that access is the main hindrance today, and that we should discuss a change in policy too. Do we really need all this packaging? Could we standardize some, or all, packaging types.

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	10	71.4%	71.4%
Social norms against the behaviour	5	35.7%	35.7%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	10	71.4%	71.4%
Not perceived important enough	8	57.1%	57.1%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	6	42.9%	42.9%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	3	21.4%	21.4%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	3	21.4%	21.4%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	1	7.1%	7.1%
Unavailability of unpackaged product alternatives	13	92.9%	92.9%
Hygiene concerns	6	42.9%	42.9%
Preferred brands have only packaged products	10	71.4%	71.4%

☰ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

To buy the alternative with reduced packaging/recycled packaging is in conflict with other factors you find important such as locally produced, eco-label etc.

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

Consulting through advisors.

make it easy to get unpackaged items - online shopping etc does not offer the choice, refill shops can require separate trips which can be difficult in time pressured lives, need space to store if purchase in bulk

to highten the disposability of unpacked food and reusable food containers.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 14

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

time
potentially money (unpackaged can be more expensive)

certain amount of time and financial resources needed for high-scale replacement of packaging; certain amount of reduction is possible for everyone

The following question regard "Buy products with reduced packaging"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 8

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	7	87.5%	87.5%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	12.5%	12.5%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
I read this to refer to reduced or better still NO packaging where possible.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste (packaging)	7	87.5%	87.5%
Self-report	6	75%	75%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	3	37.5%	37.5%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	12.5%	12.5%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	3	37.5%	37.5%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	4	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	5	62.5%	62.5%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	6	75%	75%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person (zero-waste lifestyle)	5	62.5%	62.5%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	6	75%	75%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about unnecessary packaging)	2	25%	25%
Other drivers	1	12.5%	12.5%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

see above. availability of less packed products is actually low and needs to be risen.

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	5	62.5%	62.5%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	12.5%	12.5%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	7	87.5%	87.5%
Not perceived important enough	4	50%	50%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	3	37.5%	37.5%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	3	37.5%	37.5%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	3	37.5%	37.5%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Unavailability of product alternatives with less packaging	8	100%	100%
Preferred brands have only heavily packaged products	6	75%	75%
Lack of knowledge about the specific impact of the packaging of one product compared to another	7	87.5%	87.5%
Negative effects for durability of the product (e.g., food)	5	62.5%	62.5%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 8 Randomisert: Ja

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

needs to be easy and same/lower costs.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 8

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

time and money

The following question regard "Buy easily recyclable packaging"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	2	66.7%	66.7%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	33.3%	33.3%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Buy easily recyclable packaging and avoiding packaging that consists of mixed materials or is not labeled with how to recycle it.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste (packaging)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Self-report	3	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	3	100%	100%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	33.3%	33.3%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	33.3%	33.3%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about non-recyclable packaging)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	33.3%	33.3%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	33.3%	33.3%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	33.3%	33.3%
Not perceived important enough	2	66.7%	66.7%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of availability of easily recyclable packages	3	100%	100%
Lack of knowledge about recyclability of packaging components	3	100%	100%
Packages that are easily recyclable might look less appealing	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	66.7%	66.7%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Providing information about what are easily recyclable packages	2	66.7%	66.7%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	3	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Buy products with recycled packaging (not just recyclable)"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 5

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	4	80%	80%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	20%	20%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Consumers buy packaging with a high proportion of recycled materials.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste (packaging)	4	80%	80%
Self-report	5	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	2	40%	40%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	2	40%	40%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	40%	40%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	2	40%	40%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	3	60%	60%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	4	80%	80%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	20%	20%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	3	60%	60%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about non-recycled packaging)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	3	60%	60%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	20%	20%
Not perceived important enough	2	40%	40%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	20%	20%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	20%	20%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of availability of recycled packages	4	80%	80%
Packages that are recycled might look less appealing	4	80%	80%

☰ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 5

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Reuse packaging (e.g., paper or plastic bags)"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 8

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	6	75%	75%
No, I propose to change the definition.	2	25%	25%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
This category appears very similar to "Use reusable containers, bags"
Smaller packaging can be also reused to e.g. use as trash bags.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 8 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste (packaging)	3	37.5%	37.5%
Self-report (reuse diary)	8	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	5	62.5%	62.5%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	5	62.5%	62.5%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	25%	25%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	5	62.5%	62.5%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	6	75%	75%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	7	87.5%	87.5%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	25%	25%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	5	62.5%	62.5%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 8 Randomisert: Ja

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 8 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	25%	25%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	3	37.5%	37.5%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	4	50%	50%
Triggering normative goals / framing	3	37.5%	37.5%
Other intervention ideas	1	12.5%	12.5%
Stickers that can be put on the door to prompt people to remember their containers	6	75%	75%
Implementation intentions intervention (making mental cues that get activated when going shopping)	8	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Suggestions of how to reuse packaging

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 8

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	7	87.5%	87.5%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	12.5%	12.5%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
The householders need to have capacity and ability to plan

The following question regard "Use reusable containers, bags"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 14

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	11	78.6%	78.6%
No, I propose to change the definition.	3	21.4%	21.4%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
This category appears very similar to "Reuse packaging"
Reused for any relevant purpose, not just shopping but also e.g. storage, thrash bags.
I would broaden it, as reusable containers can also be used for fast food or delivery services: Households are using reusable bags or containers, including deposit containers, to go shopping or for delivery services.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste (packaging)	7	50%	50%
Self-report (reuse diary)	12	85.7%	85.7%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	8	57.1%	57.1%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	8	57.1%	57.1%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	8	57.1%	57.1%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	7	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	8	57.1%	57.1%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	10	71.4%	71.4%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	6	42.9%	42.9%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	13	92.9%	92.9%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	3	21.4%	21.4%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 3

- Svar**
- Forgetting the containers when going shopping, spontaneous shopping trips
 - Aesthetic issues (bags or containers being crumpled/faded/scuffed etc.). Having to store these somewhere for future use.
 - see above. availability of reusable food containers in supermarkets is too low.

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 14 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	6	42.9%	42.9%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	5	35.7%	35.7%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	7	50%	50%
Triggering normative goals / framing	3	21.4%	21.4%
Other intervention ideas	4	28.6%	28.6%
Forming social groups	4	28.6%	28.6%
Providing information on reusable containers	9	64.3%	64.3%
Deposit systems for reusable packaging	7	50%	50%
Give-away of reusable containers (coffee cups, bees wrap, steel containers), maybe personalized	10	71.4%	71.4%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 4

Svar
Prompts for the door to remind to take containers to the shop Establishing routines to always have some containers in the bike bag/hand bag/car
Consulting through advisors. Cheap offers for reusable bags or containers in shops. Significant portion of food items available in shops that can be purchased by using reusable bags or containers: concerted action with shops to inform households and to increase share of food items.
see above. availability of reusable food containers in supermarkets is too low.
preparing infrastructure for wasteless shopping with advisers (shopping basket with reusable containers + bags); training wasteless shopping in groups

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 14

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	12	85.7%	85.7%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	2	14.3%	14.3%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

The householders need to have capacity and ability to plan

certain amount of spare time and headspace for trying out major shifts in shopping behaviour; certain financial resources, e.g. for buying in unwrapped stores

The following question regard "Sort and dispose of used packaging"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	4	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 4

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste (packaging) in the different fractions	2	50%	50%
Self-report (recycling diary)	4	100%	100%
Observation in the waste bins	3	75%	75%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	33.3%	33.3%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	3	100%	100%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	66.7%	66.7%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	2	66.7%	66.7%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	4	100%	100%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	4	100%	100%
Not perceived important enough	3	75%	75%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	2	50%	50%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	2	50%	50%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	1	25%	25%
Limited storage space	4	100%	100%
Unclear sorting system / unsure what goes where	3	75%	75%
Compound material makes sorting difficult	4	100%	100%
Hygiene concerns	1	25%	25%
Smell	1	25%	25%
Lack of knowledge on how clean packaging needs to be	4	100%	100%
Cleaning to cumbersome	4	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
There is no infrastructure (or it is inefficient - not close to the house; incurs higher costs) to facilitate packaging separation.

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	50%	50%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	3	75%	75%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	4	100%	100%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	25%	25%
Other intervention ideas	1	25%	25%
Forming social groups	1	25%	25%
Providing information on recycling system (what, where, how)	3	75%	75%
Providing information on what goes where and how to prepare	2	50%	50%
Providing information on what is easy to recycle	3	75%	75%
Give-away of home storing containers for separated materials	1	25%	25%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Prompts for the kitchen and other places where waste is produced.
Organizing the personal space in a way that makes it easy to sort where you are.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	3	75%	75%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	25%	25%

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

the correct infrastructure (within the house and provided by the waste collection service in their area)

The following question regard "Buy recycled products"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Receipts	0	0%	0%
Self-report (purchase diary)	0	0%	0%
Observation in the household	0	0%	0%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt about non-recycled products)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Recycled products unavailable	0	0%	0%
Favourite brands do not offer recycled products	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Providing information about which products are recycled	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☰ Is there anything else you want to say for the packaging sector?

Antall svar: 4

Svar

Provide information on what happens to the plastic that are collected for recycling in Europe. Many people dont believe in the system and therefore dont bother to sort plastics.

If people prefer convinience food, it's very difficult to avoid packaging.

Giving information isn't enough to make people do things - we need to make it easy for them

it can be very difficult for householders to have the ability to influence packaging as its often presented to them rather than them having the choice

Packaging isn't always the worst thing, it can help to extend the shelf life of the product or enable less carbon intensive transportation. it can also protect the product during transport - if someone buys something unpackaged but its bruised or broken when they get home and throw it away then the impact is greater than the packaging used to protect it

Consumers have few options in choosing less packed/unpacked/reusable packed products. The goal has to be to change what is offered in stores and supermarkets. Only the least necessary packaging ought to be allowed by law.

Now we go more into detail for the Textiles sector

In the matrix on the CircleUp server, you have entered a list of behaviour regarding circular economy behaviour in the textiles sector. Here you can find a structured overview of what has been collected. In the following, you are asked to select three of these behaviours that you consider particularly interesting for our project and there we go into detail with some follow-up questions.

Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?

Antall svar: 19 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Reduce buying clothes	15	78.9%	78.9%
Buy durable and repairable textiles	7	36.8%	36.8%
Avoid returns with online orders	0	0%	0%
Buy second-hand clothes	9	47.4%	47.4%
Swap clothes with others	3	15.8%	15.8%
Take better care of textiles / Repair damaged textiles	9	47.4%	47.4%
Reuse and upcycle, recombine clothes to new outfits	4	21.1%	21.1%
Give to clothing collections / Sort and dispose damages textiles	2	10.5%	10.5%
Give to friends and relatives	3	15.8%	15.8%
Resell	2	10.5%	10.5%
Renting clothes	1	5.3%	5.3%
Encourage the use of real (washable) nappies	0	0%	0%
Encourage the use of reusable period products	0	0%	0%

The following question regard "Reduce buying clothes"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 15

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient .	13	86.7%	86.7%
No, I propose to change the definition .	2	13.3%	13.3%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

I think I would start off with reducing buying new clothes. This seems to be easier.

Definition should focus on reduction of buying new clothes and perhaps the total number of clothes individually owned at one time. But in theory a high-throughflow of second hand clothes is not an issue.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 15

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	3	20%	20%
Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought	15	100%	100%
Self-report of origin and fibres of clothes bought	5	33.3%	33.3%
Self-report of where clothes were bought from	9	60%	60%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

Gathering information on the amount of clothing already owned would be essential to provide a driver for not buying more. Using this information with factors (carbon, energy, water) to let people know the impact of what they already own

Questionnaire to fill in, what bought, where bought, when bought and if returned online; purchase receipts could help for details.

shopping receipts

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 15

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	11	73.3%	73.3%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	4	26.7%	26.7%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	6	40%	40%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	11	73.3%	73.3%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	3	20%	20%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	12	80%	80%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person (system criticism)	6	40%	40%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	7	46.7%	46.7%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	1	6.7%	6.7%
Other drivers	3	20%	20%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	5	33.3%	33.3%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
what do i really save in the end: saving money und CO2 footprint
Buying new clothes often is not about the clothes but about getting dopamine. So, we have to tackle this issue somehow.
It becomes fashionable to wear second-hand clothes

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 15

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	6	40%	40%
Social norms against the behaviour	9	60%	60%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	6.7%	6.7%
Not perceived important enough	4	26.7%	26.7%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	7	46.7%	46.7%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	5	33.3%	33.3%
Negative emotions	1	6.7%	6.7%
Other barriers	1	6.7%	6.7%
Lack of overview of the clothes you already have	6	40%	40%
Desire for something new	11	73.3%	73.3%
Marketing from the industry	10	66.7%	66.7%
Changes in fashion	11	73.3%	73.3%

≡ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Status, want to be in fashion, which of course depends on the type. Keyword fast fashion.

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 15 Randomisert: Ja

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 2

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 15

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

All households can reduce the number of clothes that they purchase, but the big 'wins' would be focusing on those that buy higher than the average number of clothes anyway, or those that purchase lots of fast fashion

See comment above.

depends of the level of clothes bought before; households should still fulfill their basic needs with regard to clothing;

The following question regard "Buy durable and repairable textiles"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	7	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	2	28.6%	28.6%
Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought	5	71.4%	71.4%
Self-report of origin and fibres of clothes bought	3	42.9%	42.9%
Self-report of where clothes were bought from	5	71.4%	71.4%
Self-report of quality of clothes (hard to define, though), maybe price, maybe special brands that offer repairing?	5	71.4%	71.4%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

Report if the clothing purchased has an environmental certification. GOTS-certified, nordic swan ecolabel etc.

look at lifespan of existing clothes in the wardrobe. Difficult to measure on new clothes bought

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	4	57.1%	57.1%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	42.9%	42.9%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	4	57.1%	57.1%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	14.3%	14.3%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	6	85.7%	85.7%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person (system criticism)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	7	100%	100%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	2	28.6%	28.6%
Other drivers	1	14.3%	14.3%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	4	57.1%	57.1%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
need to have the income level that enables you to make this choice

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 7

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	28.6%	28.6%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	5	71.4%	71.4%
Triggering normative goals / framing	3	42.9%	42.9%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Providing information about durability and repairing	6	85.7%	85.7%
Creating social "repairing" groups	3	42.9%	42.9%
Shopping dairy	3	42.9%	42.9%
How do you recognize durable / repairable clothes	7	100%	100%
interactive city adventure for younger participants	2	28.6%	28.6%
Blogs / social media / influencers showing diversity and sustainable styles	5	71.4%	71.4%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	6	85.7%	85.7%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	14.3%	14.3%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

depends on time, economic status and interest in fashion/following trends

The following question regard "Avoid returns with online orders"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought online	0	0%	0%
Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought online and returned	0	0%	0%
Receipts of online clothes orders	0	0%	0%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person (system criticism)	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge about which sizes fit	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge about how colours or clothes look like	0	0%	0%
Changes in fashion	0	0%	0%
Desire for something new	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Standardized clothes sizes	0	0%	0%
Online tools to identify the correct size	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Buy second-hand clothes"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 9

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	9	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	2	22.2%	22.2%
Purchase diary: Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought (both new and used)	7	77.8%	77.8%
Receipts of clothes purchases (both new and used)	4	44.4%	44.4%
Circular story	4	44.4%	44.4%
Report also the category the clothes are in (e.g. children, underwear, trowsers, ...)	5	55.6%	55.6%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Questionnaire to fill in, what bought, where bought, when bought and if returned online; purchase receipts could help for details (same like reduce). timescales for clothing purchases may be beyond this project

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	4	44.4%	44.4%
Social norms against the behaviour	3	33.3%	33.3%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	5	55.6%	55.6%
Not perceived important enough	2	22.2%	22.2%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	4	44.4%	44.4%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns	6	66.7%	66.7%
Fear of not belonging / social exclusion	5	55.6%	55.6%
Changes in fashion	4	44.4%	44.4%
Desire for something new	6	66.7%	66.7%
Increasing prices of high-quality second-hand clothes	3	33.3%	33.3%
Lack of infrastructure (second-hand shops, ...)	4	44.4%	44.4%
Not everything that is needed at a specific time is available second-hand at the right point in time	7	77.8%	77.8%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 9 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	3	33.3%	33.3%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	4	44.4%	44.4%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Triggering normative goals / framing	3	33.3%	33.3%
Other intervention ideas	1	11.1%	11.1%
Second-hand fashion blogs	6	66.7%	66.7%
Role models	6	66.7%	66.7%
Interactive city adventure	2	22.2%	22.2%
Information about infrastructure	4	44.4%	44.4%
Information about the impact of the clothing industry	4	44.4%	44.4%
Apps supporting access to second-hand clothes	6	66.7%	66.7%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Consulting through advisors. Stimulating groups of young people to exchange clothes and buy second-hand, e.g., by a second-hand party.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 8

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	8	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Swap clothes with others"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	3	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	33.3%	33.3%
Purchase diary: Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought and swapped	3	100%	100%
Report also the category the clothes are in (e.g. children, underwear, trowsers, ...)	2	66.7%	66.7%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
going through the stock of clothes a household has at several points in time.

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	3	100%	100%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	3	100%	100%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	3	100%	100%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	3	100%	100%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	3	100%	100%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	3	100%	100%
Used clothes are fashionable (vintage)	3	100%	100%
Individuality rather than sticking to the current fashion	2	66.7%	66.7%
Swaping clothes is a fun social activity	3	100%	100%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	2	66.7%	66.7%
Social norms against the behaviour	2	66.7%	66.7%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	3	100%	100%
Not perceived important enough	2	66.7%	66.7%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	3	100%	100%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	2	66.7%	66.7%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns	2	66.7%	66.7%
Fear of not belonging / social exclusion	1	33.3%	33.3%
Changes in fashion	3	100%	100%
Desire for something new	3	100%	100%
Lack of infrastructure for swapping	3	100%	100%
Not everything that is needed at a specific time is available at the right point in time	3	100%	100%
Sized might not fit	3	100%	100%
One might feel obliged to take clothes one does not want to fulfil the rules of swapping	2	66.7%	66.7%
Takes time to organize	3	100%	100%
Requires large enough local network of people in similar living conditions / with similar tastes	2	66.7%	66.7%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	66.7%	66.7%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Triggering normative goals / framing	2	66.7%	66.7%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Swap challenge	2	66.7%	66.7%
Information about infrastructure	3	100%	100%
Information about the impact of the clothing industry	3	100%	100%
Establishing social groups	2	66.7%	66.7%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	1	33.3%	33.3%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	2	66.7%	66.7%

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Households need to have a network they can swap in.
Mental capacity of planning, organising and physical ability to get to the swap shops etc (location and time)

The following question regard "Take better care of textiles / Repair damaged textiles"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 9

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	8	88.9%	88.9%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	11.1%	11.1%

☒ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Taking better care of textiles involves adopting practices that prolong the lifespan of clothing items and other textile goods. This includes conscientious laundering habits, such as washing garments at appropriate temperatures and using gentle detergents to minimize wear and tear. Additionally, individuals can employ storage methods that prevent damage, such as hanging garments instead of folding to avoid creases. Repairing damaged textiles entails fixing minor tears, loose seams, or missing buttons to prevent further deterioration and extend the usability of the item. This behavior encompasses a mindset of sustainability and resourcefulness, valuing the longevity of textiles and reducing waste in the fashion industry.

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 9 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	3	33.3%	33.3%
Purchase diary: Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought and swapped	4	44.4%	44.4%
Measuring knowledge and skills for maintaining and repairing clothes	5	55.6%	55.6%

☒ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

Self-report in diary on repair of textiles (self-repair or by repair service).

circular stories; reporting repair + certain care measures in household diary, e.g. + foto

In the diary, it is noted whether any maintenance or repair work was carried out during a specified period of time.

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	6	66.7%	66.7%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	4	44.4%	44.4%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	5	55.6%	55.6%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	6	66.7%	66.7%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	5	55.6%	55.6%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	8	88.9%	88.9%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	1	11.1%	11.1%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	2	22.2%	22.2%
Emotional attachment to old clothes	6	66.7%	66.7%
Interest in skills like sewing	7	77.8%	77.8%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	5	55.6%	55.6%
Social norms against the behaviour	2	22.2%	22.2%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	6	66.7%	66.7%
Not perceived important enough	4	44.4%	44.4%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	4	44.4%	44.4%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	11.1%	11.1%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	3	33.3%	33.3%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Fear of not belonging / social exclusion	3	33.3%	33.3%
Changes in fashion	6	66.7%	66.7%
Desire for something new	6	66.7%	66.7%
Changes in size	5	55.6%	55.6%
Lack of skills	9	100%	100%
Lack of equipment	6	66.7%	66.7%
Time constraints	6	66.7%	66.7%
Costly to repair things	8	88.9%	88.9%
Lack of knowledge about repair services	8	88.9%	88.9%
Clothes have too low quality to justify repairing effort	9	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	22.2%	22.2%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	6	66.7%	66.7%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	5	55.6%	55.6%
Triggering normative goals / framing	2	22.2%	22.2%
Other intervention ideas	1	11.1%	11.1%
Swap challenge	2	22.2%	22.2%
Information about repairing infrastructure	6	66.7%	66.7%
Information about the impact of the clothing industry	2	22.2%	22.2%
Courses for self-repair	6	66.7%	66.7%
Information about adequate washing practices / washing labels	6	66.7%	66.7%
Information about airing instead of washing	5	55.6%	55.6%
Creating "product stories" (what has the piece of clothes experienced) -> strengthen identification	5	55.6%	55.6%
Give-away repairing kit	4	44.4%	44.4%
Visiting repair shops	6	66.7%	66.7%
Organizing repair workshops, making repairing a social event	9	100%	100%
Task to repair your favourite piece of clothes	4	44.4%	44.4%
Possibility to loan equipment	5	55.6%	55.6%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Consulting through advisors.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 9

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	7	77.8%	77.8%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	2	22.2%	22.2%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Mental and physical capacity/ability to repair- being handy and skilled to sew with an interest in it
People need some interest in repairing.

The following question regard "Reuse and upcycle, recombine clothes to new outfits"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	4	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 4

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	25%	25%
Purchase diary: Self-report of number / amount of clothes bought and upcycled / recombined	3	75%	75%
Measuring knowledge , skills and confidence for upcycling clothes	2	50%	50%
Qualitative interviews (starting with circular stories)	3	75%	75%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Questionnaire to fill in, what bought, where bought, when bought and if returned online; purchase receipts could help for details (same like reduce).

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	2	50%	50%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	2	50%	50%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	25%	25%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	2	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	25%	25%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	25%	25%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	50%	50%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	25%	25%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	2	50%	50%
Interest in skills like sewing	2	50%	50%
Creativity	3	75%	75%
Inspiration from social media	3	75%	75%

☰ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	2	50%	50%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	25%	25%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	3	75%	75%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	25%	25%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	25%	25%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of skills / creativity	4	100%	100%
Lack of equipment	2	50%	50%
Time constraints	2	50%	50%
Clothes have too low quality to be upcycled / recombined	1	25%	25%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	25%	25%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	50%	50%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Swap challenge	2	50%	50%
Information about repairing infrastructure	2	50%	50%
Information about the impact of the clothing industry	2	50%	50%
Courses for upcycling / recombining	3	75%	75%
Creating "product stories", photo competition	2	50%	50%
Organizing upcycling workshops, making upcycling a social event	3	75%	75%
Task to upcycle favourite piece of clothes	2	50%	50%
Possibility to loan equipment	2	50%	50%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	3	75%	75%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	25%	25%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

skilled in tailoring already

The following question regard "Give to clothing collections / Sort and dispose damages textiles"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	2	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 2 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Waste diary: report number and type of clothes given to recycling	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste: kg and ideally type of fibre going to recycling	1	50%	50%
Self-report of clothes recycling practices	2	100%	100%
Qualitative interviews	1	50%	50%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	50%	50%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	50%	50%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	50%	50%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	50%	50%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	2	100%	100%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	50%	50%
Not perceived important enough	1	50%	50%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	50%	50%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of recycling infrastructure	2	100%	100%
Time constraints / effort to deliver	1	50%	50%
Lack of knowledge about how and where to recycle fibres, what can/cannot be recycled	2	100%	100%
Lack of trustworthiness of the collectors	0	0%	0%
Difficulty to decide what can be reused and what should be recycled	2	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	50%	50%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	1	50%	50%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Information about recycling infrastructure	2	100%	100%
Information about what can be recycled and what not	2	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	2	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Give to friends and relatives"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	3	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☒ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste: kg and ideally type of fibre going to recycling	0	0%	0%
Self-report of practices of giving clothes to friends / family	2	66.7%	66.7%
Qualitative interviews	1	33.3%	33.3%

☒ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	33.3%	33.3%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	33.3%	33.3%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	2	66.7%	66.7%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	0	0%	0%
Strengthening community	2	66.7%	66.7%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	33.3%	33.3%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	1	33.3%	33.3%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Time constraints / effort to deliver	0	0%	0%
Lack of network of people in similar living situations in close proximity	2	66.7%	66.7%
Hygiene concerns	1	33.3%	33.3%
Clothes are too low quality to give away	1	33.3%	33.3%
Feeling ashamed of the clothes given away	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	33.3%	33.3%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Triggering normative goals / framing	2	66.7%	66.7%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Talking about existing networks	3	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	3	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Resell"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	2	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Weighing waste: kg and ideally type of fibre going to recycling	2	100%	100%
Self-report of practices of reselling clothes	2	100%	100%
Qualitative interviews	2	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (earning money)	2	100%	100%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	50%	50%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	50%	50%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	50%	50%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	100%	100%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	2	100%	100%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	2	100%	100%
Having fun selling via online platforms	2	100%	100%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	50%	50%
Not perceived important enough	1	50%	50%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	50%	50%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	50%	50%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Time constraints / effort to sell / deliver	2	100%	100%
Lack of network / infrastructure	2	100%	100%
Hygiene concerns	1	50%	50%
Clothes are too low quality to sell	2	100%	100%
Feeling ashamed of the clothes given away	0	0%	0%
Too low prices	2	100%	100%
Lack of knowledge how to do this	2	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 2

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	50%	50%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	1	50%	50%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	1	50%	50%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Workshop showing how to do this	2	100%	100%
Directory of services	1	50%	50%
Organizing in person events	1	50%	50%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 2

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	2	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Renting clothes"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 1

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	1	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☒ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Self-report of number of clothes that are rarely used	1	100%	100%
Self-report of practices of renting clothes	1	100%	100%
Qualitative interviews	0	0%	0%
Report on the number of purchases fir "one off" events like weddings , graduations	0	0%	0%

☒ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	100%	100%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	100%	100%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Social issues (e.g., knowing about working conditions in the textile industry)	0	0%	0%
Saving space	1	100%	100%
Being able to wear "better" clothes than could be afforded to be bought	1	100%	100%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	100%	100%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	100%	100%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Time constraints / effort	1	100%	100%
Lack of network / infrastructure	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns	1	100%	100%
Too costly (no asset at the end)	1	100%	100%
Lack of knowledge how to do this	1	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 1 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Directory of services / apps	1	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 1

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	1	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Encourage the use of real (washable) nappies"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Self-report of nappies used and type	0	0%	0%
Qualitative interviews	0	0%	0%
Weighing the amount of one-way nappies in the waste	0	0%	0%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Time constraints / effort	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns / disgust	0	0%	0%
Too costly	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge how to do this	0	0%	0%
Too much choice	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Give-away: Trial kit of washable nappies	0	0%	0%
Providing know-how on how to do this	0	0%	0%
Information about the impact of one-way products	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Encourage the use of reusable period products"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Self-report of period products used and type	0	0%	0%
Qualitative interviews	0	0%	0%
Weighing the amount of one-way period products in the waste	0	0%	0%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Hygiene concerns / disgust	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge how to do this	0	0%	0%
Too much choice	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Give-away: Trial kit of reusable period products	0	0%	0%
Providing know-how on how to do use them	0	0%	0%
Information about the impact of one-way products	0	0%	0%

Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

Is there anything else you want to say for the clothing sector?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

clothing choices are strongly associated with identity and status expression for many people. Also, we should consider the tendency for impulse buying in some individuals (applies to food sector, too).

need to make this easy and the social norm for people to do. not just provide information.

Social norms prob more important for this than some of the other aspects being discussed as this is very visible. eating leftovers for tea is more 'private'

range of materials, price, availability - needs to be easy to shop for

leasing and clothes libraries are very sensible and resource-efficient new forms of clothing, but the lack of infrastructure + relatively high prices makes it unlikely that such habits will be adopted in our case study.

Now we go more into detail for the Electronics sector

In the matrix on the CircleUp server, you have entered a list of behaviour regarding circular economy behaviour in the electronics sector. Here you can find a structured overview of what has been collected. In the following, you are asked to select three of these behaviours that you consider particularly interesting for our project and there we go into detail with some follow-up questions.

Which of the following behaviours do you consider most important to focus on in CircleUp (not generally!)?

Antall svar: 19

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Question the need of buying electronics / assess status quo	8	42.1%	42.1%
Buy durable and repairable electronics	9	47.4%	47.4%
Buy second-hand electronics	5	26.3%	26.3%
Buy products with service options	1	5.3%	5.3%
Share products (e.g., drills, lawn mowers)	14	73.7%	73.7%
Use rental / leasing offers	3	15.8%	15.8%
Repair damaged electronics	9	47.4%	47.4%
Update / upgrade electronics	0	0%	0%
Give electronics to friends and family / other people	4	21.1%	21.1%
Give electronics to proper recycling	3	15.8%	15.8%
Resell	0	0%	0%
Take care of the products	0	0%	0%

The following question regard "Question the need of buying electronics / assess status quo"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 8

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	8	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	12.5%	12.5%
Shopping diary	6	75%	75%
Qualitative interviews	7	87.5%	87.5%
Expenses for electronics / receipts	1	12.5%	12.5%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

As well as a shopping diary, an inventory of existing electronics will provide an assessment of the amount of resource already owned and identify anything that could be surplus. Applying conversion factors (carbon, energy?) could help residents understand the embedded impact of what they already own,

A key circular activity as well as not buying more could also be distributing working surplus, repairing non-working and recycling items genuinely at end of life

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	6	75%	75%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	2	25%	25%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	12.5%	12.5%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	4	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	4	50%	50%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	25%	25%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	5	62.5%	62.5%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	2	25%	25%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	1	12.5%	12.5%
annoyance with cheap products / programmed obsolescence	6	75%	75%
Attachment to old devices	2	25%	25%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	2	25%	25%
Social norms against the behaviour	2	25%	25%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	12.5%	12.5%
Not perceived important enough	1	12.5%	12.5%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	6	75%	75%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	2	25%	25%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	2	25%	25%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	1	12.5%	12.5%
Lack of maintainance of the old product (e.g., operating system)	7	87.5%	87.5%
Low costs of many items	8	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Want to own the latest "shit"

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 8

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	12.5%	12.5%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	3	37.5%	37.5%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	4	50%	50%
Triggering normative goals / framing	2	25%	25%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Collaborative in-house inspection of status-quo	3	37.5%	37.5%
fostering emotional attachment (stories from the life of the product)	4	50%	50%
Information about the impact of electronics production	4	50%	50%
Home mining challenge "finding the lost treasure"	4	50%	50%
Nudging sticker for phone: "do I really need this and for how long will I use this"?	4	50%	50%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 7

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	6	85.7%	85.7%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	14.3%	14.3%

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
probably not all households will buy the same electrical devices in project time

The following question regard "Buy durable and repairable electronics"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 9

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	8	88.9%	88.9%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	11.1%	11.1%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
.. longer and its possible to repair them.

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	2	22.2%	22.2%
Shopping diary	7	77.8%	77.8%
Qualitative interviews	5	55.6%	55.6%
Expenses for electronics / receipts	5	55.6%	55.6%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Self-report might be useful here. "Buy durable and repairable electronics" refer to more expensive products which are not bought on a weekly basis.
adviser protocols

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	7	77.8%	77.8%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	11.1%	11.1%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	5	55.6%	55.6%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	5	55.6%	55.6%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	3	33.3%	33.3%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	7	77.8%	77.8%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	1	11.1%	11.1%
Other drivers	1	11.1%	11.1%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	1	11.1%	11.1%
annoyance with cheap products / programmed obsolescence	8	88.9%	88.9%
Savings in the future / investment	7	77.8%	77.8%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
pleasure of owning a high quality product

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	3	33.3%	33.3%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	3	33.3%	33.3%
Not perceived important enough	4	44.4%	44.4%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	2	22.2%	22.2%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	11.1%	11.1%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	2	22.2%	22.2%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	3	33.3%	33.3%
Higher initial costs / lack of funding	7	77.8%	77.8%
lack of information on durability	6	66.7%	66.7%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
No information on reparability No repairable products available Repairable products of lower quality / less fashionable (Fairphone)
will it last? will it be updated? will it continue to work for the length of time I need or will i need to buy another? how much will a repair cost? how easy is it to repair?
How do I know that an electronic good is really of higher quality. Only because it costs more its not automatically longer lasting than a cheaper product.

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

Information on where to find repairable product alternatives

info on availability/cost of repair

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 9

Svar

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 3

Svar

Households need to be able to afford more expensive products in the first place

can be more expensive, need the funds available to do this

financial resources to buy a high-quality product

The following question regard "Buy second-hand electronics"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 5

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	5	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	2	40%	40%
Shopping diary	4	80%	80%
Qualitative interviews	3	60%	60%
Expenses for electronics / receipts	1	20%	20%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
self report measure (shopping diary as I understand it seem to be more useful for habitual shopping behaviors)
adviser protocols

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	5	100%	100%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	20%	20%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	20%	20%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	40%	40%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	5	100%	100%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	40%	40%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	20%	20%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	1	20%	20%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	0	0%	0%
Being able to afford brands that otherwise would not be affordable	2	40%	40%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Information on online platforms for second-hand electronics. Label/evaluation on condition/quality of the second-hand good.

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	20%	20%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	3	60%	60%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	3	60%	60%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	20%	20%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	2	40%	40%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Unsure durability	5	100%	100%
Waranty issues / lack of trust in quality	4	80%	80%
Not having the last fashionable product	5	100%	100%
Lack of trust in security (e.g., data security)	1	20%	20%
Takes time to find the product / a specific product might be unavailable	4	80%	80%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 5

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	40%	40%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	1	20%	20%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	2	40%	40%
Other intervention ideas	2	40%	40%
Normalizing the behaviour by showing models	3	60%	60%
Presenting overview of the options to buy / with or without warranty	5	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Consulting through advisors.
Common label on quality of second-hand goods.
personal advise; getting information about quality, trustworthy platforms, etc.

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 5

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	5	100%	100%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Buy products with service options"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 1

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	1	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Shopping diary	1	100%	100%
Qualitative interviews	1	100%	100%
Expenses for electronics / receipts	1	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	100%	100%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	1	100%	100%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	100%	100%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	1	100%	100%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	100%	100%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	100%	100%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	100%	100%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	100%	100%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	1	100%	100%
Peace of mind that the product is kept in good shape if necessary	1	100%	100%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 1

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	100%	100%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	100%	100%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	100%	100%
Not perceived important enough	1	100%	100%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	100%	100%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	100%	100%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	100%	100%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Higher upfront costs / only for higher value products	1	100%	100%
Unsure if needed	1	100%	100%
Not having the last fashionable product	1	100%	100%
Lack of trust in security (e.g., data security)	1	100%	100%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 1 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	1	100%	100%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	1	100%	100%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	1	100%	100%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	100%	100%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Presenting overview of the life-time perspective	1	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 1

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	100%	100%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
budget to buy the service plan with the product, time to carry out investigatory work into the best kind of service/item to buy

The following question regard "Share products (e.g., drills, lawn mowers)"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 13

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	12	92.3%	92.3%
No, I propose to change the definition.	1	7.7%	7.7%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

People seek to hire or borrow items from commercial sources or through community-led libraries of things

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	2	14.3%	14.3%
Sharing diary	11	78.6%	78.6%
Qualitative interviews	9	64.3%	64.3%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

shARING DIARY; BUT FROM THE OWNER AND NOT THE LEASERS 7 RENTERS

"Circular Story"

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	9	64.3%	64.3%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	21.4%	21.4%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	4	28.6%	28.6%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	10	71.4%	71.4%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	7	50%	50%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	8	57.1%	57.1%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	5	35.7%	35.7%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	7	50%	50%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	1	7.1%	7.1%
Other drivers	2	14.3%	14.3%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	1	7.1%	7.1%
Social event to share	7	50%	50%
Higher reliability because items are frequently checked	3	21.4%	21.4%
Testing out items that one might want to buy in the future	4	28.6%	28.6%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Near-by possibilities for sharing, e.g. tool container for a settlement.
together with social norms: Availability

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	8	57.1%	57.1%
Social norms against the behaviour	3	21.4%	21.4%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	10	71.4%	71.4%
Not perceived important enough	5	35.7%	35.7%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	3	21.4%	21.4%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	3	21.4%	21.4%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	5	35.7%	35.7%
Negative emotions	3	21.4%	21.4%
Other barriers	2	14.3%	14.3%
Lack of trust in security (e.g., data security)	5	35.7%	35.7%
Diffusion of responsibility for maintainance	10	71.4%	71.4%
Lack of infrastructure	7	50%	50%
Lack of common storage space	8	57.1%	57.1%
Need to buy higher quality products to sustain the extensive use	3	21.4%	21.4%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
negative emotions: fear that sharing self-owned products might be damaged or not handled with care
needs to be easy to get (located nearby), the right costs, and available when needed. needs to compete with the ability of Amazon to deliver next day

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 14

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	5	35.7%	35.7%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	5	35.7%	35.7%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	5	35.7%	35.7%
Triggering normative goals / framing	3	21.4%	21.4%
Other intervention ideas	3	21.4%	21.4%
Circular stories game	8	57.1%	57.1%
Tasks on group or community level	6	42.9%	42.9%
Normalizing the behaviour by presenting models	10	71.4%	71.4%
Information about formal sharing resources or legal agreements	7	50%	50%
Promoting community led sharing resources	10	71.4%	71.4%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
Consulting through advisors.
Social Game: Co-creation of a section "Virtual sharing library" in the CircleUp knowledge base to give participants the opportunity to offer their products for sharing within the CircleUp community
make it easy for people. information isn't enough to force a change, need the supporting infrastructure to be there

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 14

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	8	57.1%	57.1%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	6	42.9%	42.9%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 6

Svar

Only owners of shareable products (e.g., products where need to use them can be planned and only arises occasionally).

see above

mental and physical capacity/capability, budget/ability to finance this

need supporting infrastructure in place

Trust.

It could be challenging in rural / remote areas, or places where community networking practices have not been established.

The following question regard "Use rental / leasing offers"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	3	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Purchase / renting / leasing diary / self-report	3	100%	100%
Qualitative interviews	3	100%	100%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	3	100%	100%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	33.3%	33.3%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	1	33.3%	33.3%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	0	0%	0%
Better reliability as the company renting / leasing out maintains	3	100%	100%
Better quality	1	33.3%	33.3%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	2	66.7%	66.7%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	1	33.3%	33.3%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	33.3%	33.3%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of trust in security (e.g., data security)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Lack of infrastructure	2	66.7%	66.7%
Higher price in the long run	3	100%	100%
Not owning / no asset at the end	0	0%	0%
Unclear rental / leasing agreements	2	66.7%	66.7%
Lack of trust in leasing company	1	33.3%	33.3%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	1	33.3%	
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Normalizing the behaviour by presenting models	2	66.7%	
Information about legal agreements	1	33.3%	
Information about available rental / leasing options	2	66.7%	

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	1	33.3%	
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	2	66.7%	

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
leasing renting bigger machines might necessitate cars for transporting them from and to the owners
Challenging in rural / remote areas.

The following question regard "Repair damaged products"

✓ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 9

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	9	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

✓ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	3	33.3%	33.3%
Repair diary / self-report	8	88.9%	88.9%
Qualitative interviews	5	55.6%	55.6%
Amount of electronic waste	1	11.1%	11.1%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
repair diaries could be difficult given the timescales of the project
repair receipts, e.g. electronic shops; information on consumer rights, e.g. if shops are obliged to repair an item
Knowledge of how to repair

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	8	88.9%	88.9%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	1	11.1%	11.1%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	5	55.6%	55.6%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	4	44.4%	44.4%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	22.2%	22.2%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	7	77.8%	77.8%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	2	22.2%	22.2%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 2

Svar
Simplicity, knowledge of how or where to repair, chances of success of the repair, cost of the repair
product attachment

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	11.1%	11.1%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	5	55.6%	55.6%
Not perceived important enough	1	11.1%	11.1%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	2	22.2%	22.2%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	11.1%	11.1%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of trust in security (e.g., data security)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Lack of infrastructure	6	66.7%	66.7%
High price in relation to value of the item	8	88.9%	88.9%
Time delay	5	55.6%	55.6%
Inconvenience to get it repaired	9	100%	100%
Insecurity how long the repaired item holds	8	88.9%	88.9%
Loosing the producer warranties when opening the product	5	55.6%	55.6%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 9

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	4	44.4%	44.4%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	3	33.3%	33.3%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	2	22.2%	22.2%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	2	22.2%	22.2%
Information about cost savings	4	44.4%	44.4%
Information about legal rights / warranties	5	55.6%	55.6%
Give-aways: Repair vouchers	5	55.6%	55.6%
Information on repair options	8	88.9%	88.9%
Do it yourself workshops (where possible -> might be illegal for some products)	7	77.8%	77.8%

☒ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

Repair index like in France.

Concerted actions with households, craftsmen and repair cafés.

infrastructure needs to be there - needs to be cheap and easy and have people trust the repair

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 9

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	8	88.9%	88.9%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	11.1%	11.1%

☒ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

need to have access to the infrastructure

The following question regard "Update / upgrade electronics"

Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Upgrade diary / self-report	0	0%	0%
Qualitative interviews	0	0%	0%
Amount of electronic waste	0	0%	0%

How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	0	0%	0%
Saving time	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of infrastructure	0	0%	0%
High price in relation to new item	0	0%	0%
Time delay / waiting for upgrading parts	0	0%	0%
Inconvenience to get it upgraded	0	0%	0%
Insecurity how long the upgraded item holds	0	0%	0%
Access to upgrading parts / compatibility with future technology	0	0%	0%
Loosing the product warranty when opening the product	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Information about cost savings	0	0%	0%
Information about legal rights / warranties	0	0%	0%
Information on upgrade options	0	0%	0%
Do it yourself workshops	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Give electronics to friends and family / other people"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	4	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Giving away diary / self-report	3	75%	75%
Qualitative interviews	3	75%	75%
Amount of electronic waste	1	25%	25%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	1	25%	25%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	3	75%	75%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	50%	50%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	2	50%	50%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	1	25%	25%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	3	75%	75%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	1	25%	25%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	3	75%	75%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	1	25%	25%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	25%	25%
Social norms against the behaviour	1	25%	25%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	3	75%	75%
Not perceived important enough	2	50%	50%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	1	25%	25%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	25%	25%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	1	25%	25%
Negative emotions	1	25%	25%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of infrastructure / where to give it	3	75%	75%
Inconvenience to give it away	3	75%	75%
Data security concerns	2	50%	50%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 4 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	2	50%	50%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	2	50%	50%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	1	25%	25%
Triggering normative goals / framing	1	25%	25%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Information about secure deletion of data	2	50%	50%
Information about consumer rights / warranties	2	50%	50%
Information about local donation points	4	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 4

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	3	75%	75%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	1	25%	25%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Mental and physical capacity/capability

The following question regard "Give electronics to proper recycling"

✓ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	3	100%	100%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

✓ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	1	33.3%	33.3%
Recycling diary / self-report	3	100%	100%
Qualitative interviews	2	66.7%	66.7%
Amount of electronic waste	1	33.3%	33.3%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 1

Svar
Amount of electronic waste stored in the household

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	2	66.7%	66.7%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	3	100%	100%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	3	100%	100%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	2	66.7%	66.7%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	3	100%	100%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	1	33.3%	33.3%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	1	33.3%	33.3%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	2	66.7%	66.7%
Not perceived important enough	1	33.3%	33.3%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	3	100%	100%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	1	33.3%	33.3%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of infrastructure / where to throw it	3	100%	100%
Inconvenience to throw it away	3	100%	100%
Data security concerns	2	66.7%	66.7%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 3 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	3	100%	100%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	3	100%	100%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	1	33.3%	33.3%
Information about secure deletion of data	3	100%	100%
Information about local collection points	3	100%	100%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 1

Svar

Home mining of resources (all the old phones and appliances in the drawer that nobody will ever use again).

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 3

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	1	33.3%	33.3%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	2	66.7%	66.7%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 2

Svar

Households need to have electronic waste, but most do now.

Challenging in rural / remote areas.

The following question regard "Resell"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Resell diary / self-report	0	0%	0%
Qualitative interviews	0	0%	0%
Amount of electronic waste	0	0%	0%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (earning money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of infrastructure / where to sell it	0	0%	0%
Inconvenience to resell	0	0%	0%
Data security concerns	0	0%	0%
Liabilities / legal complications	0	0%	0%
Fear of being cheated	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Information about secure deletion of data	0	0%	0%
Information about local / online selling points	0	0%	0%
Information about liabilities	0	0%	0%
Insurance schemes for private sales	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

The following question regard "Take care of products"

☑ Do you consider the following definition of the behaviour sufficient?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, this is sufficient.	0	0%	0%
No, I propose to change the definition.	0	0%	0%

☰ Which definition do you suggest?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ How could the behaviour (and change of it) be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
I have an idea for further measures	0	0%	0%
Maintainance diary / self-report	0	0%	0%
Qualitative interviews	0	0%	0%
Amount of electronic waste	0	0%	0%

☰ How else can this behaviour be measured?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which drivers do you think are most important for this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0

Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Economic benefits (saving money)	0	0%	0%
positive emotions (e.g., pride, warm glow)	0	0%	0%
Social influence between household members (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Social influence from other households (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Easy to implement (high perceived behavioural control / self-efficacy)	0	0%	0%
Personal environmental motivation / values (attitudes / personal norm / values)	0	0%	0%
Fits the self-concept / identity of the person	0	0%	0%
Fits the person's normative goals ("this is the right thing to do")	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions (shame / guilt)	0	0%	0%
Other drivers	0	0%	0%
Knowing about the working conditions in the industry	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other drivers do you consider relevant?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which barriers do you think are most important against changing this behaviour?

Antall svar: 0 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Strong habits for the old behaviour	0	0%	0%
Social norms against the behaviour	0	0%	0%
Time pressure / complications in everyday life	0	0%	0%
Not perceived important enough	0	0%	0%
Hedonistic goals (more pleasurable to do something else)	0	0%	0%
Gain goals (does not give me benefits)	0	0%	0%
Does not fit with self-concept / identity	0	0%	0%
Negative emotions	0	0%	0%
Other barriers	0	0%	0%
Lack of knowledge about how to maintain	0	0%	0%

☒ Which other barriers do you see?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Which of the following interventions do you consider useful for triggering a change?

Antall svar: 0 Randomisert: Ja

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Social game	0	0%	0%
Feedback on own behaviour (change)	0	0%	0%
Feedback about behaviour of other people (social norms)	0	0%	0%
Triggering normative goals / framing	0	0%	0%
Other intervention ideas	0	0%	0%
Information about proper maintainance	0	0%	0%

☰ Which other intervention ideas do you have?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☑ Is this behaviour something that applies to all households?

Antall svar: 0

Svar	Antall	% av svar	Diagram
Yes, all households can do this	0	0%	0%
No, only households with the following condition (s) can do this	0	0%	0%

☰ Which conditions do the households need to fulfill?

Antall svar: 0

Dette spørsmålet har ingen svar

☰ Is there anything else you want to say for the electronics sector?

Antall svar: 3

Svar
we need to make it easy for people to do the behaviour - information is good, but they need the supporting infrastructure to do the activity
Also here the role of the supplier is most important. If all products aren't durable and easy to repair the consumers can't make the right choice. So it's the product portfolio in the shops that needs to change.
everything that extends product life and/or usage time is beneficial